

Gendering the Academy
and Research: combating
Career Instability and Asymmetries

Supported by
the 7th Framework Programme
of the European Union

GARCIA WORKING PAPERS

2

Constructing excellence: the gap between formal and actual selection criteria for early career academics

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GARCIA is an EU-Framework 7 funded project under topic SIS.2013.2.1.1-1
“Supporting changes in the organisation of research institutions to
promote Gender Equality”

Grant agreement n. 611737 • Project coordinator: University of Trento •
Homepage: www.garciaproject.eu

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Introduction

Work package 7 centers on the revealing of implicit gender sub-texts in selection processes by deconstructing excellence. In this work package, GARCIA will identify the formal and informal criteria that are widely used to construct scientific excellence in academia and research. The focus on recruitment and selection helps to unpack how the formal criteria of the job description are understood, applied or ignored in committee deliberations. The construction of academic and research excellence is particularly salient for those workers who hold precarious positions, as the label of excellence is the key to their inclusion or exclusion in academia and research. Therefore, the core research question for this report 7.1 is concerned with the identification of the gap between the formal criteria and the actual criteria used in the recruitment and selection of early career academics.

The project zooms in on the entrance to positions for postdocs, researchers and assistant professors; both permanent, tenure-track and non-permanent positions. At this stage, recruitment and selection processes act as a “bottleneck” in career progression for scientists where only a small minority among a pool of candidates are retained. The competition in an already greedy institution may bring along extra risk of producing inequalities. Statistics show how men succeed more than women to rise in the scientific ranks and leave the status of precarious worker behind. GARCIA will look into the gendered processes and practices that constitute the barriers for women to become part of or be eligible for the permanent staff.

For the analysis of formal criteria, we will analyze HR-documents about career trajectories and job demands (to analyze how the HR policies are translated into formal job descriptions). We also perform a content analysis on job descriptions of vacancies between 2010-2014 in two academic fields (SSH and STEM).

To examine the criteria as applied in practice, we use 1) focus groups and interviews with committee members and 2) analysis of appointment reports. Aim is to analyze a) how committee members construct excellence (the ideal candidate), what criteria are applied in practice and how do they relate to the formal criteria in the original job description and b) the gender practices in the recruitment and selection processes.

1. Italy

1.1 Introduction

The Italian public debate on universities and meritocracy and approval of the Gelmini University Reform Law (240/2010)

In the past fifteen years the structure of the Italian public universities has been profoundly modified by a series of reforms that have concerned both the organizational and the teaching/research system of Italian Academia. These reforms are deeply rooted in the framework of the Bologna Process (1999), and the Lisbon Strategy (2000), two European Council agreements whose aims were, on the one hand, creation of the European Higher Education Area based on the definition of quality standards in higher education, and on the other, the foundation of a competitive and dynamic knowledge-based economy.

The socio-political context in which the reforms were introduced was characterized by two main features: increasing cuts in the public financing of the welfare state, including schools and universities, and the consequent waves of mobilizations by students, researchers and teachers against the ‘privatization’ of knowledge and public services. At the same time, there emerged in the public discourse a common criticism of the so-called ‘privileges’ of Academia, often seen as an ‘ivory tower’ where a closed group of professors retained power on decisions concerning internal recruitment and funding without any kind of public control. Accordingly, demands were expressed for ‘objective’ and ‘neutral’ procedures based on meritocracy and benchmarking. In this political and social setting, the following normative decrees on the organization and evaluation of the public University were approved.

The latest organic law, the so-called Gelmini Law (240/2010) taking the name of the Education Minister who proposed the draft law to Parliament, had as its first explicit goal to raise the formal organization, ‘efficiency’ and quality of university research to an international standard.

The implementation of ANVUR: a new accountability system

At the organizational level (TITLE I), the current system foresees the centralization of administrative power from the Academic Senate to the Rector and the Board, while the Faculties have been replaced by the empowered role of the Departments. In regard to financial accounting, relative to the quality and efficiency of the university

system (TITLE II) a new procedure has been established with implementation of the National Evaluation Agency for University and Research (ANVUR), which plays a crucial role in defining the formal criteria for evaluation and recruitment within the public universities. The ANVUR was created in 2006 by the leftist University Minister Mussi, with law no. 286, but the regulation was finally approved in 2010. Consequently, the Agency's aims and functions have been specified by the above-mentioned Gelmini University Reform Law.

According to the Gelmini Law (art. 5), the main objectives of the ANVUR are: (i), to verify the fulfillment by faculties and courses of teaching, structural, organizational and qualification requirements for their accreditation; (ii), to evaluate the recruitment policies of universities; (iii) to introduce a system of periodic evaluation based on ex ante criteria in order to measure the efficiency and the results achieved in the teaching and research activities of each university (VQR, Evaluation of Research Quality). For each evaluation activity, called AVA (Self-evaluation, periodic evaluation, validation), the ANVUR defines indices and criteria based on the Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area.

Also established has been a system for evaluation of the recruitment policies of each university. Its formal criteria are based on: a) scientific output by academic staff; b) the percentage of temporary contract researchers who have not stayed at the same university for the entire period of their PhD or post-doctoral courses; c) the percentage of lecturers recruited from other universities; d) the percentage of lecturers (professors and researchers) who are scientific coordinators of international and EU research projects; e) the level of 'internationalization' of the teaching staff (Art. 5 c.5 L.240/2010).

Furthermore, in regard to financial accountability, the Gelmini Law imposes an incentives/sanctions mechanism which foresees the possibility for a university to be placed under compulsory administration in the case of non-compliance with university financial provisions.

1.2. Formal criteria

At TITLE III, "Norms in regard to academic staff and reorganization of the recruitment system", some of the most radical changes introduced by the Gelmini Law concern post-doctoral fellowships (art. 22) and the legal status of assistant professors (art.24).

Research Fellowship

The Research Fellowship, previously regulated by art. 51 of the L. 449/97, is now defined as a temporary research position granted by universities, research institutions and experimental public authorities, the ENEA (National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development) and the ASI (Italian Space Agency). The grants are intended to promote the development of specific abilities. In other words, from a legal and fiscal point of view, postdoctoral research fellowships are not considered to be jobs, so that on conclusion of a postdoctoral fellowship the researcher is not entitled to unemployment benefits.

According to the law, research grant selection procedures must be publicized and contain detailed information on the position, and the relative rights and duties. These research positions are available to graduates and PhD-holders, although admission may be restricted to only PhD-holders. The post-doctoral grant is awarded for a minimum of one year and is renewable for only three further years.

Temporary assistant professors

The changes produced by the Gelmini Reform also involve the legal status of assistant professors, in that they replace the previous permanent posts with only temporary ones:

- Temporary assistant professor of “type B” (RTD-b). It is a three-year post which is not renewable but on the tenure track: access to a permanent position is conditional on possession of ASN (National Scientific Habilitation), obtainable after a very long, complex and debatable procedure conducted by the ANVUR;
- Temporary assistant professor of “type A” (RTD-a). These posts last for three years and are renewable for only two further years after an internal evaluation.

Concerning the recruitment procedures provided by the law for the RTD-a and RTD-b positions, art. 24 states that the announcements must be public and that the general criteria and procedure established for the selection of candidates must be:

- Admission of PhD holders or of an equivalent qualification;
- Preliminary evaluation of qualifications, CV and scientific products, including the PhD thesis, according to international criteria;

- Definition of a shortlist composed of 10-20% of the candidates (or a minimum 6) suitable for the appointment, which must be made public;
- The qualifications and each publication are evaluated after the public discussion;
- Written and oral tests are excluded;
- The Department Council will then deliberate on award of the post according to the Committee's evaluation.

The criteria for the selection concern the candidate's qualifications and CV in regard to the specific academic discipline stated in the call. They are defined as follows:

- PhD;
- Previous teaching experience;
- Documented training and research activity at Italian or foreign institutes;
- Activities in research projects relevant to the Scientific and Disciplinary Sector;
- Management and coordination of national or international research groups;
- Participation in national and international conferences;
- National and international awards obtained for the research activity.

As regards scientific production, the preliminary evaluation must be based on the following indicators:

- Originality, innovativeness, methodological accuracy, and relevance of each publication;
- Congruence with the scientific discipline object of the selection;
- Scientific relevance of journals and publishers;
- Acknowledgment of the individual candidate's contribution to collective publications according to international scientific standards.

Furthermore, international indicators should be used, such as: Total number of citations; Average number of citations per publication; Total Impact Factor; Average Impact Factor per publication; Hirsch index or similar.

The Autonomy of the University of Trento

In July 2011 the Italian government approved a legislative decree which devolved to the Autonomous Province of Trento (PAT) the national normative and administrative functions pertaining to the University of Trento (d. Lgs. 142/2011). The Devolution of the University was harshly criticized by a large part of the academic staff. The main targets of criticism were the following: (i) the "authoritarian turn" (Pascuzzi, 2006)

imposed by the Province President and certain executive bodies of the University, who had not considered the opposition of almost half the academic and research staff, while students and precarious researchers had been excluded from the decision-making process; (ii) the model of academic research and teaching, too ‘business-like’ and hybrid, given its focus on competition among universities, spin-offs and start-ups, and financial issues; (iii) the role of the Province in appointment of the Administrative Council, which was considered too intrusive in the University’s autonomy.

The Devolution of the University was finally implemented in 2012, with the approval of the new statute of the University and the official introduction of the new Departments (Statute of the University of Trento, D.R. 167, April 23, 2012).

The HR documents for Temporary Assistant Professors (RTD) at the UNITN

As previously described, the above-mentioned legislative reforms modified the recruitment procedures for assistant professors. Until 2011, the matter was regulated by the Moratti Law, adopted with the DR 369/2008 and then modified by the DR 371/2010. After the Gelmini Law’s approval and the consequent implementing decree 243/2011, the regulations were further modified by DR 378/2011. Moreover, the devolution norms have led to the creation of the Recruitment and Developing of Scientific Careers Committee, approved with DR 358/2013, which issued the “General criteria for the recruitment of professors and assistant professors” (2014).

The recruiting process for temporary assistant professors: The “Moratti” RTD

Until 2011 the Moratti Reform defined the criteria for evaluation of teaching and research activities for RTD. The required qualifications and formal criteria were as follows:

- PhD or equivalent;
- Possibility for faculties to restrict admission only to the candidates who have spent at least one year of research activity at a different Italian or international university or research centre;
- Research experience at different universities or research centres and publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals are preferential requirements;
- quality and dissemination of scientific research;
- Fund raising and management.

The Committee was composed by three full or associate professors, one selected by the Faculty; one by the Department concerned; one by the Academic Senate. Several evaluation phases were foreseen: a pre-selection consisting in comparative evaluation of scientific qualifications, publications, CV, and reference letters; the advice of three external referees appointed by the Academic Senate; an attitudinal interview or seminar.

The recruiting process for temporary assistant professors: The “Gelmini” RTD

Since approval of the Gelmini Reform, the HR documents of the University of Trento have integrated the new norms by modifying the previous rules with DR n. 371/2010 and D.R. 378/2011.

The required qualifications for the RTD-a (non tenure track) are: PhD obtained at a university different from the one at which the degree was awarded or at a foreign one; and/or at least one year of post-doctoral research at internationally recognized foreign universities or research centres.

The RTD-b position (tenure track) requires instead to be a PhD-holder who has been appointed for at least three years with: RTD-a “Gelmini” contracts; RTD “Moratti”; Post-doctoral grants. Also in this case the PhD has to be obtained at a university different from the one at which the degree was awarded or at a foreign one. Alternatively, it must be shown at least one year of post-doctoral research at internationally recognized foreign universities or research centres.

The Committee is composed by three full or associate professors, one selected by the Faculty; one by the Department concerned; one by the University Recruitment Committee. Several evaluation phases are envisaged: a pre-selection, consisting in a comparative evaluation of qualifications, CV, and three reference letters; the advice of three external referees appointed by the University Recruitment Committee; consequent admission to the next phase of 10-20% of the candidates (they must be no fewer than six, in which case all the candidates are admitted). Then, a public discussion of the scientific qualifications with the Committee is foreseen. At the end of this phase, the Committee selects the candidates suitable for the appointment. The Department Council then deliberates on the candidate who will be called for the post, according to the Committee’s evaluation.

Generally, at both Departments of the University of Trento involved in the GARCIA project – the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Sciences and the Department of Sociology and Social Research – the formal criteria used for the departmental recruitment process entirely overlap with the HR documents of the University of Trento, except for the specific descriptions of each scientific profile, and the department's choice whether or not to restrict the selection to some particular criteria, as described in the following subsections.

For both RTD-a and RTD-b positions, candidates appointed with a post-doctoral grant for more than twelve years are excluded.

The HR documents on postdoctoral research fellowship grants at the University of Trento

Research fellowships have been disciplined by three regulations issued by the University of Trento: the DR894 1998 then modified by DR 187 2003 and in force until 2011; the DR 117 2011 approved after implementation of the Gelmini Law; and the DR 384 2013, still effective.

The first norms, derived from the L. 449/1997, defined grants whose aim was to promote the development of specific abilities. The Departments had to present specific research programmes submitted by a Professors to the Scientific Committee of the University of Trento. The request for grants had to provide: an analytical description of the research programme, the supervisor and the research methods; the start date of the research; the scientific and professional profile required; the financial resources required. The selection was public and conducted by a three-member committee appointed by the Head of the Department.

In 2013 the last regulation was issued, with DR 384. The grant application must be presented to the Department by an internal researcher or professor, who will be the supervisor of the research. The Department can then activate the grants in two ways: a) by publishing specific self-financed programmes; b) by publishing one announcement relative to the scientific areas of interest; in this case the candidates must present their own research programmes (in addition to qualifications and publications). In both cases, the qualifications required are the same as those stated by the law: degree or PhD, which can be the mandatory requirement if specified by the call. In this case, the grant is termed a 'post-doc' grant.

The Formal Criteria in the Job Description for the Departments Selected

RTD positions at the Department of Sociology and Social Research

A total of six assistant professor positions were opened from 2010 and 2013: two in 2010 (still regulated by the Moratti Law) and four of type “a” (non tenure track) in 2012 after the Gelmini Law’s approval.

The first two calls focused on the following scientific fields:

- DR 525 2010, “Methodology and Social Service Management”;
- DR 526 2010, “Sociology of the Environment and Territory”.

They were published by the Department of Human and Social Sciences of the Faculty of Sociology, which was abolished in 2010. At that time the Faculty of Sociology comprised two Departments: the Department of Human and Social Sciences and the Department of Sociology and Social Research. The two Departments were then merged into one single Department, called the Department of Sociology and Social Research. Moreover, in 2012 – following enactment of a national law – the Faculty was abolished and the Department of Sociology and Social Research is now in charge of both teaching and research activities.

After approval of the Gelmini Law and devolution of the University of Trento, the new Department of Sociology and Social Research opened four calls for assistant professor in 2012. It should be stressed that the recent reform merged different disciplines within broader categories. This means that there are now less but broader scientific fields. Specifically, the calls focused on the following scientific fields:

- DR 87 2012, “Demo-ethnoanthropological sciences”;
- DR 88 2012, “Sociology”;
- DR 89 2012, “Sociology of cultural and communication processes”
- DR 90 2012, “Sociology of economic, work and environment processes”.

RTD positions at the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Sciences

Since 2010 the DISI has published two calls of assistant professor positions, one “Moratti” RTD and one Gelmini RTD-a (non-tenure track):

- DR 654 2011, “Electromagnetic fields”;
- DR 19 2013, “Telecommunications”.

At that time the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Sciences was part of the Faculty of Engineering. Moreover, when the Faculty was abolished, in 2012, this Department decided not to be included in the Department of Engineering and instead created a new Department, namely the current Department of Information Engineering and Computer Sciences.

The formal criteria applied by the DISI are the same as those for the DSRS.

Postdoctoral fellowships at the Department of Sociology and Social Research

As seen above, the selection criteria included in the announcements are generally derived from the Department's HR documents. The DSRS issued 17 research grant announcements from 2010 to 2014.

In 2010 only two post-doctoral calls were announced, one for General Sociology and one for Sociology of Economic and Work Processes. Both calls required the presentation of a research programme, and they described the specific scientific profile and competences required for the grant. Underlined in both cases was the importance of demonstrating 'competences suitable' for the research, 'previous experience' on the topics and methodology; and the 'pertinence of scientific publications' to the selection procedure.

Since 2011, all the announcements of postdoctoral research fellowships have been related to specific projects financed by the EU or national/local funding. For all of them the scientific profiles required were previous methodological and theoretical experience in the programme's scientific field. In one of them, teaching experience was required. Only in one call the term 'excellence' was used, in order to require previous participation in 'excellent' international research groups. No reference was made to gender equality criteria.

Postdoctoral fellowships at the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Sciences

From the beginning of 2010 to the beginning of 2014 the DISI issued more than one hundred calls for research grants. The awards were funded by the EU (64%) or local companies and foundations (private, 7%, on behalf of a third party, 18%). Thirty-two FP7 research projects started in 2013, most of them related to Education and Mobility, Industry, Research.

The formal criteria in announcements for research grants at the DISI Department are highly standardized: the main one is the suitability of the candidate's CV. Except for the specific technical description of the scientific profile required, we found few keywords in documents specifying the kinds of skills and personal attitudes required by the programmes: previous direction and management of international and European research programmes; ability to create relationships with businesses; excellent communication skills; willingness to travel; ability to work autonomously and independently within an interdisciplinary team.

Comparative conclusions on formal criteria used at DSRS and DISI

The foregoing comparative analysis of norms on RTD and research grants from the national level to the University of Trento regulations has highlighted how different legal statuses impact on the formal criteria required for each position. While RTD are temporary dependent contracts with research and teaching duties in broad scientific fields, postdoctoral research grants are not employment contracts and they concern specific topics linked to a research programme. Consequently, the requirements in the case of RTD are broader: the quality of qualifications and the CV (i.e. previous teaching and research experience, the ranking of the universities where candidates have obtained their PhDs and conducted research activities, etc.), and the importance given to publications are decisive for the selection of the suitable candidates. On the other hand, in the case of postdoctoral research fellowships the evaluation focuses on previous experience of fieldwork or with a certain methodology, which are skills considered useful in conducting the research project.

The analysis of the job descriptions announced by the two departments highlights that the calls comply strictly with the HR documents, without particular differences.

A quantitative comparison between the DSRS and DISI research grants shows an evident disproportion in the funding related to external-financed projects, mainly due the specificity of the DISI's scientific fields, which are more connected to the industrial sector, at both the local and the international level.

Moreover, also a similarity should be stressed: no calls of type "b" for RTD positions (tenure track positions) have been opened at these two Departments. Indeed, the University of Trento was the first in Italy to adopt the new RTD positions. While in the rest of the country permanent assistant professor posts were still being opened, the

University of Trento was already creating the new temporary (and non tenure track) assistant professor posts.

Finally, no mention is made of excellence, but ‘suitability’ seems to be the term that best fits the criteria in both types of announcements.

1.3. Actual Practices

Methodological introduction

This section of the report describes the actual practices adopted for both RTD and postdoctoral research fellow appointments. In accordance with the work plan of the GARCIA project, the analysis of the actual practices was conducted on the one hand by interviewing the RTD and postdoc committee members and chairs, and on the other by looking at the appointments reports. Full reports are available only for temporary assistant professor selections (RTD) because the procedure for postdoctoral research fellowships provides only for publication of a grade without any comment.

For each Department (DSRS and DISI) 6 interviews were foreseen, with committee members who participated in a recruitment process from the 1st of January 2010 to the 1st of January 2014, and specifically:

- 3 interviews at the DSRS and 3 interviews at the DISI with the committee members and chairs who participated in postdoctoral selections;
- 3 interviews at the DSRS and 3 interviews at the DISI with the committee members and chairs who participated in selection for a position that was either a tenure track position or the first permanent academic post.

As already explained, in the two Departments selected no tenure track or permanent position has been opened in the last four years. Consequently, we interviewed committee members who had participated in the recruitment process for RTD-a positions, which correspond to dependent contracts as assistant professor for 3+3 years, without any guarantee concerning development of a future career in the same Department.

Moreover, a focus group was foreseen in the two Departments selected with 5/6 committee members who were part of an appointment committee for a position that was either a tenure track or a permanent position. This means that – since none of these positions has been opened in the two selected Departments – we were supposed to organise one focus group at the DSRS and one at the DISI with committee

members who had participated in the recruitment process for RTD-a positions. However, due to the fact that from the 1st of January 2010 to the 1st January 2014 only 6 RTD-a positions were opened at the Department of Sociology and Social Research and only 2 at the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science, we decided to increase the number of individual interviews instead of conducting focus groups. Indeed, it would not have been feasible to involve the same persons in both an individual interview and a focus group. Nevertheless, by adopting the strategy of increasing the number of foreseen interviews, we were able to interview, in both Departments, all the professors involved in a RTD-a recruitment in the period 2010-2014.

Finally, in regard to the approach used to analyse the interview texts, a content analysis was conducted using the Atlas.ti software.

The Actual Criteria in the Department of Sociology and Social Research

Eight interviews were conducted in the Department of Sociology and Social Research: 3 with committee members who had participated in postdoctoral selections, and 5 with committee members who had participated in the recruitment process for RTD-a positions. Six positions were opened between 2010 and 2014, but one of the interviewees was involved in two different committees. The interviews conducted are summarised in the following table.

N. Interview	Sex	Postdoctoral Research Fellowship/RTD Committee	Position in the Committee
1	M	RTD	Member
2	M	RTD	Chair
3	M	RTD	Chair
4	W	RTD	Member
5	M	RTD	Chair
6	M	Postdoc	Chair
7	W	Postdoc	Member
8	W	Postdoc	Chair

RTD-a recruitment processes: actual practices

In this section the committee members' opinions and considerations about the actual selection processes in which they were involved are reported. As recalled in the first section, the RTD selections in the DSRS announced between 2010 and 2014 were six

in total: two of them in 2010 under the Moratti Law and four in 2012, after the Gelmini Law's enactment.

The first question that several interviewees raised about the selection procedures in which they had participated concerned the procedure itself and the relationships among the various bodies involved. Indeed, the first critical step is the appointment of the three external referees who have to give a first assessment of publications. Since implementation of the Gelmini Law, the referees have been appointed by the Recruitment Committee without a strict link with the preferences expressed by the Department. Some interviewees criticised this detachment between the traditional relationships within a scientific community and the bureaucratic logic of the new procedure, where the referees are contacted by the administrative offices. Moreover, how the assessments made by the referees are to be used is not clearly defined, and they can be interpreted by the committee in charge of the recruitment process in a highly discretionary manner, due to the ambiguous provisions of the regulation. The first issue concerns the role of the committee of external experts, which draws up a first ranking list after evaluation of the candidates' publications.

The instructions on the use to be made of the [external] referees is the first source of broader discretionality. Our committee was able to give account of how the referees had evaluated in comparative matter. Others simply wrote: "Considering the referees' work...", and this is disrespectful of the external people that you ask to give a first opinion, to draw up a short list. So there's an ambiguity in the function and role of these three external referees (Interviewee_4_W)

Between the first assessment made by the [external] referees and the final decision taken by the department, the role of the principal Committee seems to be restricted to mere application of the formal criteria stated by the announcement to the CVs and publications presented by the candidates. Indeed, according to the most recent regulations, the role of the committee consists in drawing up a short list, from which the Department will make a discretionary choice. This sort of 'bureaucratization' of their role was a further problem for the interviewees:

The shortlist naturally took account of standard criteria, so the Committee had to draw up its ranking list by giving specific scores to the candidates' specific features and scores for specific types of scientific production. So, in short, there was this relatively restrictive 'cage' of the scoring system [...] The final short list delivered to the

department is arranged in an alphabetical order. The Department can thus appoint any of the candidates and can even safely ignore the ranking. Which has actually happened (Interviewee_1_M)

Perhaps one of the merits of the law, if there are any, is that the decision is no longer the responsibility of a commission, but of an entire body, which is the Department Council. This is a change sufficient for the decision not to be one of family reproduction but an assumption of responsibility by the Department. [...] So there's a vision in the Department Council, but it cannot be directly converted into an operational instrument because there is, I won't say a schizophrenia, but a limitation on the work of the committee, which has to abide by the principles stated in the call, which may not be those of the Department (Interviewee_2_M)

While on the one hand the final responsibility of the Department is considered positively, because it has to do with the collective and strategic decision to recruit the best researcher for actual needs, on the other, this separation of responsibility is criticized because it restricts the committee's assessment, dividing the positions of the committee and the department. Consequently, as pointed out by other studies (Van Den Brink, Benschop, 2012), when the interviewees were asked about the specific criteria used during the selection procedure, they found that the boundary between formal and actual criteria was very hard to define.

A way to get out of the 'cage' of formal criteria during the evaluation process is made possible by 'playing' with the disciplinary boundaries indicated in the announcements. Although the ministerial classification of scientific fields is very strictly-defined, the calls for RTD positions ask for general profiles, allowing a certain discretion in selecting the candidate most suitable for the needs of the department and/or for the strategic positions of the committee members.

The only real discretionality that the Committee had was to say, "is or is not the candidate's scientific profile relevant to the disciplinary field?" [...] Then, as you know, these selection processes are nuanced and somewhat nebulous because it's not always easy to establish if a candidate fits exactly within these boundaries (Interviewee_1_M)

The base conditions are certainly not those that favour trans-multi-pluridisciplinarity. This is a classic reproduction of mainstreaming, right? Because someone may deal with aspects that are not central to the discipline, because they work a field that may be relevant, but to which other disciplines contribute (Interviewee_3_M)

In other words, flexibility in defining the disciplinary boundaries is a double-edged sword. On one hand, it can be so wide that it can easily slide into arbitrariness (Allred, Miller, 2007). On the other, it could be too much tight it can sacrifice the trans- and multi-disciplinary profiles which do not fit into any precise discipline.

Concerning the formal criteria defined for temporary assistant professor (RTD), there are several issues raised about their definition and applicability to the procedure. The first criterion is 'internationalization', coherently with the mainstream discourse on meritocracy. It was not easy to find a shared definition. The concept is so vague that the ability of candidates in presenting their experiences at international level was crucial in this case:

We all agreed that international work is important, but what does working internationally mean? Does it mean having spent a long time abroad? Maybe having taught abroad? Or does it mean having publications in foreign journals and publishers? Or does it mean staying at home but belonging to international networks, etcetera? (Interviewee_5_M)

Obviously, I look among young researchers for those better able to take part in these international research projects, who have participated in all the preparatory phases, the drafting of projects, etcetera. And then of course these abilities have their importance, but there are different situations, in the sense that they can be co-opted into these international research projects (Interviewee_1_M)

The international indicator of quality was an issue for several academics because of the unclear dimension to which it refers. In this discretionary space, each committee member defines internationalization in two different ways related to participation in international research projects and publication in international journals.

Another topic mentioned by the interviewees was teaching activity. Some said that teaching skills should not be required, because the first stage of the academic career should be focused on research. Others sustain that teaching, together with other organizational and relational skills, is an important competence, because the RTD position is the first step of an academic career in which teaching is one of the main tasks.

An excellent researcher teaches something, a bad researcher may also be an excellent teacher but teaches what little he or she knows, put it that way. It would be foolish to give particular weight to teaching experience, because it is the beginning of a research

career. So we try to find the candidates best at doing research. They'll learn how to teach (Interviewee_1_M)

I've always been a supporter of these other aspects. Teaching and institutional activities shouldn't be neglected, because today those who want to pursue an academic career should consider these things as well. (Interviewee_5_M)

What seems to be clear in the last two excerpts is that the desired candidate is what Van Den Brink and Benschop (2012) have called a “sheep with five legs”: the “ideal (and impossible to find) combination of skills and experiences” typical of the academic world, which in Italy are required especially of researchers at the early stage of their scientific careers. Moreover, the following two excerpts show another skill that committee members expect to find in candidates: organizational and relational abilities.

We're forced to take people on the basis of, you know, proven scientific ability, but besides this there are relational qualities, communication skills, willingness, flexibility, enthusiasm for research, which for us are essential. We need enthusiastic people, and this is something that you can see only up to a certain point (Interviewee_3_M)

Recruiting someone who's a pain in the neck makes things awkward. A pain in the neck doesn't participate in collective processes, you see? Someone who shuts himself off in his ivory tower: I do these things, you do others, okay? But in some way he interacts, and is also a person willing to do the difficult or boring work that the university now requires of us. I mean, sitting on committees, commissions, and such like (Interviewee_2_M)

In addition to the aforementioned formal criteria, all interviewees referred to the quality of publications and their national and international relevance, together with previous research experience. Therefore, they often overlapped on the one hand with the description of the formal criteria actually used during the selection procedures, and on the other, with the competences expected to be decisive in definition of the excellent candidate.

A dimension explored in the interviews is the one related to the ways in which scientific excellence is conceptualised. The definition of excellence, according to Addis and Pagnini (2010) is “elusive” and usually made with “circular references between the concept and the criteria used to define it” in a specific environment. For the critical theory, excellence and meritocracy form an ideological paradigm which

legitimizes inequalities by representing a ‘faith’ in a fairer and objective system of evaluation without questioning the basis of inequality itself. In the academic debate excellence and meritocracy are the mainstream concepts in which the national university reforms have been politically framed. Unexpectedly, however, the interviewees rarely mentioned the concept of excellence when speaking about the formal criteria used or wanted by the committee members during the selections. When asked for a general description of an excellent profile, their responses were almost tautological:

Excellence, let’s say, is something which demonstrates the possession of exceptional intellectual gifts (Interviewee_1_M)

...Is a relatively young person, so neither elderly nor very young, someone who has excellent academic, intellectual, scientific networks (Interviewee_3_M)

Here, acknowledgment by the academic community is assumed as an objective and neutral criterion with which to measure the excellence of a scholar, without problematising the way in which national and international networks are composed and managed (Van Den Brink, Benschop, 2012). In fact, some interviewees questioned whether it is possible to define excellence, because it is an abstract and vague concept far from the description of the skills that indicate the suitability of a candidate:

With the systems that we have at present, we rely on bibliometric indexes, and an excellent candidate is one who has been able to get more of his or her work published. For me, this isn’t an indicator of excellence, but of ability (Interviewee_3_M)

In my life, I’ve never met anyone excellent. Okay? I’ve met many suitable people, some more promising than others, some I’ve liked more for a number of reasons, I like what they do, and so on, but excellence seems a rhetoric of distinction (Interviewee_4_W)

Consistently with the meritocratic paradigm, excellence is described as a quality pertaining to a few outstanding scholars, or “lonely heroes at the top” to use Benschop and Broun’s (2003) expression, because it is a scarce good not available to everyone. Nevertheless, for the interviewees, the RTD selection process was not supposed to identify who was excellent, but who was suitable for the position. While on the one hand the concept of excellence was described as impossible to define, on the other recurrent in the interviews was the question of the over-qualification of researchers applying for RTD posts:

Seven or eight excellent candidates applied. We had to make a further selection from among those seven or eight, and that was the hardest part. Because all eight of them should have been hired. I mean, how do you choose? Whatever you do is an injustice (Interviewee_3_M)

In conclusion, in accordance with Brink and Benschop (2012), we can say that excellence is an ambiguous social construct used in the mainstream scientific discourse in order to legitimate the new selection procedures. Furthermore, its purpose seems to be that of justifying the unequal allocation of resources due to the lack of funding and public research policies in Italy.

Finally, in the conducted interviews specific attention was paid on gender differences. Indeed, the idea of meritocracy is based on the idea of gender neutrality in academic assessment procedures. When asked about the importance of gender in the selection procedure, several interviewees answered by affirming the absolute impartiality of the evaluation procedure:

What should matter is ability: research skills, teaching skills and the ability to relate with others. If a man has these has these abilities, good; if a woman has them, good [...] these are individual qualities that I think are independent of gender (Interviewee_3_M)

Gender balance... I hope it doesn't offend you if I say that for me it isn't a criterion, it's something that should remain outside the university. I want good people. I think we have more women than men. Alright? What interests me is that they are good. In my opinion, the gender problem should be solved upstream. (Interviewee_5_M)

According to the majority of the interviewees, the only 'gender' (always meaning 'women') issue is motherhood, the lack of welfare state for postdoctoral fellows at the beginning of their academic career, and the scarcity of public care services.

What I would do is structure fully fair social, family, etcetera, roles. I can give examples to clarify what I mean. Take nursery provision, which is a matter close to these biologically-based gender influences (Interviewee_1_M)

So we can tell the stories that we want, but it seems to me that at some point in a woman's life, as well as a man's, there's the problem of starting a family, having children, etcetera, very often, not always. And it is then that discrimination between the man and woman begins. I'll be brief, but I tend to think that the different roles of the two genders will continue, with the social role regarding motherhood being much more

delicate and more sensitive. In my opinion, the real drama in this country is that there are no services for children and therefore for mothers (Interviewee_5_M)

Moreover, focusing on gender differences, some interviewee stressed that, although gender inequality is still very important in executive positions, in recent years the sex of applicants for first-stage career posts have been almost equally represented, due to the increasing participation of women in PhD courses. Nonetheless, it was underlined by several interviewees (both men and women) that equality actions are generally useful for overcoming the implicit internal culture that has kept women in the lower academic positions.

The analysis of the RTD-a reports

The RDT-a reports are not usually publicly available, but only to the candidates who request them after the selection. However, we were able to obtain all the minutes from the university archive, after careful anonymisation by the administrative staff. Consequently, we do not make direct references to each specific report but instead highlight the main criteria used by the committees in order to select the candidate appointed. The reports are recorded for all the shortlisted applicants. The report on the final selection drawn up by the department is instead not available.

The reports are not homogeneous as regards the completeness of each applicant's description by the committee members and the relative assessment. Some of them are more detailed (1-2 pages long), others are much more concise and only briefly report the committee's opinion about the candidate's CV and scientific activity. See annex 1 for detailed information on the sex and number of candidates and committee members.

All the reports focused on the following aspects: education, with especial regard to experience abroad and the prestige of the academic institutions; the clarity of the information described in the CV; scientific pertinence to the job description; teaching activity; research activity, with especial regard to the management and coordination of international research teams and projects; networks.

In the first two appointments (DR 525 and 526 2010), the explanations for exclusion from the shortlist related to non-fulfillment of the above criteria. Almost all candidates obtained good evaluations, but they were considered 'unaligned' with the profile described in the call. The main features appreciated by the committee

members were consistent research and teaching activity, an international profile deduced from participation in conferences and seminars at foreign universities, and an inter-disciplinary attitude. Generally, as frequently stated by the interviewees in the previous section, the main rhetoric used was pertinence to the scientific field required by the announcement.

The committee involved in the third selection decided explicitly to report its difficulties in selecting from a range of very high-qualified candidates within the limits of the shortlist provided by the regulation and the call. For this reason, they declared that the discriminating criterion chosen after the first evaluation of qualifications and publications was – in order to make the selection as transparent and fair as possible – consistent and long-term empirical research. This declaration sounds like a public complaint about the “overcrowding of qualified candidates for a single position”, which was also made during the interviews. Furthermore, the third assessment referred explicitly to excellence in regard to several candidates selected for the shortlist. This report defined excellence as the co-presence of features such as strong experience at international institutions, high levels of research, teaching and scientific activity. Nonetheless, the candidates excluded were also considered to be outstanding scholars with remarkable potential. Internationalization – from publishing to participation and management of research programmes and teams – was the decisive criterion for the shortlist.

As regards the fourth competition, the main reasons for exclusion from the shortlist were limitations in teaching and research, and a profile not pertinent to that required by the announcement. The qualities most frequently cited for admission to the shortlist were the following: a high-level educational profile, participation in international research programmes and networks, relevant teaching activity, and high-level international publications.

The evaluations reported for the fifth selection were the most detailed. They comprised the referee evaluations (which were seldom mentioned in the other reports) and the ranking of the H- and G-indexes. At the same time, they were more quantitative and descriptive and less analytical than the other assessments. Besides internationalization and research activities, the committee report focused on participation and organization of international conferences.

The last report was conversely very concise and briefly described the features appreciated by the committee members: scientific experience, teaching and research activity, international publications, and networks.

Finally, the substance of scientific publications was described in detail by only one report, while in all the others publications were merely listed.

Postdoctoral fellowship recruitment processes: actual practices

Since January 2010 to January 2014 the selections for post-doc have been 17, thus divided: 2 in 2010; 4 in 2011; 6 in 2012; 5 in 2013. 11 selections have been applied by 1 candidate, 4 by 2 to 4 candidates, and 2 by 9 to 13. The women appointed have been 12. See annex 1 for detailed information on the sex and number of candidates and committee members and on the duration of the position.

As already mentioned, the main difference between RTD-a and post-doctoral positions consists in the kind of tasks required: while the RTD is an assistant professor position (even if temporary) considered part of the academic staff of the Department, the post-doctoral awards consist of grants focused on specific research projects. Due to this narrower scope of the post-doctoral awards, the announcements usually require high level of autonomy and skills closely related to the tasks involved in the research project.

Other more general competences are autonomy at work [...] Autonomy that involves both the development of the specific question to be researched, developed, and then to bring it to a publication, because by now this is what we do. What is needed is a very output oriented person, most of all if s/he must work in projects (Interviewee_8_W)

Confidence with the international dimension, research experience. So in my case it's knowing how to conduct an interview, how to take ethnographic notes, also being able to switch rapidly between the empirical and theoretical dimensions, and certainly the relevance of the candidate's scientific production to the topics and themes of the research, and the quality of his or her publications (Interviewee_7_W)

Since 2010 the large majority of post-doctoral grants have been financed by external local and European funds within broader research programmes. The skills required and the need to employ a scholar able to enter the research team and do the fieldwork makes this kind of grant designed for very particular profiles. Thus, although the

announcements are public by law, there are often no more than one or two candidates, and they are frequently already known to the supervisor:

The official procedure requires us, and I think rightly so, to hold selections and competitions. But it must be said that in our case it's a procedure that in many situations is rather fictitious. In the sense that the grant is awarded on the basis of external requests. And of course, those who contact me do so because they know that I'm an expert on certain things. The next step is to create the team, and how to do it? I do so on the basis of my knowledge of the people available, who don't have other positions, and of course with an expertise on the research commissioned (Interviewee_6_M)

I believe that in the composition of a group it is absolutely important to include persons coming from outside. In order to stir the pot. But in Italy this is very difficult... So, on the one hand one tries to give continuity to persons one knows to be valid and then one also tries to empower them or to accompany them in their development. But this is not the main goal. Ideally, one should have a mix between persons who have already socialized in their environment, but also with a vision from outside. We have definitely difficulty doing an external recruitment here (Interviewee_8_W)

Even more than for RTD positions, the relational skills implicitly requested are essential, because the post-doctoral fellow must work in a team.

There's an element of agreement that goes beyond the mere stipulation of a work contract and is entirely entrusted to the capacity, intelligence, and willingness of whoever gives the job, the head of the research project (Interviewee_7_W)

There are people who are a bit inadequate or unsuitable, and perhaps also because team work requires close cohesion. [...] So the creation of a team is a very delicate moment, and you have to find people who possibly know each other, who have already worked together (Interviewee_6_M)

Concerning gender differences, the positions expressed by postdoc committee members are not different from those of the RTD committee members.

I have recruited both women and men. Frankly speaking, I don't believe gender played any role in the selection. Because in the end what counts is what people have done. If they become valid candidates or not. [...] Thereafter, here we are talking of selections at the beginning of the career, so hardly potential post-docs have kids (Interviewee_8_W)

The idea of meritocracy based on gender neutrality is confirmed and the difficulty, particularly for women, to have children during the early stages of the academic career is underlined.

Finally, it is important to highlight that the last postdoctoral post funded by the Department was opened in 2010. Afterwards the post-doctoral positions have all been financed by local, national or international funds. Thus, whereas previously a post-doctoral fellowship was considered to be the first stage of the academic career, the current postdoctoral positions are more focused on a specific aim of the funding research programme. In this way, post-doctoral fellowships have become more similar to scholarships and partially lost their former function, i.e. the first step of an academic career.

The Actual Criteria in the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science

We interviewed three committee members for the post-doctoral selections and two for the RTD-a recruitment. Only one of them was a woman, owing to the fact that the gender composition of the DISI is strongly asymmetric: out of 45 full and associated professors, only 3 are women. The interviews conducted are summarised in the table below:

N. Interview	Sex	Postdoctoral Research Fellowship/RTD Committee	Position in the Committee
9	W	Post-doc	Chair
10	M	Post-doc	Chair
11	M	Post-doc	Chair
12	M	RTD	Chair
13	M	RTD	Chair

The Information Engineering and Computer Science Department (DISI) was recently founded, with a strong investment on three main aspects: internationalization of research and staff; multidisciplinary approaches adopted by the research teams; integration within prestigious international research networks. These factors were frequently cited by the interviewees, who repeatedly emphasized not only the importance given to the presence of international scholars but also to having mixed-nationality research teams, which require applicants to have high relational and linguistic skills. Moreover, the extensive involvement in European projects explains

the high number of post-doctoral selections in the period considered. Instead, only two RTD-a positions were opened between January 2010 and January 2014.

As we could interview only two RTD-a committee members, we will merge the common points that emerged regarding the criteria adopted in the selection procedures, and then analyse the specificities of the cases examined in two dedicated sections.

Some aspects of the skills required for both post-doctoral and RTD-a positions refer to an evident and shared idea of dynamism and internationalisation. The rhetoric on the internationalisation and specificities of the DISI as an interdisciplinary and dynamic department recurred in every interview conducted with the committee members, both for post-doctoral and RTD-a selections. Together with excellence and meritocracy, these broader concepts are deducible from the description of the specific competences required by the selections, in a framework where 'top', 'autonomy' and 'freedom' were the terms used to describe the best candidates.

In this frame, the interviewees illustrated the evaluation processes by highlighting the separation between the 'objective' and 'subjective' phases of the selection procedure, where on the one hand formal criteria were used to make the procedure more objective and fair, but on the other, subjective and relational aspects were considered important as well. Indeed, the 'objectivity' of the quantitative indicators was associated by all the interviewees with the subjective and qualitative perspective adopted during the various phases of the evaluation.

As previously illustrated, the DISI is involved in several international projects and hosts a high percentage of European and international students and scholars, making so-called internationalization a characteristic that traverses all the department's teaching and research activities. The research teams are composed of people from all over the world, and this requires a high level of adaptability, relational skill, and mobility:

It is an added value, and it enables a person to integrate much better into a work group which is heterogeneous and international. Almost all our work groups comprise people from different countries, for whom the common language must be English. The ability to interact with, and relate to, people from other cultures and other experiences is an important factor (Interviewee_11_M)

The ability to converse with different nationalities and cultures is valued, as well as the capacity to cross the disciplinary fields composing the department's heterogeneous research programs, to which people from different countries bring different languages, skills, experiences and knowledge. Mobility between boundaries and languages is of key importance for the selection process because it concerns the team's efficient functioning and the achievement of goals. The interviewees considered the possession of multi- or interdisciplinary skills a *conditio sine qua non* for participation in international research programs and teams. The traditional frame of excellence and meritocracy, which puts the scientist in the ivory tower as a lonely producer of science, is here substituted by the importance of collective and interdisciplinary research:

I believe that research can only be multidisciplinary, conducted by a group, because an outstanding researcher is somebody who is firstly valid as a person. So I don't believe in the philosophy of someone who has a bunch of slaves [...] You have to set people free, so that they can make choices, whether to stay in a group or in another. Freedom emerges from autonomy (Interviewee_12_M)

Here excellence is the ability to work with people from different backgrounds, being able to apply methods and techniques of the community of origin, but adapted to the new context. For me, flexibility and the ability to adapt to new contexts are part of the excellence of research (Interviewee_9_W)

The above excerpt is notable for the association between multi-disciplinarity and the researcher's humanity, and the relation between the notions of freedom and autonomy. Autonomy here assumes the meaning of freedom (which does not mean solitude) and the capacity to move among different contexts within multi- and interdisciplinary projects and international networks, which are by definition collective. Concerning the formal criteria, they are mainly used in the first stage of the selection process in order quantitatively to measure correspondence to the requirements stated by the announcement. According to the committee members, the formal criteria are the "necessary but not sufficient conditions" for shortlisting the applicants. In other words, there is a twofold process at this stage: an 'aseptic' quantitative one, where publications, PhD outcomes and previous research experience are taken in account; and a second one relative to the broader CV and its pertinence to the content of the position announced:

As in all calls for applications, the necessary conditions are certified skills and especially a curriculum which certifies certain abilities and a high number of publications, and which guarantees fulfilment of a quantitative criterion consisting of bibliometric indicators: this is the initial screening stage, a first ranking that is done almost aseptically, after which there's a committee that evaluates the various curricula (Interviewee_12_M)

However, the quantitative aspect is decisive in avoiding... because, you know, during interviews you can always make mistakes, but quantitative parameters and the letter of recommendation from a top person make the difference, because they counter-balance the subjective feeling (Interviewee_10_M)

The first stage is considered necessary in order to 'neutralize' all possible subjective biases by using objective parameters, thus equalizing the rankings to which the committee will then apply more specific criteria referring to the personal and academic skills required by the announcement.

There were two academic dimensions: one was the bibliometric evaluation of the academic production, and the other was the institutions that the applicants came from. We based ourselves on this. I say 'we' but I mean a practice frequent at the DISI whereby we take a list of institutions present in international rankings (Interviewee_11_M)

The candidate is represented by reference letters, which give not entirely objective, but also subjective information. H-index parameters, etcetera, have to be considered, but we have to take into account not only the number but also the journals in which they've been published (Interviewee_12_M)

In the first phase, also the reference letters are considered, and unlike at the other Department, in this field the 'top' peer's endorsement of a candidate is quite decisive, due to the credit given to the relative international scientific community. The references represent one of the 'subjective' parts of the first stage of evaluation, and their importance derives from some implicit and non-quantifiable elements, which in the academic world are as important as the most quantitative index used. The first element concerns the prestige of the scholar who has written the reference letter, his or her status in the international scientific debate, and his or her research experience. Secondly, through this kind of implicit but wide acknowledged agreement, reference

letters link the candidate to one or more networks, the importance of which can be measured by the committee members.

The broader your network and the better its members, the better you are as well, because in the networks of top people, if you're no good, you're excluded... (Interviewee_10_M)

The aspect of trust in the scientific community recurs in regard to international networks and the citations system, which is currently a controversial issue. Indeed, it is quite well known that, because the citations system has become a core criterion for academic selections, international groups have reproduced a distorted mechanism of reciprocal citation within the same network. Despite this, according to some interviewees, 'top' scholars have an outstanding score, and stand above the 'mediocre' rankings.

Finally, as in the DSRS Department, in the conducted interviews specific attention was paid on gender differences. In this case gender is mentioned when talking about the numeric presence of women.

As regards gender, the only IT sector where you can find women is computer interaction [...] there's a large amount of intersectionality, so at the moment I think we're fifty-fifty, which is unique here. It's true that developers, geeks, etcetera, tend more to be men, while women are more from anthropology or such like, but even then there are good synergies among people working together (Interviewee_9_W)

While the three-year degree program is intended only for Italy and courses are taught in Italian, the master and doctoral programs, and then in research, we have a policy that is open, European, international, so that we can reach countries where this gender problem doesn't exist, or is not as obvious, with regard to scientific and technical subjects (Interviewee_11_M)

In some research teams women represent nowadays almost half the members of some groups, even though their profiles still pertain to the humanities. The intersectionality between nationality and gender seems to be important for overcoming the gender bias: indeed, the department's international openness allows the inclusion of women from foreign countries where the gender bias is less severe. This can solicit a more symmetric gender relationship within research teams.

Finally, it is interesting to point out that one of the interviewees described the few women enrolled on the postgraduate and master courses, or applying for post-

doctoral posts in computer sciences, as more talented and motivated than men, probably due to the greater commitment that they have to demonstrate.

They've worked their backsides off, they've had to do. They're really determined, they've got an extra gear with respect to their male colleagues, they're outstanding and they also have a relational advantage (Interviewee_9_W)

Nevertheless, this picture is at odds with a context where only three women have permanent positions and the entire selection process and all the research teams are headed by men. Indeed, although the international strategy had increased the enrolment of women on master and PhD courses, their presence in senior positions is significantly low. Similarly as in the case of the Department of Sociology and Social Research, this phenomenon is imputed to two causes: on the one hand, the structural lack of welfare policies dedicated to motherhood; on the other the hegemonic masculine culture widespread in the broader society, not within the university.

In my opinion, the selection happens ahead, as associate professor. A woman has an intrinsic disadvantage, but not because there are sexist men in our department, but because if you want to have a child, you cannot help it but have it (Interviewee_10_M)

Whilst for some interviewees the 'intrinsic disadvantage' of women consists in maternity, one claims that motherhood can also be used as an alibi for women who decide to sacrifice part of their careers for their families:

But I wouldn't want it to become an alibi, because if it becomes an alibi, then I'm sorry, a woman who puts off having children for years because she can't afford an apartment, because she isn't married, because she doesn't have... I don't know, and then giving up a child, I should penalize her with respect to another, who has a child, and then give her a less secure position. Does it seem right to you? (Interviewee_12_M)

Finally, some interviewees added some self-reflexive remarks about their responsibilities on the low presence of women at the DISI Department, and described some recent attempts to overcome the gender gap after the bachelor level.

I understood this later, when there was this visiting professor from Toronto who saw the announcement and asked me: "But how come you don't do anything for women?" "For me the best one wins." And he said "No, it doesn't work like that." In fact, then I appointed *** [a woman]. But I don't think there are enough women in my department, and it's partly my fault. But I did it out of ignorance (Interviewee_10_M)

The more women there are at masters level, the more women there are at doctoral level, the more women there could be with research grants and therefore at the university. We have to start working (Interviewee_11_M)

In conclusion, although gender asymmetries and their social, cultural and structural causes were well-acknowledged by the committee members of the DISI, what did not emerge from the interviews was a critical reflection on the relationship between gender and specific academic fields, that in the case of women means an automatic and taken-for-granted association with the “softer” part of computer science.

RTD-a recruitment processes: actual practices

As said in the first section, for the RTD-a selections we interviewed only two committee members because there had been only two RTD-a selections.

According to the department’s approach, the evaluation process begins with the selection of the committee members, one of whom is chosen from a foreign university. The point of view of a professor from an international university is considered decisive for a more balanced judgment. Moving to the criteria followed for selection, one of the interviewees expressed his disappointment for the strict regulation which imposes to artificially define a profile which cannot actually exist:

Instead of evaluating people according to what they do and how they present themselves, they make a ranking. They think that’s what you do to get a good researcher. Do you remember Frankenstein? Then there’s a theorem, look I’m an engineer, a mathematician... there’s a theorem that says that if you sum the optima, this doesn’t mean that you get the optimum (Interviewee_12_M)

On RTD-a selections, the problem is that many of these criteria are there, but they must be used with caution, as one cannot have the same attitude for an RTD-a selection and for an higher profile selection... Such criteria are for sure quality indicators, but for a RTD-a applicant I wouldn’t dare to say that the candidate is excellent, I would rather say promising (Interviewee_13_M)

The difference between a pre-defined formal criteria assessment and evaluation of the qualities of a particular candidate seems to refer to the difference between a top-down and a bottom-up approach. In other words, instead of adhering to pre-determined qualities which candidates must possess, excellence can be measured within the concrete research process: for instance, in terms of the researcher’s proven

capacity to recognise his or her shortcomings and try to remedy them by interweaving interdisciplinary and proactive relations within the research team or network.

Finally, some reflections are offered about the recent institution of the RTD positions, which have substituted the previously permanent positions as assistant professors.

With this motivation it was decided to create these temporary research posts, so that the person could demonstrate their ability in that time period, before accessing the position, and then win a selection procedure, after which in this three-year period exploit their experience and demonstrate, for the following three years, that they were valid enough (Interviewee_12_M)

The temporariness of the contract and the fact that a tenure track is not foreseen seems to be considered as less problematic than it is in the Department of Sociology and Social Research. In the next research activities we will inquire the reasons of such a small number of RTD positions opened at the DISI Department.

The analysis of the RTD-a reports

The first RTD-a selection, announced by DR 654 2011, had only one candidate. The assessment expressed by the three committee members exemplifies how excellence can be described in this field. Besides the list of teaching posts at “prestigious international universities”, “impressive scientific production” and “exceptional achievements”, the terms used by each committee member to describe the candidate’s skills were, for example, “original and innovative” and “more than qualified”. The final collegial judgment underlined the candidate’s “strong competence in the field”, his “remarkable publication record in prestigious international journals”, and finally the “excellent evaluation of the candidate”.

The second selection, issued with DR 19 2013, received applications from two women. We obtained only the final judgment relative to the one appointed. Her profile was lower than that of the other candidate, but she was nevertheless considered optimal because of her CV, teaching activity, and publications.

Importance was given to the temporal continuity of her research and her integration in international networks.

Postdoctoral fellowship recruitment processes: actual practices

As already mentioned, from the beginning of 2010 to the beginning of 2014, more than one hundred positions for postdoctoral research fellowships were opened. However, it was possible to analyse only the data from the beginning of 2011 to the beginning of 2014. Indeed, the postdoctoral positions opened when the DISI Department was part of the Faculty of Engineering are not available. Consequently, we consider totally 90 postdoctoral selection procedures, opened in 2011-2012-2013. Specifically the positions were obtained by 70 men and 22 women (See annex 1 for more detailed information).

Moving to the actual practices, coherently with the general rhetoric on internationalisation expressed by the DISI, almost all the interviewees complained about the difficulty of finding profiles matching the requirements announced for the post-doctoral grants, which are always linked to practical research outputs and shaped around the objectives of the project. Nevertheless, a particularity is that the applicative field is often local, and this paradoxically excludes all the international candidates who do not speak Italian.

More generally, one of the actual practices mainly and almost explicitly adopted before the selection procedure is the prior identification of the most suitable candidate by asking members of the network about the availability of researchers who fit the requirements. In fact, although the calls are published widely and internationally, the bureaucracy and the slowness of the system prevent the real circulation of the announcements.

The main difference with respect to the Department of Sociology and Social Research is the common practice to invite for a short term collaboration young researchers who eventually become candidates for postdoctoral positions. This could partly explain the fact that almost always only one candidate applies for post-doctoral fellowships.

Then she'd somehow also expressed her interest in applying. So a screening was made by my post docs. This was before the formal process. And when I talked to her, I thought that she was independent, determined, enthusiastic, that she believed in herself. Anyway, she came here, we had her give a seminar, she talked to my people. She said that she liked them, so soon afterwards she started. This pattern of interaction is the standard one (Interviewee_10_M)

The competences required for postdoctoral positions are usually always the same: management skills, previous experience in the same scientific area, and pertinence to the scientific field. Moreover, features like autonomy, enthusiasm and determination stand out, and they highlight the emotional and subjective skills required at this selection stage.

Differently from the DSRS Department, in the case of the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Sciences, sometimes also professional and technical skills relating to the specific subject of the program can be required.

1.4. Conclusion

What emerges by the analysis of the actual practices adopted in the two departments considered, is that all the procedure's steps are characterized by ambivalences amid which the committee members try to identify the most suitable – or the most accountable – candidate.

In both departments' practices we noted a discrepancy between the formal and the subjective criteria used for the selections.

At the Department of Sociology and Social Research, a first ambivalence concerns the apparent contradiction between the bureaucratic and the business-like logics that inspire the new norms of RTD recruitment, where the necessary accountability of the overall procedure can contrast with the department's discretionary final power of choice. The same ambivalence shapes the relations between the role of the committee and the strategic choices of the department within the procedure, with the risk of clashes between the committee's evaluation and the decisions taken by the departmental board.

At the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Sciences formal criteria are utilised as a first objective selection of the candidates. Being strictly defined by quantitative indexes, parameters and rankings, this first stage of evaluation allows, in the board members' opinion, the equality of shortlists. Hence, the subjective aspects of evaluation are used in a second stage on a range of high qualified candidates.

Even if some of these arguments are present also in the interviews about post-doctoral selections, it is clear that in these situations the criteria of choice are more focused on the specific necessities of the research programmes.

The concept of excellence is not often used by the interviewees of both departments, and in some cases it is even critically considered, because of its vagueness and abstraction. However, when it is used, it is mainly referred to internationality (publications, networks and experiences), autonomy, and high quality of research and scientific activities.

Finally, gender equality is not considered to be an issue for meritocracy. Although gender bias is recognized, at the same time it is delegated to the broader society: the only gender-related problem, and always referred to women, is the lack of social services for motherhood and children, while the possibility that an organisational culture influences recruitment procedures within academia was not considered by almost all the interviewees.

References

- Addis, E., Pagnini, C. (2010) *Scientific Excellence. Meta-analysis of gender and science research- Topic report*, available at www.genderandscience.org.
- Allred, P., Miller, T. (2007) “Measuring What’s Valued Or Valuing What’s Measured? Knowledge Production and the Research Assessment Exercise”, in V. Gillies, H. Lucey (eds) *Power, Knowledge and the Academy: The Institutional is Political*, London, Palgrave.
- Benschop, Y., Brouns, M. (2003) “Crumbling Ivory Towers: Academic Organizing and its Gender Effects”, *Gender, Work and Organization*, 10 (2): 194–212.
- Pascuzzi, G. (2012) *Università: Diario di una svolta autoritaria. La provincializzazione dell’ateneo di Trento*, Trento, Il Margine.
- Van Den Brink, M., Benschop, Y. (2011) “Gender practices in the construction of academic excellence: Sheep with five legs”, *Organizations*, 19(4), 507–24.

Annex 1

Temporary assistant professor (RTD-a) positions opened at the Department of Sociology and Social Research (01.01.2010 – 01.01.2014)

DR 525 2010 SPS/07

N. male applicants	N. female applicants	N. of shortlisted men	N. of shortlisted women	Male committee members	Female committee members	Sex of the chair	Sex of the candidate appointed
7	13	3	4	3	0	M	M

DR 526 2010 SPS/10

N. male applicants	N. female applicants	N. of shortlisted men	N. of shortlisted women	Male committee members	Female committee members	Sex of the chair	Sex of the candidate appointed
11	11	4	6	2	1	M	W

DR 87 2012 11/A5

N. male applicants	N. female applicants	N. of shortlisted men	N. of shortlisted women	Male committee members	Female committee members	Sex of the chair	Sex of the candidate appointed
9	15	3	3	3	0	M	M

DR 88 2012 14 C/1

N. male applicants	N. female applicants	N. of shortlisted men	N. of shortlisted women	Male committee members	Female committee members	Sex of the chair	Sex of the candidate appointed
13	10	3	4	3	0	M	W

DR 89 2012 14/C2

N. male applicants	N. female applicants	N. of shortlisted men	N. of shortlisted women	Male committee members	Female committee members	Sex of the chair	Sex of the candidate appointed
8	3	5	2	3	0	M	M

DR 90 2010 14/D1

N. male applicants	N. female applicants	N. of shortlisted men	N. of shortlisted women	Male committee members	Female committee members	Sex of the chair	Sex of the candidate appointed
12	8	3	3	1	2	M	W

Postdoctoral Fellowships opened at the Department of Sociology and Social Research from the 1st of January 2010 to the 1st of January 2014

Year	N. of male applicants	N. of female applicants	Male committee members	Female committee members	Sex of the committee chair	Sex of the candidate appointed
2010	2	7	3	0	M	W
2010	0	1	1	2	M	W
2011	0	1	2	1	M	W
2011	0	2	2	1	M	W
2011	0	1	2	1	W	W
2011	1	0	2	1	W	M
2012	2	0	2	1	W	M
2012	0	1	2	1	W	W
2012	0	1	2	1	W	W
2012	1	3	4	0	M	W
2012	8	5	4	0	M	W
2012	1	0	1	2	M	M
2013	1	2	2	1	W	M
2013	1	0	2	1	M	M
2013	0	1	1	2	W	W
2013	0	1	1	2	W	W
2013	0	1	1	2	W	W
TOT	17	27	34	19	8M/9W	5M/12W

Duration of the Postdoctoral Fellowships opened at the Department of Sociology and Social Research from the 1st of January 2010 to the 1st of January 2014

Duration of the position (months)	N. positions	Female appointed candidate	Male appointed candidate
12	10 (3 renewable)	7 (1 Renewable)	3 (2 renewable)
15	1	0	1
17	1	0	1
24	5	4	1

Temporary assistant professor (RTD-a) positions opened at the Department of Department of Information Engineering and Computer Sciences from the 1st of January 2010 to the 1st of January 2014

DR 654 2011 09/F1

N. male applicants	N. female applicants	N. of shortlisted men	N. of shortlisted women	Male committee members	Female committee members	Sex of the chair	Sex of the candidate appointed
1	0	1	0	3	0	M	M

DR 19 2013 09/F2

N. male applicants	N. female applicants	N. of shortlisted men	N. of shortlisted women	Male committee members	Female committee members	Sex of the chair	Sex of the candidate appointed
0	2	0	1	3	0	M	W

Postdoctoral Fellowships opened at the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Sciences from the 1st of January 2010 to the 1st of January 2014

Year	N. of male applicants	N. of female applicants	Male committee members	Female committee members	Sex of the committee chair	Sex of the candidate appointed
2011	2	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	0	1	3	0	M	W
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	0	1	3	0	M	W
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	0	1	3	0	M	W
2011	0	1	3	0	M	W
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	2	1	M	M
2011	0	1	3	0	M	W
2011	0	1	2	1	M	W
2011	0	1	2	1	M	W

2011	1	0	2	1	M	M
2011	1	0	2	1	W	M
2011	0	1	3	0	M	W
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	0	1	3	0	M	W
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	0	1	3	0	M	W
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2011	0	0	3	0	M	
2011	1	0	2	1	W	M
2011	0	1	3	0	M	W
2011	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	0	1	3	0	M	W
2012	0	1	3	0	M	W
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	0	1	3	0	M	W
2012	0	1	3	0	M	W
2012	1	0	2	1	M	M
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	0	1	3	0	M	W
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	2	0	3	0	M	2 M
2012	0	0	2	1	M	
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	0	1	3	0	M	W
2012	0	1	2	1	W	W
2012	1	0	3	0	M	M
2012	0	1	2	1	M	W
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	0	1	3	0	M	W
2013	1	0	1	1	W	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	0	1	3	0	M	W
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	W	M

2013	3	0	3	0	M	3 M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	2	1	W	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	2	0	2	1	M	2 M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	0	1	3	0	M	W
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
2013	1	0	2	1	M	M
2013	1	0	3	0	M	M
TOT	71	22	255	14	84M/6W	70/22W

Duration of the Postdoctoral Fellowships opened at the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Sciences from the 1st of January 2010 to the 1st of January 2014

Duration position (months)	N. positions	W	M
12	71	14	57
15	1	0	1
18	1	0	1
22	2	0	2
24	6 (3 renewable)	3 (2 renewable)	3 (1 renewable)
33	1	1	0
36	10 (1renewable)	4	6 (1 renewable)

2. Belgium

2.1. Introduction

We will give a short description of the institutional context in which this analysis on recruitment processes and criteria was done for C-and D-level¹ engagement in two institutes SSH and STEM at the Catholic University of Louvain in French-speaking Belgium. The SSH Institute for the Analysis of Change in Contemporary and Historical Societies (IACCHOS) is a scientific confederation consisting of 12 research centres entirely or partially inter-reliant: these are organized either according to specific variations on a topic; or as interdisciplinary centres; or as inter-sector centres; or as network centres. There are approximately 200 junior and senior researchers and academics working in IACCHOS, which are from sociology, anthropology, history, psychology and educational sciences faculties and around 20 administrative coordinators. The management of the institute is headed by the president, and has governing organs that are the council of the institute, the bureau of the institute and the management board of the institute.

The STEM Earth and Life Institute (ELI) consist of five research poles. These five research poles are again organised into (inter) sectorial, inter-institute and institutional platforms. This institute holds more than 300 senior and junior scientists – bioengineers, physicists, agronomists, ecologists, geographers, microbiologists – in order to study together the evolution of the agro-systems, the ecosystems, the water

¹ Concerning the specific target of the GARCIA project – researchers at the early stages of their scientific careers – a key consideration needs to be highlighted. As reported in the She Figures report – in the methodological notes (2012: 135) – “the statistics on the seniority of academic staff are collected at the national level through Higher Education and R&D Surveys or directly from higher education institutions as part of their own monitoring systems and from administrative records. It is important to note that these data are not always completely cross-country comparable as the seniority grades are not yet part of a formal international classification”. Though A and B grades may identify roughly the same academic position in all countries, corresponding to full and associate professors respectively, in the scientific career at an international level, C and D grades refer to different fractions of the population of researchers, depending on the country. For instance, whilst in some cases only researchers with a permanent position are included in the C level, in some others, also those with a temporary position are considered, or partially included. Among the countries included in the GARCIA consortium, it should be stressed that only Italy and Slovenia classify PhD holders (mainly postdocs) in the D level. The other beneficiary countries (Belgium, The Netherlands, Switzerland, Iceland, Austria) classify researchers with a PhD at the early stage of their career in the C level. With the aim to make a qualitative comparison between countries, we decided to re-classify for all countries the research positions. Therefore, we included in the D level postdocs or positions without the prospect of a permanent contract; and in the C level positions that are either a tenure track (a temporary position that is expected to become permanent in the long run) or the first permanent academic position (for instance assistant professor).

cycle and the climate and to develop new production methods and biotechnologies for a sustainable development.

The recruitment process we looked at in this report for UCL and at the two institutes pertains to academic tenure-track and postdoctoral recruitment only, and not scientific recruitment, which is second type of scientific career path that can be taken in Belgian universities, which is entirely funded by the National Funding for Research and Science (FNRS), however with the implantation of the appointed candidates on a permanent basis in a given university, here the UCL.

There are therefore two types of scientific careers with the following positions:

- Doctor-assistant (1er assistant);
- Postdoc (by scholarship or contract) or research assistant (contractual, PhD holders);
- Assistant professor, probatory 3 – 5 years before permanent tenure-track nomination (chargé de cours en période probatoire);
- Associate professor (chargé de cours): tenure-track;
- Professor (professeur): tenured;
- Full (ordinary or extra-ordinary) professor (professeur ordinaire ou extra-ordinaire): tenured.

And in the French-speaking Community there are temporary FNRS researchers and permanently appointed FNRS researchers:

- Doctoral candidate;
- Postdoctoral researcher (Chargé de recherche FNRS);
- Research associate (chercheur qualifié);
- Senior research associate (maître de recherches);
- Research director (directeur de recherches);

funded by the national Fund for Scientific Research (FNRS).

Sometimes, although not necessarily, an FNRS permanent researcher is simultaneously also a recognized associate professor/professor/full professor at the given university and therefore can be considered a second tenure-track path. These two status can sometimes be not synchronized (for example senior research associate, but also full professor) So, in the Belgian French-speaking universities, tenure track or tenured is to have a permanent position and be recognized by the

institution (and law) as belonging to the academic body through two career paths: professorship and permanent position funded by the National Fund of Scientific Research (FNRS).

So the appointee for FNRS undergoes both a formal recruitment process (by only documentation “dossier”) by the FNRS committees, and then a second evaluation by UCL heads for approval of the candidate chosen and granted the funding by FNRS. However, we chose not to analyse this recruitment process, as this would imply a more extensive research of the FNRS body and organization as a separate institution. In terms of figures and evolutions of members of committees and distribution of sex, some general longitudinal figures were made by our informal team member Edithe Antoine, who is the administrative coordinator for mapping gender policies at UCL, which we have integrated here with her kind approval. The following table showing the proportion of women recruited with respect to the female turnout of candidates presenting applications.

Proportion of women recruited in proportion to women applicants

Table 1 – Evolution of the proportion of women actually recruited in relation to women applicants – between 2009 et 2013

Source: UCL

It is interesting to note that with the exception of 2009, the disparity between turnout and recruits is not vast, but certainly more present before 2012.

There is also a table generated about figures of proportions of women in recruitment committees over the last five years made by the administrative coordinator of the rectors' council, who is implicated in the HR management of recruitment processes. This person made these figures on her own account for interest sakes, without any formal task given to her to do so. Please find the table in the Annex.

Despite the table of relatively less differences in women presenting applications and those retained, this second table (see the Annex) can show us that the turnout of women is considerably lower to men for academic posts, and that this is the case for both SSH and STEM sectors. Moreover, the composition of committees has often as much as one third less females than males, a percentage that persists for presidents of committees. However, there are generally fewer female academics existing in institutes and faculties in the first place, if you look also at the number recruited.

2.2. Formal Criteria

For this part of 7.1, we have analyzed 3 job descriptions each for the STEM and SSH institutes, Earth Life Institute and Institute of Analysis for Change in the Contemporary and Historical Society (IACCHOS) and Earth Life Institute (ELI) between 2010 and 2013; these were all the job descriptions that were passed on to us so far by the responsible persons in the HR departments. More job descriptions were promised, but have not yet passed on to us unfortunately; this will probably be the case beyond the deadline for this report. For the HR documents, we were more successful, as we had the opportunity to have a meeting with the responsible administrative coordinator within the rectors' office/team, who gave us the general criteria formulated by the rectors' council to all the recruitment committees in UCL, including some notes that would otherwise not have been accessible. We were therefore able to make a comparative analysis between the criteria in the job descriptions and those in the rector's HR documents.

Job Descriptions: SSH

The first section includes some (not all) job descriptions of vacancies which were advertised between 2010 and 2013 in the SSH department IACCHOS at UCL, which are for assistant professors (C level positions).

How generic or specific is the job profile in terms of academic discipline?

Post “Sociology of Education and of Socialization” (1 EFT) – Full time – SSH/IACCHOS –as per 1. Sep 2013

The description of the scientific part of the work is on a very large macro-level scale; research on the transformation of school systems, of its links with other spheres, such as family, media, formation and employment in contemporary societies, both on the international and national level, specifically mentioning the Belgian context. A need to develop the theoretical work in this domain is recommended. All these orientations have to be achieved or aimed at informing oneself about these issues during the first two years of the mandate.

Collaboration in his (description addressed to as male) research with colleagues from the institute (IACCHOS) and in particular an interdisciplinary centre is expected, keeping in mind this focus on interdisciplinary (Psychology, Educational Sciences, History in particular).

Teaching will be undertaken in the faculty of economic, social, and political and communication sciences.

The language of instruction is indicated as French and English, and the nature of teaching is indicated as inclusive of theoretical, thematic and methodological contents. The portfolio of teaching is indicated to comprise the domain of sociology of education, of formation, of education policies in different teaching programs of the faculty, and more theoretical or methodological courses in both Bachelor and Masters programs. The person will need to honor (wording) the inter-faculty engagements in terms of courses.

Openness to using ITC is required to deploy in his teaching and in his contact with the students.

Doctoral supervision will be required to give in these domains and participation in the doctoral school in social sciences.

Post “Family structures, households and intergenerational relations” (1 EFT) – full time – SSH/IACCHOS – as per 1 Sep. 2013

This description is more specific and short: The post is described as comprised of research to be conducted in a pluridisciplinary perspective on demography of the family and of its determinants: methods and analyses of the family and the household, evolution of family structures, of the construction of couples and of the descendents, of ruptures in unions, of age transitions, of parent – children – grandchildren relationships, mono-parental or composite family structures, intercultural family structures, and co-existence of multiple generations. The focus on the development of family demography is to be particularly on Europe. The institute affiliation is indicated, as well as the particular centre, which again is an interdisciplinary centre.

Post “Teacher Education and Training” (1 EFT) – Full time – SSH/IACCHOS – as per 1. Sep 2013

A very short description of the research and teaching is given: only specified as “research in teacher education, instructional and curriculum development, or professional development of teachers. Collaboration with colleagues from other disciplines is emphasized. Teaching is simply specified as comprising the above in the particular faculty.

How is excellence and/or quality described in the job descriptions?

The requirements include having a renowned scientific experience demonstrated by publications on an international level. And having the qualifications to conduct scientific research of a high level, capacity of animating, leading a team of researchers. Quality is furthermore described as ensuring of research activities and of teaching, of international visibility and that within the university. Also of having an experience and aptitude in university teaching. To be able to be creative and innovative in pedagogy and interdisciplinary. Also, a contribution to services to the society is listed, in economic, socio-cultural or development domains.

Which criteria are present in the job descriptions?

First criteria mentioned are a doctorate degree in sociology or social sciences (with a sociological orientation) or an equivalent. Publications on an international scale.

Having been abroad for a research study and having significant experience outside of UCL. Teaching experience and aptitude. Teamwork. Linking research and teaching. Creativity, innovation, leadership and conducting research of high level. Knowing written and spoken fluent French and English, or needing to acquire this knowledge in the first two years of the post appointment.

How and to what extent are these criteria specified?

They are listed as “Tasks” on the one hand, and then specified as “Qualifications”, after a more general description of the research and teaching in this post.

Which criterion is dominant in the job descriptions?

These two requirements lists “tasks” and “qualifications” are common to all job descriptions and are general, whereas the first part of the job description is about the research and teaching domains. There is an emphasis on scientific excellence in terms of “high level” publications on international level, but also involvement, conducting and leadership of “high level” research, without any specification about what “high level” involves, apart from internationally renowned, or renown in UCL. Also teamwork is emphasized. Interdisciplinary is emphasized in the social sciences job descriptions in particular: there seems to be a growing pluri-or interdisciplinary perspective to research in different themes or domains. French and English skills seem to feature both in the domain description of the post and in the general criteria.

Is there a difference in required criteria for tenured and non-tenured positions?

Job descriptions for non-tenured positions are not available, as postdoc positions are usually on very informal recruitment procedures without any formal job openings. Mostly for postdoc positions, emails or phone calls are exchanged between supervisor/project leader and person asked or asking for being considered as candidate.

Are there any references to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university?

There are no references to affirmative action/gender equality policies.

Job descriptions: STEM

The second section includes some (not all) job descriptions of vacancies, which were advertised between 2010 and 2013 in the STEM department ELI at UCL, which are for assistant professors (C level positions).

How generic or specific is the job profile in terms of academic discipline?

Post “Chemical procedures for durable development” – full time – as per sep 1. 2011

The research is described as centered around chemical, environmental and agro-alimentary procedures, with a particular emphasis on creating synergies with research groups working on applied chemistry and bio- industries and within STEM centers of the UCL. As examples of research on chemical procedures for durable development the following fields are mentioned: membrane technologies, the production of energetic vectors, the conversion of biomass, green chemistry, renewable chemistry (these two terms particularly indicated in English), or de-pollution.

Teaching is specified as main or co-lecturer in courses according to domains in:

- chemical kinetics and thermo dynamics of multi-phase systems
- genius of procedures and unitary operations
- chemical industry
- treating of gas effluents or modeling of reactors

The teaching is indicated as being situated within specific faculties.

Post “Sciences of the ground” – full time – as per 1. Sep 2010

The general description of the research is quite brief, indicating that the person will conduct research on fundamental and applied research on the role of pedological processes in biochemical cycles, specifically in relation with the occupation of grounds and of the pressures that they undergo (natural ecosystems and anthropises).

Teaching is described as taking place in both Bachelor and Masters programs in ground sciences. The Master courses are specifically focusing on ground-plant relations, on pedogenesis and the fertilization of great types of grounds, on agro-pedological systems in warm regions and the pollution of grounds. Certain teachings

will be based on practical and field work. The appointee is required to participate in framing and supervising masters' theses in the field of environmental sciences and technologies.

Post of Specialist “Agricultural Ecology” – part time 20 % - as of 1 Sep 2013

General description of research to be undertaken in the domains of phytotechnology of praries and of great cultures, with an emphasis on the management of fertility of grounds. The person has to construct (will take care to: wording in French) synergies with research groups active in the field of vegetal ecophysiology and of agro-ecosystems within the Earth and Life Institute.

Teaching is described in detail in the domains of:

- Intergrated management of ground-plant systems
- Praries and routes
- Phytotechnology
- Excursions of pedology and of agricultural and forrest ecology

How is excellence and/or quality described in the job descriptions?

The requirements are exactly the same as in the SSH job descriptions and include having a renowned scientific experience demonstrated by publications on an international level. And having the qualifications to conduct scientific research of a high level, capacity of animating, leading a team of researchers. Quality is furthermore described as ensuring of research activities and of teaching, of international visibility and that within the university. Also of having an experience and aptitude in university teaching. To be able to be creative and innovative in pedagogy and interdisciplinary. Also, a contribution to services to the society is listed, in economic, socio-cultural or development domains.

Specificity in contrast to SSH: teaching listed before research in “tasks”.

Which criteria are present in the job descriptions?

1) PhD in agronomy sciences and biological engineering, in engineering sciences, or chemical sciences, or an equivalent degree. The other criteria are essentially the same as in SSH, but also a capacity to be able to work in a team of teachers/lecturers and of integrating ongoing research in ongoing teaching.

2) PhD in biological engineering or agromonic sciences.

3) PhD in agronomic sciences and biological engineering, or an equivalent degree (subject to evaluation).

Other criteria the same as in SSH and other STEM descriptions.

How and to what extent are these criteria specified?

The same as in SSH, “tasks” and “qualifications”. Some specific qualifications/aptitudes (wording) are particularly mentioned in the general description of the post before the general criteria: Having a scientific experience recognized by international level publications and/or awards, or experience in the industrial context, or in the following domains: kinetic chemistry, genius of procedures and unitary operations applied in chemical industry, agro-or bio industry, or environmental technology.

Interesting point is that for post 3) which is only for 20% part time, the tasks and qualifications are the same as for the full time position.

In 3) description, there is a differentiation made that English and French are necessary for both research and teaching purposes, and need to be acquired in either case, within the first two years of appointment.

Which criterion is dominant in the job descriptions?

Scientific experience, which is described as significant publication in internationally renowned journals, mentioned specifically in the general description of the post, as well as in the list of criteria. Also engaging in research of high level, and of enabling the advancing of UCL in an international context. The aspect of capacity or qualifications in interdisciplinary research seems to be dominant here too.

However, teaching is enlisted before the research capacities; ensuring the teaching in the different study cycles and in continuing formation, and also the supervision of masters’ and PhD thesis as first tasks listed. And then animating research programs. And then only ensuring by undertaking research and teaching, an international visibility of the university. The difference here is that teaching is included in the kind of visibility that is required from the person to be employed. Definitely more emphasis on teaching here.

Is there a difference in required criteria for tenured and non-tenured positions?

There are differences in terms of FNRS researchers and academic tenured positions (see introduction).

Are there any references to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university?

No reference to affirmative action/gender equality policies.

For Post 3): there is a reference on top of the post description page that this offer is addressed to both women and men, despite the male address (the person, he will....) in the text of the description.

HR documents/Statistics

Dimension I: Ethical and professional aspects. The EuraxeSS charter and code for UCL

According to the UCL website and also a document (see the Annex), EURAXESS Rights provides information on the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers. Any institution that employs or funds researchers is asked to respect the 40 principles laid down in these two documents in its human resources strategy. The UCL signed the Charter and Code on 23 January 2006 and reiterated its commitment on 6 July 2010, thereby expressing its determination to support the European initiative and to implement a human resources strategy aimed at improving the recruitment, working conditions and careers of researchers.

In March 2011, the European Commission approved UCL's Human Resources Strategy for Researchers 2011-2014 .and awarded it the logo "HR Excellence in Research". By the end of their first two years of activity, UCL has conducted an internal assessment in order to measure the progress made in implementing its action plan. This document has been approved by the Academic Council on July 1, 2013. HRS4R 2011-2014 - Self-assessment. The aim was that its continuing implementation should help to improve all UCL researchers' working conditions and career advancement. There are four axes of improvement to which UCL has committed itself according to the charter, of which two in particular refer to "recruitment" and another to "promoting equality between men and women":

Dimension II: Recruitment

«The recruitment policy of the UCL strives to be of the highest possible quality. Recruitment procedures are open, effective, and transparent. Selection committees are chosen with the greatest care and bring together the necessary expertise and skills. Candidates receive the necessary information in order to apply in the most advantageous manner. In terms of academic recruitment, the UCL has a policy that is particularly open to outside control. The same also applies to the recruitment of research personnel. At the same time, the UCL is well aware that when researchers are recruited on the basis of funding coming from outside the university or the national science foundation, the posting of research positions is not systematic and international awareness of these positions could be improved. Finally, even though the University attracts a large number of international researchers, the institution would benefit from making its assets as an employer better known outside the borders of the country.»

The objective is named as: Improving the recruitment of all researchers in order to make it more open, transparent, and fair, by the following actions:

1. Professionalise the recruitment of researchers

The UCL will examine its current recruitment procedures for all research positions to improve them, should this be necessary. Whatever the funding source, and whatever the position level, the following features must be systematically present and must be totally explicit:

- The specifications of the required qualifications
- The selection criteria
- The recruitment criteria
- The recruitment procedure and/or selection procedure
- The rights and duties attached to the position

2. Increase openness to internal, external and international recruitment:

- by ensuring the visibility of all open positions by improving the use of the definition and implementation of a communications plan aimed at the continuous promotion of Euraxess Louvain International Desk + Communication Department + Research Administration;
- by promoting the use of the Euraxess Jobs portal;
- by enforcing the systematic publication of positions – especially at the doctoral and post-doctoral levels.

3. Promote internationally the UCL as an employer:

- by relying on the Louvain International Desk (LID). The LID is an administrative structure established recently with a view to co-ordinating initiatives relating to the reception of information for international researchers and students.

Dimension III

Promoting equal opportunity between men and women., with the following objective:

Promoting equal opportunity between male and female researchers and working for a better gender balance in all aspects of research. Actions are as follows:

1. Pursue the analysis of existing initiatives and practices in order to promote their development
2. Encourage examination of the steps that might be undertaken in order to correct the disparities affecting the opportunities of female researchers in their professional life (recruitment, working conditions, work-life balance, etc.)
3. Adopt, in due time, an affirmative action programme

Recruitment Processes and Policy

Postdoctoral recruitment

For the recruitment of postdoctoral researchers there isn't a standardized call for job openings: it is the supervisors who make the selection from case to case, if not choosing someone they have already in mind. Multiple ways of informal proceeding can be observed:

- Supervisor applies to FNRS (National Scientific Research Fund) proposing a project with a particular candidate usually indicated in the proposal with CV: the FNRS then decides, selects or allocates (or not) funding for projects: it is usually a yearly competition at a given date for all universities.
- Supervisor applies to Marie Curie/FSR (European co-funded by National Research Fund): same as above, selection by European Commission and FSR.
- Supervisor applies for project funding to FNRS for temporary postdocs, where then funding is allocated irrespective of candidate and it is up to supervisor to select candidate for any length of contract within the funding time frame.
- Supervisor (with signature from president of institute) applies for project grant from external funding sources, such as European Commission FP7 etc., and then recruitment the researcher.

By-the-hour lectureships

Academic paid by-the-hour lectureships are usually called for as lists of open courses for which lecturers are recruited, internal and external (invited lecturers), who have to submit an application, which is then evaluated and selected by the commission of the schools/departments teaching program, and validated by the dean and the rector.

Formal recruitment procedure of academic posts: C-Level positions

Tenure-track and tenured

Website of UCL under “academic openings” and “procedure”:

“The recruitment of new academics follows Rules of Procedure no. 1, appended to the University Statute (March 2010- This text exist only in French – hereunder “FR”), and is essentially a four-stage process:

The first stage involves collating all the applications and submitting them to the selection committees appointed by the Executive Board. Before this can happen, the vacancies (proposed by the faculties & institutes and approved by the Sector Board) are confirmed by the Executive Board prior to being advertised;

The second is the selection stage. Each selection committee selects the applicant(s) it would like to short-list, i.e. the applicant(s) it would like to interview before identifying the best candidate for the position advertised;

The third stage is when the Executive Board confirms the selection, having met the preferred applicant and read the committee's report, the opinion of the Dean/Head of the Institute and an interview report issued by the Human Resources Department (HR). An e-mail is sent to the successful applicant, offering him/her the post; Unsuccessful candidates will be informed by letter.

The fourth and final stage is when the appointment and associated conditions of appointment are confirmed by the Board of Governors and then by the Board of Trustees (“Pouvoir Organisateur”). The official letter of appointment and all the relevant documentation and information is then sent to the successful applicant(s).

In the formal general webpage for job openings and submitting an application, the following list of requirements as components of the application are given:

- A motivation letter addressed formally to the rector of UCL.
- A detailed CV.

- A complete list of publications and the abstracts of 3 of your most significant and recent publications.
- A text of 3500 characters (spaces included) describing the research project(s) (in the sense of research orientation), which the candidates (male and female given) wish to conduct in the years to come.
- A text of 3500 characters describing the pedagogical project (orientation), where the candidate must describe how he/she wishes to develop their teaching (lectures, works to be submitted, distance learning, active learning etc.). They will indicate the pedagogical questions that they are particularly engaged with.
- A copy of the final degree (PhD).
- 3 letters of recommendation given by 3 scientific renowned persons internationally, and non-UCL members.

An interview with the head secretary of the rectoral council of UCL was held, during which she enlightened us on recruitments procedures of UCL, and the role that the rectoral council plays, and also on what kind of documentation/policies are provided for the formal recruitment procedures of C-level candidates (tenure track and tenured):

- Different notes to the attention of different levels of the recruitment process in order to make clear the procedure and of ensuring an equitable choice of new academics at “our” University:
 1. A note to the attention of the President (male/female wording) of the selection committees, copied to the deans and the President of department, and can be forwarded to members of committees.
 2. Note to the attention of the members of the selection committees, copied to the president of the department and the deans.
 3. Note to the attention of the deans and presidents of institute, in order to accompany the note 1. and for specifying their role in the different stages of the procedure.
 4. AESS recommendations.
 5. A model of the report for the equivalence of the PhD degree.
 6. A note about the credit for installation purposes.

How and to what extent are criteria specified?

This note is sent to the members and president of each selection committee by the rectoral council:

“Examination of the candidate profiles (all to be evaluated in more superficial manner, *short list* needs to be looked at more in depth):

- **General profile:** adequate profile for post (but can take into account the potential of candidates).

Please be careful of taking account that selection is complementary to profiles already present in the affected entities/sector (teaching/research/services).

- **Scientific level:** publications + (a (post-) doctorate outside of the French-speaking community of Belgium is highly desirable; footnote; if this may not be the case and the candidate is still exceptional, it will be necessary to envisage this during the probatory period)): the idea is to “rub” (exact wording) with different realities, during or after the PhD thesis, or to have as per se developed contacts with collects abroad or for publication purposes).

- **Pedagogical experience:** qualities of teaching/pedagogical experience (ask for evaluations of their teachings).

- **Experience of “service to the community”:** openness to the services to society, notably in the economic, socio-cultural or cooperation to development domains.

- **International openness** and their presence in the existing networks

- **The capacity to teach in French** (for non-french speakers a formation in the IPM can be envisaged) **and in a second “useful” language (a priori English**, upon which they will be in any case evaluated, except in the case of English native speakers or having demonstrated their capacity to teach in English, in an English speaking University). This evaluation showing a lack of sufficient skill, the candidates have to be informed that their linguistic skills will be evaluated at the end of the probatory period. The rectoral council has offered as of this year, 2014 the opportunity of funding for this course by part of the FSR funding of the University. This will be proposed to all the candidates who have been evaluated below the C1 level.

This point can be broached in the negotiations of the appointment.

Is there special attention paid in the documents to C/D level positions/ junior academic careers?

In the notes that are sent to the selection committee, we are looking only at C-level positions: however, there is a precision about the level of engagement: there are cases in which the selection committee (which is normally the case) appoints the selected candidate to a C-level tenure track position, which is a probatory period of three years, in which the candidate needs to fulfill certain demands, recorded in what is called a “PAI” (Individual Accompaniment plan), and will be taken into review during and at the end of this probatory period, at which then the C-level position is converted into a tenured academic position, of associate professorship (chargé de cours), which is permanent. In rare case, in which the candidate has proven him- or herself to be capable of taking over a tenured position, the C-level tenureship is immediately appointed: in the case of exceptional CVs, or mostly in the case of already previously tenured candidates applying.

Is there a difference in required criteria for tenured and non-tenured positions?

Here in the C-level tenure track positions there is no difference in the criteria required: it is as would be for a tenured position. However, there are rarely if no cases of tenured positions appointed or called for in the first place.

To what extent do the official criteria in HR policy documents match with the criteria in the job descriptions?

The official criteria in the HR policy documents written and distributed by the rectoral council to the UCL are largely the same as in the job descriptions: however, the exact wordings in the job descriptions has been modified to include the following additions or changes to the order of criteria enlisted:

- Scientific experience of a high level: “publications internationally renowned” is added as the only indication of scientific experience, whereas in the council note scientific level instead of experience and indicated as publication (only word without adjectives) and scientific experience abroad during or after thesis, or as postdoc. Moreover in the council note, there is a further elaboration of why international mobility is desired: the experience of other realities and contacts with colleagues abroad.

- As a separate point in the job descriptions the international mobility features therefore: a research study stay abroad. And removed are the points about before or after the PhD or a postdoc, and simply stated as international mobility required.
- The order of the criteria has been modified in SSH to state scientific experience before other criteria, in STEM teaching experience and aptitude and the capacity to work with other co-lecturers goes before other criteria.
- The point about being in international networks has been removed and the institutional engagement or enrolment is included and specifically added as a point in the job descriptions: capacity to integrate into the local research team, teamwork with research colleagues and affinity to institute or centre and to UCL.
- In the note to the commission, the council specifically inserts in italics a postscript to point one of “adequate profile”: for the candidates to be complimentary to existing profiles (or staff) in the given institute/department or affiliation. This is not included as official criteria in the job descriptions. It seems to be more of evaluation criteria that is to be taken into consideration by committee members but is not intended to be transparent in candidate recruitment.

How is academic excellence and/or quality described in the documents?

Academic excellence is described as publications + international mobility; this is conspicuously not the case for the job descriptions, which are written by the institutes/department council members and heads. Scientific experience is equated to internationally renowned publications. And international mobility is another point. However other points are added in the job descriptions, which are teamwork, local integration and co-work with fellow researchers in the institute/centre or UCL particularly, whereas the council note includes affiliations to international networks. Teaching is more highlighted in the job descriptions, especially in STEM.

Teaching in French is a requirement, and proficiency in a second language, preferably in English, which is pointed out as a requirement to be achieved at least within the first year of the mandate tenure-track. English seems to be part of the academic excellence criteria definitely on UCL level. Measures have been undertaken to ensure this: formation by the IMP (Institute of Languages) and also funding by the university for this formation for the chosen candidates). However, this proficiency is subject to evaluation within the 3-year probatory period, tenure-track. In the council note there

is no reference to the capacity to conduct high level research within the framework of the institute or UCL, which explicitly included in the job descriptions.

Are there any references to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university?

The terminology of candidate is indicated in both masculine and feminine forms. Other than that there is no reference to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university.

2.3. Actual Practices

Methodological introduction

We were able to conduct 6 interviews for IACCHOS and 4 for ELI, as it was more difficult to get hold of academics in ELI having taken part in committees, as well as persons who would agree to give interviews. We were in fact still waiting for one written interview that was promised to us by an academic in ELI, but who despite reminders has not yet sent his written interview.

For both institutes we were able to hold interviews with the presidents of the institute, as well as an interview with the vice-rector (female) of UCL (and professor at IACCHOS), who is responsible for the HR policy and management in UCL. In addition to this we were also able to conduct an interview with an administrative coordinator, who works with the rector and vice-rector on HRM in recruitment issues and was able to speak to us about the process as seen by the rectors' office/council and a more top-down perspective of criteria and the experiences of the process.

However, in terms of distinctions between interviews for C/D-level positions, it was more difficult to find persons who had more experience in one or the other, there were certain young academics who have only had D-level position recruitment experience, and more senior academics who often spoke about both level recruitments as per their experience.

We have included now in this report the different functions of interviewees, which for us were an interesting set of information about visions and perspectives voiced by presidents of institutes and higher instances, however these indications have to be treated with care and not used for publication purposes, as the persons are easily identifiable. We have included this information for within project discussion only, and will be anonymized for any publication purposes.

Interviewees with experience of recruitment processes, since 2010 (and before sometimes)

1	Department	Sex	Rank	Seniority	Committee member
2	SSH: IACCHOS	Female	Associate Professor: <i>Chargé de cours</i> , >3 ys		1 D-level and 1 C-Level
3	SSH: IACCHOS	Male	Associate Professor: <i>Charge de cours</i> , >3 ys		2 D-level
4	SSH: IACCHOS	Male	Professor, > 20 ys		Numerous C-level
5	SSH: IACCHOS	Male	Professor, > 10 ys		7 or 8 C-level
6	SSH: IACCHOS/UCL	Female	Vice Rector UCL, resp. HRM, Prof, >10 ys		6 C-level and D-level
7	SSH: IACCHOS	Male	President of Institute IACCHOS, Prof > 10y		7 C-level
8	STEM: ELI	Male	President of Insititue ELI, Prof > 10 ys		8 or more C-level
9	STEM: ELI	Female	Associate Professor: <i>Chargé de cours</i> , >5ys		2 D-level
10	STEM: ELI	Male	Associate Professor: <i>Chargé de cours</i> , >3ys		3 C-level
11	STEM: ELI	Male	Professor, > 10 ys		5 C-level and some D-level
12	UCL	Female	Adminstrative coordinator, rectors' office/council		Co-responsible of HR in recruitment process

For analytical purposes, we have synthesized the themes of the different questions in the interview guide of WP7 (sometimes in different order), which also form the subsections in the analytical part:

- Which criteria does the interviewee use and consider important criterion for a D/C – level position? (Order of criteria mentioned, importance,, Field/Domain, Ideal candidate, worst candidate etc.).
- Experience of recruitment process (description of process, composition of committee, formal or informal recruitment, decisive criteria, who was selected and why, first, runner ups etc.).
- Candidates, question of gender in the recruitment process.
- Gender policies (existence, experience, opinion).

We were able to conduct a focus group with 3 members of IACCHOS and 2 members of ELI, who had been part of C-level selection committees, one of which however had only experience in D-level recruitment. The choice was made due to availability of academics, who were prepared to participate, and then again who were able to get

together on a given date according to their agendas. Two academics, who had been willing to participate however had to cancel in the last minute.

Department	Sex	Rank	Seniority	Committee member
SSH: IACCHOS	Female	Professor:	>10 ys	3 D-level, 4 C-level
SSH: IACCHOS	Female	Professor, appointee UCL “Gender Studies”,	>5 ys	4 D-level
SSH: IACCHOS	Male	Professor,	> 10 ys	Numerous C-level and D-level
SSH: ELI	Female	Associate professor,	> 7 ys	Some D-level
SSH: ELI	Male	Associate professor,	>5 ys	4 D-level and 3 C-level

Interviews on recruitment criteria and processes: Analysis

The following section is dedicated to an analysis across the different interviews, with a comparative element between institutes, domains, generation of academics, gender of academics and experiences.

The interviewees in both institutes were quite ready to speak about their experiences in recruitment processes. Some uneasiness was shown when referring to questions about their experience of certain candidates, and whether candidates who were appointed to postdoctoral positions were up to their criteria or standards. There was a difference whilst speaking to younger academics, in the sense of seniority in career with above 3 but less than 7 years of academic career experience: they seemed more careful in the way they formulated their answers, being cautious at times about what they would say about the institution or institute and what could have negative connotations. The older academics seemed quite open and more “bolder” in their answers regarding their own practices and those of co-colleagues in recruitment committees. Overall, interviewees were quite accessible in their narratives. In terms of the gender of interviewees, in the kind of answers given to questions about criteria and processes of recruitment there weren’t any particular differences to be observed. Interestingly, women and men interviewees responded equally in an open or measured way depending on the same particular questions on the gender dimension. The terminology sometimes used and which was kept in its original French wording was done so because of the specific way a technical term is used. The translation is then given in bracket, because sometimes the translation is not accurate and does not

reflect the true meaning. For instance the word “dossier” is not simply the CV of the candidate, but also the whole “application file”, comprising also a motivation letter, the CV, a research profile or proposal of what the candidate intends to do if appointed, and a teaching/curriculum profile and proposal or orientation, and recommendation letters. In the UCL context the term “dossier” therefore can have a larger significance in the interviewees narratives and was therefore kept in its original form. Also in some cases, the rank or positions were kept in their original form, such as “chercheur qualifié FNRS” (see introduction for specification).

1. C- level recruitment

IACCHOS: Scientific “excellence” or “experience”

Publication and indicators

In all of the interviews conducted with committee members of C-level recruitment, *scientific “excellence” or “experience” or capacity of “producing”, “piloting” or “conducting” good research* was named as the foremost criteria for a C-level academic recruitment (tenure-track appointment of candidates) at IACCHOS. When asked what this scientific experience, or production implies, *publications* were immediately named as a valuable indication as to whether the candidate in question was able to not only carry out research, but make it known, by what was called a “validation or legitimization in the international field” done by peer review mostly. Moreover, scientific production also meant piloting, leading or undertaking research that is of good quality.

“For me excellence, or for the institution, excellence means that the person is capable of piloting research in a rigorous and scientific manner and he or she is capable of being recognized by peers; And the peers today are international and although one could say I am recognized by my peers next door, but this is the international market, so we are looking at persons who are legitimate in the field on an international level.”
(Interviewee 6, vice-rector UCL, responsible of HRM in UCL, professor in HRM)

“When it comes to the criteria for selection, the most primary and indispensable criteria is scientific excellence, which normally is reflected in the research conducted, the number of publications, type of publications, peer reviewed, what the person has actually done in previous research. At the time when I was presiding the committees in

the institute, H-index and ranking were not so much considered. But of course, the excellence in research is first and foremost.” (Interviewee 4, History Professor)

This validation by international colleagues seemed to be for most if not all interviewees a sure requirement and sign of excellence in today’s research context, which for them has increasing international implications. The discussion about the *number of publications* was ambiguous in the sense that most interviewees, both male and female did not feel that the quantity of publications was any particular sign of quality of the candidate, and that the age and stage of the candidates presenting themselves did not often permit a long list of publications. However, the value of the few publications would increase when published in internationally known peer reviewed journals, especially in languages other than French. The publication in English was not always considered as beneficial or necessary in all fields, but recognized as something that has become a common criterion in institutional practices. However, several interviewees pointed out that requiring English from all candidates in all disciplines seemed nonsensical, as some disciplines engaged by their nature in other languages, such as studies in French didactics. This criterion seemed to be accepted by most interviewees as part of the general criteria to be evaluated by, but relative to its actual use and necessity.

Compatibility and types of researchers/academics

The aspect of co-authorship in publication showed some ambiguity in interviewees in the sense that for some, candidates who co-published articles did not necessarily demonstrate what was also considered as an important sub-criterion under scientific excellence; “the capacity to conduct and produce research on one’s own”, and demonstrating autonomy in research, and finally also a legitimization of ones’ own particular work. Co-publishing many articles was to some a sign of what was called a “labo-orientated or centre orientated” approach (labo meaning a particular research centre or community) to research, which implied an extreme form of a kind of incestuous internal work ethnic or logic, which restricts the development of research fields and approaches. Productions, which were seen to finally not be specifiable of the research done by the candidate him- or herself. However, the real ambiguity about the quantity of publications emerges in the discussion about H-index and other measuring indicators for publications and journals, about which some interviewees

felt that these were often misleading figures and would not allow for a non-biased reading of the CV and the real quality of the candidate in question. However, after this reflection, the use of the indicators was experienced as rising in its importance in the use within recruitment committees at UCL and elsewhere. One interviewee even mentioned that the candidates themselves were including this in their personal dossiers, increasingly so, thereby adding to the criteria culture. Moreover, it was not entirely condoned by the interviewees; its “underlying sense” was considered valuable after all, namely the recording of a criterion of quality of the research undertaken and the impact thereof. But the measure itself was found to be faulty and perhaps of not being put to use properly.

“I think that it is having more weight, and little by little it is being evaluated and also integrated in the dossiers by the candidates themselves. Now we all know the limits of such a tool, but I think that the criteria behind this index makes sense, but the way in which we measure this is doubtlessly not good. And the criteria is that the person is capable of conducting and disseminating research in the scientific field and for me now the scientific field is international. So in this sense, these indicators are but one indication of this. So the criteria is legitimate but not the manner with which it is measured. I think we integrated this in the policy more and more. But when I think of the colleagues who are implicated in recruitment processes, they will take this as one amongst many criteria, not like in Great Britain. So in their case, the universities are “buying” researchers who have a certain value. Here it is not the case.” (Interviewee 6, vice rector, prof)

“Evidently the publication is an indication of what the researchers are capable of doing, but evidently a young researcher is not able to publish as much as experienced ones can do. So we have to project the profile of a person and see what the person is capable of in future. And will the person be able to move on to other projects, because many researchers are concerned with valorising their PhD thesis, which they have to do, because it is important, but we have to see what they are capable of doing in future; and sometimes there are persons working after ten years on the same questions. Not only this, the capability of constructing research. And beyond the individual interests. The committees therefore will also meet the person, which is important; what is crucial today is the conditions of the production of research are not the same, in all the labs (domains or research centers), there is a logic of labo, and you can see that very strongly in the Flemish part. So the colleagues there have ten publications, but with collective co-authoring in the same labo, so they have four, five, six signatures on the single paper working in the same

labo and field, with their supervisors etc. So evidently it is impressive to see young candidates with ten publications, wow, but however it is very difficult to take into account impact factors in these different conditions; so perhaps someone who has only two publications cannot be compared to these ten publications. And we try to take this into account. In some places, if you don't have minimum impact factor of at least 2, your dossier is not even taken into consideration. But those persons who are not in this logic of labo, are penalized.” (Interviewee 7, professor family studies, president of institute)

An important point named repeatedly for C-level recruitment and equally so for postdoc recruitment interviewees, was the necessity of extracting from the dossier but also the whole recruitment process in the committee what was named “*the projection or future potential of the candidate*”. So the number of publications would not necessarily show the capacity of the candidate to be able to progress in a certain research area; rather the publications and the dossier (overall application), as well as the interview interactions with the candidates in a holistic process had to show some *emerging potential research development* for the future after being appointed. “Would the candidate be able to go beyond their own narrow research interests, often based on their PhD theses”, or “would they have the capacity to conduct research in other topics and areas” of interest to the institute in its particular job and research context and in the international context”, were voiced as important indications whether a particular candidate would be considered or chosen or not. Often there was the contrast made between three types of candidates; those who were “*genius*” or “*stars*”, and “*brilliant*” in their research, but often ego-centric, or individualists, who stayed in their own office and did not have any interactions with colleagues or students. Another type was the “*suitcase*” academic, who just wanted the UCL post as an intermediary post in order to get permanent posts elsewhere in more prestigious institutions or other countries. Often these were seen as persons coming from abroad, of whom one could not be sure that they would remain, and thus leaving the institution to assume the costs of a new recruitment process etc. Or then the candidate type who associates and is collaborative, and interested in advancing the institution’s and centre’s’ interest as much as his or her own, whilst being independent in conducting his or her research, and capable of leading research projects and teams; this ultimately was seen as the *ideal candidate* to be identified amongst the short list of three or four candidates. In other words, the *compatibility of*

the researcher or academic with the work or research environment of IACCHOS and UCL. However, this identification was not seen to be an easy task and that there were “mistakes” made in the evaluation in the committee:

“Of course the compatibility of the person with the research environment in question is necessary, there are two types of researchers/academics: there is the collaborator and the individualist: sometimes there are some geniuses who may be brilliant researchers, but with whom it becomes very difficult to work, so of course this needs to be considered. There have been cases where the person is difficult, but who was selected because of his scientific excellence.” (Interviewee 5)

This *compatibility with the research environment* was thus named as one of the aspects within the first criterion of scientific excellence, but was also considered a criterion for itself named often as a third criterion amongst their list; the capacity of the candidate to go beyond their own interests and of establishing a link with the institutional context into which they would be placed. This was enlarged to include a general *rootedness* of the candidate in UCL, and the institute/research centre: a willingness to do so, and again a projection was to be made to evaluate if the candidate would be deemed capable of doing so. When asked how this kind of capacity or projection could be measured, most of the interviewees seemed to own up that it was very difficult to measure and that it was of course easier to discern in candidates who were already present in the institute or UCL before the C-level recruitment process, in other words, *internal candidates*. This was the case for interviewees for C-level committee members in both institutes IACCHOS and ELI (see later). There seemed to be some embarrassment towards the question whether “institutional rootedness or engagement” was a criterion that was positively evaluated or played in favor of internal candidates, but eventually quite frank answers were given in that if there were equally “excellent” dossiers of candidates, of course the added value of having already been rooted in UCL or the institute, would impact in the favor of the candidate, because there is less of a “risk” taken as to that point. It was easier for committee members to know if a candidate is capable or not of “fitting” into the centre or UCL, because there was some observable proof thereof before, which is not the case for external candidates. But the interviewees seemed eager in ascertaining that this was not a requirement per se, but that in reality internal

candidates were at an advantage as to this point. Also the importance of recommendation letters in determining this “potential” were named in one interview. In direct connection to the aspect of “*institutional engagement*” was a criteria mentioned in third or fourth places often in most interviews (both SSH and STEM); having had or showing a *service to the society or to the institution*. This aspect was mentioned by several interviewees who named this as the capacity of the researcher to be collaborative in the latter sense and taking rootedness in the institution. But also of being engaged other than in university, and of the idea of service. However, when asked how this could be measured at a early career stage dossier, the interviewees were less clear. The service then seemed to limit itself to an understanding as service to the institution, meaning UCL, thereby assisting in council meetings and being proactive. However, when asked for details about what this meant, it was mentioned that in the first probatory period of appointment, the assistant professors were asked to focus on their research and teaching and of taking merely part in the minimum institutional or organizational organ meetings, and not being asked to be representees or appointees within the organs or in the planning or organizing tasks. On the whole, interviewees seemed to harp about this point, but it was not specified other than institutional engagement or willingness to engage, which again was seen as an important criterion as such.

Gender dimension

In terms of the *gender dimension*, when asked at a latter stage of each interview, whether gender could play a role in their experience in the evaluation of candidates or of their “dossiers” in terms of these criteria, most interviewees for C-level recruitment (in both institutes SSH and STEM) replied almost immediately, well “no, there is no difference that we make, we do not discriminate how we evaluate, we consider the same criteria for everyone, regardless of gender, age or origin”. However, when asked to specify about how this goes about, some did enter a bit more into their experiences when confronted within committees to female or male candidates, or in terms of different ages of candidates. Publications for instance were seen also not to require to be endless lists, because of maternity leaves for instance or taking time off for family purposes and that this had to be considered in the way the committee members were to read a CV, or publication lists. Moreover, there was an emphasis in

most of the interviews that this had to be done for both men and women in family situations ideally from their point of view (for both male and female interviewees), but that this was often not done in reality, and that for women maternity leaves were more visible and thus taken more into consideration when accounting for gaps in the CV, not necessarily though for publication lists. There was one interviewee, president of the institute, who could see a potential for discrimination in the use of impact factors in publication as a tool of evaluation:

“This is quite radical in its formula. According to me this is too excessive because it does not allow to consider young researchers, who are more individual in their undertakings and therefore would be eliminated, and also atypical candidates, who are perhaps 35 years old, having done other things before and have been passionate about research in latter years and apply themselves wholly to this path, but who wouldn’t feature in the selection, because they don’t have a nice CV. And it also eliminates young women, who after their PhD would say, it is perhaps now time to have a child, and would have published less during this period, or young men who have invested a lot during their PhDs, and now want to balance their family life, and take things more easy. So in my view, if we go in a too radical way of evaluating then we miss out on good candidates, who have other priorities other than research in their personal lives.” (Interviewee 7, president of IACCHOS)

However, when asked about whether criteria were thus after all somewhat differentiated depending upon persons, there seemed to be an ambiguity with interviewees, that they supposed that the few women having reached that stage of the recruitment did have “excellent” dossiers in any case, as the filtering was very strict according to the job descriptions given in the first place, and the selection of the short lists. In their view, the access to that stage of recruitment was doubtlessly more difficult for women, as there were few who presented themselves. Moreover, when considering *age of candidates*, this seemed to be marked out as an important indicator as to whether the publications were required to be more considerable or not, but also in terms of *typical or atypical trajectories* of persons. It seemed that atypical trajectories of candidates, who had a certain age of thirty and above, and who had just entered the research career and did not demonstrate a lot of publications etc. were worse off than other more “classical” candidates, who would perhaps have done Bachelors, Masters and PhD in the same fields and then had more significant

publication lists and indications therefore, according to some interviewees, of a more grounded CV in the given field.

Teaching

The second criterion listed amongst all of the interviewees of C-level recruitment committees, is *teaching*. Described merely as a capacity to teach, which in this group of interviewees (C-level recruitment, IACCHOS) was not particularly elaborated. When asked about the importance level or balance between research or scientific experience/production and teaching in terms of the evaluation and the job description or mandate, most interviewees in IACCHOS highlighted the scientific part of the job as being more significant during evaluation or recruitment. Teaching however, could only, in their view and experience, be evaluated during what is common in UCL practice in form of presentations or public lessons given to the committee members (often inviting the president or dean of the institute), during which the candidate is supposed to present his or her research in a pedagogical or seminar form. This teaching sessions is experienced or seen to be quite important in the recruitment or selection process, as it can tip the scale in the determination of the last classification of candidates from the short list; a candidate who has a more weaker CV or dossier in comparison to another candidate or with an equal dossier can counterbalance this by giving a good or bad impression during this session. According to all interviewees this session is quite crucial in how decision-making plays out in the committee in the last stage of selection between the two or three candidates. Also mentioned was that sometimes, presidents of institutes or deans of faculty can be convinced or confirmed in their previous impressions of a certain aspect of the mandate by this session, or even committee members are seen to sometimes tip their decisions or favors towards one or the other candidate or see some former impression or notion confirmed or counterbalanced. It was notable however that amongst the C-level IACCHOS interviewees teaching was considered as secondary to research in terms of how candidates were evaluated. This aspect was also seen as being less visible in the dossiers, as the early stage of career of researchers did not normally show much teaching experience, and that this was not seen as a negative point in the CV if the teaching session could show some potential. Again this idea of potential creeps into interviewees explanations given about

evaluation of teaching. However, if teaching experience was already present in the dossier of the candidate, this would act in favor of recruitment, and reinforce supporting internal candidates, who would have been visible in their teaching manner and style.

International mobility

International mobility, when asked about, was named as an indispensable criteria in what interviewees named as today's context. The reasons given for this importance was that researchers needed "to have seen and worked in other research environments and established connections with colleagues abroad." Less experience abroad was seen to be a weakening point in a candidate's application. At least one year of postdoctoral or other experience abroad was required. In terms of education and where the PhD was done, this was seen to be secondary, but certainly considered if excellent. However, this point raised more issues than others in terms of gender, although seen as a necessary requirement in the same interviews: some interviewees voiced concerns that probably female candidates or researchers had a harder time in terms of mobility and ensuring this in their CVs, because of family or motherhood reasons. However, here too men were mentioned of having the same concerns in today's context and that the disadvantages in terms of organizing mobility with family and settling life in one place was not only for women but for many young persons during the stage of the early career.

"This has become a commonly known criterion in UCL, and there again if someone who has little experience, they would risk of not being taken. But seeing the evolution of research and its internationalization, I would support the idea that young researchers or academics could obtain this experience within the first years of appointment. But of course this is difficult...I think we have not yet managed to find the adequate formula for articulating of family life and professional life, and these questions. I see, because I was in that situation, and because I have friends who are in these situations, and I see a lot of young colleagues, also male, who are sensitive to these issues and of this rapport of the domestic tasks to be more balanced. I know a young colleague who has chosen Paris, because Paris was close for a Marie Curie stay, but it becomes difficult with toddlers, it is frequently the spouse who has these tasks on her back, but I remember a male colleague who said, I have a wife who holds a very good position, and she cannot permit to take paid leave and to take care of the children when I go abroad, so he made

a cross on the international mobility, which of course plays negatively in terms of the career. And unfortunately our university is although it is attentive to the question, it is very difficult to offer really to the totality of the persons who are in this situation, as is the case for the sabbatical leaves to give an adequate pay for rents here and there etc, and of course the academic has his salary, but what about the spouse and what about taking care of the children etc etc. I think that there is a lot of work to be done, and I don't think it is a lack of will, and I think financially the resources is very limited.”
(Interviewee 7)

Some interviewees in senior positions and representative functions voiced concerns about being aware of the limits of certain evaluations of certain criteria, which could act as discriminations towards women or men in family situations, or in their articulation of private and professional life, but speak with a rather fatalistic tone about the lack of financial and other resources by university.

ELI: Scientific “excellence” or “experience”

In this set of interviews with C-level recruitment committee members in ELI (STEM), although scientific excellence and experience were named also as criteria for selection, sometimes in first place, and sometimes in second place after teaching, the meaning of scientific experience and excellence and the “capacity” of conducting good research was slightly different from the IACCHOS interviews: there is a mention of publication, with the same sub-criteria as for IACCHOS, but there is more emphasis on the collaborative aspect and scientific work as paired with the articulation with the local research context in which the job is centred or with whom the person is supposed to work. Collaborative work is considered indispensable in STEM fields, as the manner of working involves team work as such, also speaking in terms of “compatibility”, which is often named as a second criterion. This aspect is highlighted first, and in second place it is linked to the potential development of research of the person. In terms of the other criteria demonstrating what is understood as scientific quality the question of publications is described more or less very similarly as in the IACCHOS group, except for perhaps a slightly more general acceptance of the use of indicators in measuring the impact factors of articles and journals in which the candidate published, although quantity again is not considered a primary factor.

“What is certainly one criteria is the scientific level, at the same time expertise demonstrated by the publications, and the how he addressed issues in his discipline and also the way in which this articulates to the other things. So more in our institute than in others, professors cannot exist without others; there are always experiments to be conducted with others, and you need to do your research forcibly with others, so necessarily the way that research is conducted privileged by the candidate is articulated with this perspective and is certainly a criteria. The second criteria is the potentiality of the disciplinary field of the person and the manner in which it is treated. Here I am only speaking of scientific aspects. And after that there is the human side, which is very important in our domain, because of this co-work, so “stars”, who are susceptible of working primarily by themselves would not fit in this work environment. I do not say that they may not be considered, but I feel that the colleagues like feeling that there is a potentiality of collaboration, in the research, but also on a human level, and feel that it won’t be too difficult.” (Interviewee 8, president of institute ELI).

What is often emphasized in these set of interviewees is the play of multiple sets of criteria and that committees take all these into account in their experience:

“What we do is that evidently we ask for the CV and in the CV there is a collection of criteria that intervene, such as the previous experience, the fact of having been abroad is certainly in my view very favorable, if you haven’t always stayed in the same labo (centre) this forms a favorable opinion. In terms of publications it is not the quantity, but also the quality of the publications. We look if the person in a classic trajectory with a brilliant career; we don’t look if that person has done many publications, but some publications, good papers, with a certain impact. As I said we don’t use a single criteria, but a collection (“ensemble) of criteria to evaluate the person. And we do this in a collegial manner which is a requirement, because then this not an exclusive vision of things, but a vision that is shared amongst colleagues. In this way we try to extract really the best candidate for a particular post. So Quality is composed of a number of attributes, it is the number of publications, quality of publications, previous experience, which is the experience abroad, sometimes the number of certificates and awards (“brevets/prix”), evidently persons could have obtained awards such as FNRS, so this will play into the dossier. All the arguments that could have an impact (“play”).”

Criteria such as *international mobility* is equally important for ELI interviewees in C-level, to have had some “fresh air”, and to “have changed the context is important in an

academic career”. An addition to this is a reference to number of awards achieved. The PhD place and content is considered of value, and certainly taken into consideration.

Teaching and the “human aspect”

However, one significant difference between the IACCHOS group and the ELI group is the latter names often teaching and the willingness to teach as one of the primary criteria, which the committees are seen to put a lot of importance to. In some interviewees experience, they have made some “major mistakes” considering the appointing of some academics, who were brilliant in their dossiers (“stars”) and were taken, but then refused to teach and were unable to connect to students and transmit. So the idea of “transmission of knowledge” was considered an important new criteria for an ideal candidate. Again the idea of projection or discovering the potential of a candidate to do so, or the *human aspect*, in terms of compatibility with colleagues and students as well as research excellence were named as part of the process of evaluation of candidates in today’s context or more recent context. The personality of the candidate and the human quality reflecting in work ethic seemed to draw a lot of concern in the evaluation of selection committees in most interviewees; the idea of fitting or being a part of the institution certainly echoes strongly throughout the narratives.

Recruitment processes: experiences in SSH and STEM interviews for C-level recruitment committee members: IACCHOS and ELI

General process

Interviewees for C-level recruitment in both institutes described very similar processes in their experiences ; the examining of initial applications, selecting a short-list, and then the interviewing of the three or at the most four short-listed candidates, who are then classified (or not) as 1st, 2nd etc., while the 1st candidate is then nominated and subject to a psychology test and a language test for English or French depending on the requirement. In terms of this procedure, it is described by the vice-rector as extremely long and arduous. Moreover, she mentioned that the process has become much more professionalized, in the sense of rigorous and instrumentalized in the last ten years, before which it used to be much more informal, but also more closed affair. Now, she says “it has become a competition” and has become open to the

international market, whereas it used to operate more privately and with persons known beforehand. This is an interesting statement if one compares it to the criteria on institutional rootedness and the reflections that interviewees made about the increased facility of evaluating internal candidates, paired with their statements on the importance of international mobility and openness to outside of UCL.

Moreover, one distinctive aspect in the case of both institutes, and UCL is the existence of what is called the PAIC; the Academic Project of Individual Concertation. The interviewees in both institutes describe this as an important tool of evaluation and planning for each appointee, who is on probation so to speak for the first three years of his or her academic appointment, and who needs to formulate an individually tailored action plan in which they describe their intended research and teaching outlooks and targets. These will be taken under review during and at the end of the three years by the president of the institute and by the rectors' council. The interviewees describe this as a very important part of the recruitment process. Depending on the candidate, this PAIC can be very instructive or evaluative. So in fact the recruitment process could be seen not to stop at appointment, as is only the selection into tenure-track for three to up to five years as assistant professor. After the positive review of this PAIC then only can a candidate proceed to being nominated an associate professor.

Composition of the committee

The composition of the committee is seen to play by most if not all interviewees of C-level recruitment in both institutes a key role in the decision-making of selection. Depending on the particular persons within the committee, and particularly the person of the president of the committee, the decision-making is very varied, and some candidates are more or less likely to be selected. In one interviewees words (president of institute ELI);

(Laughs) "I can tell you my secret, but then you won't publish this! I have not counted, but I have taken part in seven or eight recruitment processes in committees in four different faculties, and in fact it is terrible to what extent the composition of the committee can have an impact; so it is not about the discussions but rather the composition. In other words, the profile of who we are going to recruit already plays out in the moment in which we define the committee. And there I think that the university

is too light on this matter, because it doesn't scrutinize sufficiently how the committees are made and operate. Who selects the committees? (Laughs); Who has the power you mean?! You have to keep in mind that the institutes are not in first line for the recruitment processes, in the description of posts. It is in first line the faculty. I think for the committee it is the dean who will propose this to the rectors' council on the basis of a consultation of the presidents of the institutes. Because here it becomes complicated, because the candidates, one does not know in which institute they will go. Generally one knows, but in certain cases, in the interface it is not always written. And there can have certain presidents who will say we will put this one there or there, and this can modify substantially the decision making! The composition of the committee is critical."

The power of the committee members and of the person who selects the committee members is undeniable in the recruitment process according to all interviewees. This is ascertained by the administrative coordinator of the rectors' office, who speaks about the decision-making in the committees that is "out of the rectors' office control", and where finally faculties, who conceive the academic posts and plan them, already initiate the selection process there. According to interviewee 5;

"The recruitment process starts around 5 years before the job offer is published. It begins with the negotiations with the faculty about teaching mandates and the distribution thereof, about what kind of teaching we want paired with what kind of research. Then there is a strategic planning going on during these 5 years, it has to be approved by the rectors' council, then it goes on with the appointment of the committee members and the formulation of the job description, the decision about which networks in which this will be diffused, and who will preside the committee, and which centres will be involved." (Interviewee 5)

Moreover, according to other interviewees, there is the importance of choosing the external members and how they will position themselves in terms of the mandate and the candidates. There is also the indirect power of the dean and the president of the institute mentioned, who can give their statements as to the interests of the institute and faculty. One interviewee speaks about "perspective caps" or roles of different members of committees and non-members:

"As president I have a priority to be attentive to the question of research, if the committee was not. From the point of view of research, that in the committees mostly to be clear about certain things. And it has happened that I as president of the

committee I would classify this person as first candidate, upon the criteria specifically research. And sometimes to add, but if you look at the global criteria, then we do not have the same classification. The deans are generally are concerned to have people capable of teaching in lectures of 400 persons, and to animate a seminar. So the roles are there, and it isnt me who choses these roles; if tomorrow I would be dean, and I dont have this aspiration nor the wish, then I would also look at the teaching aspect. So it is the function that creates the perspective through which we will evaluate the post. As president of the institute I have to take care that the research dimension has really been taken into account.” (Interviewee 7)

Differences in opinion have been experienced to arise between the committees’ proposal of a candidate, and the rector’s council, sometimes leading to the dissolution of the position. Or shifted to the following year. Also sometimes, interviewees experienced that external members would refer strongly to the opinons given by deans and presidents of institutes as to the importance of certain criteria for a given post. They would then counterbalance a particular preference by internal members. This was seen to be annoying for committee members, as externals “did not know the internal context” or “dynamics” and were seen to be an interrupting factor, positive sometimes and sometimes too “foreign to our house”. The dynamic of the commission is deemed a very important and decisive factor in influencing the selection of candidates. The composition itself is composed in the following manner according to one interviewee:

“In the composition of the committee it is important to note that a majority of (3) members are often from within the institute or faculty and are often close to or belong to a centre, so are double internals, so to speak, plus one external-internal from UCL (belonging to the same institute but not the same centre) + and one external-external (often international). member + the opinions given by the president of the institute and the dean, which throw the weight towards the internal-internal scale. The external-external member has weight in order to counterbalance, however he or she will be strongly influenced by the requirements voiced by the institution members in – and outside of the committee.”

However, very few interviewees thought that having *more female members of committees* would substantially change the selections. They mentioned in some cases that often female members are more bound to be “strict” or even “biased” about

female candidates, notably about family situation or motherhood clashing with the organization of work.

Comparison ELI and IACCHOS

There are not many differences visible between the two institutes in terms of the importance or experience voiced in recruitment processes by interviewees from ELI and IACCHOS; both seemed equally affirmative of the importance of the committee members in the determination of the selection. Moreover, both sets of interviewees seemed to believe implicitly in the efficiency of this system of evaluation; terms such as “impartial”, “multi-criteria based”, “non-discriminatory” and “undivided” were used quite frequently and seem to express a general feeling of the justification of such a system. Moreover, interviewees seemed to speak in rather collective terms when speaking about committees, colleagues were not singled out for any negative behavior, or oppositions. Although the word “power” did arise several times, it was not used in terms of the committee itself, but rather towards its dynamics, and also in terms of the perspective caps that several interviewees were speaking about, according the representation of faculties, deans or presidents of institutes, either research or teaching or institutional engagement were highlighted and made to be included in the selection process. Rather than seen as a power game, the interviewees seemed to believe that this was a good counterbalancing system in the recruitment process.

Gender policy in recruitment and beyond – ELI and IACCHOS

Ensuring non-biased procedures

Most if not all interviewees in both institutes ascertained of not having seen any gender policy or implementation in recruitment practices at UCL and in either institute. One interviewee in ELI (STEM) speaks about how in one job description there was a particular mention of women being favored in the case of “equally excellent” dossiers of candidates. And that this in his view was as far as gender policy would go. He believes that the recruitment processes would be non-biased and not run the risk of discrimination if what he says is the “turn-over” and diversity is ensured:

“Firstly, I participate in many processes of scientific evaluation, independently of recruitment processes, in terms of councils, I am also member of the research council for example. And there we have to evaluate dossiers for Postdocs and for juniors, and at a time I was also in the FNRS and FVO in the Flemish part, so we have a certain experience here. That which appears to me extremely important is there is a turn over, that these persons don’t stay too long time in these committees, that there is in order to avoid bias and subjectivities and other things, it is always important to have a good turn over, that one doesn’t stay too long. And secondly that in each committee we always have a diversity of the disciplines and institutes that are present. For instance if we are recruiting in a certain faculty that there are persons of other faculties that are participating in this. So that we always have an external point of view. Not only external to the faculty but also external to the university.” (Interviewee 11, Professor. Agronomist)

Most interviewees moreover, as an initial reaction are hesitant to answer to this question about gender policy, as they say, they are “not quite clear” about what the best policy is. The reasons given for this are multiple; some interviewees explain that for instance introducing women quotas in committee members as in several other countries would not solve the issue, - which they clearly do ascertain as being a real issue in the low turn out of female candidates -, as recruitment or selection processes according to most interviewees are considered pretty non-biased by the multiplicity of precautions taken in the structure of the process, namely the diversity of the members of committee and what they call evaluation of “general” criteria of excellence, as indicated in the quote above. The vice rector explains that recruitment processes are much less discriminatory than ten years ago, where generational parentage nominations were common, and that today the introduction of international criteria of scientific quality in fact created a more open ground for competition rather than nomination. The general criteria given by the rector’s council thus are viewed by the majority of the interviewees as being comprehensive of this priority given to scientific excellence, which is evaluated indiscriminately in their point of view. However, when asked whether the evaluation of scientific excellence itself should contain any gender policy, some interviews go deeper in their answers and give cases in which women, or men in family situations or parental situations would be disadvantaged in terms of the high demands for being selected in an academic post.

“Do we have a policy for gender for recruitment procedures? No, not to my knowledge unfortunately. We have never had any specific policy towards this theme. However, during the recruitment processes we are confronted with female candidates, who are young mothers and so on, and where we can take into account situations to explain why certain dossiers are not so dense, or don't have that many publications or research projects. This would act in their favor. No, we do not exclude selecting candidates who are young mothers. However, in the end, scientific excellence is indispensable, that is what counts for selection.” (Interviewee 4, Professor in History, over 20 years of seniority)

Reductionism of gender dimension in recruitment

Many interviewees speak of what they think is an importance of integrating a gender reflection in scientific and academic careers, however, they seem to be preoccupied about what they call the reductionism of the gender question to the sex aspect or the maternity leaves or motherhood, and of not taking into account that young men may face the same obstacles whilst being fathers or family men. There seems to be a sensitivity today about non-preferential treatment for women, because family has become something that in their view has become more of a preoccupation and priorities in both sexes' lives.

“Well, I would think there are three elements of reflection; I am very favorable of paying attention to this dimension in the measure where we differentiate gender and sex. I see a series of young male academic who are also very attentive to the gender issue and work life balance, so taking into consideration this dimension does not mean simply giving a prize to women. But of course it becomes very difficult; how does one know in front of you...of course it is easy to see if there are two maternities in the CV, it is there, but how do I have access to gender dynamics and conjugal logics etc. that can be tangible, which are not linked to the pregnancies? So finally, I would agree that we need to be attentive to this; and that this is not solely a question of pregnancies, but also really other questions. So as I told you in the case of my friend who has to go to Paris, and put his child to the creche and then go on the train etc. So this is something really crazy, and this is the reality. And couples are heading out with egalitarian ideas, although this may change; however, the arrival of children changes things, which sociology is very aware of. How to take into consideration the gender question without limiting oneself to the question of the sex. First element. Second element, is that gender

is important but it isn't all; like the logic of quotas in Switzerland, to favor women, and then to discriminate men from lower socio-economic background to favor women from a more favorable background. We should not use gender as a lens with the effect of stamping out other dimensions. (...) And third element is that I think we need to think about mechanisms; for example I think that it is important to have women in the committees, but often having a woman in the recruitment process for administrative jobs, who is presiding to have questions certainly about "how will you manage if you are pregnant etc.", it isn't the male members who asks this, it's the big boss women who would. Because they are experienced in organizing a service and they are well aware that this will disorganize the service. So I think that you have to think about mechanisms, but going beyond the idea of simply putting more women in committees. We have to study the different ways discriminations come about and operate." (Interviewee 7)

However, in some interviewees' experience, they have stereotypes in terms of how men and women work, and that often women are seen or experienced to be more organized in managing their time and engagements, and that they were considered more efficient, and that this "positive" stereotypes made them tend to wanting to take on female candidates. Another young female academic in STEM, ELI, in the Biology field, openly acknowledges that given a choice between two equally excellent candidates with opposite sexes, she would favor the woman, in order to promote her "because she is a woman".

However the question about the low turnout of female candidates was answered much the same for all interviewees in ELI, and somewhat more positively for IACCHOS. Things seem to have changed throughout the years for some more senior academics amongst the interviewees, they felt that they saw more women coming into the academic or scientific field than even ten years ago, especially in ELI. But all interviewees don't see the actual "issue" of the leaky pipeline as being situated in the recruitment processes as per their own experiences in recruitments, but rather already much earlier. One interesting aspect that was named by more than one Interviewee is that often women who did get selected or had been at last selected into the short-list often had a certain type of profile and weren't in family or motherhood situations.

Certain types of criteria and organizational knowledge/codes

In terms of the evaluation of certain types of criteria, interviewees named international mobility as being a demand that was very hard to fulfill for people meaning to settle down and build families. Also the idea of a full CV, teaching experience and publication list were deemed as sensitive to this issue of evaluation. Interestingly, the institutional rootedness and engagement were not at all linked up to the gender dimension. However, whilst confronted with this question, some interviewees, four in particular (Interviewees 6 and 7 in IACCHOS and 8 and 10 in ELI), engaged in a detailed narrative part about the knowledge of organizational culture, ways of doing things, informal institutional and institute codes that were considered very important elements of integration of young academics, especially for external candidates, who would be selected. However, this *organizational knowledge* was seen to be very hard to come by, and that there was already a requirement or criteria of institutional engagement etc. within the recruitment process that would put internal candidates at an advantage. Generally, *academic organizational codes* were considered as very deeply engrained in interactions, and practices and hard to learn and to come by, except through many years of working in the institute, faculty and the UCL. This brought the narratives round to an idea of work ethics and logics of functioning in the academic profession itself, which was considered hostile for women and for men in terms of the *articulation of private and professional life or health*, in terms of *workload* and the *imbalance of tasks*, the changes in *teaching environment and students' attitudes*, *knowledge* as well as the *influence of technology* to name a few of the issues that were named in what was called the “social degradation of the academics' lives”:

“I think it is extremely difficult for a university to take into measure the changes of the society in which we are. It means that before researchers were married more to their research than being married to their wives or families. And when you see the number of non-married women who are administrative posts, and other in UCL as well. But the question is, “do we accept the change”. Because if we keep saying, we want to have researchers who are working 60 hours in average per week on research then I think we will loose a lot of good male and female researchers; I see many researchers, behind you you will see, she has defended her thesis, very excellently done, but she measures by persons she knows she says I am not ready to invest all this. Do we need to accept

that we have to work 50 to 60 hours per week, then I think we are trouble. I am troubled by the amount of young colleagues, of my age, well I am not that young any more, but of a given age, who have serious illnesses, and not only female but also male, burnout and cancer in the female and heart diseases in the masculine, it is shocking.” (Interviewee 7, Professor Sociology, IACCHOS)

“I think the challenge is the access to the recruitment committees, that women are confronted with;.....in fact is that the academic career does not have points of reference, to know your way round. I think that beyond the gender question, it would be interesting to research the social degradation of the academic life. The cause of email and technology, the hours in which you receive emails, and I don't think that academics write emails simply to show that they are working and I think they are really working in such hours. And there you can objectify a social degradation of academics' lives which is terrible. Today it is possible that a woman who knows this world, would say to herself “wow, do I really want this?”. And that perhaps men would be more work-aholic, I don't know. (...) As academics we have come one generation too late, because when I see how my professors were comfortably installed; here we are completely exposed to students, who are so reactive and demanding, and also the relationship to knowledge has changed, we no longer have the monopoly of knowledge and also the institutional aspect has changed enormously. And the fundamental research is complicated, so all has complicated and today the academics are less helped and the technologies we can observe that secretaries are less efficient today because of these technologies. I think you need to reinvent the profession of the academic, if not we will loose out. I think there is a recomposition of the academic profession which is incredible and the reorganization of the university pedagogy and the institution does not follow. I dream of an institution where the professors do not have to occupy themselves with administration and organization. The professors are there to teach and to do research and all the rest of work that has to be done is too much, because they are presidents of institutes, because they are deans, because they are program committees, they organize. Here is a casting error. This is an enormous amount of work.” (Interviewee 8, ELI, Professor in Bioengineering, President of Institute)

These narratives are very strong in the sense that they were both coming from each president of institute and had similar lines of reflection in why the academic profession could be “scary” for women, because of the way in which the profession is heading. The term “reinvention” of the profession and the imbalance between the different tasks and what the actual work of academics is and should be are very

strong arguments that both interviewees provide in making sense of leaky pipelines and the gender dimension in academia and in UCL, but also much more in general as to the work organization of academics, the place of the university within the changes of society, and the kind of orientation or shape it is taking in research, teaching and work ethics.

The vice rector speaks about auto-determination as an important element contributing to this kind of work ethic and organization;

“In fact our job is a very autonomous job, which also presupposes a certain auto-determination and demands that we put upon ourselves. I think that often we as researchers are faced with a lot of “black boxes” in terms of what kinds of services exist in our institutions and outside of institutions, so the young female researchers especially have a misinformed or partial information about the job and the possibilities. So there is an aspect of auto-determination in this job that can reorientate persons. Excellence in this sense is also orientated or dictated by the objectives and criteria that researchers themselves put for themselves in their work. The requests for co-research and project if often the most tempting thing, and one is tempted to accept something and then be completely overloaded with tasks. So the clarity about this job is not there, as often things are not discussed in the open. There is a kind of ideal that everybody strives to meet but which is not reality. Perfectionism and aut-censure is often at the order; I could have published in a better journal, I could have... And of course apart from that there is the institutional demands, which pushes to looking for excellence, for publishing in the better journals, in excellence in teaching and this pushes to the question of being excellent in everything, and if possible to be excellent in the institutional engagement and service. And this could scare young persons and if one is in a pipeline that they would try to escape outside to see otherwise.” (Interviewee 6 female, Professor HRM, vice rector)

Transparency and assistance

There was quite a substantial part of some narratives dedicated to the question of the transparency of the workload and balance of tasks of the mandate and the gender dimension in the demands of the job that are required and need to be fulfilled and evaluated in the probatory period of appointment. Some interviewees maintained that while scientific excellence was quite clear in its requirements in the job descriptions and process in the committees, the question about actual workload or

balance was not given beyond the formal job descriptions. This was mainly discussed after the nomination of the candidate classified as 1st, and who is finally nominated as assistant professor for the 3 year probatory period. This discussion would take place within the PAIC (Individual Academic Project). The question about whether after recruitment the appointees were tutored or accompanied was deplored as something lacking yet in the organization of the academic career, however, the PAIC was mentioned as an important tool for accompanying a newly appointed academic, but that

2. Postdoctoral recruitment: criteria, process, gender policy and dimension

The academics who were interviewed about D-level recruitment were all four associate professors, one male and one female associate professor from IACCHOS and one male and one female associate professors from ELI. Incidentally they were all in a relatively comparable age group between 34 and 40, with seniority ranging between 5 to 10 years of academic work after appointment for tenure-track. The gender differences in some aspects of the interviewee narratives for this group was more striking than for the C-level interviewees, whereby the gender dimension questions were answered quite differently depending on sex of interviewee. The differences between domains seemed more pronounced for the postdoctoral demands and criteria than for the C-level group.

Informal processes of recruitment

The reason for discussing this aspect before the criteria, is that the postdoctoral recruitment in comparison to the C-level recruitment is very a very informal process as described by the interviewees of both ELI and IACCHOS; two particular types of processes could be differentiated; one in which the project funding was obtained without any attachment to a postdoctoral or doctoral position, and the interviewee, along with other academic colleagues in the project would then decide upon whether postdoctoral or doctoral research was to be conducted and by whom. So they would then formulate the job description and disseminate the call to internal mailing lists or other networks, through the university or via associations of the particular field. The other type of project funding is attached to a particular postdoctoral project application, such as Marie Curie actions of the EC, co-funded by UCL, or FNRS postdoc

funding. In this case, the project leader, the interviewee or another colleague would have been contacted and associated as applicants on behalf of a particular candidate, or would launch an open call for a potential candidate. In most if not all the interviewees' cases of postdoctoral recruitments, they had somebody in mind beforehand, through knowledge of networks both internal and external to the institute or external to Belgium, even abroad. The internal and external networks (mailing lists) were considered as key in having informants for particular fields or disciplines, which were sometimes new or uncertain for interviewees, as these were relatively first-time project fundings that they had obtained during their mandate as associate professors. Mailing lists were seen to include also externals met at conferences and added throughout the years, so that a considerable network had been acquired in the institutes. In two interviewees' postdoctoral recruitment cases, the networks extended to France, however rarely to English speaking countries. There seemed to be a certain reluctance in extending the call to countries other than french-speaking, or other than countries in the vicinity of Belgium and the UCL. However, the requirement to extend the calls to these countries was seen as essential because the persons in the field in Belgian universities was seen to be known fairly well and thus a bit exhaustive in choice. The reasons for preferring persons living close by were often because of practical purposes:

“We weren't interested in France as such; but now in our french-speaking Belgian community we know who is who, and although we did diffuse this amongst our own colleague, so we were doubtful of not finding someone here, and we thought that France would be a good place to look, also in terms of what we know about expertise in this particular field.” (Interviewee 3, male, IACCHOS)

The applications in IACCHOS were in both interviewees experience from around 10 to 15 initial applications received, however shortened down to around three or four candidates that they thought could be interviewed. In the ELI interviews, applications were more numerous, however sized down more easily in the interviewees experience. In the IACCHOS experiences, there seemed to be as many women as men applicants. And finally even resulting in women outnumbering men in the final shortlist. In ELI, in some cases there were no women applicants, and in one case one female applicant, who finally got selected for the postdoctoral appointment.

However, despite the more formal call for applications, almost all interviewees and associated colleagues had somebody or some few distinctive candidates in mind for the postdoc post in question; but, often in three or more cases, the “favorite” candidate was not “ready” to engage in the proposal, or else in mid-application process was hired elsewhere for a permanent or tenure-track post, often in other countries from which they applied from. Interviewees called this the risk of the recruitment process, of persons dropping out during the recruitment process, but more often also after taking up the offer or being selected, sometimes in mid-project realization. This was perceived to be a frustrating and arduous process of looking afresh for candidates and of having to “start all over again”.

An important dimension which distinguishes the postdoctoral recruitment majorly from the C-level recruitment is the aspect of “project” engagement, both in terms of the short duration and time frame, the contractual type of work, and the nature of project work itself and the kind of demands this brings forth.

Criteria for recruitment

In line with this “project” orientation of the postdoctoral recruitment, criteria named for the recruitment were very different from C-level, especially in terms of priorities named and what was perceived as essential in order to work with somebody hired on a project. The quality of the project proposal in the cases of project funding obtained by interviewee was something that was deemed very important and even the primary criterion considered by one female interviewee. The topic of the PhD thesis, the literature, and even more methods and approaches of the research already conducted were named as first criteria that were evaluated in the dossier and CV. Publications were mentioned, but more content based; the content was of interest to interviewees in terms of the research of the postdoc project to be engaged in. The place of PhD was seen as important, but not the only factor of quality in a dossier. In the more qualitative part of the evaluation during interviews with final candidates, the capacity of conducting research independently, and of coordinating a research team, or of innovation in research methods and the planning of research were deemed indispensable by most interviewees. However, in reality, the actual candidates were sometimes falling short of one or the other criteria or quality in their experience, in what were even perceived as “weaknesses” of the candidates who were chosen from

or recruited. One other criteria mentioned by both male interviewees was an institutional engagement or the willingness to stay in Belgium at least for the period of the postdoctoral contract, or an agreement of carrying out the research in a reasonable frame during the week if traveling was required., as was the case for more than one interviewees' postdoctoral colleagues appointed by them.

However, the two female interviewees seemed very happy with their current appointees, both of which were female. They felt that their expectations and demands were being met by these postdocs, and that the quality of methods and capacity of handling data sets were considerable.

Gender dimension in evaluating and recruitment

This group of interviewees, especially the men, were quite cautious and pensive when it came to answering this question, as though they were weighing their words, and wanted to be true to what they would say. Again, the project dimension of the job in question and the candidates' requirements seemed to determine the kind of issues that interviewees foresaw. It was particularly a kind of tension between the restrictions that the interviewees as promoters of projects experienced in terms of pressures from project funding, time frame and organization, which had an effect upon how they would perceive the candidate's profile and gender under this angle:

“More in the practical aspect.....a little also in the management of the research. In the case of our postdoc there are some difficulties that persist. Lets say that we think a bit egoistically, we have obtained the funding and now we need to find someone who can do this, and assuredly do it. Although, we do regular meetings, we do meet often and we discuss and co-write.” (male interviewee 3)

The same interviewee had employed or selected, along with another male colleague in the project, a female candidate, who was pregnant at the time of recruitment, and who lived in Luxembourg, which is a neighboring country to Belgium, and who did not want to relocate to Belgium, but rather preferred to shuttle to and fro. However, despite the reluctant approval of the candidate by the two supervisors (she was not their first choice, the first choice, also female was french and obtained a tenure track position in France during the recruitment process), there seemed to be a lingering discontentment as to the given situation:

“Well, we came to terms with it pretty quickly, although of course we were keen to start in July because we knew that other project teams has started in July and were progressing in their behalf, and that we did not have a real coordination of the project during this time. And the coordination of the project finally would start only five months later (due to maternity leave of candidate), and we were annoyed because we ourselves didnt have time to do all this. We told ourselves, what the heck, but to be absolutely honest, if we would have the same profile, and there would be a person who says, I would settle in Louvain, then yes, we would rather take her. That is sure. We know that this generates problems and we would have chosen differently.” (Interviewee 3)

The pressures felt by the interviewee and colleague themselves become quite visible in this narrative; a lack of time to do the work themselves, the pressure to ensure being within the time frame of the project in its different stages, coordination with other project partners at other universities, and also a point mentioned latter on in the interview, which was the concern that the person in question would be able to coordinate, plan and “lead” the project with the delay caused by her maternity leave and also in terms of coming into work only several days a week. However, despite these difficulties, the two colleagues tried to ensure a certain degree of organization with the candidate by having multiple discussions with her before her appointment. The female interviewees had a slightly different angle to the question, by addressing more societal and image orientated aspects that could play into discrimination at recruitment, however being more doubtful whether recruitment itself was the primary evil in the matter:

“This is a very difficult thing to measure, I personally think, in the parity of all factors, education etc., between women and men, men still have a superior status in society. But in parity of all the other factors, because if you compare someone who has more education and brilliant you cannot say that the man was taken discriminately. But I feel this. But sometimes this also plays in the roots, let’s say in the relation with the supervisor. A woman really needs to affirm herself in order not to be treated in a different manner. But I have difficulties to look for specific examples. Let’s say that the discrimination can play in the recruitment, but I would say it plays much earlier. How does one prepare the career, how is one treated, the image or perception of others upon oneself. So I think on the level of the recruitment, its already the person, who have had a certain filter already. I think that you always need good luck to get a position, you need

to be there at the right time, etc. But sometimes, the women who get to the position, who have already been strongly selected.” (female Interviewee 2, associate professor in Demography, IACCHOS)

This point about the filter working much before the actual recruitment is also supported by many interviewees in the C-level recruitment group. Another female interviewee also spoke about the difficulties beyond recruitment, the “affirmation” mentioned in the previous quote and which connects with the kind of work ethic and logic quoted by C-level interviewees, also was seen to persist beyond nomination, once the tenure track was obtained. This interviewee took her own example – which all interviewees of this group tended to do, as they were closer to recruitment themselves in their own career than the C-level academics generally – and spoke about how at recruitment she was selected pretty unanimously by the committee members at a very young age of 28, due to what she explained was scientific excellence of her dossier (publications in top journals in her field of Biology, special awards for PhD thesis and postdoctoral research, international mobility). However, almost immediately after appointment she faced what she said were the “real hurdles”:

“There are so many gender stereotypes in this academic environment. I was not taken seriously by more senior staff members, especially technicians in the labs. I was snubbed for obtaining fundings and for supervising PhDs with personal problems. I was also made often very sexist remarks such as “do dress less provocatively for meetings”. It is really hallucinating. So no I don’t think that discrimination stops at recruitment.” (Interviewee 9, female, associate professor Biology, ELI)

Women were seen by interviewees to face other kinds of obstacles in the scientific career, which seemed to demand or promote certain types of profiles, terms of a gender dimension at work at this specific state of life and career:

“In this specific case, yes there is a difference of course, because it is her who is doing the journeys, and she is the one having looked for the daycare, her husband is architect, head of the bureau of architecture, and he probably works more than she, and she has to assume more in terms of the family. To speak in more general manner, I have difficulties in saying clearly upon this topic. I can say that for early career, having kids is quite tricky I have to say, because I have three children, of which two are still toddlers and that is really difficult to manage with the demands of the work. I think that depends

how the couple organizes itself, I think even where the man in the couple helps out even 50% of house and care work, it is as difficult, and having a scientific career is difficult. And in my case, my spouse works half time, which we could conceive in my case for instance in terms of salary. (...) Articulation of private family and work is quite difficult in our profession.” (Interviewee 3, male, associate professor Sociology/Psychology, IACCHOS)

Once again, a personal experience was integrated into the perspective that the young academic has in this case of the issues that academics and researchers face during this period. There seems to be a tension voiced by all interviewees of the desire to take into account the family and private life situation of candidates in recruitments, which was often the case of the kind of candidates that were selected by interviewees (both male and female interviewees) as postdocs, and their own frustrations of dealing with what they experience as inconveniences or organizational difficulties arising from these appointments and the adjustments these necessitated.

Focus group: the discussion topics and links to interview themes:

In the focus group, unlike in interviews for obvious reasons, the themes about recruitment criteria and experiences of the process, as much as personal opinions about how things are and how they should be, were thrown back and forth amongst discussants, whereby a “red thread” of discussion emerged. The main topics of the discussion were the following:

- The ***multi-criteria in evaluating or selecting a candidate***, not solely the scientific excellence, but a collection of multiple criteria, amongst which the capacity to work in a team, collaboratively and the local integration and compatibility were named in a very similar manner as in the C-level interview group. The final selection amongst the last shortlisted candidates was considered extremely difficult, but also something that had to include not only a solid dossier (which more than list of publications, also had to demonstrate a variability and adaptability to new and institutional research contexts), but all the more what was named by more than one discussant as the “potential” of the candidate, to fit in, adapt, collaborate etc. Institutional engagement was debated as being crucial for a “good candidate”, also called “*durable inscription in the institution*”; and the need to feel out this potential while being face to face with candidates. This was also confirmed in the case of postdoctoral recruitment; by

another female discussant from ELI, the importance of the personality of the person. Can I work with this person on a daily basis, was a question that was frequently seen to play an enormous role in who one would appoint.

- The **multi-levels of the recruitment process**: a process of “*negotiation*” was often described, in which these above multi-criteria were weighed, challenged and articulated to the institutional requirements and needs. The difficulties of this process were addressed much more than in the interviews, where discussants had some key notions about this negotiation process. One female discussant spoke about how the final selection had to “mirror” this negotiation effort of the process and of committee members. Another male discussant spoke about the importance of the “*circumstantial*” and how consensus and compromise often played out in this negotiation process. Often, he explained, committees also had to face a refusal or rejection by the higher instances, and thus would often take decisions in favor of candidates who would meet with the institutional requirements according to the higher instances, and less their own preferences. One discussant named what he thought was an attitude very own to the UCL as an institution, perhaps enhanced by its Catholic past, of “*avoiding conflict*”; committee members tended to lean towards more powerful personas within the committee or without, in persons of deans, presidents of institute and rectors’ council, in order to avoid any conflict. So often decision making happens non-conflictually, in which “weaker” personas bent themselves to a dominant preference or tendency towards a given candidate.

- “**Power games**” or “**geometry of power**”; at a given point the discussion about negotiation slipped into a more frank exchange between all discussants (except one female discussant who was more silent and in the background, who is incidentally also appointee for gender studies program at UCL) about how in the recruitment processes in committees, each person mattered in the sense of their institutional, disciplinary and personal positioning and also personality. Did they have someone particular in mind? Did they favor having a particular type of profile? And would they push this through in the manner of interacting with the other committee members. The impression of *power games* was explicitly discussed, how finally some persons had the capacity to push through a preference, despite external committee members, or despite other co-members. Also the relationships of persons with higher instances and persons at UCL was seen to play a determining role in how candidates would finally

be evaluated. There was generally a consensus amongst discussants that the power dynamics of committees had at least as much impact on recruitment of candidates as their own particular dossiers or profiles.

- **“Tribal behavior”**: One female discussant from ELI spoke of a kind of ego dimension in the committees, which could play out between persons. A kind of *self-affirmation* that needed to be made heard, of making ones’ place in the institution through the committee as well. Another male discussant then spoke about how often he experienced how colleagues would prefer a “low key” profile to high flyer profiles in order to *avoid being eclipsed* in their own research or field. So often, scientific excellence played a role up to the point of the short-list and beyond which the decisions were made in a more subjective, interest-driven and *strategic* way.

- **Gender dimension**: The discussion about how gender plays into recruitment evoked a discussion about the temporality issue of the scientific/academic career. In theory, the discussants agreed that there were multi-faceted ways of criteria evaluation, but that in practice the conditions of entering into the competition were not the same for women and men at that stage of their lives. Mainly the effect of having kids and maternity leaves was named as something that becomes visible and not accepted as a “standby” of the career. However, the female discussants were explaining how they would even integrate these leaves in their Cvs, and had thus been hired “despite” these obvious family situations. There is the issue addressed of decreased mobility after having had kids, that in fact continues throughout the career, which was something also evoked in the D-level interview group. One male discussant spoke about how the scientific field acts as an elite, who wants “sportspersons of high level”, who want vocation, which is a model that serves this elite finally, and the question to ask was “what is done in this field to allow this kind of model”? Another female discussant spoke about the danger in this kind of logic for women, as in certain countries such as Italy (place of origin of person) women of a certain generation gave up having kids in order to follow this line of logic in the scientific field. And she pointed out the trouble that finally one “*did not know what one’s real value is*”. One female discussant evoked a final question about whether science would allow the co-existence with the “*feminine*” with a big F, intrinsic to women and men, a way of working, thinking and being that was feminine, a kind of counterlogic to the existing – masculine - one in the scientific field.

2.4. Conclusions

The joint vision upon the contents of the job descriptions, the HR documents provided by the rector's office in UCL, the different groups of interviews and the focus group provide a very rich picture of different dimensions of organizational logics and extra-organizational logics at play. What emerges for the case of UCL and the two institutes in question, IACCHOS and ELI, is that there is a kind of *overarching tension* becoming visible that confronts criteria and demands of young candidates in recruitment processes of D- and C-level posts that are more general and what can be called “**de-localized**” criteria and more **local and institutional requirements**. On the one hand, what becomes visible in both the job descriptions, criteria described and circulated in HR documents and interviewees experiences of criteria in their committees is a rising importance of what is called scientific “excellence” or “experience”, which is equaled to production of research, made visible and validated through publications. These publications, on the local practical reality of committee recruitment processes of selection, on the level of the initial applications by and large, are not required to be long lists. However, the legitimization and validation of publications and of candidates' research is required to happen through international approbation. Peer review in internationally renowned journals is something that is accepted and recognized by most if not all interviewees as something that has become indispensable for candidates' dossiers these days, and for what can be called a good “quality” of the research carried out. The impact factor indicators or other indicators are seen to be not entirely reliable in measuring quality, but are nonetheless accepted as a measure becoming more common in various fields, as much in SSH as in STEM fields. International mobility is something that without exception was seen as something essential in the formation process of becoming a good researcher, of having seen other research contexts, of having acquired international contacts and colleagues abroad. Thus one could say that the “de-localized” criteria have gained some ground in both fields in the experience of committee member academics in recruitment processes today, at least on the level of the initial selection and filtering of applications in the process. Moreover, these more de-localized criteria are named and seen as being important changes in the recruitment process in what was seen as a more non-biased, non-subjective and open recruitment, in terms of *competition*, rather than nomination or appointment. The higher instance interviewees in key

positions moreover spoke of the opening of scientific and academic jobs to the international market. We could speak about the introduction of new regulation logics (productivity, competitiveness, accountability and mobility). There is therefore the idea of a market logic that has entered the university institution, but seen as something favorable to ensuring equity and non-discrimination. However, upon more detailed questioning of interviewees, what becomes perceivable is that this very focus upon international criteria (publication, mobility, networking) could in itself be discriminate, as it the criteria are applied in a non-differentiated way to all applicants and candidates, without taking into account “gaps” or “stand bys” in careers often non-declared in Cvs, or in terms of what the job actually required at appointment. The requirements and criteria prerequisite a certain type of profile, somebody who would have had the necessary time and personal situation to publish, to travel etc. In this sense, the type of profile could be subscribed to by women (or men) or not; the question was raised whether this kind of profile was something many women could imagine being or working to the detriment of family life and situations, or whether they would rather deviate to other career paths in the first place, already before recruitment. Often, interviewees would speak about how women candidates arriving at the final stage of selection would have a certain type of profile that “fits” with the requirement model of the scientific excellent candidate; bachelor, non-committed, ready to relocate, to adapt etc. One could draw a first conclusion that the scientific profile in the general criteria highlighted in both SSH and STEM institutes, perhaps more so in SSH, is orientated around mobile researchers, and de-localized criteria.

If we now put this in comparison with the other criteria named by most if not all interviewees and focus group discussants, is what they see as the vital importance of institutional engagement, service to the institutional, rootedness, organizational logics and knowledge thereof, the evaluation of the potential of the candidate to “fit” and to articulate with the institutional context and its research and teaching context, the emphasis on teaching capacity in the case of SSH and willingness to teach in STEM, then we could call these criteria more “local” or “localized”. These criteria are less highlighted in the initial job descriptions and HR documents, although they are enlisted, sometimes even in first place before scientific experience or excellence. However, according to the criteria named by interviewees, teaching and institutional engagement come after scientific excellence, and become important decisive criteria

only in the final short-listed selection of three to four candidates in C-level appointment. Along with this, there is a whole narrative focus upon organizational logics, the power dynamics between committee members and other hierarchical instances. All these factors point to the “local” dimension, which is very strong in the sense that candidates are seen to require this organizational knowledge, rootedness, a teaching culture and collaborative ways or working that go far beyond the mere scientific logic of the initially named criteria. The potential of the person to “fit in” and to become a member of this internal and local logic and “elite” is not something given to all candidates, especially when looking at all the emphasis of requirements of scientific excellence defined as “internationally legitimized and validated” (peer reviewed publications in international journals, international mobility, int. networks and research project work); many interviewees acknowledge that internal candidates are easier to evaluate in the sense of knowing whether they would “fit” because they are already there. Whereas, external candidates, despite scientific excellence in most cases, are more “risky” in the local sense; will they “fit”, will they “stay”, do they have “local interests at heart and mind” are all concerns voiced about candidates that are not necessarily only externals, but also research types, who are considered individualists, ego-centric etc., and a menace to the local work organization.

There seem to be multiple ambiguities or tensions that can be named with respect to this opposition between the “de-localized” criteria and logic of recruitment and the “localized” logic:

A) firstly the difference between the focus of requirements of the scientific career in its early stages, as of the Phd, which is clearly connected with demands and requirements of scientific or research orientation; developing ones’ research, consolidating it and validating this in visible publications. The postdoctoral criteria affirm this research profile, by the project type work and its particularities (time frame, work load, leadership, coordination, independence, innovation etc.) and the criteria named by that group of interviewees. The final selection criteria are however much more academic, simply because finally the recruitment of C-level posts are “academic” posts and not research posts. Ensuring teaching, ensuring institutional engagement become key criteria for an academic appointment. The scientific factor or excellence shifts therefore into the background, and in fact is sometimes penalized as a too “individualist” or ego-centric “star” logic, which cannot function as a sole

criteria. So there is a problem of making and promoting scientists through the scientific excellence criteria gaining ground in institutions, and then requiring academics, who finally have very different qualities and require certain very local ways of being. This becomes visible when interviewees speak about having made “mistakes” in recruiting excellent researchers, who however could not fulfill the academic teaching mandate, because they simply did not like teaching and did not have rapport with the students. And others who wanted to be left in peace for doing research. This becomes further visible in the description of the tool PAIC, which is supposed to assist newly appointed academics, but which ends up being an additional pressure to ensure teaching as well as research.

B) Another tension is in the form of recruitment processes itself, in that the “localized” organizational logics and dynamics that exist and operate within the centers, institutes and UCL itself plays out in the committee and finally has as much of an impact on recruitment decisions, as much as initial criteria of scientific excellence; the initial filtering is perhaps done according to these general criteria, which are supposed to open the competition and ensure a non-biased process; however, the final decisions are very local. There is also the discussion that recruitment processes are long and arduous, and begin at planning periods within faculties, and extend beyond nomination through the hard process of probation of three years before becoming a permanent employee and tenure-track. There is a tension between ways of operating between different stages of the recruitment process that are somewhat de-coupled, and the continual struggle of affirmation and validation of candidates throughout the entire process.

C) Finally, the gender dimension aspects emerging from the document and interview/focus group material from these opposing logics described in A) and B), are likely to contribute to the subscription or not of women and men to playing the game, or of gaining membership. The period of recruitment has to be extended to much before the actual recruitment, in the sense of how easy or difficult is it for persons (of either sex) of entering into these existing often opposing logics of competing demands, and are they willing to do so. The low turnout of women may perhaps partially apply to this conflict. There is also the interesting figures in UCL that the turnout of women in recruitment processes and the percentage engaged are very close, therefore throwing doubts about the discrimination potential of recruitment

processes. Another question to be asked is whether, having gone through the selection and being chosen, do they “survive” and persist in this logic, and what does this do to their work and personal experience, and quality and balancing of different aspects of life.

Annex 2

European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the recruitment of researchers

Human Resources Strategy for Researchers 2011-2014

Introduction

On January 23, 2006, the Université Catholique de Louvain (UCL), member of the Board of Rectors of the French-speaking Universities of Belgium (CRef), signed the ‘European Charter for Researchers’ (the ‘Charter’) and the ‘Code of Conduct for the recruitment of researchers’ (the ‘Code’). On July 6, 2010, the UCL formally reiterated its commitment, emphasising its determination to support the European Commission initiative with a view to promoting and furthering the mobility of researchers in Europe (Euraxess). In addition, the UCL wishes to state very clearly that it sees the European initiative as an opportunity to intensify the efforts made over a number of years in order to improve the recruitment, the working conditions and the careers of researchers.

In accordance with the recommendations of the European Commission, and in order to define its ‘Human Resources Strategy for Researchers’ (HRS4R), the UCL has conducted an internal analysis aimed at evaluating its current institutional procedures in light of the 40 articles of the ‘Charter’ and the ‘Code’. Upon completion of this analysis it appeared that most of the principles laid down in the ‘Charter’ and the ‘Code’ have already been largely put into practice within the UCL. However, the UCL has identified a number of aspects for which there is room for improvement.

Euraxess at UCL

Since 2006, UCL has played an active role in the Euraxess initiative, which was launched by the European Commission in order to promote and facilitate the mobility of researchers.

The UCL has made a commitment to promote the use of the Euraxess jobs portal to post job offers for researchers. The UCL has also signed the ‘Quality Charter’ for

posting job offers online. In due course, job offers posted on Euraxess jobs will be visible on the UCL portal.

The Louvain International Desk (LID) was set up in February 2010 and plays the role of ‘Euraxess Services Centre’ for the whole of the ‘Académie Louvain’. It aims to provide international students and researchers with the best advice and support.

Finally, the UCL has signed the ‘Charter’ and the ‘Code’ on January 23, 2006 and on July 6, 2010 reiterated its commitment, so expressing its determination to support the European initiative and to put into practice a human resources strategy aimed at improving the recruitment, working conditions and careers of researchers.

Steps taken towards implementing the Charter and the Code

In order to examine how current practices compare to the ‘Charter’ and the ‘Code’, the UCL conducted, as recommended, a comprehensive gap analysis. A qualitative analysis of the UCL environment in light of the 40 principles was conducted, which was finalized during Spring 2010.

In May 2010, the University’s Rector launched two working groups, assigning them the mission to identify the discrepancies between the standards of good practice described in the Charter and Code on one hand and the UCL’s policies, procedures, and activities on the other hand. These two groups comprised a series of key players in terms of research areas and career levels within the UCL. The first group was composed of seven expert researchers (professor, full professors, FNRS senior research associate, FNRS research director, head of the research institute, chairman of doctoral committee). The second group was composed of seven young researchers (assistants, postdoctoral researchers, doctoral candidates, FNRS postdoctoral researchers).

The two groups conducted the internal analysis with an eye on 4 specific areas: Ethical and professional aspects, Recruitment, Working conditions & social security, and Training. On top of these two groups, the following members of the senior management level also took part in the process: Professor Bruno Delvaux (Rector), Professor Jacques Grégoire (Vice-Rector for Human Resources), and Professor Vincent Yzerbyt (Vice-Rector for Research).

In light of this gap analysis, the UCL concluded that current practices in the institution are in global agreement with the overall principles of the 'Charter' and the 'Code'. At the same time, and in full recognition of the voluntary nature of the recommendations, the UCL also highlighted areas where there is room for improvement and defined its institutional human resources strategy for researchers (HRS4R). This is the outcome of methodical and in-depth analysis and this strategy reflects the expectations formulated by the researchers and, more broadly, by all the actors involved in the construction of a more open and attractive European research space.

This HRS4R, summarised below, now forms the basis of a four-year plan for 2011-2014 presented in relation to the four axes laid down by the European Commission. It was approved by the Executive Board (*Conseil Rectoral*) on September 22, 2010 and by the Academic Council (*Conseil Académique*) on October 4, 2010.

Priority actions

Dimension 1: Ethical and professional aspects

At the UCL, whether in terms of academic and research freedom, of ethics or of professional responsibility, the current principles and practices conform to those outlined in the 'Charter' and in the 'Code'. The existing rules and procedures provide researchers with a high-quality framework for their research. The necessary structures and instruments are in place for all researchers, allowing them to manage all aspects related to intellectual property, to respect financing methods, to the dissemination and exploitation of their results, etc. However, it would be desirable to give stronger visibility to the Research Ethics Committee (Commission de déontologie de la recherche) and to expand local initiatives dealing with the 'Guide to Good Practice for Researchers' to the entire university.

Objective: Increasing the visibility of existing mechanisms related to ethics and code of practice. To this end, UCL will carry out the following actions:

1. Inform all its researchers about currently existing best practices and promote their adoption by the largest possible number.	- Implement widespread use of the 'Guide to Good Practice' for researchers - Organisation of regular workshops for exchange of good practice	Human Resources Department /Faculties Human Resources Department	Continuously Continuously
2. Define and, wherever necessary, expand the field of action of the Code of Practice Committee; especially in its role of co-ordinating with local committees	Revision of the Internal Regulations (ROI) and definition of the scope of the commission + coordination with local commissions	Ethics Commission + Staff Office of the Rector	To be Finished by end 2012
3. Establish a process allowing regular dissemination of information regarding the mechanisms and the tools available to researchers	Definition and implementation of a communications plan aimed at informing each researcher	Communication Department + Research Administration	Start in 2013 then Yearly

Dimension II: Recruitment

The recruitment policy of the UCL strives to be of the highest possible quality. Recruitment procedures are open, effective, and transparent. Selection committees are chosen with the greatest care and bring together the necessary expertise and skills. Candidates receive the necessary information in order to apply in the most advantageous manner. In terms of academic recruitment, the UCL has a policy that is particularly open to outside control. The same also applies to the recruitment of research personnel. At the same time, the UCL is well aware that when researchers are recruited on the basis of funding coming from outside the university or the national science foundation, the posting of research positions is not systematic and international awareness of these positions could be improved. Finally, even though the University attracts a large number of international researchers, the institution would benefit from making its assets as an employer better known outside the borders of the country.

Objective: Improving the recruitment of all researchers in order to make it more open, transparent, and fair. To this end, UCL will carry out the following actions:

<p>1. Professionalise the recruitment of researchers. The UCL will examine its current recruitment procedures for all research positions to improve them, should this be necessary. Whatever the funding source, and whatever the position level, the following features must be systematically present and must be totally explicit:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The specifications of the required qualifications - The selection criteria - The recruitment criteria - The recruitment procedure and/or selection procedure - The rights and duties attached to the position 	<p>Examination of procedures and recommendations</p> <p>Approval of a HR policy with a view to implementing the recommendations</p>	<p>Human Resources Department + Staff Office of the Rector</p> <p>Academic Council</p>	<p>To be Finished by end 2012</p> <p>03. 2013</p>
<p>2. Increase openness to internal, external and international recruitment - by ensuring the visibility of all open positions by improving the use of the existing communication channels and, most importantly, by promoting the use of the Euraxess Jobs portal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - by enforcing the systematic publication of positions – especially at the doctoral and post-doctoral levels 	<p>Definition and implementation of a communications plan aimed at the continuous promotion of Euraxess</p> <p>Communications plan targeted especially at supervisors</p>	<p>Louvain International Desk + Communication Department + Research Administration</p> <p>Communication Department + Research Administration + Staff Office of the Rector</p>	<p>Starting 2011</p> <p>Continuously</p>
<p>3. Promote internationally the UCL as an employer - by relying on the Louvain International Desk (LID). The LID is an administrative structure established recently with a view to co-ordinating initiatives relating to the reception of information for international researchers and students.</p>	<p>Definition and implementation of a plan for the promotion of UCL (conditions of reception and of work, advantages, etc.)</p>	<p>Communication Department + Louvain International Desk + Research Administration + Human Resources Department</p>	<p>To be finished by end 2012</p>

Dimension III: Working conditions and social security

For many years, the UCL has been investing energy in order to offer its researchers attractive working conditions, good salaries, and a rewarding and pleasant work environment. Through the implementation of a separate management structure for teaching and for research, the UCL's recently adopted organisational structure, which should contribute very significantly to a further increase of the quality of the research environment, making it more stimulating, more visible, and more effective. At the social level, the UCL has always been a proactive institution. As a case in point, as early as 2003, the UCL has been able to offer the extension of social security coverage to post-doctoral researchers. In its implementation of legislation, the UCL adopts the rules that are the most favourable to researchers by making the best possible use of the legal framework. In addition, the UCL plays an active role in all initiatives aimed at improving researchers' professional situation and attempts to remove the shackles from scientific mobility. The UCL is deeply involved in the development of the Scientific Visa. Last but not least, the UCL is also committed to the promotion of equal opportunity. Unfortunately, in spite of its efforts, the UCL observes the persisting inequality in the proportion of women in the highest research positions.

Promotion of equal opportunity between men and women

Objective: Promoting equal opportunity between male and female researchers and working for a better gender balance in all aspects of research. To this end, UCL will carry out the following actions:

1. Pursue the analysis of existing initiatives and practices in order to promote their development	Inventory of existing practices and initiatives (Human Resources Department)	By end 2012
2. Encourage examination of the steps that might be undertaken in order to correct the disparities affecting the opportunities of female researchers in their professional life (recruitment, working conditions, work-life balance, etc.)	'Affirmative action' group Human Resources Department + Vice-Rector for Human Resources	By end 2012
3. Adopt, in due time, an affirmative action programme	Define an affirmative action programme Vice-Rector for Human Resources	By end 2013

Complaints and appeals

Objective: Clarifying complaint and appeal procedures. To this end, UCL will carry out the following actions: To this end, the UCL intends to:

1. Analyse the situation by including the identification of all possible channels for registering a complaint - all the actors and/or competent authorities - all existing appeal procedures	Analysis of existing procedures, identification of possible failings & recommendations for rectifying these failings Human Resources Department + 'Legal Group'	By end 2011
2. Increase the visibility of the channels and clarify the role of the actors and of the appeal procedures	Definition and implementation of a communications plan aimed at informing researchers of all existing procedures and actors Communication Department + Human Resources Department	By end 2011
3. Promote an approach that prevents conflict through the creation of workshops for the exchange of best practices	Creation and then regular organisation of workshops for the exchange of best practice for researchers Human Resources Department	Starting 2012, then continuously

Dimension IV: Training and career

With respect to the academic career, the UCL relies on specific career development tools, namely the so-called DVP (Dossier de Valorisation Pédagogique – ‘pedagogical development record’) and the so-called PAI (Projet Académique Individuel – ‘individual academic project’). Regarding the scientific career, the doctoral training offered in the doctoral schools meets the highest quality standards. The requirements of young researchers lie above all in career coaching and management, especially in the transitional period at the end of the doctorate or the beginning of the post-doctorate.

Training

Objective: Increasing the quality of supervision, especially for young researchers. To this end, UCL will carry out the following actions:

<p>1. Support the training of young academics</p>	<p>Development of an offer of specific training (particularly mentoring and coaching) Evaluation of this training</p>	<p>Staff Office of the Rector + Human Resources Department Human Resources Department</p>	<p>By end 2012</p>
<p>2. Guarantee the genuine observance of assistants' research time (the 50/50 rule)</p>	<p>Definition of 'scientific and teaching responsibilities'</p>	<p>Staff Office of the Rector + Human Resources Department</p>	<p>By end 2012</p>
<p>3. Promote improved coaching of doctoral candidates by</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - informing doctoral candidates about the demands of the career and of the issues at stake in a doctorate (training for research through research allowing the acquisition of transversal skills) - suggesting to doctoral candidates that they prepare themselves for professional life from the very beginning of their doctoral training - disseminating the reliance on the 'thesis charter' as a tool that fosters the acquisition of transversal skills - pursuing the efforts that have been made to aid entry into professional life - developing those specific services that already exist for career orientation on completion of a doctoral dissertation - supplying the UCL with an analytical tool monitoring the production of a doctoral dissertation (length, interruption, finance, attrition, etc.) 	<p>Definition of an awareness programme aiming to inform final-year students of the demands of the thesis</p> <p>Dissemination of the thesis charter & use of tools (skills reference frameworks, skills appraisals, ...)</p> <p>Continuation of Pro-doc & other initiatives Specific orientation service for future and young PhDs</p> <p>Development of a software to cover the thesis period</p>	<p>Research Administration + Centre for Information and Guidance for Students + Communication Department</p> <p>Human Resources Department + Institutes</p> <p>Research Administration + Centre for Information and Guidance for Students Centre for Information and Guidance for Students + Research Administration IT + Research Administration</p>	<p>By end 2012</p> <p>2012</p> <p>Ongoing</p> <p>2013</p> <p>By end 2013</p>

Career

Objective: Better career management

To this end, UCL will carry out the following actions:

1. Increase the quality of reception for young researchers and of their integration into the work environment	Map of the reception process, identification of failings and/or possibilities for improvement of the process & recommendations	Human Resources Department + Louvain International Desk + Research Administration	By end 2011
2. Guarantee a better distribution of tasks for assistants	Analysis of the management of tasks & recommendations aimed at improving the process	Staff Office of the Rector	By end 2013
3. Pursue efforts to promote the value of a doctorate outside of academia	Pursue and develop communication aimed at the world of business so as to promote doctoral training and its graduates	Research Administration + Centre for Information and Guidance for Students	+Ongoing
4. Promote the standing and reputation of the profession of researcher	More intensive communication on research and the profession via the UCL portal	Research Administration + Communication Department	Ongoing, then continuously
5. Develop the use of the PAI ('Individual Academic Project') in order to monitor and orientate the academic career	Definition and implementation of a process aiming at systematising the use of the PAI (Individual Academic Project)	Staff Office of the Rector + Human Resources Department	By end 2013

Implementation of the 'Charter' and of the 'Code'

UCL has given responsibility for the implementation of its 'HRS4R 2011-2012' to the 'Comité Stratégique EURAXESS' (EURAXESS Strategic Committee), which is in charge of the various initiatives taken in the context of EURAXESS (Euraxess Jobs, Euraxess Services, Euraxess Rights, Euraxess Links).

This Strategic Committee is composed of: the Vice Rector for Personnel Policy; the Pro-Rector for Research; a member of CORSI ('Corps scientifique' – Junior Academic Staff); a member of CORA ('Corps académique' – Academic Staff); and a member of the CNE (Centre Nationale des Employés – National Centre of the Employed). Its mission is to make a regular examination of progress, to take note of the recommendations of the working groups and to define the priorities for implementation of these recommendations. In particular, it oversees the coordination of initiatives and their relation to institutional policies.

The Euraxess Strategic Committee relies on a Steering Committee whose mission is the effective implementation of strategy. It is chaired by the Vice Rector for Personnel Policy and is composed of two members of the Rector's Office and four members of the general services directly involved in the operational implementation of strategy, namely research administration, the human resources service, the Louvain International Desk and the management of institutional and cultural development (communications).

At the end of 2012, the Committee will evaluate the effective implementation of the university's 'HRS4R' and will draft further recommendations with a view to pursuing, in 2013 and 2014, the implementation of the 'Charter' and the 'Code' within the institution.

The UCL is convinced that recognition of the quality of its 'HRS4R' by the European Commission will constitute an additional attractive factor for European researchers and will contribute to increasing the mobility of its researchers.

2	SSH: IACCHOS	Female	Associate Professor: <i>Chargé de cours</i> , >3 ys	1 D-level and 1 C-Level
3	SSH: IACCHOS	Male	Associate Professor: <i>Charge de cours</i> , >3 ys	2 D-level
4	SSH: IACCHOS	Male	Professor, > 20 ys	Numerous C-level
5	SSH: IACCHOS	Male	Professor, > 10 ys	7 or 8 C-level
6	SSH: IACCHOS/UCL	Female	Vice Rector UCL, resp. HRM, Prof, >10 ys	6 C-level and D-level
7	SSH: IACCHOS	Male	President of Institute IACCHOS, Prof > 10y	7 C-level
8	STEM: ELI	Male	President of Insititue ELI, Prof > 10 ys	8 or more C-level
9	STEM: ELI	Female	Associate Professor: <i>Chargé de cours</i> , >5ys	2 D-level
10	STEM: ELI	Male	Associate Professor: <i>Chargé de cours</i> , >3ys	3 C-level
11	STEM: ELI	Male	Professor, > 10 ys	5 C-level and some D-level
12	UCL	Female	Administrative coordinator, rectors' office/council	Co-responsible of HR in recruitment process

For analytical purposes, we have synthesized the themes of the different questions in the interview guide of WP7 (sometimes in different order), which also form the subsections in the analytical part:

- Which criteria does the interviewee use and consider important criterion for a D/C level position? (Order of criteria mentioned, importance, Field/Domain, Ideal candidate, worst candidate)
- Experience of recruitment process (description of process, composition of committee, formal or informal recruitment, decisive criteria, who was selected and why, first, runner ups etc.)
- Candidates, question of gender in the recruitment process
- Gender policies (existence, experience, opinion)

We were able to conduct a focus group with 3 members of IACCHOS and 2 members of ELI, who had been part of C-level selection committees, one of which however had only experience in D-level recruitment. The choice was made due to availability of academics, who were prepared to participate, and then again who were able to get together on a given date according to their agendas. Two academics, who had been willing to participate however had to cancel in the last minute.

Department	Sex	Rank	Seniority	Committee member
SSH: IACCHOS	Female	Professor:	>10 ys	3 D-level, 4 C-level
SSH: IACCHOS	Female	Professor, appointee UCL "Gender Studies",	>5 ys	4 D-level
SSH: IACCHOS	Male	Professor,	> 10 ys	Numerous C-level and D-level
SSH: ELI	Female	Associate professor,	> 7 ys	Some D-level
SSH: ELI	Male	Associate professor,	>5 ys	4 D-level and 3 C-level

3. The Netherlands

3.1. Introduction

Radboud University Nijmegen was founded in 1923 and is a student-oriented research university. The University focuses in particular on four major domains: Arts & Humanities, Social Sciences, Natural Sciences, and Life Sciences (2013 research report). Research at the University takes place in 17 dedicated institutes. Two of these institutes are the cases used in this study.

The participating STEM institute at the Radboud University Nijmegen in the Netherlands is the Institute for Mathematics, Astrophysics and Particle Physics (IMAPP), which is one of the six research institutes at the Science faculty. In January 2005 the IMAPP came formally in existence. The IMAPP is divided into four departments: Mathematics, Astrophysics, Theoretical High Energy Physics, and Experimental High Energy Physics.

The participating SSH institute at the Radboud University Nijmegen in the Netherlands is the Institute for Management Research (IMR), the research institute of the Nijmegen School of Management. The IMR is divided into five sections: Business Administration, Economics and Business Economics, Political Science, Public Administration, and Geography, Planning and Environment. Each section is divided into different departments.

In both institutes we study postdoc positions (temporary research positions without the prospect of a permanent contract) and assistant professor positions (a position that is either a temporary position that is not expected to become a permanent position in the long run, or a tenure-track position, or a temporary position that is expected to become a permanent position in the long run). Assistant professors have both research and teaching duties. A postdoc position is usually a research only position, which is often externally funded.

In 2013, the IMR had 56.9 FTE (full time equivalent) academic staff (this number excludes PhD students) and the IMAPP had 37.4 FTE academic staff (both tenured and non-tenured; these numbers exclude PhD students). Both institutes had on average 30 FTE assistant professors and postdocs (IMR 32 FTE, IMAPP 28.6 FTE).

3.2. Formal criteria

Formal criteria STEM institute

HR documents

We analysed the strategic plan of the Science faculty (of which IMAPP is one of the six research institutes) for the years 2012-2016, a memo on tenure-track positions written by the faculty board of the Science faculty in December 2010, a memo, written in 2011, on the transition from a tenure-track to a permanent position as assistant professor in the Science faculty, and a guideline for the recruitment and selection of assistant professors (date of publication is unknown). We also analysed the University Job Classification (UFO) profiles for assistant professors and postdocs.

Is there special attention paid in the documents to junior academic careers?

The strategic plan briefly describes that the most important area of attention is the improvement of the PhD trajectory because the faculty wants to create an appropriate basis for its young academic talent to pursue an academic career. No special attention is paid to postdoc and assistant professor positions.

The 2010 and 2011 memos contain the selection criteria for tenure-track positions and the requirements one has to fulfil during the tenure-track. The memos state that there is an increasing demand/need to offer young talent a career trajectory or tenure-track, mainly on the level of assistant professor.

How is academic excellence and/or quality described in the documents?

The strategic plan describes that excellent researchers distinguish themselves by top publications and by successfully acquiring prestigious, personal prizes, awards, or funding. Furthermore, the document states that the combination of research and teaching qualities is of utmost importance when selecting talented academic staff from the assistant professor level on, as this level includes teaching and research activities.

Which criteria for junior academic careers are present in the formal documents?

In the documents of the faculty there is no information on the criteria for postdoc positions. The faculty makes a distinction between assistant professor level 1 (UD1) and assistant professor level 2 (UD2). UD1 is part of the permanent staff, UD2 is a temporary position (written in the Guidelines). The general competences an assistant professor

candidate should have, as mentioned in the University Job Classification (UFO) profile², are: conceptual ability, self reflexivity, presentation skills, results orientation. The UFO classification provide the core activities and results that have to be achieved. Table 1 provide the criteria for researchers (e.g., postdocs) and assistant professors.

Table 1: Criteria for researchers and assistant professors (UFO profiles)

	Researcher	Assistant professor
Teaching	Supervising students	Supervising students Development of education Execution of education Examination Evaluation of education
Research	Developing a research plan Research coordination Execution of research Publishing research Supervising PhD candidates Acquisition of contract research Supervising collaborators	Research coordination Execution of research Publishing research Supervising PhD candidates Acquisition of contract research and education Distributing scientific knowledge and insights Management of equipment and laboratories
Management	Task forces and committees	Task forces and committees
Other	Patient care	Patient care

Source: VSNU, 2013

More specific are the criteria mentioned in the guidelines for the recruitment and selection of assistant professors and a memo on tenure-track positions written by the faculty board in the year 2010. The following criteria are taken into account in the selection of assistant professors:

General:

- PhD degree within the field
- Masters the Dutch language, or will sufficiently do so within two years
- Masters the English language, or will sufficiently do so within two years
- Proven/demonstrable experience in acquiring external project grants
- Familiar with the supervision of students and PhD candidates

² The UFO system was developed by the all Dutch universities together. It comprises a description of jobs and job levels, and shows how the various positions at a university relate to each other. The job descriptions are based on core activities and results that have to be achieved. Universities use these profiles in the selection and promotion of staff.

Research:

- Extensive experience with scientific research, as proven by:
- Some years of postdoc experience, also abroad
- Scientific creativity, as evidenced by ... (depending on department)
- Various publications (number depending on department), also after the PhD defence
- Recognition as an expert within the field
- Has a clear vision on the development and execution of research. This vision should fit within the faculty research policy.

Teaching:

- Didactic qualities, as proven by:
- The Dutch University Teaching Qualification (BKO), or
- Extensive experience in different teaching methods, positive teaching evaluations, and the willingness to acquire the BKO
- Has a clear vision on the development and execution of education. This vision should fit within the faculty education policy.

How and to what extent are these criteria specified?

Most of the criteria mentioned in the faculty documents are not very specific, e.g., experience in acquiring external project grants. This does not tell how much money should have been acquired, from which funding organisation, etcetera. The research and teaching criteria are more specified, however, there is a lot of room left to manoeuvre. “Some years of postdoc experience” is not specific, neither is “also abroad”, or “scientific creativity”. “Recognition as an expert within the field” is also generic as it does not tell what this “expertise” or “recognition” includes. The formal criteria leave room for the different departments to adjust the criteria to their specific field.

Is there a difference in required criteria for tenured and non-tenured positions?

A tenured position in this institute means a permanent position. There are differences between the criteria required for a tenure-track position versus a tenured position. To get a tenured assistant professor position, someone should have fulfilled the following criteria within six years on a tenure-track. These criteria are written down in the memo on tenure-track positions created by the faculty board in the year 2010.

- Supervised at least two PhD candidates till completion of an approved manuscript within 48 months.
- On average three scientific publications per year
- Acquired at least two subsidies, each with a minimum of 200 k€
- At least 3 publications in journals in the top 10% of the applied faculty ranking
- More than five invited lectures
- Membership of scientific committees or societies
- Membership of an editorial board of a scientific journal
- Should have a demonstrable international network

Within three years of the tenure-track the assistant professor should already have fulfilled the following criteria:

- On average three scientific publications per year
- Acquired at least one subsidy with a minimum of 200 k€
- Completed teaching qualification (BKO)
- Have had the responsibility to provide and manage a course and received a good assessment ($\geq 3,5$)

Are there any references to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university?

A number of references to affirmative action are made in the documents. In the strategic plan of the faculty they write that most of the (under)graduate programs succeeded in attracting a high percentage of women students by targeted recruitment. The faculty aims for an equal distribution of men and women among students. Every program that had an inflow of less than 30% women students in 2010 has to realise an increase of 25% of women students.

The guidelines for the recruitment and selection of assistant professors emphasizes that a selection committee has to consist of a woman employee of at least the same positional level as the particular vacancy. It also states that the selection committee should actively search for possible women candidates. Furthermore, it says in the guidelines that within the science faculty women are preferred over men candidates for the positions in which women are underrepresented [which is in all positions within IMAPP]. In the report that the selection committee sends to the faculty board, the committee should justify, if this is the case, why no women candidates have been nominated for selection.

Job descriptions

We analysed six assistant professor and two postdoc job descriptions from the IMAPP institute that were advertised between 2010 and 2013. The assistant professor vacancies in IMAPP are all tenure-track positions, with five years temporary and possibly a permanent contract afterwards, as specified in the job descriptions. Two vacancies were for an assistant professor *or* associate professor position. All vacancies comprised a full time appointment.

Table 2: Assistant professor and postdoc vacancies by year and department

Year	Position	Faculty / department	Duration of position
2010	Assistant professor – for women	Faculty of Science	Tenure-track, 5 years
2011	Assistant professor	Experimental high energy physics	Tenure-track, 5 years
2011	Assistant professor	Mathematics	Tenure-track, 5 years
2011	Postdoc	Astrophysics	2-3 years
2012	Assistant professor	Theoretical high energy physics	Tenure-track, 5 years
2012	Postdoc	Experimental high energy physics	2 years
2013	Assistant professor/ Associate professor	Mathematics	Tenure-track, 5 years
2013	Assistant professor/ Associate professor	Mathematics	Tenure-track, 5 years

In 2010 two tenure-track positions were advertised for female scientists only: the Joliot-Curie fellowship (0,8 - 1,0 FTE³). This fellowship was offered to “talented young women with outstanding potential in the field of chemistry, physics, and astronomy” and was initiated to increase the number of women scientists in the Science faculty. Two positions were available for three research institutes in the faculty, so there was a selection committee appointed by the faculty, that comprised of staff from the 3 different research institutes. IMAPP hired one female assistant professor on this tenure-track.

How generic or specific is the job profile in terms of academic discipline?

Vacancies are discipline specific, in the sense that the topic of the available position dictates the topic of the PhD and the field of research candidates should have experience in.

³ FTE is Full Time Equivalent.

How is excellence and/or quality described in the job descriptions?

It is hard to infer how excellence or quality is described in the job descriptions. Some vacancies use superlative forms of language (e.g., ‘you are an expert’, ‘you are highly talented’) but most of the vacancies do not. In general there is a difference in language between vacancies (e.g., “you need good teaching skills” versus “you need outstanding teaching skills”). The following paragraphs will shed more light on the dominant criteria, which can tell us something about excellence criteria.

Which criteria are present in the job descriptions?

We found two broad clusters of criteria that cover both research and teaching capabilities. The first cluster contains criteria regarding the candidate’s degree, postdoc experience, a research track record, and experience with acquiring research funding. All assistant professor vacancies within IMAPP require a PhD degree and all except one of the positions require postdoc experience. Two of four job descriptions that require postdoc experience mention this experience to be “preferably gained abroad”. Four out of five job descriptions require an (international) track record, specified as either publications (in peer reviewed journals), invited talks at conferences and/ or an international reputation. Two out of five descriptions expect applicants to have experience with acquiring external funding. One vacancy asks for the ability to supervise PhD students.

The second cluster contains criteria on teaching experience and language proficiency. All but one of the vacancies require teaching skills or teaching experience. Three of the five require a university teaching qualification or the willingness to obtain such a qualification within two years. All but one of the positions require a good proficiency in English and fluency in Dutch or the willingness to learn Dutch within two years. Two vacancies ask for good communication skills. Two other vacancies require the ability to perform outreach activities and to help attract more students, which implicitly demands good communication skills too.

The criteria mentioned in the Joliot-Curie Fellowship are hard to distil as the following is what is written in the job description:

The Faculty of Science at the Radboud University Nijmegen (Netherlands) is pleased to offer several tenure track fellowships to talented young women with outstanding potential in the field of chemistry, physics, and astronomy. The Joliot-Curie fellowships are available in three of the faculty’s prestigious research institutes. This highly interdisciplinary and

collaborative environment offers exceptional research opportunities to independent, motivated and gifted female scientists.

So talent, independence, motivation, and being gifted seem to be the selection criteria. Since the fellowship is looking for women academics in different fields, the criteria might not be so specified.

The two dominant criteria present in the postdoc vacancies are: a completed PhD, and experience with particular methods of analysis.

How and to what extent are these criteria specified?

The number of criteria asked vary quite substantially between vacancies. The criteria are hardly specified. Postdoc experience, if specified, is mostly required to be 'several years'. 'External funding', 'regular publications in leading journals', 'good teaching skills' are only a few examples of unspecified criteria. Many of the vacancies mention that a candidate should have 'the ability to' or 'potential for', which is not very specific. This leaves room for the committee to decide what this entails.

Which criterion is dominant in the job descriptions?

The dominant criterion for postdoc positions is research. In a couple of the vacancies of the assistant professor positions it is hard to point out the dominant criterion. In some other vacancies research related skills criteria are dominant and in one vacancy research and 'soft skills' are equally important.

Is there a difference in required criteria for tenured and non-tenured positions?

All the positions are non-tenured positions but the assistant professor positions can become tenured after five years, depending on performance. Two of the descriptions specifies the tenure conditions: achievements in research, teaching and supervision, and the attraction of external funding.

Two of the vacancies are either assistant or associate professor level and they describe the difference between the two levels as follows:

If you are an experienced researcher, have built up your own research line and international network, and have successfully acquired external funding, please apply for the associate professorship. Less experienced researchers are requested to apply for the tenure track assistant professorship.

Are there any references to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university?

One of the vacancies specifically refers to affirmative action: 'In case of equal qualification, preference will be given to female candidates.' The job description of the Joliot- Curie Fellowship emphasizes that the positions are offered to talented young women.

Formal criteria SSH institute

HR documents

We analysed a report on staff development, published on April 4, 2013 by the Nijmegen School of Management. We also analysed the University Job Classification (UFO) profiles for assistant professors and postdocs.

Is there special attention paid in the documents to junior academic careers?

In the report on staff development attention is paid to junior academic careers, mainly by describing how the core staff is organized versus the flexible staff on fixed term contracts (e.g. temporary assistant professors, lecturers, postgraduate researchers, doctoral candidates, student assistants). "When one of these contracts ends, a critical review is conducted of the need and financeability of a contract renewal." The report states the following:

It is becoming more common for young employees who have recently earned their doctorates to be hired for teaching tasks, but they should also be offered research time. This creates the opportunity for these employees to build their academic careers. The extent of research time will differ case by case, taking into account the amount of concrete research output that is feasible within the employment period. This means an individual may be given less than 40% research time, which is more or less considered standard at the faculty.

This quote highlights the importance of giving research time to young employees so that they can build on their academic careers. The report also devotes a paragraph to postdocs and researchers in particular.

Postdocs and researchers are employed temporarily for research projects. These are mostly research projects funded by external sources (indirect government and private funding). The duration of temporary appointments is determined by the available financial

resources and the conditions that apply to the six-year term with no more than two renewals⁴.

For the purpose of the development of the careers of postdocs and researchers, the faculty may offer them an appointment as a temporary assistant professor, when they have a substantial teaching task.

With regard to assistant professor positions, the report does not mention a tenure-track system.

How is academic excellence and/or quality described in the documents?

Excellence is mentioned a few times in the staff development report, but not with regard to junior academics. Excellence is only mentioned in relation to the achievements of full professors in the field of teaching and research and in the description of criteria for promotion from Level 2 professor to Level 1 professor.

How quality is described can be inferred from the requirements that academic staff have to meet. All scientific staff with teaching duties (assistant professors, associate professors and full professors) will be evaluated based on the following criteria:

- Teaching standards
- Research standards
- Internationalization
- Functioning in the organization/group

The higher your job position, the higher the requirements in each of the four criteria.

Which criteria for junior academic careers are present in the formal documents? How and to what extent are these criteria specified?

Similar to IMAPP, there is no information on the selection criteria for postdoc positions in the faculty specific documents. Neither do they contain information on the selection criteria for non-tenured assistant professor positions. This is due to the policy of the IMR regarding selection criteria, as is stated in the staff development:

The criteria for evaluating and selecting candidates is derived from the profile/job descriptions. Needless to say, the requirements and expectations are elaborated further

⁴ Academic staff who hold a PhD cannot get more than three consecutive temporary contracts. The total period of temporary employment cannot exceed six years (Collective labour agreement for Dutch Universities).

depending on the different positions and academic fields. These requirements are specified in the vacancy profile.

So the criteria are not formalized but created by the persons who write the job descriptions. This leaves room for them to decide what the criteria entail.

Is there a difference in required criteria for tenured and non-tenured positions?

A tenured position within IMR means a permanent position. The main difference is that the criteria for tenured positions are defined in the staff development report but there is hardly anything mentioned on non-tenured positions. One distinction that is stated in the staff development report is that starting assistant professors (UD2) need to obtain a University Teaching Qualification (BKO, usually within two years) and that employees from Level 1 assistant professor (UD1) and above need to obtain a Senior University Teaching Qualification (UKO). The report states that the university and senior teaching qualifications have become increasingly important over the past years.

Are there any references to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university?

The only reference to gender equality measures in the staff development policy is the one sentence: “At least one member in each appointment advisory committee should be a woman with a position comparable to the one in the vacancy” (p. 8).

Job descriptions

We analysed job descriptions of 18 assistant professor and five postdoc positions from the IMR published between 2010 and 2014. In three cases, IMR recruited multiple assistant professors at the same time. Two of the positions (both at the section of Business Administration in the year 2012) were for permanent employment, all others temporary. Most of the job descriptions do not mention the word tenure-track. However, the majority of the documents mentioned that in case of a good evaluation after the initial contract period a contract for an indefinite period of time can be offered. The vacancy texts do not specify what the conditions for a permanent contract are.

Table 3: Assistant professor vacancies per year and section

Section	Business Administr.	Public Administr.	Political Science	Economics	Geography, Planning and Environment	All sections
2010		2	1	1		
2011		2	1	1		
2012	2		2	1		11 positions available
2013	1			1 (2 positions available)	1 (2 positions available)	
2014	1					
Total	4	4	4	4	1	

Postdoc appointments range from one year to four years. Two of the five job descriptions mention that the initial contract is one year and that the contract might be extended (after a positive evaluation). Assistant professor appointments within the IMR vary between two years and four years.

The majority of the assistant professor vacancies in IMR comprised a full time appointment, except for one part time position and three positions in which the candidate could choose for full time or part time employment, with a minimum of 0.8 FTE.

Table 4: Postdoc vacancies per year and section

Section	Business Administration	Political Science	Economics and Political Science
2010		2	
2011	1		1
2012			
2013	1		
2014			
Total	2	2	1

How generic or specific is the job profile in terms of academic discipline?

Vacancies are discipline specific, in the sense that the topic of the available position dictates the topic of the PhD and the research interests of the candidates.

How is excellence and/or quality described in the job descriptions?

Two third of the assistant professor vacancies refer to some extent to excellence, quality or “expertise”. When this criterion is mentioned, it is often related to publications in (international) academic journals. For example: “You have proven qualities in contributing to the international, academic discussion in your field, as apparent from publications in academic journals”, or “Your excellent research and teaching expertise is

evidenced by corresponding reports from others, teaching evaluations and research papers”. In the expected criteria of one postdoc job description excellence is defined explicitly: “academic excellence, evidenced by a track record of conducting and publishing academic and applied research”.

Which criteria are present in the job descriptions?

The criteria present in the job descriptions are quite similar over all different sections. Job descriptions from one particular section often use the same or a very similar text for multiple assistant professor positions over different years (i.e., they do not adjust the text). The job descriptions often require ‘abilities’ or ‘potential’, e.g., “the ability to acquire research funds”. We found two broad clusters of criteria that cover both research and teaching capabilities.

The first cluster contains criteria regarding the candidate’s degree(s), a research track record, and methodological skills. All assistant professor vacancies within IMR require a PhD degree, however some vacancies mention that a PhD does not yet have to be attained at the time of application. The section of Public Administration also specifies the MSc degree that is required. All job descriptions, except for two, require a track record of publications, most of them specify this to be in international journals. Almost half of the job descriptions require certain methodological skills: “You possess knowledge of and skills in modern methods of qualitative and/or quantitative research”. Only the Business Administration (two out of four of the vacancies) and the Political Science section (all of the vacancies) expect applicants to already have experience with or request the ability to acquiring external funding.

The second cluster contains criteria on teaching experience. The teaching criterion is present in all job descriptions (except for two vacancies in Business Administration (Strategy) that contain hardly any criteria). They require teaching experience and/or teaching skills, which is for example formulated as: “you must have teaching experience and good didactic skills”. Three vacancies go a bit further and require a teaching qualification (BKO).

The criteria in the postdoc job descriptions focus on methodological skills (e.g., “expertise in qualitative and quantitative research methods and interventions”) and language proficiency (e.g., “a good command of Dutch and English, both spoken and written”). All postdoc vacancies within IMR require a PhD degree. Furthermore, all but one of the descriptions contain the following criterion: “a willingness to work with

others in an interdisciplinary group”. Also three of the positions require the candidate to have organizational talent.

How and to what extent are these criteria specified?

In two third of the assistant professor vacancies the criteria are not specified. For example, the number of publications has not been specified, neither was the type of funding a candidate should have acquired. Interestingly, language differs across vacancies. For example, some descriptions state: “You must have teaching experience and good didactic skills” and others write: “You preferably have experience with providing academic education”. In the first case, teaching experience is a must and in the latter it is a plus.

Which criterion is dominant in the job descriptions?

The dominant criterion for postdoc positions is research expertise. In the majority of the vacancies for the assistant professor positions research capability is also the dominant criterion. In four vacancies, it is difficult to infer the dominant criterion and in one case teaching is more dominant.

Is there a difference in required criteria for tenured and non-tenured positions?

There were two vacancies that comprised tenured assistant professor positions (both in 2012 in the Business Administration section). The criteria that were mentioned in these vacancy texts were not different from the non-tenured positions. The criteria in the vacancy from the Organizational design and Development group was a bit more specified than most other vacancies. The criteria do not require ‘potential’ but already proven abilities, e.g., proven qualities in contributing to international, academic debate in the field, demonstrable thorough knowledge of recent theoretical and empirical developments in the field, shown success in attracting external funding for research projects, an excellent teaching record and proven didactic skills.

Are there any references to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university?

Five of the job descriptions refer to affirmative action policies; two assistant professor vacancies from the Economics section and three assistant professor vacancies from Political Science (Centre for International Conflict, Analysis and Management). They mention that female candidates are explicitly invited to apply. Also, a few of the

vacancies mention the following: “Radboud University Nijmegen offers dynamic positions in an attractive working environment and has excellent conditions of employment, including an attractive retirement scheme, financial child care compensation, and (partly paid) maternity leave.” The mentioning of financial child care compensation and (partly paid) maternity leave might signal to potential applicants that the organisation values combining an academic career with having children.

Comparative conclusion formal criteria STEM and SSH

All Dutch universities officially follow the UFO qualifications, so the dominant criteria are similar for at the IMAPP and the IMR for postdocs and assistant professors respectively. However, the interpretation of the criteria in internal documents differs per institute. The criteria in the UFO profiles regarding teaching are more specific than the teaching criteria in the job descriptions. Within the IMAPP, the formal criteria, as written in the HR documents, are more extensive than the criteria in the official job descriptions. From the documents, we can distil that the criteria in the IMAPP are more formalized than in the IMR. The IMAPP (or Science faculty) has documents in place which focus particularly on assistant professor positions. This is not the case for the faculty of which the IMR is part.

The number of criteria required varies quite substantially between job profiles. In most IMAPP and IMR, the criteria are hardly specified. This leaves room for interpretation by the committee members. Excellence or quality is not directly addressed in the documents, but it can be inferred from the criteria that are dominant. When comparing the criteria required by both institutes, we find that for both the IMAPP and the IMR the dominant criteria for assistant professors largely involve features as quality of research, publications, and teaching, and experience with applying for or obtaining research funding. Yet, in the IMR it is possible to be hired on an assistant professor position when candidates have recently or not yet defended their PhD. On the contrary, the IMAPP requires a finished PhD and a number of years of postdoc experience. Thus, candidates for assistant professor positions at the IMAPP have to be more academically ‘mature’ compared to the IMR, in terms of research experience and academic age (number of years after PhD). Within the IMR, it is more so that the potential to become a successful assistant professor is assessed, whereas in the IMAPP the proven qualities of the candidates are important. Other differences between the institutes concern social skills.

Almost all vacancies within IMAPP ask for communication and/or social skills, while the vacancies within IMR hardly ever mention social skills.

The dominant criterion for postdoc positions is research expertise for both the IMAPP and the IMR. This is defined by experience with particular methods of analysis (and not by a publication track record). The IMR also formalizes in its vacancy texts that the willingness to work with others in an interdisciplinary group is a criterion. This is probably stressed because the research institute values multidisciplinary approaches (website IMR). Contrary to the IMAPP, the IMR does not have many postdoctoral researchers working in the institute.

Within the IMAPP a number of references to affirmative action are made in the HR documents. However, there was only one reference that made this explicit in the vacancy text (“In case of equal qualification, preference will be given to female candidates”). Within the IMR, there is no reference made to affirmative action in the formal documents but five of the IMR vacancies specifically refer to affirmative action (“Female candidates are explicitly invited to apply”).

The IMAPP has implemented tenure-tracks for all assistant professor positions in the period between 2010 and 2014. These positions are temporary for the first five years and possibly permanent afterwards. In the IMR, assistant professor positions are not labelled as tenure-tracks, however in most of the vacancies it is stated that the contract can become permanent in the future in case of good performance. The duration of the contracts within the IMR vary (2-5 years) and they are shorter than in the IMAPP (5 years). The positions within IMAPP are all on a fulltime basis, except the tenure-track developed for women (0,8 – 1,0 FTE). Within IMR the contracts can differ between 0,8 and 1,0 FTE.

3.3. Actual practices

Actual practices STEM

Interviews and focus groups

Interviewees have been selected based on the names of committee members in the appointment reports that were available. Six interviews have been conducted with committee members who participated in a recruitment process in the period 2010-2013.

- 5 interviews with committee members who participated in selection procedures for tenure-track assistant professors.
- 1 interview with a committee member who participated in a selection procedure for a postdoc.

One focus group (FG) has been conducted with four committee members who participated in selection procedures for tenure-track assistant professors (three male full professors and one male associate professor). It was difficult to find committee members for postdoc positions as there were no appointment reports available for postdocs. It is not mandatory to write an appointment report for postdoc selection procedures. Postdoc positions are often not openly advertised and since then there is no formal selection procedure, there is no selection committee either. All interviewees and focus group participants were men, as the selection committees consists mainly of men. The women committee members that have been present in the procedures between 2010 – 2014 were often working in another university and in another country. As the focus of this study is on the formal and applied criteria within IMAPP, we have selected committee members who are employed by IMAPP.

Table 5: Information on IMAPP interviewees

N. Interview	Sex	Assistant professor or Postdoc committee
IMAPP 1	M	Assistant professor
IMAPP 2	M	Assistant professor
IMAPP 3	M	Assistant professor
IMAPP 4	M	Assistant professor
IMAPP 5	M	Postdoc
IMAPP 6	M	Assistant professor

Abstract criteria – assistant professor

The dominant criteria used within the IMAPP according to the interviewees are: 1) scientific quality and independence, 2) teaching, 3) personality and way of presenting, 4) acquisition of funding.

First, scientific quality is mainly assessed by someone's publications, which should be published in high ranked journals.

Interviewee: The list of publications is important, absolutely, yes. And not so much the number, but the quality.

Researcher: And how is that assessed, the quality?

Interviewee: That is also something that won't go bibliometrical. Because it is a, so you are interested in a certain area. And then we look at publications and sometimes. We look at the amount, the length of the publications, how many co-authors. If yes, with whom? Is this a celebrity in the field, yes or no? Or in what journals. Are these top journals or not? [...] And that's why we have those experts in the selection committee, they can assess the content of the article. (IMAPP 3)

In the Mathematics section it is important that someone has solved a problem and / or wrote an article that has been picked up by the scientific community. In Experimental High Energy Physics it is important that someone has taken a leading role in an experiment and therefore in internal publications that are published in the context of the experiment as well. In most sections, except for Mathematics, it is important that a candidate has published in different areas or has covered different topics. This indicates that someone has been independent and published own ideas.

Independence is also expressed by someone's mobility. All committee members said that candidates for a tenure-track assistant professor positions must have been mobile and preferably went abroad. They expect candidates to have at least three or four years of postdoc experience, gained by doing multiple postdocs.

At least two postdocs, so two times three years away from here. In the United States, or I don't know. Or in England, but really outside to see what happens there. And then return with experience. (IMAPP 1)

We actually demand in fact that those people have experience abroad, that they did a postdoc abroad. That can be many things. That is actually one of the requirements, that they have built their own network. That they are capable of building their own line of research, have already built it, or are currently working on that. (IMAPP 3)

According to these two committee members, going abroad leads to 'experience that is different from working in your home country', or as a respondent from the focus group argues, "you just learn more if you work in different places". It also enables early career academics to build their own international network. In addition, international experience is a great plus on someone's CV and can therefore help in acquiring external funding. Quality of the (research of the) candidate is not only deduced from the CV but also assessed via reference letters that are requested by the chair of the committee.

You want to judge the postdoc on his [sic] quality, on his [sic] potential. And yes, of course that is a bit vague, what is potential? So then you'll look at: what did he show so far and

what can you expect? And then you try, you'll always ask the supervisor for a letter, if the defence was recent. [...] You really try outside the group of friends, you try to get independent judgements. Preferably from different sides. (IMAPP 6)

This quote points towards the importance of reference letters in the selection process. All committee members have mentioned reference letters to be important to check the quality and potential of the candidate.

Second, teaching experience is a dominant criterion. Interviewees said that assistant professors have quite a high teaching load, so it is assessed whether candidates have experience with designing a course and if someone can inspire students on different levels. All candidates have to give a presentation for the committee about their research or a lecture for students. Students are present during these presentations and evaluate the candidates. Also, it is a plus if a candidate has supervised master students or, in a rare case, PhD students.

It should be someone who can do teaching. A tenure-track assistant professor is not required to have extensive teaching experience, but we do look at it, therefore the presentation [a candidate has to give]. So he or she preferably has a teaching qualification (BKO) or at least be able to acquire one on a short term. We demand of the tenure-track assistant professor that he will speak Dutch within a couple of years. (IMAPP 3)

Third, the interviews and focus group revealed that the way candidates perform during the interview plays an important role, particularly their communication skills are critically assessed. It tends to be important and sometimes even decisive that candidates can express themselves clearly and answer the questions posed in an eloquent way. This is exemplified in the following quote about two different women candidates:

In this case she had an outstanding track record, if you looked at publications and where she had been and she received extra money as a postdoc to extend her stay there. But she replied so badly to questions and she could not empathize with those PhDs, or how she would supervise them. So we said: 'It is not sensible to do this now'.

[...]

Well, she [another female candidate] came here and it was just evident that she had that drive. The way she spoke as well. She could also tell difficult things in a clear way. And she could verbalize her ambition very well. So from different aspects it was clear: this is a really good candidate for this position. (IMAPP 2)

Another quote also shows that being able to verbalize your thoughts accurately can convince a committee: "He had a great story, completely clear, everything was flawless.

The boy had never given a lecture and he stood there and, well, slides were perfect, the use of his voice was perfect” (IMAPP FG). Communication skills are considered to show competence but committee members also told that this is a skill necessary to be a good teacher.

Fourth and finally, it is mentioned in all of the interviews that the ability or potential to acquire external funding is increasingly important in the selection of assistant professors. In the focus group it became clear that according to the faculty board “money” is the most important criterion: getting a VENI grant (from the Dutch Organisation for Scientific Research) or another grant like a Marie Curie. A committee member explained:

For the faculty that [money] is certainly most important. If you check things, money is the most important thing you check, yes certainly. Actually everything is related to that as well. So for example experience abroad, that means you have a higher chance to get money. So therefore it is a better candidate. I mean, that’s how the reasoning goes. (IMAPP FG)

The committee member described the reasoning of the faculty, how the potential of acquiring research money is very much related to research quality according to the faculty. The committee member continued by saying that he thinks this is an alarming development, as he thinks that acquiring “money” is not what excellent researchers should be rejected upon.

Selection process

The selection process for an assistant professor starts when a position becomes vacant. It is then decided by the heads of department in what area / discipline an assistant professor is needed. The head of the particular department and the director of the institute decide together on the profile that has to be agreed upon by the faculty board. Based on the profile, a selection committee is composed. The compiling of the profile and the selection committee fall under the responsibility of the faculty board. According to the guidelines for the recruitment and selection of assistant professors, the selection committee should consist of at least one woman who holds at least the same positional level. Also, the committee should include a full professor of the department that has the vacancy, a student, a representative of the education institute, and an expert from the field (working in the own or another university). The committee is supported by an HR advisor. Every member in the committee is responsible for a certain task, for example to

assess the teaching qualities. One committee members explains the importance of having external experts from the field in the selection committee:

No you should prevent that [tunnel vision]. As well as the filling of all vacancies with internal candidates without selection committees, in closed rooms, that seems very insensible to me. [...] In general, every post we can fill, should be externally recruited. With a selection committee for which external members are available. (IMAPP 3)

After the committee has been installed, the job description is advertised on academic job websites and distributed via mailing lists of the particular discipline. In general, the recruitment is always open and intended to reach and attract as many applicants as possible. Based on the applications, the committee makes a ranking. The chair of the committee then proposes a short list, preferably of about six applicants. So far, most of the contact between committee members takes place via email. At the time the job interviews take place, the committee gathers together.

Gender

When the committee members was asked if gender plays a role in the selection of candidates they almost all responded that in their opinion, gender does not play a role. One committee member responded: “Yes, so for me it actually is that we always made the choice ‘yes or no’ and that gender did not really play a role in that” (IMAPP 2). Another committee members is less certain:

Yes, for assistant professors, I don’t think that it plays a role, in the sense that, let’s put it this way, there certainly is, in my opinion, no explicit discrimination. If there are underlying prejudices, yes, that could well be. (IMAPP 3)

Most of the interviewees agree that there is a problem when it comes to the low number of women among faculty staff, however they do not ascribe this to gendered practices in the recruitment and selection: “So yes, according to me, there is no gender issue really. There is a problem, but I have been here twenty five years, and I cannot say that there has ever been internal discrimination or anything” (IMAPP 4). The interviewee most likely meant there is no open discrimination against women. The conversation about gender often moved towards the committee members explaining that for example mathematics is a ‘sport’ that is preferred by men, that the ‘problem’ starts at high school or before, and that it is a cultural issue that is typical for the Netherlands. So they make

women responsible by addressing their choice of study instead of looking at gender practices in the system.

In the interviews and focus group, committee members often referred to “he”, “him”, and “his” when talking about postdocs or assistant professors. Some interviewees spoke at the beginning of the interview about “he or she” but during the course of the interview started using just “he”. The use of language reflects the masculine environments in which the committee members operate.

STEM appointment reports

We have analysed six appointment reports for tenure-track assistant professor positions. The appointment reports match the job profiles that have been analysed in part 7.1.1. of this report. There are no appointment reports available from postdoc appointments.

A professor from the STEM department told us in a private conversation that appointment reports are written in a way to ‘sell’ the committee’s decision to the faculty board. Disagreements are not mentioned and decisions are polished in order to justify the committee’s choice. The director of the institute told in an interview that the report functions as an advice to the director and informs the director on the top three candidates that came out of the selection process. The director reads the report and more detailed information on the top three candidates. Preferably, the director also has a conversation with the number one candidate. This conversation is used to get to know each other and to inform the candidate on what the institute expects of them. It happened once that the director did not follow the advice of the selection committee, because he thought the candidate had not proven himself sufficiently and was too young and inexperienced for a tenure-track. It was too much of a risk that the candidate would not pass the tenure-track. Therefore, he was at that time appointed as postdoc because he was considered to have potential. If the director agrees with the appointment of the candidate, he sends an advice to the faculty board. Finally, the faculty board decides whether or not to appoint the candidate.

Content analysis

This paragraph provides the results of the analysis of the appointment reports that focused on the question: What were the decisive criteria in the selection of the preferred candidate?

All reports taken together, most emphasis is placed on research achievements, assessed by different indicators such as previous experience, research field in which the candidate is positioned, independence (e.g., leading a group, publishing independently), reputation and recognition, and someone's publications. Another important criterion that played a role in the selection of candidates was former success in acquiring research funding and / or potential to do so in the future (e.g., when the quality of the research is high, but scientific age is also mentioned a couple of times). Furthermore, all candidates were assessed on their teaching experience and teaching skills. Most of the selected candidates had (some) teaching experience and experience with supervising BSc or MSc students and / or PhD students. Another factor that got attention in almost all the reports is the possibility to cooperate with other research groups in the department and university. Candidates were assessed on the breath of their research topic and their research interests. Committee members looked for a fit with the group but also for possibilities to cooperate with others, and therefore interdisciplinarity is valued. Finally, the experience with or possibility to engage in outreach activities was important in some of the cases. This criterion is not defined in the reports. Research quality and experience, scientific independence, and a track record of acquired funding were the decisive criteria.

Gender

In 2010 there has been a position advertised in the field of Physics, for women only, the Joliot-Curie fellowship, with the aim to increase the number of female faculty members at the faculty. IMAPP appointed a woman on this “gender tenure-track.”

Two appointment reports paid considerable attention to numbers of male and female staff. One report stated in the introduction: “The committee was well aware of the dramatic lack of female faculty members of the math department within IMAPP (0 among 16 fte).” Before the announcement of the final ranking, it said:

The point made earlier about the absence of female mathematicians at IMAPP was made again at this stage, but the gap between candidate [name] [F] on the one hand and candidates [name] and [name] [both M] on the other was agreed to be too big to overcome.

In the paragraph written on the woman candidate it said that the reason to put her on the third place was that she lacked “at least one particularly resounding research result”.

In another report, a woman candidate was ranked second, but considered an excellent candidate:

The committee would like to draw attention to the excellent female candidate ranked as no. 2, who is somewhat junior and with complementary expertise, and urge the Faculty Board to explore the possibility of obtaining additional funding to employ her as well.

Following this recommendation, the director of the institute requested to the dean of the faculty to consider the possibilities to appoint the woman. The fact that the second ranked candidate was a woman, seemed to play a role in the request as the director of the institute emphasized the gender of the candidate in his letter to the dean. Also, in the report was written: “... this will arguably be an excellent future investment for the University, also in terms of increasing its pool of female talent.” An interviewee mentioned this particular selection case and it turned out that the female candidate received a VENI grant and decided to go abroad because her partner was there.

So, gender means the number of women, and although there is an aim to change the low number of women in the staff, this is not effectuated in the appointment of women candidates. There is no recognition or awareness of gender processes in the recruitment and selection process or in the construction of criteria.

Quantitative analysis

All but one of the reports included the sex of the total number of applicants and all reports mentioned the sex of the applicants on the short list (the gender tenure-track was not counted). Of the six appointed candidates, one was a woman, which was in the case of the gender tenure-track. At least two out of the six appointed candidates were Dutch, three were non-Dutch and the nationality of one candidate is unknown (see Table 8 in the annex for more detailed information). Regarding the composition of the committee, out of the six cases, women held the position of committee chair two times. In all cases there were one or more women on the committee, but female committee members were often external and from the HR department. In five cases, the number of men on the committee outnumbered the number of women. Only in the case of the gender tenure-track there was an equal number of men and women on the committee.

Actual practices SSH

Interviews and focus groups

Interviewees have been selected based on the names of committee members in the appointment reports that were available. Seven interviews have been conducted with committee members who participated in a recruitment process in the period 2010-2013.

- 4 interviews with committee members who participated in selection procedures for assistant professors.
- 3 interviews with committee members who participated in selection procedures for postdocs.

One focus group (FG) has been conducted with three committee members who participated in selection procedures for assistant professors (one female and one male associate professor, and one female full professor).

Table 6: Information on IMR interviewees

N. Interview	Sex	Assistant professor or Postdoc committee
IMR 1	F	Assistant professor
IMR 2	F	Assistant professor
IMR 3	M	Assistant professor
IMR 4	M	Postdoc
IMR 5	M	Assistant professor
IMR 6	F	Postdoc
IMR 7	F	Postdoc

Abstract criteria – assistant professor

Assistant professor positions within the SSH department are usually filled by academics who recently finished their PhD. Therefore, all interviewees agree that the criteria for an assistant professor position cannot be too stringent. The dominant criteria used within the IMR according to the interviewees are: 1) publications, 2) teaching experience, 3) international network, and 4) personality and way of presenting.

There is consensus among all committee members who participated in the interview and focus group study that the most important criterion in the selection of assistant professors is the publication track record of “peer reviewed international articles” (IMR FG). The committee members look at the amount of articles, type of articles, co-authors, and type of journals. Preferably, a candidate has one or multiple “A-publications” (IMR 3). However, in some sections, it is “very hard to really have a publication at the end of your PhD” (IMR 5). In these sections they, however, expect applicants to have a couple of papers in the “pipeline” or under review. Also, research wise, the majority of committee

members said that they look for someone who fits the profile, and more specifically, the topic of the profile.

Secondly, the criterion that was mentioned as being really important is teaching experience. All committee members agreed that a candidate has to have at least some experience. If possible, the teaching skills are assessed by reading the teaching evaluations that students report on the candidate. Nonetheless, this criterion seems to be more fluid than the publication criterion:

Teaching is also important, but there you actually just want to see that they did some teaching. So, they know what it is. And that the evaluations of those courses are not completely bad. I mean, if they're average, you say, "Okay," you know? You can ... – he or she can probably still learn it. (IMR 5)

If a candidate does not have any teaching experience, something that does not seem to happen a lot in this field, committee members assess the way the candidates present themselves and they try to retrieve the information they want by posing questions:

People who just finished their PhD or for example a postdoc, yes, they do not do a lot of teaching. So then you will ask like, 'what did you do so far? And what did you like about it? And do you think you are a good teacher? And if so, how does this show? Or what would you like to improve?' So then you talk about this, instead of what someone factually did. (IMR 2)

Committee members said that having a teaching qualification (BKO) is a plus, but it is not decisive for assistant professors. They mentioned that candidates who do not have a BKO yet, are supposed to acquire the qualification as soon as possible.

Thirdly, a number of interviewees mentioned an international network or international experience to be important. This was also discussed in the focus group. More specifically, committee members expect candidates to have been to conferences, have talked to other academics about their research, have built a network, etcetera. However, as the following quote shows, it is not a decisive criterion:

Interviewer: an international network, or experience abroad, or something like this? How important would that be?

Interviewee: Hmm. Yeah. I think – I think it does help, and it's also sometimes mentioned as a point – as a positive point, but it's a bit like with the personality, you know, it's nothing which you would – which you would pin down as one of the most important requirements, which definitely have to be done, or have to be fulfilled. Maybe in the future, more and

more so. (IMR 5)

The fourth criterion, personality and way of presenting, will be described below, as it also a criterion that plays a role in the selection of postdocs.

Abstract criteria – postdoc

The most important criterion in the selection of postdocs is the academic quality, measured by the quality of the publications, rather than the amount of publications, or the quality of the dissertation. When assessing publications, committee members are interested in the individual contribution of the candidate to the publications. They would like to see that the candidate is able to conduct research independently and has own ideas. For a postdoc position, it is important too that a candidate has the necessary expertise needed to conduct the research project. Lastly, the motivation of the candidate to apply for the job is considered important.

Role of personality

What is considered very important for both postdocs and assistant professor positions is the candidate's personality and particularly the way they present themselves in the interview. The following quote shows the role that a candidate's personality can play in the selection process:

...but might then make the difference, you know? And then you would be able to also argue in the commission that you say, uh, but you know, this other guy maybe has not – there's one publication less, or I'd know what you know, but therefore, we actually all were quite overwhelmed with this personality, you know, so – and think that he would fit very well into our group, and then everybody says, "Yeah, your right." And so there's – but it's at the margin, right? (IMR 5)

Also, it is valued if candidates present themselves well and if they can communicate their arguments clearly and eloquently. However, the above quote shows that this only matters on the margins, when the candidates are seemingly equal in terms of the other qualifications. Another committee member explains that she does not 'get fooled' by the 'sales talk' of candidates who are smooth talkers:

I prefer content over form. I just listen really carefully to what someone is saying. [...] A nice sales talk is not what convinces me. Someone who is more thoughtful, more calm,

needs to take his time, but comes forward with an outstanding content related answer. And really knows to get to the core, that appeals to me much more. [...] But what I notice a lot in committees, also in selection committees, that people let themselves be fooled. That the one who easily expresses himself and who, you know, that that is appreciated. While I, yes, for me that is no guarantee to success. (IMR 2)

Communication skills, personality, and a candidate's way of presenting oneself are considered important. Committee members expressed that they are looking for someone they can cooperate with in a pleasant way and personality is also considered an indication whether or not someone will fit in the group.

Selection process

The selection process for an assistant professor starts when a position becomes vacant. It is discussed with the head of the section and the dean whether it is financially possible to fill the vacancy. If so, a job description is created. The HR department has a template for this. Faculty policy prescribes that assistant professors are openly recruited, however, there are exceptions to this norm. One of the appointment reports we analysed revealed that the candidate was recruited via a closed procedure and the interviews revealed that there are more such cases. When a position is openly recruited the vacancy is advertised on the Internet. When composing the selection committee, the main tasks the assistant professor will have to fulfil are taken into account. For example, the coordinator of the bachelor programme will take part in the committee when the assistant professor has to do a lot of teaching in the bachelor programme.

When all letters of application have come in, the committee makes a short list of candidates to interview. The committee members make a selection based on the CVs and the letters of motivation. Internal candidates have to be invited for an interview in line with faculty rules. A number of applicants who just did not make it to the short list are put on a reserve list. At the time the job interviews are scheduled, the committee often meets for the first time in real life. The job interview usually consists of one meeting with the candidates, in which each candidate has an interview with the committee. Based on all interviews, the committee discusses the candidates and decides on the preferred candidate. In case the committee cannot make a decision, a second round of interviews can be organised in which the remaining candidates for example give a presentation or a short lecture.

Gender

When the committee members were asked if gender plays a role in the selection of candidates, a variety of responses were given. Some thought it played a smaller role than it used to do in the past, some strongly agreed that gender plays a role, and some said that gender played a role but in a way beneficial to women, e.g., because they have a lack of women in the section and therefore a woman candidate is seen as an asset, given that she is qualified.

All committee members who agreed that gender plays a role in selection processes were women. They gave examples of situations in which they had encountered gender bias.

It plays a role everywhere. It plays in the postdoc selection, everything from [name of male professor] being the chair of that committee to the women candidates being more, or not as convincing in the way that they presented themselves. They were being too modest, right? And this is the old cliché about women are accused of being more modest, or too modest, but then when they're not modest, then they get accused of being aggressive bitches, right? (IMR 6)

Yes, but quality is also assessed differently. Because what counts for one person, does not count for another. Because it is not equal. No. And for example [...] it is my task as chair to pay attention that that is assessed equally. So I am very strict with regard to that matter. If people for example say in case of one candidate, yes this one has already seven articles and blah, blah, blah. And then in case of another candidate, yes but this one has to progress a bit more. Usually that is then a woman. Very annoying. Then I say, yes but listen, this one also has seven and the other also had seven and that one you thought was very great, good, so what's the difference? They don't always like that. (IMR 2)

These two committee members are aware of the gender practices that play a role in the selection of junior academics. The first committee member refers both to the way the selection committees are organized as well as to the way the behaviour of women is assessed, according to expected feminine behaviour. The second committee member explains how committees can evaluate men and women differently. According to the interviewees in the Economics section, gender plays a role in a way that advantages women candidates:

Um, but even if the profile isn't 100 percent fitting, even if there are some other things; uh, if there's nothing which really speaks against her, she's definitely going to be invited. That's definitely – that's basically the rule. [...] the argument that this is a woman is very often then also openly discussed in the sense, like, "Yeah, but you know, we need more women,

and we want to support,” blah, blah, blah. So, this argument, also, at the margin later on may even overpower certain – uh, so it also happens that the female candidate is slightly less qualified, but not much, really slightly less, but therefore has the advantage of being female, meaning you fulfil the quotas, you know, you fulfil the political correctness, you know, fulfil basically the – what also the University Board, everybody wants from you, right? (IMR 5)

This committee members said that the sex of candidates is openly discussed during committee deliberations and that women are preferred over men candidates because of the low number of women in the group. The committee members also vocalised that they have to abide by the targets the University board poses on them.

To several interviewees within the IMR, gender means the number of women academics. Committee members within the Economics section, related gender to the number of women in their section. They argued that because of the low number of women staff in their section, women tend to have an advantage in the selection procedure. A number of women committee members did not refer to the number of women in the IMR or the section, but pointed towards the pervasive role gender can play in the selection of candidates. They gave examples of how women are evaluated differently compared to men and how feminine characteristics can be of influence. So some of the committee members are aware of gender processes in the recruitment and selection process but others are not. There seems to be little to none recognition or awareness of gender processes in the construction of criteria.

SSH appointment reports

We have analysed 25 appointment reports, 22 for assistant professor positions and three for postdoc positions. In three cases, two candidates were selected, so the written reports were identical. This means that we have analysed 22 unique reports.

The reports are not homogeneous with regard to the completeness of a description of the recruitment and selection procedure, each applicant’s description and the relative assessment. Some of them are very detailed (2-4 pages), others are very brief and only report a description of the appointed candidate (0.5 page). The length and thoroughness of the reports differ across sections (e.g., the Economics section but particularly the Public administration section provide very limited information).

Similar to the IMAPP, a professor from the IMR told us that appointment reports tweak the selection process in a way that it convinces the dean:

I mean, ideally, the commission should be unanimous. Um, if there's somebody on the commission who says, "I really can't this; I'm not giving this – please write in the report to the dean," because then there comes the advice of the dean, which has to be written up. If you then say, "I really want that you wrote into the advice that I'm not supporting this," then the dean will definitely think twice, and also ask – and probably also invite the commission again to discuss this together with him. (IMR 5)

Content analysis

This paragraph provides the results of the analysis of the appointment reports that focused on the question: What were the decisive criteria in the selection of the preferred candidate?

Assistant professors

Almost all of the appointment reports mention the fit of the appointed candidate with either the profile or the research group / section the candidate will be part of to be an important criterion for appointment. Interestingly, besides the fit with the group, some reports mention that the candidate was appointed because he/she expands the research topics of the group and is therefore complementary to the existing expertise in the group, however this was a criterion in a much smaller number of cases.

In almost half of the appointment reports for assistant professors, the strongest emphasis was on both research and teaching. In the other half of the reports, the emphasis was *either* on research *or* on teaching. The criterion of teaching was usually assessed by teaching experience (i.e., the number and type of courses taught, the topic of the courses taught), teaching evaluations (usually filled out by students), and in a very limited number of cases a teaching qualification. In cases where the appointed candidate had little teaching experience, it was written that the vision on teaching was assessed or that the committee could assess the teaching potential by looking at the way the candidates presented themselves in the interview or during a presentation. The criterion of research was assessed by looking at the number of publications, the publication outlets (e.g., "top journals"), quality of the publications (often not defined what this entails), expertise with research methods, research topic (of previous work), or expertise in a particular field.

Another important criterion is the appointed candidate having a relevant and / or international network, as this was mentioned in almost half of the cases (e.g.,

“internationally oriented and good international network”). This is related to the previous universities / research institutes where the candidate has worked, either internationally or nationally.

Three of the cases mention the experience with acquiring funding to be one of the skills of the appointed candidate and in one case it is written that the appointed candidate has the *potential* to acquire funding from the Dutch Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO). Also, four reports state that one of the criteria on which the applicants will be selected is the ability or potential to acquire research funding, however, there was nothing written in the report on the ability or potential of the selected candidate to do so.

Finally, half of the reports mention one or more personality traits of the selected candidates, for example, being open minded, ambitious, motivated, enthusiastic, etcetera. When a personality trait is mentioned, this is usually reported as a positive characteristic.

Gender

Within all the reports analysed, there has no explicit attention been paid to gender.

Quantitative analysis

Eight out of 25 reports included the sex of the total number of applicants and 18 reports included the sex of the applicants on the short list. Of the 25 appointed candidates, 11 were women. 12 out of 25 appointed candidates were Dutch, five German, and eight had other nationalities (see Table 8 in the annex for more detailed information). All three postdocs and ten assistant professors were non-Dutch. The reports do only in eight cases provide the sex of the applicants and in 18 cases the sex of the shortlisted candidates. Therefore it is very difficult to conduct an analysis of the percentage of rejected men and women after a first selection of candidates. Regarding the composition of the committee, out of 23 cases (2 cases were unknown), women held the position of committee chair only three times. In just one case there was no woman on the committee. In 16 cases, the number of men on the committee outnumbered the number of women. In five cases, the number of women outnumbered the number of men. In four cases, the number of men and women on the committee was the same. Of the committees for a postdoc position, the chair was always a man.

Comparative conclusion STEM and SSH actual practices

Abstract criteria

Overall, the criteria used in the recruitment practices within the IMAPP and the IMR are quite similar. Both the IMAPP and the IMR focus on research and teaching performance in the selection of assistant professors. Research performance is assessed mainly by the CV of the candidate. Teaching performance is assessed by teaching evaluations and / or the job interview (IMR) or a presentation (IMAPP). Also, in both research institutes, the personality of the candidates and the way they present themselves during the job interview play an important role in the selection process. Within the IMAPP they also pay attention to the candidate's track record of acquired research funding or the potential to acquire funding in the future. Within the IMR, this is considered less important. At the level of assistant professor, candidates at the IMR do not have to show that they already have acquired funding. In some cases it has been a criterion "but in practice it is not really applied yet" (IMR 1). It is definitely considered a plus if someone already applied for external funding and was successful, but at this level committee members will look if they have the potential to do so in the future.

Committee members in the IMR look at the candidate's international network and consider this to be an important criterion. The IMR focus group members said that going abroad to attend conferences is a signal of independence and curiosity, which is something they value. Candidates in the IMAPP are expected to have international research experience (e.g., a postdoc abroad) in order to build a network, gain valuable experience in other research environments, and increase the success of acquiring external research funding. So in both research institutes international experience is valued, but the way they assess this experience differs.

Within the IMAPP a few discrepancies between the different data sources that we analysed to study the actual practices have been found. The decisive criteria mentioned in the appointment reports and the decisive criteria in the interviews and focus group do not fully correspond. The interviewees within the IMAPP did not mention the ability to cooperate with other research groups in the department and university or to engage in outreach activities. However these criteria played a role according to the appointment reports. Within the IMR there is consistency between what the committee members said during the interviews to be important criteria and what is written in the appointment reports.

Selection process

The actual steps of the selection process for assistant professors are very similar in both the IMAPP and the IMR, however the execution of some of the steps is different (e.g., composition of the selection committee, candidates only having to do a job interview or also a presentation / lecture).

Gender

Within the IMAPP, the faculty board and the committee members are aware of the lack of female academic staff. In the IMAPP interviews, gender is referred to as something that concerns the number of men and women staff. The committee members are not aware of gender practices in the formulation or application of selection criteria. Within the IMR, some committee members referred to the number of women in the group when gender was discussed. However, other committee members tend to be more aware of the gender practices, particularly the practices in the evaluation of women candidates. It should be noted however that the committee members who were aware of gender practices are women. Nevertheless, and similar to the IMAPP, the committee members in the IMR were not aware of gender practices in the formulation or application of selection criteria.

3.4. Conclusions

Overall, comparing the formal criteria and the criteria applied in practice, we conclude that there is overlap, but also significant differences between the formal and the applied criteria in both the IMR and the IMAPP. Differences between the formal criteria in the different documents we analysed and differences between the criteria applied in practice as reported in the appointment reports and interviews were also found. We found that the criteria that are formalized do not all have the same importance when applied in practice. For example, the proven experience in acquiring external project grants (IMAPP formal criterion) or the teaching experience required within the IMR, tend to have some leeway in the actual selection process. The job profiles show the ambition to recruit the 'ideal academic' that has it all, but committee members often have to tune down their demands in practice. We also observed the opposite; criteria being applied in practice that are not emphasised in the job profile. For the postdoc positions in the IMR the interview data showed that publications are considered very important in the selection of postdocs, whereas this is not mentioned in the job descriptions. Thus, formal criteria can be applied selectively, or less strictly. Also, the specific job profile may emphasize

some criteria over others. The nature of a vacant position might for example demand experience with a specific research method or extensive teaching experience, which would therefore be of more importance than other criteria. Hence, the formalized criteria do not all carry the same weight. Because dominant criteria can shift and because criteria are in most cases not specified, there is room for interpretation and room to manoeuvre for the selection committees. This points to the relevance of selection committees and their decisive role in recruitment and selection, and nuances the importance of formalization of criteria.

A criterion that turned out to be very important in the actual selection process in both the STEM as SSH field, but is not formalized in the documents, is the personality of the candidate and the behaviour during the job interview. This criterion depends very much on personal preference of and a 'click' with the committee members. If the committee is not aware of possible biases of this criterion, this could disadvantage certain candidates while benefit others. Ideas about personality and presentation in male dominated environment may narrow ideas about suitability of candidates. Research shows that the implicit ideal worker fits men better than women, particularly in male dominated academic environments (Benschop & Brouns, 2003; Bleijenbergh, Van Engen, & Vinkenburg, 2013; Van den Brink & Benschop, 2012) such as in IMAPP.

The formal criteria in the documents do not often contain the word 'excellence'. When excellence is mentioned, it mainly refers to top publications and success in acquiring prestigious, personal prizes, awards, or funding. Within the appointment reports, the word excellence is seldom used to justify the choice for the number one candidate. The interviewees only spoke about excellence when we asked them to explain the difference between a candidate with minimal requirements and a really excellent candidate. The results show that excellence is neither a strictly formalized criterion, nor part of the discourse of committee members.

We noticed some clear differences between the institutes in relation to gender and gender awareness. Within the IMAPP, gender means the number of women staff. Both the formal documents as well as the committee members explicitly pay attention to the lack of women staff within the research institute. At this moment, among the permanent staff there is one female professor and one female assistant professor. Although there is an aim to change the low number of women in the staff, this is not effectuated in the appointment of women candidates, as in every procedure men candidates are preferred

over women candidates. There is no recognition or awareness of gender processes in the recruitment and selection process or in the construction of criteria.

Within the IMR, the number of women academics is much higher than within the IMAPP. It could be that because of the increased number of women staff compared to earlier years, some committee members think that nowadays gender plays less of a role in the IMR than it used to do in the past. Within the IMR, gender also means the number of women staff, in sections where few women are employed. Committee members argued that because of the low number of women staff in their section, women tend to have an advantage in the selection procedure. However, in IMR other meanings of gender are also present. A number of women committee members pointed towards the pervasive role gender can play in the selection of candidates. They gave examples of how women are evaluated differently compared to men and how feminine characteristics, such as women being too modest, can hamper a positive evaluation for women candidates. So some of the committee members are aware of gender processes in the recruitment and selection process but others are not. Similar to the IMAPP, there seems no recognition or awareness of gender processes in the construction of criteria within the IMR.

References

- Benschop, Y., & Brouns, M. (2003). Crumbling ivory towers. Academic organizing and its gender effects. *Gender, Work & Organization*, 10(2), 194-211.
- Bleijenbergh, I., Van Engen, M. L., & Vinkenburgh, C. J. (2013). Othering women: Fluid images of the ideal academic. *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion*, 32(1).
- Van den Brink, M., & Benschop, Y. (2012). Slaying the seven-headed dragon: The quest for gender change in academia. *Gender, Work & Organization*, 19(1), 71-92.

Annex 3

Quantitative data IMAPP

Sex	Nationality	Year of PhD	Internal / external candidate	Research group	Contract type	FTE	Total N. applicants	N. male applicants	N. female applicants	Total N. on shortlist	N. shortlisted men	N. shortlisted women	% women applicants	% women shortlisted	N. male committee members	N. female committee members	Sex of committee chair
1 M	non Dutch		External	Experimental High Energy Physics	Tenure track assistant professor	Fulltime	22	20	2	6	5	1	9	17	3	2	M
2 M	non Dutch	2008	External but via personal network of committee chair	Mathematics; Applied Stochastics	Tenure track assistant / associate professor	Fulltime	29	24	5	7	6	1	17	14	5	1	M
3 M	Dutch	2007	External	Mathematics; Algebraic geometry	Tenure track assistant professor	Fulltime	33			6	5	1		17	6	2	M
4 M	German	2004	External	Theoretical High Energy Physics	Tenure track assistant professor	Fulltime	41	37	4	5	3	2	10	40	6	1	F
5 M		2012	External	Geometry and Quantum theory	Tenure track assistant / associate professor	Fulltime	99	85	14	7	5	2	14	29	7	1	M
6 F	Dutch	2002	External	Astrophysics	Female tenure track assistant professor	0,8 - 1,0	45	NA	45						4	4	F

Quantitative data IMR

Sex	Nationality	Internal/external candidate	Department	Position	Total N. of applicants	N. male applicants	N. female applicants	% female applicants	N. internal applicants	Total N. on shortlist	N. of shortlisted men	N. of shortlisted women	% women on shortlist	Internal candidates interviewed	Male committee members	Female committee members	Sex of committee chair
1 M	German	External	GPM	assistant professor	58					9	5	4	44	3	3	1	M
2 F	Dutch	External	GPM	assistant professor	58					9	5	4	44	3	3	1	M
3 F	German		Business Administration	assistant professor	22					6	5	1	17		2	2	
5 M	Dutch	External	Economics	assistant professor	18					2	2	0	0		4	1	M
6 M	German	External	Political science	assistant professor	26	21	5	19		6	3	3	50		1	3	M
7 M	German	External	Economics	assistant professor	27					4	4	0	0		4	1	M
8 F	Dutch		Public Administration	assistant professor	5					4					3	1	M
9 F	Dutch	External	Business Administration	assistant professor	15					5	3	2	40		1	4	F
11 M	Dutch		Public Administration	assistant professor	17					6					1	3	M
12 M	Dutch		Public Administration	assistant professor	17					6					1	3	M
13 M	Dutch	External	Public Administration	assistant professor											2	2	M
14 M	France	External	Political science	assistant professor	27	19	8	30	2	7	5	2	29	1	2	1	F
15 M	Ireland	External	Political science	assistant professor	27	17	10	37		6	5	1	17		2	1	F
16 M	China	External	Economics	assistant professor	39					9					2	1	M
17 F	Dutch		Public Administration	assistant professor	3					3					4	0	M
18 M	Dutch	Internal	GPM	assistant professor	54				8	8	4	4	50	2	3	1	M
19 F	Dutch	Internal	GPM	assistant professor	54				8	8	4	4	50	2	3	1	M
20 M	Belgian		Business Administration	assistant professor	14	10	4	29	2	4	2	2	50	0	3	1	M

21	F	USA	Internal	Political Science	assistant professor	37	27	10	27	2	15	1	3	2	2	1	33	1	2	2	3	1	1	M
23	F	Dutch	External	Public Administration	assistant professor	8							4						2	2	2	2	2	M
24	F	Dutch	Internal	Political science	assistant professor														2	1	2	1		
25	M	Canadian		Political science	assistant professor	13	11	2	15	2	15	1	3	2	2	1	33	1	2	2	2	2	2	M
4	F	Italian	External	Political science	postdoc	18	5	13	72	2	72	2	6	1	1	5	83		1	2	1	2	2	M
10	M	Turkey	External	Economics/ Political science	postdoc	6							4	2	2	2	50		3	1	3	1	1	M
22	F	German		Political science	postdoc	6	3	3	50	3	50	2	3	0	3	100		2	2	1	2	1	1	M

4. Iceland

4.1. Introduction

The University of Iceland is organised into five academic schools with 25 faculties (departments) and four interdisciplinary study lines. The two selected departments within the academic fields of SSH and STEM at the University of Iceland are the Faculty of Political Science and the Faculty of Physical Sciences. Due to the small size of these departments and difficulties to fulfill the requested data collection of WP7 it was decided to broaden the data collection to the complete schools of Social Sciences (SSH) and Engineering and Natural Sciences (STEM).

For the mapping of the formal criteria the requested data was in regard to job descriptions of vacancies for C- and D- level positions and tenure-track and non-tenure-track positions, advertised between 2010-2014, within the two academic fields, as well as HR-documents about career trajectories and job demands. The University of Iceland however, only advertises job vacancies for C-level positions (assistant professors) and those positions are temporary full-time positions with the prospect of a long-term contract after 5 years. The data on the job descriptions for the C-level positions were available. Within the university there are D-level positions, that are also non tenured-track, but they are not advertised.

The selection process takes place in two stages as determined by the Rules for the University of Iceland No. 569/2009. First an evaluation committee evaluates if candidates fulfill the minimum requirements for the position. The evaluation committee consists of three members, two members appointed by the University council and one specialist appointed by the department. The applications of qualified candidates is sent to the selection committee. After the evaluation committee has evaluated candidates, the selection committee takes over in order to make the final decision on who is going to be hired for the position. The evaluation committee consists of five members, the head of the faculty (department) that is also the chair of the committee. One standing member appointed by the department. Two specialists appointed by the department and one member appointed by the University's rector. When it comes to participation in the evaluation and selection committees it is stated in the Act on Equal Status and Equal Rights of Women and Men no. 10/2008 that participation of women and men in public

committees and boards has to be approximately equal (minimum 40%), this also applies to the University of Iceland.

To examine the criteria as applied in practice the requested data derive from focus groups and semi-structured interviews with committee members as well as an analysis of appointment information. All academics within the School of Social Sciences and the School of Engineering and Natural Sciences, that had been on an evaluation or selection committee, between 2010 and 2014, were asked to participate in the focus groups. If they declined they were asked to take part in an interview. The SSH focus group consisted of five committee members; two women and three men. The STEM focus group was made up of just three committee members; one woman and two men⁵. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with five committee members in SSH, four men and one woman, and four committee members in STEM, one man and three women. Due to the small number of committee members we were unable to obtain an equal number of female and male participants. In total, seven female and ten male committee members participated in the focus groups and interviews. At the University of Iceland appointment reports are not a part of the appointment practices, but some quantitative data was available with regard to the composition of committees and basic information on candidates such as their sex and whether or not they were appointed.

4.2. Formal criteria

How generic/specific is the job profile in terms of academic discipline?

The report details and reflects upon the content of job descriptions from two schools of the University of Iceland, STEM and SSH as assigned by GARCIA. The advertisements are from the period 2010-2014 and count in total 56 advertisements; 27 from STEM and 29 from SSH. The report is based on the questions listed on the work sheet for WP7:

- How generic/specific is the job profile in terms of academic discipline
- How is excellence and/or quality described in the job descriptions
- Which criteria is present in the job descriptions
- How and to what extent are these criteria specified
- Which criterion is dominant in the job description

⁵ Unfortunately we had two last minute cancellation in that focus group from one female and one male committee members. It was impossible to reschedule the focus group because all the committee members that couldn't attend the focus group, and were willing to participate in the research, had been scheduled for an individual interview.

- Is there a difference in required criteria for tenured and non-tenured positions (not relevant in the Icelandic context).
- Are there any references to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university.

ATLAS.ti was used to conduct the content analysis of the formal criteria. The criteria coded were 25 in total, thereof 20 predetermined by the WP7 team with extra 5 added by the Icelandic team. The criteria present in the job descriptions are listed below.

The structure of the positions advertised in both schools examined at the University of Iceland, SSH and STEM, is highly standardized and schematically similar. The adverts from the schools is therefore analysed parallel to each other. The title of a job advertisement is the title of the position advertised. The advertisement begins with a description of the position advertised such as: “The faculty of [...] seeks an applicant to fill the position of Assistant Professor in the field of [...]”. The advert then proceeds with detailed requirements for the specific position in question such as “teaching” “undergraduates/graduates” and/or “carry out research”. The specified clause always includes an emphasized demand for an applicant possessing strong “social skills” and/or “communicational skills”. All positions advertised in both schools are temporary full-time positions with the prospect of a long-term contract after 5 years as determined by the University regulation nr. 569/2009 article 31⁶. Towards the end of an advert is a standard clause, in all school and faculty, describing general demands including: “degree criteria, research, publications, working experience and management skills”. This clause is typically as follows:

Applicants shall include with their applications certificates attesting to their education and work experience, a list of their publications, a report on their scholarly work and other works they have carried out, and an outline of their research plans if they are offered the position. Applications must make clear which of their publications, the applicants regard as the most important regarding the advertised position (no more than eight publications should be selected). Applicants must send the most important publications with their application, or indications as to where they are accessible in electronic form. When more than one author has produced a publication, the applicant must account for his or her own

⁶ See Rules and regulation, retrieved from: http://english.hi.is/rules_and_legislation/legislation_and_rules (not yet available in English).

contribution to the work. Applicants are also expected to include references for their teaching and administrative work, as appropriate.

At the very end of the majority of adverts from both schools is the notation: “The University of Iceland applies its equal opportunity policy to all appointments”.

Upon a closer look the profiles of jobs advertised in the two schools, STEM and SSH, differ on a few levels. The STEM advertisements tend to be more detailed than the SSH adverts with more articulated demands as demonstrated in the following examples:

SSH-advert: “Experience in research and teaching in the field of [...] along with other work-experience in the field.”

STEM-advert: “Candidates should also demonstrate abilities in high quality research for [...], teaching both undergraduate and graduate courses, advising PhD students, and providing appropriate service to the department, university and the profession.”

Also, SSH advertises almost exclusively in Icelandic, limiting the applicants to Iceland whereas STEM advertises both in English and Icelandic extending the range of possible applicants. This is in line with the University’s policy, according to that the University wishes to recruit employees with diverse backgrounds and for that purpose it “will whenever appropriate advertise academic jobs internationally” as stated in the policy.⁷

How is excellence and/or quality described in the job descriptions?

The discourse of ‘excellence’ is predominately to be found within the job advertisements from STEM, with the exception of the department of law at SSH. In the advertisements from the law-department at the University of Iceland, the discourse of excellence is frequently applied. In almost every incidence excellence is linked to the University as an institution and its academic employees as the following example demonstrates:

At the University of Iceland, students receive excellent academic training and extensive schooling in critical thinking and independent methods of work. On account of their eminent scientific work, the teachers of the University have good reputation worldwide. The University collaborates with the most prominent Universities and faculties in the world.

The discourse of excellence in this case is rationalized and thus legitimized with the assertion of international recognition. Most of the STEM faculties apply a declaration of and/or claim for excellence in a number of their job advertisements. The enactment is on

⁷ See the policy of the University of Iceland 2011-2016
http://english.hi.is/files/afmaeliforsida/policy_2011-2016.pdf

many levels; referring to the University as an institution, the faculty in question, academic staff, reputation, aims and requirements to the applicant her-/himself. The STEM faculties typically open their job advertisements by praising the University, either in a broad and general way as this example shows: “The University of Iceland is a progressive educational and scientific institution, renowned in the global scientific community for its research.” Or in a more specific manner as the following quotation reveals:

The University of Iceland has for years been leading in the field of teaching and research regarding renewable energy in Iceland. There are many opportunities in this field, both locally and globally. It is clear that energy use in harmony with nature and society is one of the big projects this century faces. The University has, therefore, decided to further strengthen research based graduate studies in the field of renewable energy.

The quote reveals the capturing of excellence on several levels. The first sentence of the paragraph refers to the University of Iceland as the highest local institution of science and research in the country. It also interconnects the academy with expertise by tying the mastering of the nature of the country to excellence. The local academics claim expertise on home ground so to speak, an assertion intertwining the discourse of excellence with the code of national context. The paragraph goes on by hinting hidden opportunities of the field in local and global sense and thus plugs Iceland with the rest of the world. The connection itself is based on the excellence of the first mentioned, Iceland, that according to the advert has something to offer the world and not as a future resource but with its scientists as future leadership-team. The need for specialized knowledge is addressed. An underlying subject is the well-known pending danger of a great lack of energy-sources in hand with the negative side effect of the existing utilization of the same resources. This calls for development in the field and simultaneously the reproduction of experts of excellence to become viable rescuers at critical times.

Lastly the appropriate candidate is addressed in the advert; one that fits the described profile of institution and its staff: “Applicants must demonstrate a potential and interest in achieving excellence in research and teaching in the areas of power plants, power distribution, energy efficiency and/or environmental aspects of energy utilization.”

The demand for excellence from the applicants is frequent within STEM. A very qualified candidate is seen as both befitting and an addendum to the rank of a field/institute in general: “The field of expertise and the research program of the successful candidate should complement the strengths of the Faculty and the Institute of Earth Sciences

(IES).” Or, as other adverts demonstrate; excellence is required from the candidates on many levels:

Applicants must have either demonstrated or possess a clear potential and interest in achieving excellence in research and teaching. Successful applicants must be active in enhancing educational and research links within the community.

Here, the candidate is required to proof (capability of) excellence in the two main areas of her/his possible post, research and teaching, and beyond that s/he is expected to gain and extend academic ground.

Criteria in the job descriptions: How and to what extent are these criteria specified?

Below the codes will be listed and reflected upon:

1. ‘Acquiring funding’ occurred nine times in the data. The criteria is referred to by calling for experience of obtaining funds: “The applicant should have experience in obtaining independent research grants”.
2. ‘Collaboration’ occurred 41 times in the data, mostly unspecified and interlinked with another code; social skills: “Strong communication and interpersonal skills are essential assets.” The code also occurs in a more elaborated context within a certain unit: “S/he will also have an important role in the development of the program in collaboration with the program board...” And even in a global context: “The candidate is also expected to collaborate with scientists outside the faculty, outside the university and internationally.”
3. ‘Contribution to academic field’ was mapped 30 times in the data. The criteria is brought up in connection with development within a certain program aimed for the applicant to work on: “S/he will also have an important role in the development of the program”, or in connection with developmental work within a field or faculty advertising: “...applicant takes full part in the organization and development of courses and program in [...]” and “Applicants are expected to build a graduate program both at masters and PhD levels in [...] at the Faculty.” The criteria is also adverted to in connection with the University as an Institution: “The successful candidate is expected to run a strong research program and thereby strengthen graduate studies at the University in his/her area” and even on international scale: “The selected candidate will take part in developing research in [...]. The candidate is also expected to collaborate with scientists outside the faculty, outside the university and internationally.”

4. 'Degree' criteria is by far the most frequently used criteria; 105 times. The reason for the frequency is that it is commonly mentioned two times in and advertisements; at the beginning of an advert that addresses the specified position advertised. The degree is demanded in the special field advertised: "The applicant should have a doctorate degree in [...]" or an equivalent field: "Applicants should have a doctorate degree in [...] or equivalent" and then again in the standardized part at the bottom of each advert: "Applicants shall include with their applications certificates attesting to their education." In some cases the criteria of degree is linked to the code of national context. In the case of the law department this is frequently the case: "Applicants are expected to have completed final examination in law with Master's degree from an Icelandic University or a comparable degree from a foreign University". Other faculties also make similar requests as for example one of the faculties of engineering: "The applicants are expected to be able to obtain Icelandic state certification for Professional [...]", referring to the authorization of the professional titles.

5. 'Equality law' was added by the Icelandic team in order to count the number of times the equality right program is mentioned which was in total 40 times. The clause is standardized and appears at the end of an advertisement: "Appointments to the University of Iceland do take into account the Equal Rights Project of the University of Iceland." Once, the code was applied twice at the end of the ad and the upper, descriptive part of the advert. There equality was mentioned in connection with the teaching abilities of the applicants: "The associated professor is required to teach and conduct research within the field of sociology in [...] and equality."

6. 'Excellence', also added by the Icelandic team, was used to pin-point the discourse of excellence within the data that occurred 28 times. The discourse of excellence is covered in section (i) in the report.

7. 'Independence', referred to 11 times, refers to both students and (future) staff of the University. As an example of reference to students: "The University also places great demands on its students in critical thinking and independent working methods".

Applicants are required of "independence in working methods" "and to have proven their ability to pursue independent research".

8. 'Interest in particular field' could be detected two times in the data when stressing the applicant's interest in their own field.

9. 'Language skills'. The code was mapped five times in the data requesting the ability to teach in Icelandic. The demand is typically articulated as follows: "Lectures in undergraduate courses are generally given in Icelandic" and once the applicant is given a certain time limit to adjust to the country and language: "If the native language of the successful applicant is not Icelandic he or she is expected to have gained competence to use Icelandic in teaching within three years of taking up the position."

10. 'Management' is mentioned 58 times in the data. The number of occurrences of the criteria show that it is restated in a couple of adverts. The routine occurrence is within the standardized clause at the end of an advert saying: "Applicants are also expected to include references for their [...] administrative work, as appropriate." The attachment "appropriate" hints that the criteria is not stressed as significant. The criteria is stressed at a few times however and thus underlined as important for the post, for example when an applicant is expected to: "participat[e] in the management and growth of the program".

11. 'Methodological skills' are only referred to five times as a part of teaching-ability: "Competence to teach numerical analysis is desirable".

12. 'Motivation' was applied 16 times. The example where the code motivation was detected in the data was in hand with either the requirement of the applicant to participate in developments within the academia: "Applicants are expected to build a graduate program both at masters and PhD levels in [...]" or the code is intertwined with the intendment to achieve excellence: "Applicants must have either demonstrated or possess a clear potential and interest in achieving excellence in research and teaching."

13. 'Multidisciplinarity' was detected five times as optional i.e.: "Applicants with expertise in structural geology/tectonics, stratigraphy, petrology and/or mineralogy are particularly encouraged to apply."

14. 'National context' (added by the Icelandic team) was mapped 22 times. As revealed before it is typically detected in connection with language skills: "Lectures in undergraduate courses are generally given in Icelandic" and when advertising within the faculty of law: "Applicants are expected to have completed final examination in law with Master's degree from an Icelandic University or a comparable degree from a foreign University". National context is important and can be seen when the adverts address juridical aspects of the positions advertised. Lastly, the University sometimes calls for

official, national approval of academic skills: “Applicants must be able to meet the requirements of the Icelandic Ministry of Industry for engineering certification”

15. ‘Networking’ could only be detected two times in the data. Networking was not addressed as professional attainment of the applicant but a part of the job-description: “It is expected that the assistant professor will join efforts with scientist outside the faculty, the University and on international arena”.

16. ‘Outreach’ was mapped 13 times in the data. The code was detected as a term of reaching out to other academic institutions either on individual basis: “The candidate is also expected to collaborate with scientists outside the faculty, outside the university and internationally”, or on the basis of the University as an establishment: “The University collaborates on research [...] with other universities and faculties that are among the highest ranking in the world.” As the latter examples shows the discourse of outreach is intersected with the discourse of excellence. Outreach was most often connected to the University as a whole, frequently implying the excellence of the institution both locally: “The University is the driving force of advancement in the vocational- and national life in Iceland” and globally: “There are many opportunities in this field, both locally and globally. It is clear that energy use in harmony with nature and society is one of the big projects this century faces.”

17. ‘Possible promotion’, added by the Icelandic team since all posts advertised are tenure track positions, was found seventeen times in the data. The regulation of the University allows exception from the rule granting “The Rector of the University [...] to appoint the successful applicant at the associate professor level if the applicant is qualified.”

18. ‘Postdoc-experience’ only occurred twice: “some postdoctoral experience is preferred.”

19. ‘Publication’ occurred 64 times in the data. Occasionally, a “list of publication” is a part of the upper clause of an advert. The demand for publication is always a part of the standardized clause at the end of an advert: “Applicants shall include with their applications [...], a list of their publications [...]. Applicants must make clear which of their publications s/he regard as the most relevant to the advertised position [...]. Applicants must submit these three publications with their application, or indicate where they are accessible in electronic form. When more than one author has produced a publication, the applicant must account for his or her own contribution to the work.”

Publication is an important criteria since it proofs the ability and effectiveness of the applicant in the field of research. The publication platform counts as additional hallmark so to speak.

20. 'Research' is intertwined with code nineteen, 'publication'. Research is directly addressed 80 times in the data, more often than the sister-code 'publication', as research is more often referred to in both the upper specified clause and the bottom standardized clause of the advertisements. In the upper clause, the specified demand is centered upon the advertised position: "The Assistant Professor is expected to carry out research in the field of [...]" and sometimes the clause addresses both the applicant and his possible future students: "S/he will be [...], as well as doing research, supervising students in their research theses". The demand for research is articulated in a more general and open manner in the standardized clause: "Applicants shall include with their applications [...], and an outline of their research plans if they are offered the position". This clause is then followed by asking for publication as demonstrated above. Publication is a "proof" of the research experience and skill of the applicant giving the more experienced a head start for the post.

21. 'Social skills'. The criteria is mentioned 53 times in the data; almost all adverts. It is frequently stressed as a criteria of highest importance, typically as follows: "Strong communication and interpersonal skills are essential", and on numerous times it is linked with the request of cooperative skills: "In addition the appointee should be open to collaboration and easy to get on with".

22. 'Supervising students'. The criteria was mentioned 23 times in the specified clause addressing the post in particular. The supervising of students is a part of the teaching part of a position: "The successful candidate is expected to conduct research and teach in the area of [...], supervise graduate students, teach undergraduate and graduate courses, and participate in teaching of [...]."

23. 'Teaching' in general is mentioned directly 56 times. The demand occurs as referent to the specific position: "The successful candidate is expected to [...] teach" and/or s/he is asked to: "to include references for their teaching" being a part of their work experience.

24. 'Vision'. The criteria was mapped in total 17 times mostly indirect but also direct as the following reference shows: "In the application, the applicant's vision of [...] future at the University of Iceland should be stated".

25. ‘Working experience’ is a frequently mentioned criteria, in total 67 times. The criteria is applied either in a general manner: “The applicants should provide certificates attesting to their [...] work experience” and/or specifying the working experience required for the position: “experience in research and teaching in the field of [...]” or “Experience of teaching at university level is desirable”.

Which criterion is dominant in the job description?

According to the number of occurrences, the ‘degree’ code is the dominant criterion, followed by ‘research’ and ‘working experience’. Out of the 25 codes used for the analysis of the advertisements of academic posts the ‘degree’ criterion is the most inevitable. The double-occurrence in most of the ads can be seen as a matter-of-course; the criterion is mentioned once when specifying the field of the position and once the degree criteria is a standardized demand of the University as an institution and work place. The two criterion following, ‘research’ and ‘working experience’, stress the importance of the two main factors of the job of an assistant professor: research and teaching. Research is an important part of the job of an Assistant Professor both in developing her/his own academic skills and as a contribution to the academic institution employing her/him. The third most frequent criterion ‘working experience’ is often associated with ‘teaching’ which is a criterion addressed in all the adverts examined. The criterion ‘working experience’ is thus a required experience of ‘teaching’, or even mentioned in terms of academic teaching, or it is mentioned in connection with the applicants working experience in general. ‘Working experience’ is always a part of the standardized clause of an advert and as such an unquestioned part of the applicants CV, despite sometimes young age. When viewed in connection with yet another code, ‘national context’, the requirement of ‘working experience is evident since it has been custom in Iceland to take part in the labour market at young age and references are typically attained from that sphere.

Are there any references to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university?

The criterion ‘equality law’ added to the codes by the Icelandic team was created in order to count the number of times the advertisements include reference to the Equal Rights Program of the University of Iceland. The reference to the equal right program was, with one exception where teaching abilities in equality was asked for, applied in one sentence at the end of an advertisement: “Appointments to the University of Iceland do

take into account the Equal Rights Project of the University of Iceland.”. As accounted for at the beginning of the report the data consist of 56 job advertisements. The occurrences of the equality code counted in total 40 times thereof twice in the ad requesting equality-teaching. This leaves 16 ads without the reference to the Equal Rights Program of the University. The lack of occurrences were found equally in both schools STEM and SSH.

Comparative conclusion formal criteria STEM and SSH

The overall structure of the job advertisements in SSH and STEM, is standardized. An advert typically begins with a short description, then proceeds with numerating the criteria demanded for the position and ends with a detailed, standardized clause of requirements. All advertisements refer to the recruitment law of the university and most of them address the Equality Policy of UI. The adverts differ in two key aspects: accuracy and language. The advertisements from SSH are more general and only in Icelandic whereas the STEM adverts are more detailed in descriptions and both in Icelandic and English which is in line with the University’s policy.

4.3. Actual practices

SSH interviews and focus groups

Abstract criteria

According to most of the committee members, both in the evaluation and selection committees, the selection process is very formal and inflexible because of laws and regulations on a national and institutional level. The evaluation committee checks if candidates have a PhD degree, the number of research points they have acquired according to the University of Iceland evaluation system, as well as other criteria that are mentioned in the job description. According to a female evaluation committee member the work of the selection committee:

[...] is carved in stone. There are acts on public higher education institutions, on minimum qualifications of the applicants, and then, sometimes the job description has extra criteria. So the evaluation committee, and of course the selection committees, do not have much leeway. Because you are looking at defined criteria: Education, research, teaching and administration.

The same discourse was found among the selection committee members, as one female selection committee member points out:

“We have little flexibility. Everybody is well aware of that in the selection committee. We are a public university and we need to follow the laws and regulations”.

However, when discussing the criteria with the committee members it is clear that the criteria is more subjective than they express.

How candidates are selected depends first and foremost on the job description, as one male selection committee member describes it:

“The first thing you do is to look at the job description. What is asked for in the job description? How is the wording of the ad? You basically look at that”. Later in the interview he says: “It is important that the candidate fits in with the needs of the department”.

What is being referred to here as “the needs of the department” concerns most often the research field which can be the decisive factor, even though another candidate has more research and teaching experience. The job description is made by the department that is seeking an assistant professor and it can be “tailor-made” for a specific candidate. As one evaluation and selection committee member puts it

“there have been job descriptions that are tailor-made for some candidates and only one can apply”

and some selection committee members spoke freely on this when talking about the lack of teachers in a specific field:

“If we knew about a [subject] teacher we would advertise and get him”.

The most important criteria is research and research related activities, which according to most of the committee members is an objective criteria. According to a male evaluation and selection committee member:

“Publications and journals are number one, two and three”.

The focus is first and foremost on whether the candidate has been active in the last five years and if the candidate has published articles in international peer reviewed journals:

“Having like every second year an article in a fancy international journal”, or “real publications, not trifles”,

as one male selection committee member put it. When discussing the research criteria it becomes obvious that the criteria is subjective, as a one male committee member points out:

“Each [selection committee member] gives candidates points for research, and after that the scores are compared and even discussed and sometimes they evaluate differently”. He continues: “It can be difficult when one candidate finished his degree seven years ago and the other two years ago to evaluate who is going to be more productive, because what we are trying to evaluate in the selection committee is what we can expect in the future; will this candidate be productive in research?”

While it is considered a plus if a candidate has international connections, education from a non-Icelandic university and research funding experience, these factors are never considered to be the decisive criteria. Most committee members link these criteria to new emphases within the policies of the University of Iceland.

Teaching is, according to most committee members in the beginning of interviews, the third most important criteria (after the job description and research). If a candidate has teaching experience the teaching evaluations are used as a tool to evaluate that experience. If a candidate has received negative feedback from the teaching evaluations this is considered to be a minus. It turns out though that teaching experience is not considered an important factor, but is used when necessary. On teaching experience, one male selection committee member says:

“You cannot depend on that 100%, because some of the candidates have not tried that and others have tried more. So we need to ask ourselves, how important is it?”

This quote shows how committee members diminish teaching requirements when it suits them. As one male evaluation and selection committee member describes it:

“Can the candidate teach or not? We check that, you cannot compare candidates more than that”.

Even though the Rules for the University of Iceland (e.g no. 569/2009) state that the evaluation should be based on research, teaching and administration, the committee members consider administration experience not to be important. Administration experience is considered to be a *“plus, not a requirement”* in the words of a female selection committee member and a male committee member stresses that *“it does not weight heavily”*. One male committee member on why administration isn’t an important criteria:

“[...] You have to keep in mind that we are discussing recruitment for an assistant professor [and] that they do not have administration duties. Therefore administration experience cannot be a factor that people can use to select a candidate”.

“Communication skills” is considered to be a very important criteria, or being a “team player” as the committee members describe the qualities of a candidate that fits into the team. According to all committee members this is a new criteria within the job description. A male selection committee member described it as follows when asked what he meant by that:

“I would say, a candidate that can work with others, to be a team player, that can think about the whole team and not be a stick in the mud, damaging. It is more important than the [selection] process acknowledges”.

Another male selection committee member said

“it is important to verify that the candidate has etiquette”.

All committee members think it is difficult or even impossible to evaluate communication skills, but they consider it important as one selection committee member describes:

“When a candidate has a reputation for having communication difficulties... you know, this is a small country. Then we have to ask for recommendations and of course we follow equality legislations and ask everybody for a recommendation from an employer”.

Interviews and lectures are also used to evaluate this criteria. One evaluation and selection committee member does not agree on having “communication skills” as a criteria in the job descriptions, he points out that

“sometimes it is obvious that [the department] is just making criteria in the job description so they can just do what they want or to justify their selection”.

Actual selection process

All positions for an assistant professor are advertised. When the committee members describe the selection process, after a position has been advertised, it is always according to the Rules for the University of Iceland No. 569/2009. When it comes to the work of

the selection committee it depends on the number of qualified candidates as one committee member describes it:

Sometimes when there is only one qualified candidate then this is quite simple, but most often there are more candidates and sometimes it is quite obvious who is most qualified, the one with most research activities, that fits the research field as described in the job advertisement and in those cases we just recommend that candidate [...] In most cases there are interviews, often a short list when there are candidates that stand out, fit the job description or have more publications. After that the committee comes to a decision and gives a recommendation.

Discussing generally the decision making process, one committee member describes it as:

“people can value things differently and always when I have been a part of a selection committee there are discussions, but in the end all the members of the selection committee agree [on the selected candidate]”.

On the decisive criteria generally all the committee members point out that it is a “comprehensive evaluation”, then they mention the following criteria: the research field mentioned in the job description, research activities, teaching and administration experience. When discussing diversity the committee members most often talked about the need for a diversity of research fields, not diversity in terms of gender.

Most committee members were unwilling to talk about their latest selection procedure. When asked it is obvious that they feel very uncomfortable and they state that they cannot talk about specific cases. Only one male committee member, from an all-male department with the exception of one female professor, talked about his latest appointment. In that case a man and a woman made it to the short list, he described how difficult the selection process was because both candidates had “outstanding” research activities, but the committee selected the male candidate because of his research field.

Most committee members did not have opinions on the performance of the selected candidates, who are now their colleagues. One committee member mentioned a candidate that performed beyond expectations when he created a new course “that turned out to be very fun and totally different from everything we have done [in the department]”. When asked about a candidate that underperforms, those committee

members who had an opinion on that mentioned candidates that were doing well in teaching but “do not much more than that”.

Gender

Many committee members do not consider gender discrimination to be a problem anymore. In the discussion of gender there is a tendency to talk about female dominated departments, such as nursing and social work. Also the committee members rather want to focus on other discriminatory factors, such as age, ethnicity and nationality, which is interesting because all assistant professor positions in SSH are only advertised in Icelandic. When asked about why that is one male committee member answered:

“To be realistic. We just don’t expect that international applicants will apply, at least not the ones we would be interested in”.

His opinion is that it would be difficult to have non-Icelandic teachers because the administration at the university is all in Icelandic and he thinks that students want to speak Icelandic with their teachers. Then again he thinks the desirable candidates will not apply because of the low salary that is offered at the University of Iceland.

When asked if gender matters in the selection process, few male and female committee members think that it matters and there is an *“awareness to increase diversity, both scientifically [...] and age and gender”*. But, as one committee member explains it:

“we can never look at that [gender] until everything else is equal. That’s how the law [Act on Equal Status and Equal Rights of Women and Men 10/2008] is”.

Another male selection committee member describes it like this:

There are these formal factors that matter. It is research activities, and specialty and the needs of the department, and then we have to ask ourselves does gender matter?

The committee members that consider gender to be important are mostly women that are working in or have been part of a selection process in all-female departments. Only one male committee member felt there should be more definite actions taken towards gender representation of the academic staff, he stresses the need to apply gender quotas in the selection process because of the gendered culture within his department.

The male committee members from a male dominated department talk about how the department has actively been seeking qualified women for the last 20 years for their academic positions. One committee member is certain that 9 out of 10 women that have

applied for a position in the department were appointed, but the quantitative data on appointments shows that this statement is incorrect. The view of these committee members is that there has been a “fundamental change” of the academic staff and they have been “successful” with gender equality. One of the members even predicts that in 20 years women will form the majority of academic staff within the University.

In accordance with article 26 of the Act on Equal Status and Equal Rights of Women and Men no. 10/2008, equality and equal respect for both genders should be ensured in all university job advertisements. In the University of Iceland’s Equal Rights Policy it is stated that:

If two or more applicants for a position are equally qualified, an applicant shall be chosen of the gender that is in minority in that area of work; according to article 26 of the Gender Equality Act, no. 10/2008.

When asked about the gender equality policy most committee members were aware that it existed but most of them did not think that it was relevant to the selection process. While the committee members were aware of these articles, none of them had experienced “*the need to apply them in the selection process*”. Some committee members wanted clearer instructions on how to apply them, and one male committee member doubted that the gender equality actions actually work because “*in the end it seems that it doesn’t weight up against the other criteria*”. The committee members say that they make a decision that reflects the notion of “academic meritocracy”. The male committee member explains:

“because it defines your own career [...] it is unfair if I publish and publish and then in the end something else [gender] matters, that is just unfair”.

Most committee members did not express their opinion on the equality policy, one committee member thinks it is too detailed, “it should focus on A and B and C”, and he thinks there are articles in it that are “completely ridiculous” such as

“efforts should be made to have equal representation of male and female authors of teaching material”.

His view is that it doesn’t matter if the author is a man or a woman, if the book is good it is good.

SSH appointment reports

In the time period between the 1st of January 2010 and the 1st of January 2013 there were 24 assistant professor positions publically advertised; five in 2010, three in 2011, eight in 2012 and seven in 2013. In one case the advertised position was a 50% position, the others were all temporary full-time positions meaning that after a five years period the contract will either be terminated or replaced by a long-term contract. Of the 89 individuals that sent in an application for at least one of these positions were 55 men and 34 women (a ratio of 1.62 man per woman).

All advertised positions were filled except for in one case. Of the 89 applicants, 6 candidates (6.7%) withdrew their application after the evaluation committee had written their report, 24 were hired (27%) and 59 were rejected (66.3%). Information with regard to shortlists is unavailable, but the group of candidates that were hired (n=24) consisted of 14 men and 10 women. The hiring ratio according to sex is therefore 1.4, indicating that for each woman that was hired, 1.4 men were hired.

When looking at the data for male and female applicants separately it appears that of the 55 men that applied, 4 withdrew their application (7.3%). Of the remaining 51 male candidates 14 were hired (27.5%) and 36 (70.6%) were rejected. Of the 34 women that originally applied, 2 withdrew their application (5.9%). Of the 32 remaining women, 10 were hired (31.3%) and 22 were not (68.8%). A chi-square analysis ($X^2:(1, n=89) = 0.167, p = n.s$) reveals that the binary variables *sex* and *hired* are independent of each other.

Information about the nationality of each applicant is unknown to us, but at least 20 of the appointed candidates have an Icelandic name (ending in “son” or “dóttir”), while the names of the other 4 successful candidates can be rated as possibly Icelandic but definitely “Nordic”. The provided data does not indicate when the successful candidate obtained his/her PhD degree, or whether the appointed individual was an internal or external candidate.

With regard to the evaluation committee. In three cases there was no selection committee established because there was only one applicant. In the other 21 cases the chair of the committee was always a man, and the other standing member was always a woman. The representative appointed by the department was in 15 cases a man, and in 6 cases a woman. These 6 female representatives of the department were holding in 5 cases a full professor position, and in 1 case an associate professor position.

With regard to the selection committee. The chair of the committee was in 17 cases a man (70.8%) and in 7 cases a woman (29.2%). The standing member appointed by the department was in 11 cases a man (45,8%) and in 13 cases a woman (54.2%). The two specialists appointed by the department were in all cases one man and one woman. The rector's representative was a man in all 24 cases (100%).

Graph 1: The number of women and men hired between 2010 and 2013 in assistant professor positions in SSH.

Graph 1 reveals that between 2010 and 2013 men were more frequently hired into SSH assistant professor positions than women, except for in 2011 when more women (2) were hired than men (1). In 2013 women were hired as often as men. The men/women hiring ratio's are therefore 2 - 0,5 - 2,5 - 0 for respectively 2010, 2011, 2012 and 2013.

STEM interviews and focus groups

Abstract criteria

According to the committee members the criteria stated in the rules for the University of Iceland No. 569/2009 are the only criteria they can use when evaluating and selecting candidates for an assistant professor position. According to the rules the evaluation

should be based on research, teaching and administration. A male evaluation committee member, participating in the focus group, thinks that the requirements for an assistant professor are “dangerously low”, and other participants agree on that. One female committee member describes this evaluation:

“we look into these three criteria and who scored the most in all those criteria, and maybe not necessarily [a candidate] that scored the most in all those three criteria but you know [a candidate] is the best “whole-package””.

Research is considered to be the most important criteria. The committee members focus on the research field, number of published articles and the journals. There is a special attention paid to articles published in international peer-reviewed journals and most preferably that are within the ISI-database, but this can differ between departments. Some departments put a post-doc fellowship as criteria in the job description for an assistant professor position. As one male committee member describes it

“it is almost impossible to get an assistant professor position without having that experience”.

Some committee members think that one or two post-doc fellowships from a non-Icelandic university are necessary, to show that “*you can stand on your own*”. One female committee member notes that a post-doc:

“is only important if you have published while you are doing your post-doc fellowship”.

The research field has to coincide with the department, and committee members note that they have to consider:

“if there is someone [of the academic staff] that can work with the candidate and if the research field is something that is missing from the department”.

One evaluation committee member notes that there is a thin line between finding someone that fits the department and “the old-boys network”.

In some occurrences the advertised positions are “open”, and a candidate with qualification for an associate professor or full professor position can get a fast-track promotion to the “appropriate” position. Some committee members consider the excellent candidate someone who has a lot of experience, such as being a professor at another university, with many publications and a very good network. Other committee

members consider that problematic, because it is very difficult to compare someone with “great experience” to someone that is newly graduated.

There is an advantage to appoint someone young because then you can expect a longer career but if you appoint someone with a lot of experience that has acquired a lot of research funding you can of course expect that he will continue doing so, but then again, a candidate that is maybe 60 years old, has fewer years left of his working life.

Another female committee member put it like this:

“of course you have to look at the candidates’ background [...] but in reality you are not interested in what he has done in the past unless it is evidence that the candidate will be a good faculty member for the department”. The opinion of another female committee member is that a newly graduate that has published many articles “looks as good as someone who has been publishing a lot for a long time”.

The committee members take international connections into account and feel that it is important that the candidate has research experience from abroad, not only as a student but as being part of an international research team and having co-written articles with international colleagues:

“If a candidate has been part of a European research it sounds very well and it doesn’t only mean that the candidate is qualified but it also means that she/he has a good network and has been active in research”.

Experience in the field of acquiring research funding is by most committee members considered a plus and something that cannot be expected from a newly graduated candidate:

“If the publications are ok, then this would not change our minds”.

In one department it is considered very important that a candidate brings research funding

“because you cannot continue working on your research unless you have funding, the university is not going to support you with that [funding]”.

Some committee members are of the opinion that a candidate with a PhD from the University of Iceland is not desirable, but for others that degree is “good enough”. If a candidate comes from a university that the committee members do not know, they have reservations about it “because it takes more effort to check how good it is”. A degree

from a well-known non-Icelandic university is seen as important for some committee members, or as one female committee member explains it:

“It helps, if we talk about engineering, if candidates went to ETH Zurich or TUM Munchen, or something like that. Then we know. No idiots go there!”.

Teaching is an important criteria if the department is seeking a candidate to teach certain courses or to supervise PhD candidates in their position as assistant professors. Experience with supervising graduate students, including PhD students, is for most committee members an important criterion. Teaching is often regarded as something you can “evolve” while working at the University. However, it can never be the main criterion as one female committee member explains:

“Even though there is an emphasis on teaching [...] it still weights a lot that the candidate has potential for publications”.

Administration experience is not considered an important criterion. Some committee members regard it as something positive but unimportant. A male committee member says he does not remember

“whether that has ever been something that was [considered] important”.

“Communication skills” are important criteria, and most committee members think that a department is successful if the academic staff can cooperate:

“If there is a group of divas that don’t see anything else but themselves it would be a terrible department”.

It is not considered positive if a candidate works alone and publishes alone,

“especially if you are going to be a professor that supervises PhD students and post-docs, because you are not going to write the articles alone. Everybody knows that you can’t to do this alone”.

All committee members think it is difficult to evaluate communication skills, but candidates are asked for recommendation letters and are invited to interviews. One committee member describes how interviews can indicate the communication skills of a candidate:

“if a candidate is always looking the other way or has difficulties with communicating”.

One evaluation committee member does not agree on evaluating communication skills because:

“we cover the whole range [of personalities], from very shy to arrogant, and it is unknown what is going to benefit us the most [...] we only have to look around us to see this same variety”.

Actual selection process

All positions for assistant professors are advertised, and according to our committee members all of them are advertised internationally. As stated above the participation of women and men in the selection committees have to be approximately equal. A female candidate criticizes this rule because a committee member should be gender-neutral: “

A person should be selected for the evaluation committee on a professional basis”.

When the committee members describe the selection process, after a position has been advertised, it is always according to the Rules for the University of Iceland (no. 569/2009). Two evaluation committee members criticise the purpose of the evaluation committee, in their opinion they are

“just counting the candidates research points [...] we are not evaluating whether the candidate is qualified for the position”.

According to some selection committee members the selection process depends on the committee they are working with at each time, and especially the chair of the committee because he “sets an example” on how the process should be. Most often that process is smooth. The course of the appointment process most often starts with the chair of the committee sending a meeting invitation and documents on the candidates, which include statistical information such as the number of publications and number of citations. Some departments have one committee member from a non-Icelandic university to minimize the likelihood of connections with candidates. Then at the first meeting they make a short list, in that phase they discuss the candidates until they reach a consensus. A female committee member describes her last committee appointment process as a

“successful process because the committee agreed upon the selection method beforehand”.

After that meeting there are interviews that are prepared with a representative from human resources. Usually they make a standard questionnaire before the interviews to avoid discrimination. Since there are many candidates that are not living in Iceland many committees conduct all their interviews via Skype “*so everybody has the same opportunities*”. In the interview candidates give a lecture and after that there is the

interview. Based on the performance in the interviews the top candidates are invited for a visit to give a public lecture. Many committee members talk about inviting prospective appointees, from Iceland or abroad, for a visit before inviting them to take the position of an assistant professor, as one male committee member explains:

“In that way we always have an opportunity to get to know a candidate better, but it is also seen as an opportunity for the candidate to see our working conditions”.

One female committee member describes how often committee members have different opinions on candidates

“but then it is just discussed and somehow we just get to a common conclusion”.

Most committee members were not interested in talking about their latest appointments. One male committee member described it shortly, in the selection process he referred to 37 candidates applied and 35 were considered qualified. The two unqualified candidates had not finished their PhDs. Four candidates were selected for the shortlist. A female candidate was appointed for the position. One female committee member mentioned an appointment where there were only women on the short list. None of the committee members felt comfortable expressing their opinion on whether a candidate had performed beyond expectations or underperformed. One female committee member said she had not been following the selected candidates after their appointment. Many committee members talked about the problem of the selected candidates not accepting the position of assistant professor. They think it is because the salary at the University of Iceland is very low compared to universities in other countries. One female selection committee member touches up on this, in her opinion it is better to advertise again, later, than appointing someone with minimal requirements.

“I think it doesn’t do anything for the department to have a person that just passes the requirements, not if we are going to have ambition for the profession”.

Gender

Gender is not considered something that matters, when asked about it directly committee members usually give a straight and short answer: “no”. One female committee member talked about the committee discussing gender in the selection process when the committee was trying to decide what candidates to invite for an interview. Gender is not on top of their mind, as this quote from a male committee member shows:

“No, but if I remember correctly, if there are two equally qualified individuals then we should select the sort with the fewer people”.

This committee member is clearly referring to article 26 of the Act on Equal Status and Equal Rights of Women and Men (no. 10/2008). However, none of the committee members had applied this article in the selection process. A female committee member stressed that candidates can never be equally qualified and she would never be able to accept selecting a woman “only because she is a woman”.

When asked whether there is a gender that negatively affects female candidates the answer was most often just a plain “no”. Two female committee members even got annoyed when they were asked this question. Another female committee member felt that qualified women and men have the same opportunities to get appointed, and she worried about discrimination against men. There is a contradiction in this interview, because later on she points out how parental leave, which creates a gap in a woman’s career, makes it difficult for women to start a career in academia

“because [the evaluation committee] doesn’t take that into account when reviewing their CV”.

When other committee members were asked if they took into consideration that women are more likely to take a longer parental leave and are therefore less likely to be productive during that time, the committee members agreed that they had never taken that into account. One female committee member stated:

“it doesn’t mean they will forget all science during [the parental leave]. It isn’t like that”.

One male committee member noted that

“if they are Icelandic applicants they have a right to the same parental leave”

and in that way he dismissed the gendered work within the home and that even though men and women have the equal right to a paternity leave in Iceland women still take a longer leave.

Asked about gender equality policies the committee members were aware of the Act on Equal Status and Equal Rights of Women and Men no. 10/2008, and that if two or more applicants are equally qualified, the gender composition within that field should be looked at, and the applicant representing the gender minority in that area of work

should be chosen. Most committee members were unaware of the University of Iceland's equality policy, and those who did had not read the policy.

STEM appointment reports

Between the 1st of January 2010 and the 1st of January 2013 there were 26 assistant professor positions publicly advertised within the STEM departments; three in 2010, nine in 2011, seven in 2012 and seven in 2013. All advertised positions were temporary full-time positions with the prospect of a long-term contract after 5 years. The university received 328 applications; 286 written by men (87,2%) and 42 by women (12,8%), which indicates a ratio of 6.8 male applicants per female applicant.

The advertised positions were almost always filled; in four cases more than one candidate was hired into the position and in two cases no one was hired despite respectively 16 and 32 applications for these particular positions. Of the 328 initial applicants, 4 male candidates (1.2%) withdrew their application during the selection process. In the end 26 candidates were hired (8%) and 298 were rejected (92%). Shortlists have been unavailable but of those that were hired (n=26) there were 19 men (73%) and 7 women (27%). The hiring ratio according to sex is therefore 2.7 indicating that for each successful female applicant there were 2.7 successful male applicants.

When looking at the data for male and female applicants separately it appears that of the 286 men that applied, 4 withdrew their application (1.4%). Of the remaining 282 male candidates 19 were hired (6.7%) and 263 (93.3%) were rejected. Of the 42 women that applied, 7 were hired (16.7%) and 35 were not (83.3%). A chi-square analysis ($X^2:(1, n=328) = 5.041, p = 0.025$) reveals that the binary variables *sex* and *hired* are dependent of each other. A Phi value of 0.124 indicates a moderate association between the variables.

Information on the nationality of each applicant is unavailable for the STEM departments but of the successful candidates 19 have an Icelandic name, 3 a possibly Icelandic/Nordic name, and 4 successful candidates have a foreign name. Furthermore, it is remarkable that the list of applicants for the two positions in which no one was hired, solely contained foreign names (respectively 16 and 32). There is no information available on when the applicants received their PhD degree, nor whether the appointed individual was an internal or external candidate.

With regard to the evaluation committee. In three cases there was no selection committee established because there was only one applicant. The chair of the selection committee was in 22 cases a man (84.6%), and in four cases a woman (15.4%). The opposite was true for the other standing member, in 4 cases this was a man (15.4%) and in 22 cases a woman (84.6%). The representative of the department was in 23 cases a man (88.5%) and in 3 cases a woman (11.5%). These female representatives of the department either occupy a full professor or associate professor position.

With regard to the selection committee The chair of the committee was in 25 cases a man (96%) and once a woman (4%). The standing member appointed by the department representative was in 17 cases a man (65%) and in 9 cases a woman (35%). The two specialists appointed by the department were in total 41 men (80%) and 10 women (20%). The rector's representative was only once a man (4%) and 25 times a woman (96%).

Graph 2: The number of women and men hired between 2010 and 2013 in assistant professor positions in STEM

Graph 2 reveals that between 2010 and 2013 men were more frequently hired into STEM assistant professor positions than women, except for in 2012 when more women (3) were hired than men (2). The men/women hiring ratio's in STEM are therefore 3 - 4 - 0,67 and 6, for the years 2010, 2011, 2012 and 2013 respectively.

Comparative conclusion STEM and SSH Actual practices

When comparing the actual practices of SSH and STEM, there is much more emphasis on excellence in STEM. This is notable in their emphasis on which university the candidate graduated from, on post-doc fellowship/s, on the number of published articles and number of publications in journals in the ISI-database. The committee members in STEM think that the department should not appoint candidates if they aren't excellent enough, while in SSH this does not seem to be the case. In SSH a post-doc fellowship isn't even mentioned. Fitting into the team, or being a "team member", comes up both in SSH and STEM. In STEM the focus is that academics need to work together doing research and therefore it is important that the candidate fits into the team. In SSH the academics seem to work more alone because a candidate that brings something new, they talk about wanting "diversity" of research fields within the department, therefore the emphasis is more that the candidate has to fit in the group socially because it seems that the academics won't work that much together on research projects.

4.4. Conclusions

There are clear differences observed between the formal and actual practises within SSH and STEM. Informal criteria, such as "communication skills", are now in most cases in the job description. One can say that the informal criteria are therefore in disguise as formal criteria. The in/formal criteria "communication skills" cannot be found as criteria in regulations but is of high importance in the actual practices within STEM and SSH. The formal criteria of administration experience seem not to weight at all in the actual practices, it is considered a plus if a candidate has such experience but it is not a minus if a candidate does not have it. The formal criteria of teaching experience does not seem to be of much importance in the actual practices. In STEM it is viewed as something you can learn on the go and in SSH you have to show you can teach but the number of courses, or the amount of experience does not seem to matter.

Despite both Schools belonging to the University of Iceland, there were also clear differences observed between the schools of SSH and STEM with regard to appointment practises. When comparing the actual practices of SSH and STEM, there is much more emphasis on excellence in STEM. This is notable in their emphasis on which university the candidate graduated from, on post-doc fellowship/s, on the number of published articles and number of publications in journals in the ISI-database. The committee members in STEM think that the department should not appoint candidates if they aren't excellent enough, while in SSH this does not seem to be the case. In SSH a post-doc fellowship isn't even mentioned. Fitting into the team, or being a "team member", comes up both in SSH and STEM. In STEM the focus is that academics need to work together doing research and therefore it is important that the candidate fits into the team. In SSH the academics seem to work more alone because a candidate that brings something new, they talk about wanting "diversity" of research fields within the department, therefore the emphasis is more that the candidate has to fit in the group socially because it seems that the academics won't work that much together on research projects.

When it comes to gender, there is a clear difference between STEM and SSH. In STEM they seem to have no interest in gender or the gender equality policy of the University of Iceland. In STEM they state that gender is not an important criteria. In SSH they speak more about gender, and all committee members knew of and most had read the equal rights policy of the University of Iceland. When discussing gender the committee members usually start talking about equality for men or other marginalized groups. Also, the committee members had the urge to explain or even defend themselves, or the department, when it comes to gender equality.

5. Switzerland

5.1. Introduction

Academic institutions and career structures in Switzerland

Switzerland is a small, federal country, characterized by very decentralized political processes, and this is reflected in the organization of the higher education and research sector.⁸ Primary responsibility for education lies with the cantons (states), although the Confederation and the cantons are obliged, within the scope of their responsibilities, to jointly ensure the high quality and permeability of the Swiss Education Area. Based on the new Article on higher education institutions (Art. 63a), under the Federal Act on Funding and Coordination of the Higher Education Sector (HFKG) the entire higher education sector (universities, universities of applied sciences and universities of teacher training) will soon be jointly managed by the Confederation and the cantons on the basis of standard principles. An inter-cantonal agreement between the cantons is required in order to create the new steering bodies; for the cantons this agreement forms the basis of cooperation with the Confederation. The Inter-cantonal Agreement on Higher Education (Higher Education Agreement) is currently undergoing the cantonal accession process is due to come into force in early 2015.

There are ten cantonal universities and two Federal Institutes of Technology. The universities in Basel, Bern, Lucerne, St. Gallen and Zurich and the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich (ETHZ) are in the German-speaking part of Switzerland, while the universities of Geneva, Lausanne and Neuchâtel and the *École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne* (EPFL) are in the French-speaking part of Switzerland. The University of Fribourg is in the bilingual canton of Fribourg (French and German), and the *Università della Svizzera italiana* in the Italian-speaking canton of Ticino. In addition, the Graduate Institute of International and Development Studies (Institut universitaire des hautes études internationales et du développement [IHEID]) in Geneva, the Swiss Graduate School of Public Administration (*Institut de hautes études en administration publique* [IDHEAP]) in Lausanne, the *Institut universitaire Kurt Bösch* (IUKB) in Sion and the Distance Learning University Switzerland are all considered to be university-level institutions.

In addition to these university-level institutions, there are seven universities of applied sciences recognised by the Confederation. These are distributed over seven Swiss

⁸ https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/fpfis/mwikis/eurydice/index.php/Switzerland:Higher_Education

regions and comprise around 60 affiliated schools and departments. The universities of applied sciences prepare students directly for entry into professional life, after studies at Bachelor or Master level. Unlike conventional universities, the universities of applied sciences cannot award doctorates. However, they do employ academic and research staff, some of who have completed a PhD at one of the Swiss universities.

Given the practical nature of their courses and their research in this specific vocational area, the universities of teacher education are classed as universities of applied sciences. Unlike the universities of applied sciences the cantons are responsible for their regulation, as they train students for the teaching profession which is regulated by the cantons. The cantons are also responsible for the organisation and funding of universities of teacher education, for which they are the maintaining bodies. The vocational and professional training and professional development of teaching staff and of experts in the field of special education is academic in nature and is mainly carried out at universities of teacher education.

Throughout the GARCIA project, we will focus on academic careers within the traditional universities. It should however be remembered that the universities of applied sciences provide a relatively large number of academic employment opportunities, both for doctoral students and for post-docs, and may represent an alternative route into an academic career in the Swiss context.

The SHS and STEM Faculties selected for study

The University of Lausanne (UNIL) is a higher education teaching and research institution where approximately 13,350 students and 2,800 researchers work and study. Under the leadership of an elected Rector and a team of vice-Rectors, the UNIL is organised around seven Faculties⁹, of varying sizes, which have a relatively high level of organisational autonomy, within the limits set by the University level rules and regulations.

The Faculties we have selected for this study are organized in slightly different ways.

Since 2003, the **STEM Faculty of Biology and Medicine (FBM)** has been divided into two sections that collaborate in teaching and research: the Section of Basic sciences (SF) and the Section of Clinical sciences (SC). The first one is fully integrated into the University organizational structure, whilst the second one operates in collaboration with the Vaud canton University teaching hospital (CHUV - *Centre Hospitalier Universitaire*

⁹ <http://www.unil.ch/central/en/home/menuinst/organisation/les-facultes.html>

Vaudois). Staff recruitment procedures there are partly dependent on the needs and resources of the hospital. Therefore there is an independent Human Resource (HR) Department, and some of the rules and regulations differ from those of the Basic Science Section and of the other Unil Faculties. The Basic Science Section is divided into 10 departments, including: Ecology and Evolution; Fundamental Microbiology; Plant Molecular Biology; Physiology; Fundamental Neurosciences; Pharmacology and Toxicology; Biochemistry; Genomics; Medical Genetics; Oncology. In our case study, we focused (as far as possible) only on the Basic Science departments, although our interviewees sometimes found it difficult to maintain this distinction and also talked about the experiences of early-stage post docs in the Clinical Sciences Section of the Faculty.

The **Faculty of Social and Political Sciences (SSP)** underwent a structural reorganisation in the mid-2000s, and is now based on four Institutes (the equivalent of the Departments in the STEM Faculty), covering the domains of Social Sciences; Political Science and International Studies; Psychology and Sports Studies. Each of these Institutes is in turn composed of a number of research centres or units. The Faculty is smaller than the FBM (see Table A2, in the Annex), but student numbers have been increasing rapidly in recent years, particularly in Psychology and Sports Studies.

In the Vaud canton, academic positions are no longer “permanent” in the absolute sense of the term. Professors and some categories of Senior Lecturers (MER) are offered contracts for a 6-year duration, which are renewable for an unlimited number of times, subject to a formal evaluation process. Cases of Full professors not having their contracts renewed are practically unheard of. Overall, members of the academic community are divided into different categories that do not necessarily reflect the stability / precariousness of their employment contract: professorial, intermediate and administrative and technical staff. The intermediate staff category is composed of a “lower” and an “upper” level. The lower level includes funded PhD students (*assistant-e-s diplômé-e-s*) and the lowest position open to post-docs (*premiers/ière assistant-e-s*: Post-doc Assistants). These positions are fixed-term, for a maximum of 5 years, and cover research and teaching activities. The upper level of the intermediate category is composed of temporary and junior (*Maître assistant-e-s - MA*) and permanent and more senior (*Maître d’enseignement et de recherche - MER*) lectureships, which are also subdivided into MER1 and MER2 categories. The meaning of this distinction varies somewhat between the Faculties, but the MER2 positions are usually associated with

relatively heavy teaching duties, or even with teaching-only duties, whereas MER1 incumbents are expected to combine teaching and research activities, in similar proportions to the professors.¹⁰ Finally, the professorial category includes temporary positions – Assistant professors – with or without tenure track (PTC¹¹), and permanent “tenured” positions – Associate and Ordinary (full) professors.

In both Faculties, these categories of academic staff work alongside a large number of junior and senior researchers who are hired through externally funded research projects (like GARCIA, for example), or to cover temporary teaching needs. Thus, the overall structure of academic positions is similar in SHS & STEM domains. As shown below, the difference in size of the Faculties is mainly due to the larger number of (funded) PhD student positions in FBM, as compared to SSP. Likewise, both Faculties have approximately the same number of lecturers as they have professors. This “middle heavy” career structure makes access to professorships particularly slow and competitive. Although some of the Senior Lecturer positions mentioned here are, in fact, permanent positions, there is no automatic, promotion pathway between the different levels of the Swiss academic hierarchy. These middle-level permanent positions do not enable access to a professorship on the basis of length of service, despite the fact that their incumbents often pursue the full range of academic activities, including PhD supervision and autonomous research and teaching activities. A Senior Lecturer who aspires to become a professor will usually have to wait for a professorship to be advertised and to enter into competition with applicants from outside the institution. The cantonal LUL (Lausanne University Law) defines any promotion (e.g. from Senior Lecturer to Professor) as an “exceptional” possibility, for which individuals have to be nominated by the Dean and approved by the Rector. Furthermore, public employees of the Vaud canton are only entitled to **one** promotion in the course of their career.

As also shown in Table 1, there are very few “tenure track” professorships (Assistant professors PTC) in either Faculty. The other junior professorships are usually dependent on external Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) funding (FNS 2008, art. 3b), where the beneficiaries are integrated into university-based research and teaching activities, following a national selection process (cf. the FNS professorships in Belgium).

¹⁰ A full-time position = approx. 6 hours teaching a week (excluding Master and PhD supervision) in the SSP Faculty, usually less in the FBM Faculty.

¹¹ Professor·e assistant·e en pré-titularisation conditionnelle.

These are always fixed-term, non-tenure track positions (3-6 years), to which post-docs can apply at different stages of their career.

Table 1. Number of full-time equivalent positions, by academic grade, SSP and FBM, 2012

Academic positions	Faculty of Social & Political Science		Faculty of Biology & Medicine	
	Total	Of whom, women	Total	Of whom, women
Full & Associate professors	41.1	14.6	52.8	4.9
Assistant professors	6.4	2.0	7.6	2.4
Post-doc Senior Lecturers + Researchers	50.7	19.6	52.1	12.8
PhD students (funding for 5 years, including teaching duties)	122.0	69.0	203.5	100.5

Source: *Annuaire statistique de l'Unil*, 2012-2013 (see the Annex for details).

The FNS offers so-called “Early” and “Advanced” mobility grants (to a foreign academic institution): the former can be awarded to PhD students in year 4 or 5 of their Doctorate, or to post-docs; the later are reserved for post-docs, for a duration of 1-3 years, with the possibility some funding for a “return” period to a Swiss university (usually not where the PhD thesis was defended). Once this period of international mobility has been completed, post-docs can apply for funding for more senior post-doc positions, which include funding for salaries and independent research costs: so-called “Ambizione” grants are awarded (on a competitive basis) for a maximum duration of 3 years to post-docs in the 5 years that follow their PhD defence; “SNSF Fellowships” can be obtained, for a duration of 4 to 6 years, starting between 2 and 9 years after the PhD. Both require candidates to provide invitation letters from a Swiss academic institution, confirming their support for their research project and their willingness to *consider them* for any future professorial position in their institution. The Directive 1.32 relating to the employment of Assistant Professors with SNSF grants (Direction UNIL, 2008) states clearly that these post-docs are **not** considered to be on a tenure track during the time spent in the host institution.

In fact, in the Swiss context another tenure track operates between fixed-term and permanent Lectureship positions. Once a post-doctoral period of 1-3 years (usually abroad) has been completed, it is possible to apply for fixed-term (4-6 years) junior academic positions (Post-doc Assistant or Maître assistant - MA). Lausanne University

offers some of these post-docs (the MA, but not the Post-doc Assistants) the opportunity to be “stabilized” (i.e. tenured), following a formal evaluation of their performance. They can therefore aspire to a permanent *Maître d’enseignement et de recherche* (MER1 or, more rarely MER2) position, which is equivalent to a Senior lectureship / Readership in other national contexts. In practice, some Faculties do not really make much use of the “stabilization” procedure and, following their 5 years on a fixed-term position, the MA post-docs have to apply for an Assistant or Associate professorship, or for a permanent (MER) Senior Lectureship. In the Basic Science section of the Biology & Medicine Faculty, for example, only those MA whose positions have been explicitly designated (and budgeted) as “transformable” are eligible to follow the internal stabilization procedure to an MER position. In the SSP Faculty, on the other hand, all MAs can request the transformation of their post into an MER position, after a three-year period of employment. They are then subjected to the quite rigorous evaluation procedure that we will describe in more detail below.

In both Faculties, access to Full / Associate Professorships rarely happens before candidates reach their late-30s to mid-40s, and usually through international competitive recruitment procedures. Indeed, when considering academic recruitment, it is important to note that the Swiss academic labour market is one of the most internationalised in the world. The overall share of foreign staff in doctoral degree-granting institutions (i.e. excluding Universities of applied sciences) increased from 30.7% in 1999 to 40% in 2011 (OFS 2011). In universities, foreigners (i.e. non-Swiss citizens) make up more than 50% of all professorships, and in some technical fields, their share of newly recruited professors is over 80% (OFS 2011).

Affirmative action/gender equality policies in the Swiss academic context

Gender equality issues and, more precisely, the explicit aim of recruiting / promoting more women to senior academic positions, occupy a visible place within the Unil recruitment procedures, both in the job advertisements and during the meetings of the recruitment boards.

Since 2000, the Conference of Rectors of Swiss universities (CRUS) has created and supported a Federal Equal Opportunity in Universities Programme, which has been formalised in three successive phases (2000-2003; 2004-2007 and 2008-2011 – extended to 2013), each funded at a level of approximately 16 million Swiss Francs.¹² The

¹² 1 CHF = 0.83 Euro.

precise content of each of these programmes has evolved over time, but promoting women's access to senior academic positions has always been the primary objective. To this effect, professorial job announcement (tenure track or not) must include the following footnote: "Concerned with promoting women's access to academic careers, the University encourages women to apply" (Direction UNIL 2005, art. 1.3.1, p. 8). As indicated in the 2011 information brochure (see the Annex), the Programme, which concerned all of the Swiss Universities (including the Engineering Schools) covered various types of measures, including Mentoring programmes for young academics, financial incentives for Universities who hire women to tenured academic positions, support for the creation of "gender-sensitive courses", and the development of child-care services (under the auspices of wider "work-life balance" objectives). One of the most important results of this programme has been the development of dedicated "Equal Opportunity Offices" within almost all Swiss Universities. In Lausanne, the BEC (*Bureau de l'égalité des chances*) now has a full-time Director, 3 part-time collaborators and 1 part-time secretary; all funded from the University cantonal budget (i.e. from structural funds).

Figure 1. Federal Equal Opportunity in Universities Programme, 2008-2011

Module 1 Annual budget of CHF 0.8 million (2008-2011)

Incentive programme for the promotion of female professors. This programme seeks to encourage universities to hire female professors. At the end of each academic year, the total budget is distributed according to the number of newly hired female professors who have been given a permanent contract. Universities are free to use these funds as needed. The main portion of the budget is used for a variety of gender equality purposes. The annual ranking of universities and academic fields encourages upper management to give greater priority to this issue and enriches discussions.

Module 2 Annual budget of ± CHF 0.8 million (2008-2011)

Mentoring programme for the promotion of female junior researchers. This programme covers a total of 39 highly diverse projects whose funding may be renewed from one to five times. There are eleven one-to-one mentoring projects, five mentoring networks, four communication platforms, twelve course programmes, lectures or seminars, three information days for secondary school students and one database for female experts and temporary positions. In order to broaden implementation of these projects, universities needed to contribute 50% of the total funding.

Module 3 Annual budget of CHF 0.3 million (2008-2011)

Work-life programme for greater balance between academic career and family. This programme has prompted all Swiss universities to introduce childcare measures in one form or another. The new project objective for the 2008-2011 period: establish support at Swiss universities for dual-career couples (DCC).

Flat rate and variable contributions

Annual budget of ± CHF 1.8 million (2008-2011)

All universities are provided with the same amount of flat rate funding. They also receive variable funding, which depends on the number of women who take their final examinations. This funding must be spent in accordance with the objectives established in Modules 2 and 3. A portion of funding may also be used to develop gender-sensitive courses.

Source: CRUS, 2012, *Swiss Federal Equal Opportunity in Universities Programme*, Bern: p. 2

At a very general level, the Law on the University of Lausanne (UNIL 2004) specifies in Article 14 of the Equal opportunity policy document that: “the University respects equal opportunity, especially between men and women, at all levels of the university. To this end, it adopts specific measures.” Amongst such measures (partly funded by the Federal

Academic EO programme), most are aimed at increasing women's access to an academic career.

In addition, the UNIL Directive 0.2 on the "Promotion of equal opportunity at the University of Lausanne" stipulates in its 1st article that: "the Rectors' Office of the University leads an active policy, especially regarding equality between women and men. The Rectors' Office implements measures aimed at sustaining equal opportunity policies in practice" (Direction UNIL 2007).

On the one hand, the University has an Equality Commission, a representative body, chaired by the Vice-Rector in charge of early academic careers and diversity. On the other hand: "In order to guarantee equality of treatment in recruitment processes, the Rectors' Office organises an Equality Delegation (...) aimed at sustaining equality in order to: 1) Inform Recruitment Board members about the rules regarding gender equality at the University and 2) Ensure that the rule of minority preference is applied when there is a need to choose between a male and a female candidate who have identical research and teaching qualifications and who are judged to be equally suited to an academic appointment" (Direction UNIL 2007). Thus, once a job announcement (Associate or Full Professorship) has been published, the secretary of the Equality Delegation invites members to volunteer to follow the procedure. If an equality delegate agrees to take on the task, s/he will become an official member of the Recruitment Board (without voting rights), will receive all the documents relating to the procedure, will take part in all the interviews and internal discussions, and will report back to the Equality Delegation chair (the Vice-Rector) on the results of the deliberation. In some rare cases, the final ranking of candidates proposed by the Recruitment Board has been refused by the Rector's Office, on the basis of the Equality delegates' report.

To sum up, we can stress that: « The promotion of gender equality has been institutionalised at the UNIL backed by the Federal Equal Opportunities Programme. Under this programme the Equal Opportunities Office was set up and a gender equality programme was initiated at the UNIL. This policy is strongly supported by the Rectors' Office and incorporated into its' strategic plans. The staff of the Equal Opportunities Office is fully integrated in to the UNIL budget. The active promotion of equality by the UNIL is incorporated in to the Law on the University and in the Unil Directive "Promoting Equality at the University of Lausanne". Following the renewal of the University management team in 2011, the directorate for Junior Faculty and Diversity was set up under Vice-Rector, Prof. Franciska Krings, one of its responsibilities being to

promote gender equality (...). In addition, the UNIL is developing and supporting teaching and research in Gender Studies, which contributes to the production of knowledge crucial for the advancement of equality» (UNIL Equality Action Plan, 2013 – 2016: p. 6)¹³

The results of this pro-active advancement of women measures obviously vary according to the disciplinary fields, and therefore by Faculty: in the Social and Political Sciences (SSP) Faculty, women currently represent 36.5% of Full & Associate professorships, whereas in the Faculty of Biology and Medicine there are only 9.4% women professors. The figure for the Unil as a whole is 21% women professors.

This internal variation in the “success rate” of existing equal opportunity measures has led to a new initiative in the latest phase of the Federal programme. Since 2012, the Universities are invited to adopt “tailor-made” solutions for each of their internal structures, in this case, the Faculties. Thus: “The theme of ‘equality’ has also been strengthened in the Faculties’ auto-evaluation process and is one of the quality criteria ». According to the new «50/50 vision» policy document: “The general objective of the Rectors’ Office is to tackle the ‘leaky pipeline’ and ensure that, by 2016, 40% of appointments to a professorial rank are made to women” (UNIL-BEC, 2012). Recognising that it may face particular difficulties, a specific target of 25% of women in all new appointments to professorial positions has been set for the STEM (FBM) Faculty. The adoption of this “decentralized” phase of equal opportunity policies coincided with the election of the first female Dean at the Faculty of Biology and Medicine (she’s a biologist). Under her leadership, the Faculty set up an internal working group, with the brief of elaborating an ambitious Equality Action Plan for the Faculty. This document has been approved by the Faculty Council and has led to the recruitment of a Faculty “gender equality officer”, who is in charge of implementing the different dimensions of the Action Plan.¹⁴

The Faculty of Social and Political Sciences also set up an internal working group, in order to elaborate its’ own internal Gender Equality Action Plan. Unfortunately, the Vice-Dean in charge of this project fell ill and the working group was unable to meet as regularly as initially planned. Despite approval from the Faculty council of a “skeleton policy document”, the Dean decided to re-convene a new working group in 2014, and the

13 <http://www.unil.ch/egalite/home/menuinst/promotion-de-legalite/plan-daction-pour-legalite.html>

14 <http://www.unil.ch/fbm/fr/home/menuinst/la-faculte/egalite-femmes-hommes.html>

recommendations from the web survey that has been carried out recently are expected before the middle of 2015.

Methodology

Given the academic employment structure in Swiss universities, we chose to investigate the appointment procedures to two types of positions:

a) Fixed-term post-docs with no direct access to a permanent position: these include post-doctoral research and/or teaching positions, usually funded by the SNSF or other competitive, external funding bodies, Post-doc assistantships (up to 5 years after the PhD), Maître Assistants in non-transformable positions (only in the FBM Faculty), and invited professors on various SNSF-funded post-doc programmes, including Ambizione (before PhD + 5 years) and SNSF Fellowships (before PhD + 9 years). Although these could all be considered as equivalent to “D positions” in other national contexts, it is important to stress that access to them is extremely competitive in the Swiss context, and that they can be occupied in succession, covering a total period of anything up to PhD +15-20 years.

b) Fixed-term post-docs that can be considered to be on a tenure track, since transition to a permanent position is possible, usually after a probationary period of approximately 4-6 years. These include all Maître Assistantships in the SSP Faculty, along with some MA posts in the FBM Faculty, and also tenure-track Assistant professorships (PAST PTC). These positions correspond to the definition of “C grades” in most EU classifications (e.g. SHE Figures), although they are often less prestigious than some of the non-tenure track positions mentioned previously.

The different stages of the study reported here initially appeared to be quite straightforward and manageable in the planned timeframe. However, each of them turned out to be fraught with difficulties and unforeseen hurdles. These problems related to different aspects of the research process that can be summarized as follows:

- Availability of data
- Access to and reliability of data
- Project coordination in a complex and multilevel institutional context

Availability of data

In order to carry out the research required under the first stage of WP7, we needed access to early post-doc job advertisements over a 4-year period (2010-2013), to analyse internal documents relating to recruitment criteria and procedures, and to carry out interviews and focus groups with members of recruitments boards in the two Faculties.

Since the mid-2000s, it has become obligatory to publish almost all academic jobs on the University web site¹⁵, which has a dedicated space, entitled “Working at the Unil?”¹⁶, subsequently divided into three sub-sections: academic appointments; PhD positions (assistantships); administrative and technical positions (including apprenticeships). As far as our study is concerned, the simplicity of this division is somewhat misleading, since junior / early career positions can be found under each one of these headings. Thus, for example, tenure-track Assistant professor positions (PAST PTC), as well as Junior (MA) or Senior (MER) Lectureships, and some temporary teaching positions are published under the heading “academic appointments”; Post-doc assistantships are (usually) published under the heading “Assistantships”; and a whole range of project-based post-doc research positions are published under the “Administrative and technical – PAT” heading.

Furthermore, most full and associate professorships are also advertised through more traditional channels (Swiss and other national newspapers, academic journals, on-line discussion groups, etc.) and this is sometimes the case for more junior, fixed-term post-doc positions, particularly when paid through external sources of funding.

The publication of a job advertisement on the University web page follows a fairly standardized procedure, whereby administrative staff from the unit where the job will be located (department, research centre, Institute) propose a job description to the Faculty HR administrator, who must approve the content and wording of the announcement before it can be uploaded to the appropriate space on the web site. Each Faculty provides its’ own standardized and predefined templates for all the types job advertisements (although not all job offers make use of these). These usually have to be approved by the Faculty HR Administrator and/or by the Dean, a procedure that

¹⁵ Article 1.3.1., of the University Regulations states that: “All positions are advertised publicly, with the exception of *ad personam* professorships and those destined to be filled through direct nomination channels” (Direction UNIL 2005, art. 1.3.1, p.1). These exceptional procedures are quite rare in SSP, but more frequent in FBM. They usually concern senior people with particular professional competencies / activities, with whom the Faculty wants to collaborate on a long-term basis.

¹⁶ <http://www.unil.ch/central/home/menuinst/organisation/les-emplois.html>.

probably explains the tendency for them to be quite uniform in format and content (see below).

The length of the call for candidates depends on the status of the position to be filled; the more prestigious the job on offer, the longer the position is supposed to be advertised (3-4 months for a full Professorship, 2 months for an Assistant professorship, 1 month for a junior Lectureship (MA), 2 weeks for a Post-doc Assistantship, etc.). Once the final date for applications has passed, the advertisement should (in theory) disappear from the web site. Some of these announcements appear to be archived (in paper form) by the administrative assistant of the Vice-Rectors, because they are considered important for the follow-up of the entire recruitment procedure. However, as we discovered, this is not systematically the case. Many of the more junior job advertisements simply disappear without trace from the University records.

In order to access past job advertisements for the two Faculties, we therefore needed the support of the web administrator, who, under instructions from the Vice-Rector in charge of early stage careers and diversity, agreed to provide an Excel file containing the information included in the job advertisements that had been published by the SSP and FBM Faculties over the 2010-2013 period.

Secondly, we had initially believed that it would be straightforward to obtain access to the written reports that are systematically provided by the Chair and members of the Recruitment Boards. Once again, this procedure is highly regulated. All recruitments to permanent and tenure-track academic positions have to be approved by the Faculty Council¹⁷ and, ultimately, by the Rector's Office. These procedures are also potentially open to scrutiny by the Equality Delegation that is responsible for sending so-called "equality delegates" to observe a selection of the professorship recruitments procedures. In order to facilitate communication between all the instances involved in academic recruitments, each procedure is summarized in a detailed (10 – 25 pages) written report. These reports provide a brief description of the gender composition of the applicants to the position advertised, give a short summary of each of the applications (age, nationality, date and topic of PhD, research, publications, teaching and administrative activities) and describe the discussions and decision-making process that led to the ranking of candidates by the Recruitment Board members. In the absence of a consensus within the Board, a so-called "minority report" can also be annexed, providing

¹⁷ The main decision-making body at Faculty level, which is composed of elected representatives of all categories of staff and students.

arguments in favour of an alternative recruitment proposal. The Faculty Councils are free to follow the recommendations of the Recruitment Board report, or of the minority report, or to propose a totally new ranking of the short-listed candidates. In turn, the Rectors' Office is entitled to follow the vote of the Faculty Council, or not. In all cases, the Rector always interviews the 1st ranked candidates for Full professorships and sometimes for Associate professorships.

Although the detail and content of the written Recruitment Board reports vary significantly, between Faculties, departments / institutes, Chairs, etc., they obviously provide a potentially good indication of the criteria that were mobilised and discussed during the Recruitment Board meetings. However, many recruitment procedures to more junior academic positions do not require the approval of such a detailed written document, which is extremely time-consuming to produce. We were thus unsure how useful the archives of these very formal recruitment procedures would be for this stage of the GARCIA project.

Finally, we wanted to interview members of Recruitment Boards that had been involved in hiring junior / early stage academics in the 2010-2013 period. However, since nomination to many of the post-doc positions we had selected was not as formalised as for the professorships, it was not easy to identify who had recently been involved in such procedures. This was obviously easier in the SSP Faculty, where we had personal information about the recent recruitments to early-stage career positions and could identify the main protagonists. We used expert interviews to gain comparable information from the FBM Faculty, but this was not always sufficient. Finally, it should be remembered that the recruitment of the SNSF-funded (Ambizione / Fellowship) professorships actually takes place **outside** the host institutions, by interdisciplinary, national selection boards, composed of representatives of different Swiss universities.

Access to and reliability of data

Contrary to our initial expectations, every stage of the research process outlined above presented us with unforeseen difficulties and delays. Some of the problems were related to the access to data; others raised issues about the reliability of the data available.

Firstly, simply finding past job advertisements for junior / early-stage academic positions in our two Faculties proved to be much harder than we had anticipated. The absence of on-line archives makes it impossible to identify the number of such positions

that have been filled over the past 4 years or to analyse the type of positions that are available at any given time.

After long delays and many reminders, we finally received an Excel file with 65 job descriptions from the Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, and 63 entries from the Faculty of Biology and Medicine. A preliminary analysis of this data set revealed that at least 11 of the SSP entries and 17 of the FBM entries were duplicates, which were eliminated; **leaving us with 54 SHS post-doc job descriptions and 49 STEM job descriptions**. As we will discuss in more detail later, a closer analysis of the content of the data base led us to conclude that the archives of the two Faculties recruitment procedures were probably not complete for the period under study, raising some doubts as to the exhaustive nature of the data provided by the central administration of the Unil. Secondly, despite initial support from one of the Vice-Rectors', we were refused authorised access to the archived recruitment reports that are stored in the office of the (same) Vice-Rectors' administrative assistant. Data protection was the main argument given to justify the “confidential” nature of these documents. This argument is somewhat fallacious, given that several members of the GARCIA team are elected representatives on the SSP Faculty Council. As such, they already have unlimited access to all the written reports that pertain to the recruitment procedures that have taken place in their own Faculty over the past 4 years. This argument did not convince the Rectors' Office to open up the archives for closer inspection.

Following this official refusal, we decided not to analyse the SSP reports to which we had access, through our personal channels. Not only would this have provided only partial data for our study (no possibility of comparing the contents of the recruitment reports in the SSH and STEM fields), it would also have masked the institutional barriers placed on the analysis of gendered academic recruitment procedures. These barriers clearly exist in Lausanne, despite repeated institutional commitment to the “transparency” and “fairness” of academic recruitment procedures and despite long-term support for equal opportunity measures on the part of the University management.

Project coordination in a complex and multilevel institutional context

Despite the frustrations they caused, we have decided to consider the difficulties encountered in obtaining access to the required data as significant research results. Along with the doubts we have about the reliability of the information we have obtained,

these difficulties are indicative of several structural characteristics of academic careers in the Swiss context.

Firstly, we were struck by the complexity of the institutional regulation of academic recruitment procedures. Despite an apparently clear relationship between the central (Rectors' Office), intermediate (Faculty) and most decentralized (Department / Institute) levels of the University organizational structure, there is no instance with exclusive and clear responsibility for the recruitment and management of all types of academic staff.

In the Swiss context, post-docs in the early stage of their academic careers may be affected by rules and regulations adopted at each level of the institutional hierarchy; they are also confronted with potential differences in practice between these different levels of regulation, and with employment opportunities through competitive funding channels that exist outside / alongside academic (host) institutions. Furthermore, precisely because recruitment to different types of early-stage academic positions is managed at different levels of the academic institutions, but also across different funding channels and according to different procedures and criteria, there is absolutely no global vision of the career paths that are followed by the members of our study population at the University level.

The multiple and decentralized institutional structures involved in the publication of academic job offers, the selection of candidates and the definition of their working conditions make the coordination of data collection extremely complicated and time-consuming. This multi-layered organizational structure also hinders the comparative analysis of any available data, which is not collected according to the same protocol or time-scale at all the levels of the institution. These are important factors to remember when interpreting the empirical data presented below.

5.2. Formal criteria

Formal criteria for recruitment to academic positions at Lausanne University are defined at different organizational levels (canton, University, Faculty, Departments / Institutes) and in plethora of Laws, Directives and Recommendations. It appears that all the institutional actors are committed to an increased formalization of the recruitment procedures at different levels of the academic hierarchy (including for funded PhD positions). Although the Faculties (and their departments / institutes) are free to define

the criteria that are judged to be most pertinent to their particular fields, there is increased pressure on them to adopt the centrally defined recruitment procedures. These cover issues such as: the publication channels for job announcements; the information provided for candidates (job content + employment conditions, including duration and possibility of renewal); the technical solutions proposed for receiving job applications; the composition of recruitment boards and the definition of their duties (including recommendations for dealing with any potential “conflict of interest”); the rules for selecting and short-listing candidates; the duration and content of interviews and other selection exercises; the structure of the written recruitment reports, etc.

Despite the leeway given to the Faculties in defining their own criteria for recruitment / promotion, the University nevertheless outlines a series of general criteria that are judged to be important and relevant in all academic fields. Interestingly, the formal recommendations insist on the requirement to take all the dimensions of academic work (research, teaching and administration) into account when evaluating job applications and/or candidates for promotion or stabilization. As we will show in more detail below, the University insists that its’ academic staff should achieve measurable levels of performance in all the dimensions of their activity and recommends that recruitment boards should not consider an exceptional research / publications record as a means to compensate for below expected results in teaching or a lack of investment in academic governance and management tasks.

Officially, recruitment processes and conditions are defined by the RLUL [*Règlement d’application de la Loi sur l’Université de Lausanne*] (UNIL 2004, art. 53), and therefore apply to all the internal components of the University, including the Faculties. As a result, the following section presents the criteria as formalised at the University level, only mentioning the Faculties when their formal procedures differ significantly from the University-level rules and regulations.

Formal recruitment procedures at the University and Faculty levels

As already indicated, there is a high degree of procedural formalization for recruitment to all permanent academic positions, but also quite explicit guidelines on the conditions candidates are required to fulfil before obtaining tenure, both at MER and Professorial levels. However, somewhat surprisingly, the legally binding RLUL (UNIL 2004b, art. 43) provides only very broad indications as to the criteria that should be taken into consideration when recruiting academic staff. Furthermore, there is no clear distinction

between what is expected of future or tenure track Professors, as compared to future or tenure track Senior Lecturers, for example. Both of these categories of staff are simply expected to: “testify as to their aptitude for teaching and research” and to “hold a PhD”.

Here we should probably insist on one of the particularities of the academic recruitment process in Switzerland (more precisely in the Vaud canton) that has direct consequences for post-docs at the early-career stage (in comparison, see Le Feuvre, 2009; Le Feuvre and Latour, 2007). This concerns the fact that most academic positions are advertised with the possibility of being filled at different hierarchical levels. This requires some explanation. As we have already seen, within the Unil, there are actually two distinct “tenure tracks” within the academic hierarchy:

- **Fixed-term junior lectureships** (Maître assistant·e·s – MA), where there is the possibility to move into a permanent Senior Lectureship (Maître d’enseignement et de recherche – MER1 or MER2), through a “tenure track” procedure, that is formalized in University and Faculty-level Directives. This procedure is more common in the SSP Faculty than in the STEM Faculty;
- **Fixed-term Assistant professorships** (PAST – PTC), where there is the possibility to move into a permanent Associate or Full Professorship (PAS or PO), through a “tenure track” procedure, that is formalized in University-level Directives.

In the 1st case, positions are usually advertised at MA **or** MER levels. Depending on the profile of the candidates, the Recruitment Board can either decide to recruit a candidate directly as a tenured MER (who will still have a 4-year probationary period to complete, before obtaining his/her first truly “permanent” 6-year contract), or to recruit a candidate on a fixed-term MA contract, but with the opportunity to obtain MER status through a future internal “tenure” procedure.¹⁸

In the 2nd case, professorial positions are usually advertised at several, alternative hierarchical levels. The Unil Direction Directive 1.3 presents no fewer than 9 possible denominations (and combinations) for professorial job announcements, as follows:

- Full professor
- Associate professor
- Assistant professor
- Assistant professor on a tenure track to a full professorship
- Assistant professor on a tenure track to an associate professorship

¹⁸ As defined in the Decanat SSP Directive 1.5.

- Full professor or assistant professor on a tenure track to a full professorship
- Associate professor or assistant professor on a tenure track to an associate professorship
- Full or Associate professor (the level of the position to be decided on the basis of the profile of the chosen candidate)
- Full, Associate or Assistant tenure track professor (the level of the position to be decided on the basis of the profile of the chosen candidate)

(Directive de la Direction 1.3: page 2).

It is always necessary to define the hierarchical level of the position before the job advertisement is published, and this is decided by the Faculty-level Planning Commissions and validated by the Faculty Councils and the Rector's Office. Once defined, the status of the position can't be changed at any point during the recruitment or nomination procedure. When sufficient funding is available for a Full professorship or when the position is the result of the retirement of a Full professor, there is a tendency to restrict the job announcements to this level. In most other cases, the Faculties tend to "hedge their bets" and to allow a combination of different academic levels.

It is therefore true to say that there are very few exclusively junior (or tenure track) professorships on offer at Lausanne University. It is frequent for early-career stage post-docs to find themselves in direct competition with much more senior candidates (either those who already occupy an MER position in the same or another institution, or those who already have professorial status at another – Swiss or foreign – institution), **in response to exactly the same job announcement.**

Although some Recruitment Boards obviously do chose younger and "promising" candidates in preference to more experienced colleagues, this system usually puts early-career stage candidates at a structural disadvantage. This is particularly the case in a country that provides university professors with relatively comfortable employment and working conditions, and that is therefore very attractive to quite senior and reputable candidates from abroad.

Furthermore, once a candidate has been recruited to one of the hierarchical levels specified in the job announcement, he or she will come under the Vaud Canton promotion guidelines, which specify that no cantonal employee can be promoted more than once in his/her entire career (and, of course, solely on recommendation from the Dean and Rector) to a higher-level grade. Deciding to recruit someone (at age 35+ or

45+) to an Associate professorship implies that his/her chances of ever becoming a Full professor within the same institution are extremely slim.

Formal recruitment criteria for non-tenured and tenured positions

We have already noted that variations in the formal criteria for recruitment to academic positions do not necessarily depend on whether the jobs concerned are temporary and non-tenured, or not. Some fixed-term positions are associated with quite rigorous and formalized procedures and with extremely high levels of competition for jobs. This is because tenured and non-tenured positions exist both at the Senior Lectureship and at the Professorial level of the Swiss academic hierarchy. In spite of this characteristic, we have maintained the tenured versus non-tenured distinction as a template for analysing the formal recruitment criteria we have identified in HR documents pertaining to each of our case study Faculties, and to Lausanne University as a whole.

Formal recruitment criteria for non-tenured positions

University Directive 1.34 provides guidelines for the recruitment of PhD Assistants and post-doc Assistants. In both cases, the employment contract is of a maximum duration of 5 years, as defined by Article 21 of the Unil Assistantship Regulations. These fixed-term contracts are usually presented in the following manner: 1 + 2 x 2 years, indicating an initial 1-year (probationary) contract, followed by two potential renewals, of two years duration each.

This Directive mainly insists on the formal recruitment procedures, with no mention of selection criteria, which are explicitly left up to the employing organisation to determine, according to their teaching and/or research needs. When the Assistants or Post-doc assistants are recruited to positions funded through the main budget of the University, a Selection Board composed of at least two members, including the Director of the Department / Institute, must be approved by the Dean. However, if the positions are funded through external sources, the Directive states that: “No Selection Board needs to be established. It is the responsibility of the person in charge of the funding to propose the hiring of a suitable candidate” (Directive 1.34: p. 2).

There is no formal procedure for the intermediary renewal of these contracts. The Directive states that it is up to the Director of the Department / Institute to decide on the renewal. A lack of funding is mentioned as a legitimate reason for non-renewal or contract termination at any point during the 5 years. In that case, the Post-doc Assistants are entitled to just 2 months notice.

In most of the Unil Faculties, with the exception of SSP, similar procedures apply to the fixed-term, non-transformable Maître assistantships. In theory, the total duration of these positions is limited to 4 years, with a possible 2-year extension “in exceptional circumstances”; these may include periods of maternity and/or (unpaid) parental leave, but may also be granted to candidates for the MER stabilization process (see below), who fail to pass the evaluation tests.

Formal recruitment criteria for tenure track positions

As we have already mentioned, tenure track positions can be identified at both the senior lectureship and professorial levels. The formal criteria are similar for both, although the composition of the Recruitment Boards differs for the Senior Lectureship and Professorial tenure procedures.

From fixed-term Maître Assistantships to permanent Senior Lectureship (MER) positions

Because all their MA positions can potentially be “stabilized” at MER level, the SSP Faculty has produced very detailed guidelines, specifying the criteria for tenure as a MER (Décanat SSP-UNIL 2007). This 10-page document ranges from the general statement that the process should lead to the retention of “persons with high achievements in research, teaching and contributions to the wellbeing of the institution”, to the presentation of the standardized criteria that the dedicated Recruitment Board should apply in all cases. Two Annexes to the Directive itemize the evaluation criteria and contextualise their use, providing examples of previous candidates who have achieved tenure as an illustration of how the formal criteria are used in practice. A quantifiable performance scale is provided for each of the three areas of academic activity (research, teaching and contributions to institutional wellbeing). In each domain, different levels of attainment are associated with a certain number of points.

A minimum of 12.5 points out of a possible maximum of 25 is required **in each of the three areas** in order for tenure to be granted. In this case, there is a high level of formalisation and specification, but also room for adaptation to disciplinary specificities. Table 2 presents the criteria on which the Board members are invited to base their recommendation. These guidelines are widely available to all candidates and to other members of the SSP Faculty, notably through the Faculty web site.

Table 2. SSP Faculty criteria for tenure at Senior Lecturer (MER) level

Activity Domain	Specific dimensions	Evaluation scale
Teaching	Teaching Experience	17 points, on the following basis:
	Seminars	From 0 (none) to 5 (varied)
	Lectures	From 0 (none) to 5 (varied)
	Supervision	From 0 (none) to 5 (10+ Masters)
	Teaching outside the Faculty	Maximum: 2
	Teaching Quality	8 points, on the following basis:
	Innovative pedagogy / teaching programmes	Maximum: 3
	Student evaluations	From 0 (no evaluation) to 5 (excellent)
	Total Teaching	Maximum 25 points
	Research	Output
Annual productivity (all types of publication)		From 0 (less than 2) to 3 (more than 5)
Peer-reviewed journal articles / year		From 0 (less than 0.5) to 2 (more than 2) (+1 if high quality journals)
Monographs or edited books / 8 years		From 0 (less than 0.5) to 2 (more than 2) (+1 if high quality publishers)
Book chapters / year		From 0 (less than 0.5) to 2 (more than 2) (+1 if high quality publishers)
Funding		8 points, on the following basis:
SNSF or similar research project funding		0 (none) - 1 (co-author) - 2 (main applicant)
SNSF or similar grant		From 0 (none) to 2 (for 2 years+)
Other funding		From 0 (none) to 2 (several)
Submission unsuccessful funding applications		From 0 (none) to 2 (main applicant)
Networking		5 points, on the following basis:
External mobility		From 0 (none) to 2 (2 host institutions)
Conference papers / year		From 0 (none) to 3 (at least 1 international)
Total Research	Maximum 25 points	
Institution	Investment in scientific events / activities	16 points, on the following basis:
	Editorial activities (academic journals, etc.)	From 0 (none) to 4 (regular)
	Conference organisation	From 0 (none) to 4 (several, with lead role)
	Scientific evaluation activities	From 0 (none) to 4 (several, with lead role)
	Outreach / expert activities	From 0 (none) to 4 (regular)
	Institutional implication	9 points, on the following basis:
	Active role in centre / Institute, including supervision + admin	From 0 (none) to 4 (regular)
Active role in Unil decision-making bodies	From 0 (none) to 4 (regular + varied) (+1 if Unil-related voluntary activity)	
Total institution	Maximum 25 points	

In the FBM Faculty, the guidelines are not as formalized as in the SSP Faculty (probably because very few Maître Assistants are eligible for the stabilization / tenure track channel). Reference is made solely to the University Directive 1.34, and to the revised Faculty Directive for promotions that the FBM Faculty will introduce at the beginning of 2015. According to our interviewees, the aim of this document is to offer more recognition for the clinical practice of young academics (particularly those who have joint employment contacts with the teaching hospital (CHUV) and the University).

However, since the SSP Guidelines and FBM Directives are also based on the Unil recommendations, no significant differences between the disciplinary fields appear. Notably, the importance of a “balanced” profile (i.e. not all research, nor indeed, all teaching) would seem to be overriding criteria, shared at all levels of the University.

From tenure track Assistant professorships to permanent professor positions

The criteria for gaining tenure at an Associate of Full professorship level are equally formalized in written University and Faculty-level Directives. The main differences between tenure procedures at lectureship and professorship levels concern, on the one hand, the composition of the Recruitment Board and, on the other hand, the importance given to the demonstration of leadership qualities at the professorial level.

For decisions concerning access to professorial tenure, the Evaluation Committee is usually composed of at least 6 members (+1 potential representative of the Rector’s Office), including a Dean or Vice-Dean, who must not be a member of the same Department / Institute as the candidate, 2 professors from the same Faculty (the Directive recommends that the same professors follow several tenure procedures, over an extended period of time, so as to ensure a continuity in way the formal criteria are interpreted and applied in practice), and, finally 3 experts in the same research field as the candidate, from outside Lausanne University, nominated by the Dean of the Faculty. Unlike the procedure for direct recruitment to Associate or Full professorships, the tenure evaluation Committee does not include undergraduate and graduate student representatives.

As in the case of MER tenure, the University Directive insists on the equal importance of the three domains of academic activity: “Evaluation covers 3 dimensions: institutional integration, research performance and teaching skills. More specifically, it is expected that the person who has been recruited to a PAST-PTC [Assistant tenure track professor] position will have made a contribution to improving the functioning of his/her research

group, the Faculty, and the overall wellbeing of the academic community. This person should have advanced his/her particular research field and offered high quality teaching. For the clinical sciences section of the Faculty of Biology and Medicine, the evaluation process will also include their clinical activity”. Moreover, “the evaluation procedure should demonstrate above average abilities in all of the aspects considered (integration, research, teaching), and **not** to calculate a global score, such as an average score across the various indicators” (Direction UNIL 2005, Directive 1.4., Art. 1.4.4: p. 2).

The Evaluation Committee not only takes into account the application submitted by the candidate (including CV, research and teaching projects, publications list, teaching syllabus and student evaluations), but also the written reports provided by his/her immediate boss and by the Head of the Faculty Teaching Commission. As well as an interview with the Board members, the candidate also has to be inspected during a teaching exercise (i.e. the Board members sit in on a class or tutorial). It is also specified that the evaluation must take the personal circumstances of the candidate into account, especially in case of “maternity leave or parental leave”.

The Directive includes a detailed list of questions that the Evaluation Board members are invited to explore are summarised (in order of appearance in the most recent version) below.

Table 3. University level criteria for tenure at Associate or Full professor positions

Domains	Questions / topics to be reported
<i>Institutional integration</i>	
	Candidate’s involvement in the institution?
	Institutional management responsibilities?
	Ability to collaborate in teaching and research activities?
	Ability to work in a team / demonstrate team leadership qualities?
	Quality of relations with colleagues and collaborators?
	Ability to communicate in French?
<i>Research performance</i>	
	Ability of the person to develop a personal research project?
	Personal research project, confirmed by publications?
	Personal research perimeter?
	Scientific output and visibility?
	Personal position within specialist field?
	Research results and publications higher than average for an individual of the same age in the same domain?
	Quality and range of journals in which the candidate has published? (may be evaluated though bibliometric indicators, where these exist)
	Originality, innovation and timeliness in research topics / methods?
	Ability to interact with other researchers?
	Interdisciplinary experience?
	Research management experience / abilities?

Teaching skills	
	Extent to which courses fulfil students' expectations?
	Extent to which teaching corresponds to academic standards?
	Ability to interact with students?
	Ability to develop teaching skills demonstrated?
	Ability to introduce change following student evaluations?
	Coherent teaching method choices, with regard to objectives?
	Shared / divergent perceptions by students, Committee members and Teaching Commission chair on candidates' teaching performance?
	Does the supervision provided contribute to the progression of Master and PhD students' work and to students' scientific development?

Source: Direction UNIL, 2005, Directive 1.4.

The Directive also mentions that this list is not exhaustive. It can be supplemented or modified depending on the faculty or on disciplinary specificities. However, for each additional criterion, it is important to specify on what basis the experts and the commission have made their assessment.

In October 2014, the Rectors' office published a joint Annex to this Directive, along with the CHUV (University hospital) HR Service, specifying the processes and criteria that apply specifically to the promotion of academics working in the Clinical Sciences section of the Faculty of Biology and Medicine. Quantitative indicators appear to be more developed here than in the initial Directive. In addition to teaching, research and institutional investment (called "Leadership, management / mentoring" here), guidelines are also provided for evaluating the clinical activities of candidates for tenure. In addition to the points listed in Table 3, this revised document also mentions "Prizes and honorary recognition" and the development of university-industry collaborative projects.

To sum up, it this appears that extremely detailed formal recruitment criteria are provided by the central HR services. Both the STEM and the SHS Faculties have undertaken an adaptation of these documents to their own needs and circumstances. This tailoring of the University-level rules to the needs of a particular Faculty has been taken further in the SSP Faculty, notably due to the decision to enable all Maitres Assistants to apply for tenure, through the highly formalised "stabilisation" procedure. Although this opportunity is not offered to all MAs in the Faculty of Biology and Medicine, there would not seem to be any major differences in the way the University-level criteria are adopted by the Faculties. Notably, the figure of the "well-rounded academic", equally invested in research, teaching and administrative duties would appear to represent a shared ideal-type across Faculties and disciplinary fields.

From formal recruitment criteria to job announcements: Continuity or contradictions?

As we have already mentioned, the University Regulations provide a broad template for all professorial job announcements, irrespective of the Faculty. These documents, are always approved by the Dean and by the Communication Service (Unicom) web administrator, and they have to make the following information available to prospective candidates:

- The disciplinary field of the position
- The institutional affiliation (i.e. the Faculty, Department / Institute, Research Centre / Group)
- The profile the chosen candidate is expected to demonstrate
- The hierarchical status of the position

In addition, all job announcements have to include a standard indication that the Unil is “committed to improving women’s access to academic careers and encourages their application”

It is therefore hardly surprising that the job announcements we have analysed from the SSP and FBM Faculties demonstrate a lot of similarities, in terms of appearance and content.

Table 4a: Post-doc job announcements published by the SSP Faculty, 2010-2013¹⁹

	2010	2011	2012	2013	Total
SNSF post-doc researcher	2	2	2	2	8
Postdoc assistant	-	3	4	6	13
MA	3	1	2	1	7
MA or MER	2	-	-	1	3
PAST (not tenure track)	-	-	1	-	1
PAST PTC	-	-	-	-	-
PAS or PAST PTC	3	-	3	2	8
PO or PAST PTC	1	-	-	-	2
PO, PAS, OU PAST PTC	1	-	1	-	1
Total	12	6	13	12	43

Non-tenure track = 22; Tenure track (Senior Lectureship)= 10; Tenure track (Professorship)= 11

¹⁹ Glossary: MA = Maitre Assistantship; MER = Senior Lectureship; PAST = Assistant professorship, with (PTC) or without tenure track; PAS = Associate professorship; PO = Ordinary (Full) professorship.

Table 4b: Post-doc job announcements published by the FBM Faculty, 2009-2014

	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	Total
SNSF post-doc researcher	-	1	5	5	2	-	13
Postdoc assistant	1		9	9	4	7	30
MA	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
MA or MER	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PAST (not tenure track)	-	-	-	-	-	(1)	(1) ²⁰
PAST PTC	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
PAS or PAST PTC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PO or PAST PTC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PO, PAS, OU PAST PTC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	1	2	14	14	6	8	45

Non-tenure track = 43; Tenure track (Senior Lectureship) = 1; Tenure track (Professorship) = 1

Types of post-doc positions advertised in the SHS and STEM Faculties

The results presented here are based on a comparative analysis of the job announcements published by the two Faculties, between 2010 and 2013. As indicated earlier, we have analysed 43 post-doc job announcements (eliminating what appeared to be 11 duplicates in the initial data file) from the SSP Faculty, and 45 announcements (without the 17 duplicates) from the FBM Faculty, where we only considered non-clinical positions, particularly from the following disciplines: Genomics, Protein Analysis Facility, Biochemistry, Cell/Molecular Biology, Biotechnology, Ecology and Evolution, Cell Biology and Morphology, Physiology.

Thanks to our inside knowledge of the SSP Faculty, it would seem that the database is not complete, since some post-doc positions that we personally know about do not appear in the Excel file that was provided to us by the central administration. As they appear in the data set, the positions advertised are presented in Tables 4a (SHS) and 4b (STEM).

Because of our uncertainty as to the exhaustive character of the information contained in the data set, it is with considerable caution that we compare the nature of the positions advertised in the SHS and STEM Faculties. Firstly, the total number of post-doc positions advertised over the given period is quite similar in the two Faculties, reflecting their roughly equivalent size, and the fact that some of the medically qualified PhDs will choose to continue their careers in some form of clinical activity, which we have not taken into account here. Secondly, It would appear that just under half the post-doc positions advertised in the SSP Faculty correspond to a tenure track career option, either at MER

²⁰ Although advertised by the Basic Science section of the Faculty, the position has a large clinical component, so it was not included in the content analysis.

or professorial level. This is absolutely not the case in the FBM Faculty, where almost all of the positions advertised are for fixed-term non-tenure track post-doc researchers or Assistants.

Generic versus specific post-doc job profiles in the SHS and STEM Faculties

In order to compare the content of the post-doc job advertisements from the two Faculties, we devised a 4-stage scale to characterise the degree to which they referred to generic or specific applicant characteristics and/or job requirements. Allocating each announcement to one of these categories was not always an easy task, since the format and length of the documents varied considerably, even within each Faculty. Table 5 gives some indication of the classification of job announcements from the two Faculties studied.

Table 5. Share of generic or specific requirements in SSP and FBM post-doc job adverts

Type of job requirements	SSP	FBM
GENERIC+	11	7
GENERIC-	10	18
SPECIFIC-	6	12
SPECIFIC+	17	8
<i>Total</i>	<i>43</i>	<i>45</i>

The first level is the *most generic* one (GENERIC+) characterizes 11 of the SSP job descriptions and 7 of the FBM ones. Under this category we have identified advertisements with only a very broad and sometimes quite vague definition of the tasks involved. Information on the requirements of the job remains very general (large disciplinary scope for the degree / PhD; not much detail provided as to the characteristics, skills and abilities that are sought after). For example:

Applicants are required to have a Ph.D. in the social sciences (anthropology, sociology, educational science, political science, etc.) or equivalent. They must demonstrate a distinct competence in the field of gender studies and possess extensive teaching and research experience at the university level. The ideal candidate has high level research activities and publications in the field related to the post. S/he has clearly demonstrated the potential to conduct research and to work in a team. S/he also participates in international scientific networks. A full-time PhD assistant will be associated with this post.

<i>The department of physiology is seeking a post-doc Assistant</i>	
Job description	Requirements
Working in a structured research environment, where objectives consist of stimulating collaborations between research groups at three different institutions (UNIL-CHUV-EPFL) and improve training within the field of metabolism, nutrition and ageing.	PhD in Life Sciences or equivalent title. Experience in metabolic physiology and solid knowledge in nutrition are desired.

A second category (defined as GENERIC-) is characterized by requirements that focus on a single specific disciplinary field, but include explicit criteria on the candidates' characteristics, skills and abilities and also indicate the type of research and/or teaching they will be required to undertake. For example:

<i>The Department of Cell Biology and Morphology invites applications for post-doc researcher jobs</i>	
Job description	Requirements
Our present projects deal with: 1) basic questions such as understanding Ca ²⁺ signal encoding in astrocytes and its significance for synaptic functions, 2) pathology-oriented questions such as understanding the impact of pro-inflammatory cytokines on the astrocytic input to synapses and its role in the pathogenesis of brain diseases. The selected candidates will work in an environment including neurophysiologists, imaging specialists and an engineer developing microscopes and image analysis programs.	Doctorate degree in Neuroscience with solid experience in combined electrophysiology and dynamic cellular imaging techniques, interested in pursuing advanced studies on the role of astrocytes signalling in synaptic transmission.

<p>Maitre assistantship or Maitre d'enseignement et de recherche position in CULTUREL AND SOCIAL ANTHROPOLOGY</p> <p>The candidate will be able to teach a course entitled "Cultural and Social Anthropology: Introductory Texts and Methods", as well as a course entitled "Notions and Themes in Anthropology". The candidate will pursue his/her own research interest and contribute to collective research projects. The total teaching load will be adjusted to the type of position. A PhD in Anthropology or an equivalent qualification is required.</p>
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The third category (SPECIFIC-) refers to announcements for which more detailed requirements are detailed. These job descriptions include information on the discipline and method on the one hand, and on the selection criteria and the working environment on the other.

<i>The Centre for Integrative Genomics (CIG) is seeking a Postdoc Assistant</i>	
Job description	Requirements
<p>The research project focuses on the control of melanoma progression by the nuclear receptor PPAR³.</p> <p>The applicant will collaborate frequently with the other team members and participate in their projects under the supervision of Dr. LM.</p> <p>At least 50% of the usual working time will be devoted to personal research work.</p>	<p>A position is available in the group of Dr. LM for a highly motivated scientist, interested in the molecular basis of melanoma development. Applicants must have a Ph.D. in a related field with a strong component of cell culture and in vivo (mouse) experiments, to have an understanding and a keen interest in molecular and cellular biology. The successful applicant will have the opportunity to work in a dynamic interdisciplinary environment and will have access to cutting edge facilities and technologies</p>

<p>Maitre assistantship in Social Psychology and the Life-Course</p> <p>TEACHING (30%): 2 courses within the study programme of the Institute of Social Sciences · 1 Social Science Methods course (quantitative or qualitative) · 1 course related to the candidates' own research interests and/or to the LIVES Research programme. Some supervision expected of Master and PhD students' research projects.</p> <p>RESEARCH (60%): The candidate is expected to develop his/her own research and to contribute to the projects of the social psychology & the life-course team and those IPs of the LIVES Centre of excellence that work in that area.</p>

Finally, the very specific (SPECIFIC+) category refers to positions on which precise information is given, regarding the degree / PhD field, the skills required, and the type of research to be conducted. The tasks / duties / responsibilities of the job are described in some detail and here is usually a link to the website of the future research centre or unit. The ideal candidate is defined through explicit criteria, including expected levels and type of experience, publication record, language skills, etc. In FBM Faculty, an explicit mention of gender promotion issues is often an integrative part of this type of job

description. In the SSP Faculty, this type of announcement is more commonly used for positions in psychology than in the other disciplines of the Faculty, such as social sciences or political science. For example:

<p>Post-doc Assistantship in cognitive and experimental psychology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 50% of the job will be dedicated to research (experiment design, data analysis, publications) - 50% will be dedicated to teaching BA and Ma psychology courses and other institutional activities. <p>The candidate should have a confirmed interest in and very sound knowledge of the neurobiological aspects of memory, and should be able to demonstrate past experience in carrying out and analysing EEG experiments (e.g. through articles already published in peer-reviewed journals). Past experience in teaching on psychology courses would be an advantage. Candidates aspiring to an academic career in experimental psychology are particularly encouraged to apply. A PhD in psychology (or related domain) is required, on a topic that reflects the candidates' experience in psychology or neuroscience. Desire to conceive and conduct experimental protocols on the neurobiological aspects of memory. The applicants should be motivated to join and collaborate with a research team (<i>Laboratoire de Recherche Expérimentale sur le Comportement</i>) and demonstrate the ability to collaborate and cooperate with members and associate members of the Centre. They should have an interest in developing academic writing skills and critical thinking. Good French language skills for teaching – Good English language skills for research activities.</p>
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<i>Post-doc Assistant in the interface between Biology and Human and Social Sciences</i>	
Job description	Requirements
<p>The candidate will develop teaching and research activities within the “Biology and Society” and “Sciences au carré” services. These programmes are interdisciplinary. They aim to raise the awareness of biology students on social challenges and to reinforce dialogue between the sciences. The candidate will teach the Biology and Society programme at Bachelor level in Biology as well as the “Sciences au carré” course of the Master degree. S/he will be in charge of developing interdisciplinary exchange, supervising students and doing research focused on links between biology and human and social sciences. A full job description is available at: http://www.unil.ch/fbm/page64812.html.</p>	<p>The candidate must have a PhD in a domain that cuts across biology and Human sciences, with excellent knowledge of the challenges and current methods in biology and social sciences, a solid teaching experience and also postdoctoral research experience of several years. S/he will be able to lead an interdisciplinary, demanding and original research programme, publish in international journals, interact with male and female researchers and students from different horizons, in French and in English.</p> <p>http://www.unil.ch/biologiesociete http://www.unil.ch/sciencesaucarre</p>

Recruitment criteria mentioned in the SHS and STEM post-doc job descriptions

As shown in Table 6, the PhD degree discipline is the most mentioned criteria in the social sciences. It is closely followed by research-demonstrated competencies. In SSP, these 2 criteria could be considered as the dominant criteria. They are almost mentioned for every position. “Interest in a particular academic field” also seems to be of importance. “Collaboration” with other institutions or colleagues is mentioned in almost half of the job offers, as are “methodological skills”. Language skills are mentioned as requirements for junior positions (6 for post-docs and 7 for postdoc Assistantships), whereas “publications” appear to be more frequently associated with more senior positions (5 for Assistant professorships, 2 for MA). This criterion is also mentioned in 4 offers for postdoc Assistantships. However, this request is usually accompanied by a request for a research project outline (this formula is mainly used in political science). Nevertheless, the young researcher should attest that s/he has already published and that s/he is “of high potential”.

In the SSP Faculty, post-doc research positions are always linked to specific research projects and the job offers rarely mention any teaching activities, with the exception of some student supervision within the research unit. The job description often includes a description of the funded research project and frequently refers to methodological and/or technical skills.

The positions of postdoc Assistants are the ones in which the reported percentage of job content for research is highest (up to 70%). Teaching obligations are usually not mentioned at all for these positions, but the postdoc Assistants are expected to coordinate the scientific activities of their research unit (N=4), and to participate in research-related administrative tasks (N=2).

Finally, in the SSP Faculty, Maître Assistant (MA) positions are advertised with a strong emphasis on teaching, the title of the courses being often given. Compared to the postdoc Assistantship adverts, they have surprisingly few administrative tasks.

In the Faculty of Biology and Medicine (FBM), the most frequent and therefore the most dominant criterion in the job descriptions is the disciplinary field of the doctorate (PhD in the field or a related field judged as equivalent). The latter is followed by a set of equally important criteria that vary according to the position on offer. However, taken together, they seem to constitute “core” of the expected characteristics within FBM positions (in addition to the PhD field). These criteria are mentioned as follows: interest in a particular field, research experience in a given area, methodological skills and the

ability to collaborate in a team. Motivation, language skills, networking and multidisciplinary appear far less important, although they are mentioned in some of the descriptions.

Thus, independence, publications, postdoctoral experience, contribution to a given academic field, and the capacity to acquire funding rarely appear explicitly in the FBM job descriptions.

Table 6. Criteria mentioned in the post-doc job descriptions of the SSP & FBM Faculties

SSP Faculty	N u m b e r o f occurrences	FBM Faculty	N u m b e r o f occurrences
Degree criteria	43	Degree criteria	39
Research experience	39	Interest in particular field	38
Thematic interests	30	Research experience	31
Collaboration skills	21	Methodological skills	29
Methodological skills	21	Collaboration skills	26
Language skills	15	Motivation	17
Publication record	12	Language skills	15
Contribution to field	8	Networking skills	11
Motivation	6	Multi/pluridisciplinarity	10
Management skills	5	Independence	8
Outreach skills	3	Publication record	7
Multi/pluridisciplinarity	2	Postdoc experience	4
Networking skills	2	Contribution to field	3
Postdoc experience	1	Acquiring funding	2
Acquiring funding	0	Outreach skills	0
Independence	0	Management skills	0

The absence of ‘excellence’ in the post-doc job descriptions

In the job advertisements from the **SSP Faculty**, the term “excellence” is very seldom used (N=6) and when it does occur, it usually refers to specific methodological skills (N=3) or to the mastering of languages (N=2), and only once to the candidates’ publication record. The remaining job advertisements may implicitly refer to excellence through expressions such as “solid background in” or “experience of” or “competences

in”. Since the term “experience” appears 9 times (in the 11 announcements for professorial positions), it would seem to characterize these positions more than the other post-doc positions. The term “experience” is also used in reference to teaching in the announcements for MA positions (3 times out of 7). The same term also appears in job descriptions for postdoc Assistantships (4 times) and for post-doc research positions (twice), but here it is linked to specific skills.

Likewise, only two job announcements from the **FBM Faculty** explicitly mention the term « excellence ». Interestingly enough, both are for postdoctoral positions where the requirements are presented in extremely specific and precise ways. The remaining announcements refer to excellence rather implicitly: a « solid/strong background », « solid experience » and « interest » are the most common features defining the requirements of the jobs. Only a small minority of the advertisements refer to research productivity / publication criteria, or to methodological / management / language / teaching skills.

We could not identify any significant differences in the terminology used between job announcements for tenured and non-tenured positions. We can also conclude that the term “excellence” is treated with some scepticism in both the Faculties studied here.

References to affirmative action/gender equality policies in the job announcements

In over half (26) of the SSP job announcements, the Equal Opportunity Policy of the University is indicated and women are encouraged to apply. The Unil equal treatment policy is always mentioned when the job is advertised in newspapers.

On the contrary, in those FBM job descriptions published before 2012, there is almost no reference to the Unil gender equality policies (except for an Assistant Professor position published in 2010 (and which was excluded from the frequency analysis because of its clinical orientation). From mid 2012 onwards, every job description encourages women candidates explicitly, either by using the gender-neutral grammatical form in French, or by mentioning the gender equality policy in the job description.

5.3. Actual criteria

The Faculty of Biology and Medicine (FBM)

Selection criteria for interviews and focus group in the STEM Faculty

For the selection of our interviewees, we first contacted three persons we already knew inside the FBM and we asked them about the best way to reach representatives of different disciplines and domains for the interviews. We chose two Full professors (who were also Heads of department) from the webpage of the Section of Basic Sciences (SF) of the FBM. At the beginning of November, we had a meeting with the person in charge of early-career stage academics (*Commission de la relève*) and the Equality Officer of the Faculty and asked them for advice about the best way to organize our focus group. They confirmed that there were no formal appointment procedures for post-doc Assistantships or for SNSF post-doc research positions, but that the FBM has a Permanent commission for hiring or promoting candidates to MA, MER and Privat-Dozent positions. Therefore, we contacted those members of the Commission who came from the non-clinical FBM disciplines (6 male professors and 1 woman representing the intermediate level). Three professors wrote back informing us that they didn't have the time to take part in a focus group, due to work overload. Despite two reminders, the other colleagues never answered our invitation, or filled out the Doodle we had prepared, in order to plan the meeting.

Sensing that the focus group might prove difficult to organise in the FBM Faculty, we asked to be allowed to take part – as participant observers – in the meeting of the Faculty Equal Opportunity Commission (*Commission Pro Femmes*) and in the meeting of the *Commission de la relève*. For this last commission, we asked to have some time (30 minutes – 1 hour) at the end of the meeting to organise a focus group. We have been invited to join the next session of the FBM Equal Opportunity Commission, on December 11th 2014. We are still waiting for the date of the next session of the *Commission de la relève* to be announced. We are however confident that we will be able to collect additional information through these channels, in order to complete our analysis for the next deliverable of WP7.

Criteria mentioned in the STEM Faculty

As in the SSP Faculty, interview questions about the criteria that enter into the post-doc selection process usually provoked amusement and humorous reactions from colleagues

in the STEM disciplines. When asked how he thought it best to judge an application and to measure the ability of a candidate, this male professor laughed:

“Well, if only I knew how to measure that kind of thing, I’d be over the moon! It’s quite an art, that is! It’s more of an art, really, I don’t think that it’s a science, and art is a difficult thing!” (Male Professor, STEM).

However, when pushed to explain what they really looked for in applications, most of our interviewees agreed that two main selection criteria for post-doc positions were important: **publications** and an **interest in a specific research topic**, and/ or in the research area of the team the postdoc will join. Neither of these criteria appears to be more important than the other, since the “best possible candidate” (Male Professor, STEM), appears to be defined by a combination of motivation (interest in the particular research domain / topic) and proof of research ability (as confirmed by the existence of publications).

However, some the interviewees stress that the “perfect match” between the job opening and potential candidates is not always easy to achieve at the post-doc level, notably because of the tight time-scale associated with externally funded research projects. Once a professor receives notification that one of his/her research funding applications has been accepted, it is important that they avoid delaying the project. It is often more important to find someone who is willing to start immediately, than to “waste time” searching for the “best possible” candidate for the project.

Publications and research funding

According to our interviewees, for early postdoc positions, a minimum of 2-3 (almost always joint-authored), published journal articles is expected of candidates, in order to confirm their writing skills and their ability to get a paper published. Proof of the ability to put research into print is generally seen as a sign that the candidate has completed a “successful professional socialization process” in the course of the PhD (Male Professor, STEM).

On the contrary, having already attracted research funding is not a discriminatory criterion at the early post-doc phase. Most of our interviewees agree that candidates should be able to demonstrate that they have written some applications for funds, without having had to accumulate important sums of money. Bringing research money into the department / research group is clearly seen as a professional competence that

increases with age and experience, and that is the responsibility of the “seniors” or Heads of section: “

No, I wouldn't expect a 1st year post-doc to have attracted a lot of funding. It would be good if he could show that he had received some small grants, for getting an article published, or something like that, but I wouldn't expect him to have funding for a whole project. I mean, if I'm hiring a Senior researcher, after 4 or 5 years as a post-doc, then of course I would expect more; that he had really been able to unblock funds for a project... and also some proof that that person is able to manage a whole project” (Female Professor, STEM).

Research topics and past experience

As we have already seen in the analysis of the job descriptions, a thematic “good match” between the candidates and the post-doc position is seen as vitally important by all our interviewees. One female professor explained the reason for this in the following terms:

“If I'm recruiting someone for a post-doc just after the PhD, the topic is really important for me [...] We're really looking for someone where there's a match between what we need and what the person can bring” (Female Professor, STEM).

Another interviewee agreed with this focus on the subject area, but also stressed the importance of the motivation of the candidate to join his team / research centre:

“What counts is the interest they have in what we're doing in our lab', and their own expertise [...] we have people who are interested in our specific research topics, who've read what we do, who have perhaps already worked a little bit on similar topics and so who have scientific technical expertise in that area” (Male Professor, STEM).

The importance of hiring someone who has already acquired a number of technical skills that are needed within the team or particular research project explains the attention that the STEM colleagues pay to the past experiences of the candidate, and particularly the lab' / team / university where they completed their PhD. It is through their own academic networks and contacts that the senior academics read the CVs of the applicants and identify those who have worked in places or with specific people who are likely to have trained them in particular research techniques and/or perspectives.

International mobility and potential for leadership

However, knowing where a candidate comes from is not really enough to confirm a potential “match”. Once the box of technical skills has been ticked, it is the ability of the

post-doc to grasp the “bigger picture” of the research project that really counts, and that makes some candidates stand out from the other post-docs. As this male professor explained:

“There are those who are technically good and who can learn just about any technique [...] and then there are those who are really good. The first lot, they don’t do a lot, they don’t have the ability to think by themselves; you have to tell them what to do [...] they might be technically good, but they’re not yet; they’re not the ones who are really going to drive the research forward and who pose the right questions; they don’t really understand what the next step might be” (Male Professor, STEM).

The main problem for the recruiters is that this potential to “drive the research forward” is not immediately visible in the CV or even past publications of the applicants. It is therefore necessary to place the post-doc *in situ*, in order to determine whether or not they have this particular commitment to the project, over and beyond any potential technical contribution they may be able to make. One solution to this difficulty is to offer early post-doc positions to candidates that have already proven their worth, particularly to ex-PhD students from the same lab’.

However, the University has quite strict rules about the possibility to continue from a funded PhD to a post-doc position in Lausanne. Once PhD students have reached the threshold of 5 years employment at the Unil, they can’t be re-employed until they have interrupted their contract for at least 12 months. This is obviously a measure designed to encourage recently qualified PhDs to widen their horizons and to gain experience in another research environment, preferably abroad, and usually with SNSF funding. This obligation also feeds into the time-management problems of the senior academic staff, because they need to plan their research funding applications to fit into the international mobility plans of their best / most appreciated ex-PhD students. Since the SNSF mobility grants and the main research funding programmes only have two calls a year, juggling with these different time frames can be quite complicated and can explain why it is sometimes impossible to wait for the “perfect match”. However, in most cases, STEM research projects involve several PhD and post-doc collaborators and can thus be organised around the international mobility experiences of one of the team members. As this professor explains:

“In practice, when we know the person and we know that s/he is really good, very able, and that s/he is willing to go abroad to build up more experience, then we are always

ready to take that person back, if it's really someone worthwhile, absolutely, yes" (Female Professor, STEM).

Teaching experience

There is unanimous agreement that teaching experience or ability is almost irrelevant for recruitment to post-doc positions in the STEM disciplines. As we have seen, most of the jobs advertised in the FBM Faculty in Lausanne are post-doc Assistantships and post-doc positions on SNSF-funded projects, which do not include any teaching duties, with the occasional exception of some research supervision or lab management. As this interviewee explains:

"In our department, post-docs don't do a lot of teaching, so that's not really a very important criteria for me [...] they might give a 1 hour lecture once in a while, but really, most of the courses at the University, they're taught by the professors, and even they have to fight to clock up enough hours themselves. I only have 24 hours a year to teach myself, so for the post-docs... no, that's really not important" (Female professor, STEM).

This is an interesting result, since it suggests that the content of the work given to post-docs is quite different from that expected of their hierarchical superiors and that it corresponds to quite specific criteria, which differ from those mentioned in the recruitment guidelines for tenure track positions.

Contribution to the wellbeing of the Faculty

According to our interviewees, post-docs are not expected to make any significant contribution to the wellbeing of the Faculty. Again, a consensus exists as to the lack of expectations in this domain:

"There isn't really any (cough); let's say that they might have to take part in the Open Days, for the school kids or other members of the public. So, there might be events like that where they're expected to take part, but that's really such a small, small part of..." (Male Professor, STEM).

The lack of attention paid to teaching abilities or to contributions made to the collective institutions of the Faculty suggests that some junior members of the STEM Faculty may experience difficulty in making the transition from what is required of them in order to fulfil the needs of a fixed-term post-doc position and the criteria by which they will be judged when applying for more stable, tenure track positions, later in their career.

Accounts of an actual/recent selection procedure in the STEM Faculty

One of the most surprising results of this part of the fieldwork in the FBM was to discover that many of the post-docs who join the research teams have not waited for a job offer to be published before contacting the directors of the Department or of a specific research team. Some of the more experienced post-docs are already in contact with the labs', as potential places of work in the case of a successful application to the SNSF for their independent research funding (Ambizione / Fellowship programmes). In this case, they have been pre-selected, according to procedures and criteria that are external to the Faculty. Likewise, many of the more junior post-docs also make informal contact with the Faculty, in order to signal their interest in any future research position. Thus, one of our interviewees explained that the recruitment procedures he has been involved in were mostly initiated by the candidates, rather than by the institution:

“As a rule, I don't really publish any job announcements; I don't announce openings. Usually, I receive applications directly. I have advertised jobs in the past, but I haven't done that for a long time now” (Male Professor, STEM).

Whether the candidates manifest their interest in the research being carried out “spontaneously” or in response to a job advertisement, the decision to hire them (or not) clearly depends on the opinion of the person in charge of the department / research centre. However, this individualized recruitment procedure is often masked by the fact that, after a pre-selection of some applications, potential recruits are invited to meet the whole team involved in the project. One of our male interviewees was quite frank about the decision-making process in his lab':

“When I bring in people who are interested in working here, they always come for a visit beforehand. They are invited to present their previous research at a seminar and they have the opportunity to chat with the lab' members, including myself; and so I have the opportunity to chat with them too. So, afterwards, I can see what the members of the lab' have thought about the candidates, to get their feedback [...] Of course, my collaborators are really nice people, they tend to like just about anyone, they're a bit shy, they wouldn't dare tell me if they thought that one of the candidates was a complete disaster [laughs], so their feedback is usually positive. So, I talk about it with them, but it goes without saying that I have my own opinion and so, I kind of try to check it out, to ask some questions to see how people react. Of course, when it comes to it, the decision is mine, of course” (Male Professor, STEM).

Gender issues in the STEM Faculty

When asked about the importance of gender in recruitment procedures, most of the FBM interviewees were eager to dispel any idea that the selection procedures could be “biased” in any way. This account is quite typical of the reactions:

“No, the person’s gender doesn’t matter at all. I don’t pay any attention to their gender, to their nationality, to their sexual preferences. Let me tell you, I can list all the people that I have – their colour, of course – I’ve had just about everything, I still have a bit of everything. So really, that doesn’t have any impact. [...] For the most recent recruitment, it’s true that I had an application for a woman and I didn’t offer her the job, but there were also men who didn’t get offered the job either” (Male Professor, STEM).

There was also a tendency for the interviewees to over-estimate the number of women in positions of responsibility within the Faculty, or their department in particular. Thus, for example, a female professor reversed the direction of the “gender problem”, by focussing on her own research group, rather than discussing the position of women in the whole of the Faculty:

“In my centre, women are in a majority; I’d say we are probably 70% women and fewer men. So really, gender isn’t a criterion for me, because if it was, from time to time I would really have to offer a job to a man [laughs]” (Female Professor, STEM).

Despite the systematic denial of any gender discrimination in their selection criteria and recruitment practices, a number of interviewees nevertheless expressed strong opinions about the problems posed to research activities by *people* asking to work on a part-time basis. In a country with one of the highest part-time activity rates for mothers (just behind the Netherlands), the gender-neutral designation of part-timers is quite unnecessary. In some cases, the fact that the request for part-time work has come from women is made explicit, as in the following example, from a Head of department who explains why he is not very happy at the idea of granting a young mother in his lab’ the opportunity to work part-time (they have requested a four-day week, or 80% of a full-time position):

“I know full well that her productivity rate will be reduced by at least 50%. In a competitive international research context, that’s not a very good thing. I don’t really like this idea of a percentage reduction, because it just doesn’t fit in with the way work is organised [...] I mean, people are here, they organise their experiments, and the kind of experiments we do here, they last 3 days, 3 or 4 days. Something like that, once you’ve

started, you just have to see it through. So that means that if we have someone who stops work on a Thursday, with an experiment that lasts 3 days; she's going to start work normally on the Monday, and then after Wednesday, she's not going to be able to do anything else, even if she's paid until Thursday evening!" (Male Professor, STEM).

This quotation perfectly illustrates the extended work-time culture that would appear to dominate the STEM Faculty. Despite strongly refuting any hint of gender discrimination, there is a clear sense that FBM professors believe that the only possible condition for women's progression through the academic hierarchy is for them to adopt the employment practices that have historically been the prerogative of (married) men.

The Faculty of Social and Political Sciences (SSP)

Selection criteria for interviews and focus group in the SHS Faculty

As for the FBM fieldwork, we Emailed a selection of colleagues from the SSP Faculty, immediately stating that we were looking for contacts with experiences in recruitment procedures for Maître Assistantships, postdoc Assistants, SNSF-funded research postdocs, or senior researchers). In this first phase, we attempted to select people at both Senior Lectureship (MER) and professorial level, and from each of the disciplinary domains. Some MER declined our invitation, since they had never participated in hiring procedures of this kind. This was also the case for one of the professors we later contacted for the focus group. During interviews for WP4-WP6, a male tenure track Assistant Professor told us:

"You know, there are committees and committees. At the moment, I'm involved in committees that are not so important to our faculty, whereas appointment Committees, especially for professors, and things like the Faculty Planning Committee, they're full of tenured Professors. As a PAST PTC, you're not invited to join them. Important decisions are taken by other kinds of people" (Male Assistant Professor, SHS).

In total, we interviewed 3 men and 2 women from the SSP Faculty: 2 MER, 1 tenure-track Associate Professor and 2 Full professors. The SHS focus group was composed of 4 men and 2 women: 1 Associate professor and 5 full professors (from a wide range of disciplinary backgrounds), including people who had occupied an executive position, as vice dean or dean.

Criteria mentioned in the SHS Faculty

It was rather difficult for some of our interlocutors to speak about the abstract criteria, as they were considered to vary considerably, even for the small range of positions we were investigating. One female MER said that it was impossible to generalise about the criteria. Other interviewees remarked that:

“the criteria are always the same, it’s rather that you’re going to have different expectations according to the hierarchical status of the position being advertised (Male Professor, SHS). Another professor disagreed with that suggestions, stating that: “the higher up the academic hierarchy you are, the criteria get more abstract and less closely related to the job description; or the job description just becomes less precise” (Male Professor, SHS).

Nevertheless, the majority of our interviewees were able to cite the three criteria they considered to be the most important in the Social Sciences, and to put them into the following order: 1) Scientific record (i.e. research and publications); 2) Teaching Experience and 3) Willingness to make a contribution to the life of the Faculty. As one MER interviewee said:

“I think that I would mention the scientific record, in terms of research and publications; secondly, teaching and, thirdly, also some consideration of the institutional integration; well, that’s quite a standard list. But I do think that the most important criterion has to be the persons’ Scientific record, but that should be evaluated according to the type of teaching load” (Male MER, SHS).

It is interesting to note that all our interviewees mention the formal criteria that are mentioned in the tenure track guidelines of the SSP Faculty (see above). However, contrary to the Directives, they spontaneously establish a hierarchy between the three dimensions of academic activities. As already noted in previous research carried out on the SSP Faculty (Fassa *et al.*, 2012), several of our interviewees noted a historical shift towards the requirement of scientific publications, even for very early-career stage job opportunities:

“The criteria have evolved a lot. I’m into the 32nd year of my career, and I can confirm that the criteria have evolved. In the past [in order to apply for a post-doc position], you just had to have defended your thesis; that’s no longer the case today” (Female Professor, SHS).

Publications and research funding

Our interviewees all agreed that, for early post doc positions, the most important criteria would be: 1) the quality of the PhD manuscript and 2) the number and quality of other publications. For access to tenure track positions, candidates would also have to demonstrate their ability to obtain competitive, external research funding. Although most people insisted on the different types of expectations that each disciplinary field would prefer, there was actually quite a strong consensus as to the “most valued” type of publication:

“An international peer-reviewed journal. Hang on, when I say ‘International’, I don’t necessarily mean that it has to be in English. I mean, ‘international’ in the sense that the journal has an Editorial Board, a distribution network that it can be found in different libraries, that it can be ordered and purchased easily. I mean, not the kind of publication that can only be found on the second to last shelf of the very beautiful, but obscure institution [...], where even if you write something absolutely brilliant, no-one will ever get to read it” (Male Professor, SHS).

There was also agreement that single authored monographs, edited volumes and even book chapters could be considered to meet the “potential for international dissemination” criterion.

Another point on which our interviewees shared similar opinions concerned the need to look at the content of the applicants’ publications, and not just to count their number or to measure their H-index:

“I don’t just look at the CV, I always read at least two or three publications, to check them out, because, even with journals that have a high index, you can have some nasty surprises. So, with colleagues, we always check the content of some of the publications; in any case, that’s how we do things here” (Male Professor, SHS).

A request for candidates to supply an example of their written / published work would seem to be a systematic practise in the Faculty, even for access to funded PhD positions (students send their MA dissertations).

H-index or impact factors were never mentioned as important selection criteria for post-doc positions in the Faculty. There was even agreement that the publication practices of the different disciplines represented in the Faculty were so different that any consideration of bibliometric indicators would only serve to give an unfair advantage to those applicants whose research methods were closest to those of the “hard sciences”

(e.g. experimental psychologists), to the detriment of qualitative sociologists or historians.

Teaching experience

As in the STEM interviews, teaching experience was only considered important for recruitment to tenure track post-doc positions. For most of the post-doc SNSF research jobs, almost no attention is paid to the applicants' teaching experience:

“it might be nice if the person has already done a bit of teaching, but that's not a priority, especially if they're applying for a research positions” (Female MER, SHS).

However, for applicants who have completed their PhD in Lausanne (priori to their obligatory 12 months international mobility), the teaching evaluation forms are sometimes taken as an indication of the candidates' relational skills.

Past experience and international mobility

As in the STEM Faculty, the place where the PhD was defended, along with the name of the supervisor, are also taken as reliable indications about the “qualities” of post-doc candidates in the social sciences. As one interviewee stated:

“You must at least have heard of the PhD supervisor; that's really important for the candidate” (Female Professor, SHS).

Put in another way, the position of the supervisor and the PhD institution in the academic environment of the recruiting Board members is vitally important, mainly because these factors act as “reassurance” about the ability of the candidate:

“Obviously, if you've got someone from a prestigious Parisian institution, there's a strong chance they'll end up on the short-list, just because they inspire more confidence. It's better to have done your PhD under the supervision of [name of female prof in Paris], than with some obscure person from the provinces. Unfortunately, it's terrible to say things like that, but it's true (Female MER, SHS).

The “insurance policy” offered by the international recognition / reputation of the PhD supervisor obviously reduces the recruitment opportunity for candidates who originate from outside the circles of interaction and personal contact. Students from developing countries are placed at a particular disadvantage. *A contrario*, one of the most obvious strategies for reducing the uncertainties associated with the internationalisation of academic careers is to offer post-doc opportunities to candidates with whom there has

been previous (satisfactory) collaboration, and particularly to one's own ex-PhD students. The rules in the SSP Faculty are identical to those mentioned earlier in FBM. A student who has been employed for 60 months (5 years) to do a doctorate by the University can't be offered a new academic contract until they have clocked up a 12-month break in employment, preferably abroad. The ideal recruitment solution is thus to help certain PhD students to get an SNSF Mobility grant immediately after their PhD defence, then to apply for research funding, including a post-doc position, in time for the ex-PhD to be entitled to return to employment at the University.

This practice is obviously quite widespread in both our Faculties. In the Social sciences, it is presented as being potentially beneficial to the early-career stage post-docs, and to their supervisors:

"I recruited [name of female MA], it was much easier, because she was one of my PhD students, so I know her abilities, I know that she's a worker, I know that she's got staying power [...] I recruited her principally on the basis of the knowledge I have about her; her abilities, her interests, obviously the fact that she was interested in this position, and on the basis of what I believe she's capable of doing in the course of her career, if we help her and if she's well supervised; if we give her an idea of the criteria and the tricks of the trade" (Female Professor, SHS).

So, although international mobility is frequently mentioned as an important criterion for access to post-doc positions, this is probably at least in part due to the fact that it is an institutional obligation for all candidates who received their PhDs from Lausanne University to spend at least 1 year abroad, before they can apply for a post-doc position at their home institution. Another consideration relates to exactly what the candidates have achieved during their time in foreign institutions. As one interviewee explained:

"The fact that someone has spent 1 month or 5 years abroad doesn't really matter; I'd be personally more interested in someone who had spent just 1 month at [international research centre], who manages to use that time to draft two quality articles, with two specialists in the field, and to get them published in a prestigious journal; that's perfect for me. But, if he spends 5 years away and doesn't publish anything worthwhile during that time, then it's just a waste of time" (Male Professor, SHS).

A similar circumspect attitude towards the automatic advantages of international mobility (an institutional requirement, which are interviewees are obviously judging as they speak) is expressed by another interviewee:

“I have quite a multidisciplinary background, so I think of mobility in the sense of being able to shift from one research domain to another. It doesn’t necessarily mean moving across national boundaries, because there are some people who go abroad for a year, wherever that might be, and they just end up doing the same old things: As far as I’m concerned, that’s not a very constructive experience” (Female Professor, SHS).

At several times during the interviews, there were signs of quite heated debates as to the idea of recruiting so-called “local” candidates to early-career positions, despite the fact that the institution had received (sometimes “hundreds of”) applications from many different countries. As this ex-Dean explained:

“We had this exceptional recruitment opportunity; a new project which enables us to create 4 tenure-track positions in the Faculty. We received applications from all over Europe and, in the end we selected three people, out of the four, who were local candidates. Of course, some people were outraged and denounced some kind of fraud. Personally, I have no problem with that aspect of the procedure, because what did that mean? Firstly, that they were local candidates, of course, but that in terms of their abilities, they corresponded exactly to all the formal ability criteria. Secondly, it just so happened that we already knew them and so we could tell that they were probably also going to fit... meet our criteria for integration into the institution. So, quite frankly, rather than taking the risk of recruiting someone who doesn’t speak French very well, where we not exactly sure what they’ve done beforehand...” (Male Professor, SHS).

In reaction to the generally perceived institutional promotion of international mobility, a number of our SHS interviewees also insisted on the material difficulties experienced in attracting foreign post-docs to Switzerland, particularly when the jobs on offer were of a limited duration (under 2 years) or were not full-time. In relation to gender equality, it was often argued that the institution could not expect individuals to move themselves and their families, sometimes across the world, often across Europe, under such precarious employment circumstances.

Contribution to the wellbeing the Faculty

Contrary to the interviews conducted in the STEM Faculty, our SHS interviewees frequently insisted on the importance of recruiting future colleagues (even on short-term contracts) who were willing to take their share of institutional responsibilities and who would make a positive contribution to the general wellbeing of the Faculty. The following account, where high levels of performance with regard to H-index publication

criteria are opposed to institutional integration criteria, is indicative of this form of argument and justification:

“I have absolutely no interest in recruiting someone with a super impact factor, if I never get to see him, if he doesn’t look after his students properly, if he doesn’t get things done and, what’s more, if he is always grumpy, because he’s got a personality problem. No, no. There are clear Directives at the University, which state that the person we select must really be the most adapted to the position and to the needs we have, and the ideal person doesn’t have to be a future Nobel prize winner, that we would be waiting for with open arms, but who couldn’t actually do the job properly. That’s why we should be so careful when writing the job descriptions; because that’s really the document we’re always going to refer back to. You know, you can say, yes, we’ve got 10 good candidates, with an excellent impact factor, or whatever else, but some of these people obviously won’t be able to do what we have said that we wanted them to do, in the job description. So, we shouldn’t recruit those candidates. It’s not that they’re not good candidates at all; it’s just that they don’t correspond to our requirements” (Female Professor, SHS).

These accounts of what “counts” during the recruitment process can obviously not be isolated from more general preoccupations, particularly within the social sciences, with perceived evolutions towards those recruitment criteria that are supposed to improve the position of academic institutions in different “ranking” exercises (for example, the reference to a potential Nobel prize candidate in the previous quite clearly refers to the Shanghai international classification system).

Likewise, in the local context, references to the relative importance of international mobility in academic careers directly reflect the recent generalization of what was previously seen as a recommendation, rather than a strict rule, and which makes it impossible for PhD supervisors to recruit their ex-doctoral students as post-docs, immediately after their viva.

These issues are central to the accounts of recent selection procedures that we were able to collect in the SHS Faculty.

Accounts of an actual/recent selection procedure in the SHS Faculty

In the SSP Faculty, there is an overriding concern with the fact that the interests of the person who is seeking to recruit an early-career stage post-doc may not be entirely congruent with the interests of the candidates themselves. More precisely, as seen earlier, there is an explicit reference to the fact that the post-doc job should provide an

opportunity for the candidate to improve their chances of moving on to a more stable and durable academic position in the future. There is often the suggestion of a potential tension or contradiction between the characteristics of a candidate who will be most able to advance up the academic hierarchy and the characteristics that would be the most useful to the person who is hiring them. Implicit references can be found in the interviews (and focus group) to a potential “post-doc trap” that may keep very valuable young researchers in a succession of fixed-term positions, where they meet all the requirements of their jobs and expectations of their bosses, but where they fail to accumulate the resources needed to move on to more permanent and prestigious academic positions. This “post-doc trap” has indeed been identified as a particular risk for female post-docs in the Swiss context (Studer, 2012).

When asked to explain the considerations that had led to the decision to recruit a post-doc for an SNSF-funded 3 year research project, an MER explained:

“Well, we weren’t going to give the job to someone who had done her thesis 20 years ago, even if she had worked on the same topic [...] It’s perfectly true, in all objectivity, we had better CVs [than the person we chose], quite objectively [...]. But we weren’t going to give the job to someone who was looking for their 10th post-doc position in a row” (Female MER, SHS).

At the same time, at another point in the interview, this same MER insists on the importance of hiring someone with enough experience to be immediately “operational”:

“The post-doc must be able to work autonomously straight away, otherwise you just can’t manage” (Female MER, SHS).

Implicitly, this tension between experience and as yet untapped potential refers to the implicit question of what a post-doc position should enable the young researcher to achieve. As other interviewees explained, the contribution of the person to the project or institution is not (should not be) the only consideration. What the post-doc period will enable the candidates to achieve is also important to analyse:

“Recruiting a post-doc, it’s a way of giving someone who has just completed their PhD to make this achievement fruitful, to build up a good research record, a good CV” (Female MER, SHS).

“I want to supervise people who have the prospect of a successful academic career once they move on” (Male Professor, SHS)

“You can’t really recruit someone without thinking about the future career of that person, without doing a kind of projection 10 years ahead, in some kind of way, whereas we all know that the position is usually much more limited in duration” (Male Professor, SHS)

“[When you recruit a post-doc] you actually place a bet on the person’s potential to develop” (Female Professor, SHS).

When asked to talk explicitly about some of the recent post-doc recruitment procedures they had personally been involved in, almost all the interviewees referred to the University and SSP Faculty guidelines. Although most of them believe that these documents are very useful in establishing a common set of selection criteria and of ensuring that the candidates are treated fairly, they also insist on the fact that, once a short-list of equally-qualified candidates has been established on the basis of these “objective” criteria, more subjective considerations inevitably intervene in the final decision:

“Of course, there are the objective criteria, and then it’s more pffffff, I can’t really say, it’s more a question of a subjective appreciation of the interview, the potential you perceive, the way you’re inspired (or not) by the project” (Male Professor, SHS).

“I’m always a bit uncomfortable when people start talking about the candidates” personality or things like that. You know, things like: ‘I wouldn’t want to go on holiday with that one’, that sort of thing. I really don’t believe that that kind of consideration should enter into things. But, of course, implicitly, those kinds of things do enter into things, although it’s always difficult to know how much they weigh on the final decision” (Male Professor, SHS).

Although many interviewees recognised that the formal criteria were so numerous that they could never be applied in a “strictly scientific” manner, there was nevertheless a strong consensus around the idea that the vast majority of recruitment procedures were not “totally arbitrary”. As one interviewee explained:

“I must have been on tens of recruitment Boards now, and I can honestly say that, even if we sometimes have doubts about who should be 1st, or 2nd, or 3rd, I can honestly say that in 95% of cases, the result is not arbitrary. The problem isn’t that we’ve made the wrong decision; the problem is that we could easily have recruited three, four, five, sometimes even six of the best candidates; they would have all been suited to the job” (Male Professor, SHS).

So, it is amongst these short-listed candidates, who all “fit” the objective recruitment criteria, that the final selection takes place. It is precisely at this point in the procedure that all our interviewees recognise that more “subjective” or “irrational” considerations come into play. Some of them even mention that this phase is more or less favourable to female candidates.

Gender issues in the SHS Faculty

Responses to questions about the role of gender in the recruitment processes inspired somewhat less defensive reactions in the SSP Faculty than in the FBM. Most interviewees referred to the recent increase in women’s share of academic positions within the Faculty over the past years, although they also recognised that “more could be done” (either by women themselves, or by the institution). Most of the male and female interviewees were quite well informed about the existing equal opportunity measures, although some were critical of their potentially misleading influence on early-career post-docs. Most of the interviewees either had some expertise in gender issues or had followed a “gender awareness” internal training courses in quite recent years. Probably as a result of the relatively strong “equality culture” in the Faculty some of the interviewees stressed that gender equality objectives would never be reached if there was no attempt to modify men’s practices and to promote a more “de-gendered” model of professional and family life:

“You also need to encourage, at a wider social level, to encourage men to invest in other spheres than just their profession, so that they leave a bit more space for the women at work; you need to give more value to men’s role in the family. The equal opportunity measures are too focussed on the women, they don’t bother about the men; but you really need to bring about change for men and women. Men need to be able to make a claim on other kinds of success, in their family lives, for example” (Male Professor, SHS).

There was also mention of the need to encourage women to be more pro-active in claiming equality for themselves:

“I’m a bit doubtful about these equality measures, because women are not under threat of extinction, nor are we a minority in the human race. So, I really believe that we should get ourselves organised, rather than just to keep asking for special treatment” (Female Professor, SHS).

This view was partly shared by another female Professor, who pointed out the potentially negative effects of some of the mentoring programmes offered to early career stage post-docs:

“I’ve often said to the Equality Office people that all this stress on networking gets on my nerves; it’s too vague. I mean, you can spend a hell of a lot of time ‘networking’, and all that time you spend at drinks evenings, you’re not using it to write your articles [laugh], so that’s not really what they need to hear at that point in their careers” (Female Professor, SHS).

However, despite their willingness to engage in discussions about gender discrimination, the opinions of the SSP interviewees are not that far removed from those of their colleagues in the STEM disciplines. Concerns about the effects of part-time employment are similar to those expressed in the FBM Faculty, although here they are directed more at the women themselves, and less focussed on the problems that part-time work poses for the institution. For example, this female professor says:

“it’s OK to tell people that they can work part-time when they have kids, but that’s a sure way of blighting women’s career prospects” (Female Professor, SHS).

Likewise, whereas concern is often expressed for the work-life balance of female post-docs with young children, their male counterparts are never even mentioned. Having a child and/or child-care responsibilities tends to be seen as a “handicap” for women and women alone, even when the senior mentors are sensitive to the associated risks:

“I always check whether or not the female candidates have children. Because you know full well that a child will create a certain number of problems, additional difficulties in terms of publications, in the way you accompany the person on her career path, so yes, I always take that into account” (Male Professor, SHS).

By wanting to appear “attentive” and “concerned” by the plight of their female junior collaborators,²¹ the SHS interviewees obviously run the risk of reproducing and reinforcing some typical gender stereotypes. Contrary to their FBM colleagues, they seem to be at least partially aware of such risks. They often start their remarks with sentences like:

“I’ll probably look like a horrible macho by saying this” (Male Professor, SHS).

²¹ In a context where some members of the GARCIA team are well-known for their previous research on gendered academic careers.

Their subsequent comments refer to women's lack of "fighting spirit" and willingness to engage in the highly competitive academic environment:

"I have to say that I've sometimes seen that with the female applicants. Generally speaking, the guys, they're ready for... I mean, you sense immediately that they're ready to work a 20-hour day [laugh], to scrub the floor, if you ask them to, and it's often a question of internalised stereotypes. Usually, the women, they're more [sigh] careful, reserved (Male Professor, SHS).

Comparing actual recruitment practices in the STEM and SSH Faculties

In conclusion to this study of actual recruitment practices in the two Faculties, a number of comparisons can be drawn.

Firstly, in both Faculties, there is a relatively clear distinction drawn between the criteria that are considered most important, according to the type of post-doc position on offer.

On the one hand, most of our interviewees refer to the criteria for fixed-term, project-related post-doc positions, for which they believe that it is important to recruit people who are: 1) technically / methodologically competent; 2) reliable; 3) immediately available for hire and 4) easy to get along with. For these positions, the place where the PhD was defended and the recommendation of a trustworthy colleague are considered to be sufficient guarantees of achieving a "good match". Teaching experience, access to research funding, and personal publication record appear as somewhat secondary or even irrelevant criteria here.

On the other hand, some of our interviewees focus more on recruitment procedures leading to tenure track post-doc positions (MA > MER or PAST PTC > PAS or PO), for which the criteria appear to be slightly different. In this case, the "irrelevant" criteria for access to the previous type of post-doc positions suddenly become far more important, as does the potential of the candidate to contribute to the general wellbeing of the Faculty (i.e. take on administrative and pastoral duties).

Although it is rather difficult to draw clear conclusions from the comparison of the actual practices in the two Faculties, it would appear that at least some of their differences we observed can be explained by the fact that they effectively do not recruit post-doc of the same type in equal proportions.

For example, FMB interviewees are more likely to talk about the criteria for recruitment to project-related post-doc jobs. We would suggest that this is because almost all the post-docs present in this Faculty occupy non-tenure track positions of this kind. In

comparison, almost half the post-doc positions advertised in the SSP Faculty were of the MA and PAST PTC type. It is therefore quite logically that our interviewees more frequently mentioned the criteria they thought appropriate to select candidates to this type of post-doc positions.

Contrary to initial impressions, we would suggest that the actual recruitment practices to each of these types of post-doc positions are surprisingly similar in the two Faculties. However, since the share of each of these types of post-docs is not comparable, this creates an illusion of difference between the disciplinary fields.

5.4. Conclusion

To sum up this preliminary study, we can suggest a certain number of tentative conclusions.

Firstly, not all the (quite numerous) post-doc positions in the Swiss academic system automatically lead to those positions associated with a tenure track opportunity, or a stable academic career. A lot of the academic research (and a smaller proportion of teaching) currently taking place in Switzerland is funded externally, on the basis of competitive research procedures. This implies that only a small proportion of the male and female post-docs who contribute to these externally funded research projects, through a succession of fixed-term, sometimes part-time, post-doc positions, will ever gain access to a stable academic career.

Secondly, in the face of increased (international) competition for tenure track positions, the Unil has significantly increased the pressure on its' Faculties to formalise their selection procedures and to promote gender equality in recruitment. Although there is rhetorical respect for disciplinary specificities in the choice of indicators, the formal criteria for access to tenure track positions appear to be very similar across the SHS and STEM Faculties. They are available to all members of the academic community and are presented regularly to graduate students at all stages of their PhD completion (and more explicitly to women, through a number of highly visible mentoring schemes and dedicated funding programmes). To a certain extent, there is a shared feeling the "everyone knows what you have to do to continue working in the academy after a PhD". What's more, these requirements are relatively similar across the Faculties and disciplines.

Thirdly, although there is almost no explicit reference to “excellence” in any of the official documents studied (either at HR or Faculty level), they nevertheless provide a description of the idealised academic profile, which is thought to be well suited to an increasingly international and competitive environment. This ideal-type figure could be described as the **well-rounded academic**, who is expected to “perform” equally well in research (by attracting competitive external funding - notably to keep the post-docs in employment -, and publishing in the top international, peer-reviewed journals), in teaching (by attracting high quality graduate students), and in maintaining high levels of “organisational wellbeing” (particularly by taking on administrative duties). In addition, this (imaginary) figure of academic equilibrium should know how to set aside time for non-academic activities (leisure, sport, culture, even family-life...). In both Faculties, this ideal figure is symbolically opposed to a number of negative images, most of which centre on the “one-dimensional professor”, who neglects his (not usually her) teaching and management duties to focus exclusively on his or her “research output” (or H-index). Finally, the discourse of “excellence” appears to take on quite negative connotations in both the SHS and STEM Faculties. More precisely, it is a critical evaluation of the criteria on which excellence could or should be judged that is shared by our interviewees. This enables them to justify the introduction of “subjective” selection criteria into the early-career selection procedures and to reject the sole use of bibliometric or financial performance measures. These indicators are not presented as unimportant. In practice, they are often used to reach a “short list” of prospective candidates and are presented as perfectly legitimate tools at this stage of the selection process. It is after this first “sifting” exercise that they become redundant and that more “qualitative” indicators are sought.

At this stage of our research, it is difficult to determine the gendered consequences of the emergence of the figure of the **well-rounded academic** in the Swiss context. We know from experience that the use of quantifiable performance indicators and the adoption of more formalised recruitment procedures are usually favourable to under-represented groups, including women. At the same time, previous research has suggested that a strong focus on research productivity indicators and the promotion of geographical mobility through international career paths are not conducive to women’s academic careers. In our case study, it could be that attempts to broaden the criteria on which post-doc candidates are judged, beyond metric research performance indicators, will prove to be more favourable to women applicants. On the other hand, if the critical

attitude we have identified towards existing indicators of “academic excellence” simply leads to a blurring of recruitment criteria and to the legitimisation of “subjective impressions” as to who would (or would not) be a “good match”, female candidates may not necessarily benefit from this potential shift in the dominant academic ethos.

These are questions we hope to explore further with the data collected for the GARCIA project.

References

Canton de Vaud. Loi sur le personnel de l'Etat de Vaud (RLPers-VD), 2001. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

http://www.google.ch/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=2&ved=OCCMQFjAB&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.vd.ch%2Ffileadmin%2Fuser_upload%2Forganisation%2Fdfin%2Fspev%2Ffichiers_pdf%2Flois%2FLPers.pdf&ei= bmAVJeIH6a4ygODr4AI&usg=AFQjCNEJvbSgHtD9IIUut6L_TDI0ZriXw&bvm=bv.80642063,d.bGQ

CRUS (Council of the Rectors of Swiss Universities). *Swiss Federal Equal Opportunity in Universities Programme*, 2012. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

<http://www.crus.ch/information-programmes/egalite-des-chances-etudes-genre-programme-cus-p-4/programme-federal-egalite-des-chances-2000-20122013.html?L=1http://www.crus.ch/information-programme/programme-cus-p-4-equal-opportunity-gender-studies/federal-programme-equal-opportunity-2000-20122013.html?L=2>

Décanat FBM (Faculté de biologie et de médecine – Université de Lausanne), 2008. Directive concernant le statut des maîtres assistants et la procédure de stabilisation des maîtres assistants en maîtres d'enseignement et de recherche au sein de la Section des sciences fondamentales. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

<http://www.unil.ch/files/live//sites/fbm/files/shared/mprimus/Directive MA et stabilisation MA en MER.pdf>

Décanat FBM (Faculté de biologie et de médecine – Université de Lausanne), 2014. Mesure de soutien pour une chercheuse ou un chercheur lors d'un congé familial. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

http://www.google.ch/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0CB0QFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.unil.ch%2Ffbm%2Ffiles%2Flive%2Fsites%2Ffbm%2Ffiles%2Fshared%2Fegalite%2Fbrochure_parents_egalite_interactif.pdf&ei=lruAVMPRDoPmyQPMkIKACA&usg=AFQjCNESkqsCTDFwlQy8CRaSp3JZkPxPAw&bvm=bv.80642063,d.bGQ

Décanat FBM (Faculté de biologie et de médecine – Université de Lausanne), Plan d'action « AGIR pour l'égalité » de la Faculté de biologie et de médecine de l'Université de Lausanne dans le cadre de la Vision 50/50 de la Direction de l'UNIL, 2013. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

http://www.unil.ch/egalite/files/live/sites/egalite/files/shared/Promouvoir_Egalite/Vision_5050/PlanAction_AGIR_EGALITE_FBM_20130607.pdf

Décanat SSP (Faculté des sciences sociales et politiques – Université de Lausanne), 2007. Directive du Décanat SSP 1.5. Procédure de stabilisation de MA à MER. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

http://www.google.ch/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CB8QFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.unil.ch%2Fssp%2Ffiles%2Flive%2Fsites%2Fssp%2Ffiles%2Fshared%2Freglements%2Fdirectives%2F1_5_Stabilisation_MA_MER_VF.pdf&ei=XraAVJPJMcXqyOO5tYHQCg&usg=AFQjCNEDVHHNL27r4ussqZESjhrP8fccVA&bvm=bv.80642063,d.bGQ

Direction UNIL. Directive de la Direction 0.2. Promotion de l'égalité à l'Université de Lausanne, 2006. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

http://www.google.ch/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CB8QFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.unil.ch%2Finterne%2Ffiles%2Flive%2Fsites%2Finterne%2Ffiles%2Ftextes_leg%2FO_aff_gen%2Fdir0_2_promotion_egalite.pdf&ei=bLCAVLHmDojNygOIg4GgCQ&usg=AFQjCNH2eGuDOQ6yZ9_z2Fji91tmKRsydA&bvm=bv.80642063,d.bGQ

Direction UNIL. Directive de la Direction 0.4. Politique de prévention des atteintes à la personnalité dans les relations de travail et d'études au sein de l'UNIL, 2007. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

http://www.unil.ch/interne/files/live/sites/interne/files/textes_leg/O_aff_gen/dir0_4_mediation_politique_prevention.pdf

Direction UNIL. Directive de la Direction 1.1. Définition des fonctions du corps enseignant et taux d'activité, 2005. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

[http://www.unil.ch/interne/files/live/sites/interne/files/textes leg/1_ress_hum/dir1_1_definition_fonction_taux_act2.pdf](http://www.unil.ch/interne/files/live/sites/interne/files/textes_leg/1_ress_hum/dir1_1_definition_fonction_taux_act2.pdf)

Direction UNIL. Directive de la Direction 1.3. Procédure d'engagement du corps professoral, 2005. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

[http://www.google.ch/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CB0QFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.unil.ch%2Finterne%2Ffiles%2Flive%2Fsites%2Finterne%2Ffiles%2Ftextes leg%2F1_ress_hum%2Fdir1_3_procedure_engage_crps_prof4.pdf&ei=rLCAVLKYPIGgyAObl4GYDQ&usg=AFQjCNETJ-cLEy8FWZK9onFW4_69K5gGw&bvm=bv.80642063,d.bGQ](http://www.google.ch/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CB0QFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.unil.ch%2Finterne%2Ffiles%2Flive%2Fsites%2Finterne%2Ffiles%2Ftextes_leg%2F1_ress_hum%2Fdir1_3_procedure_engage_crps_prof4.pdf&ei=rLCAVLKYPIGgyAObl4GYDQ&usg=AFQjCNETJ-cLEy8FWZK9onFW4_69K5gGw&bvm=bv.80642063,d.bGQ)

Direction UNIL. Directive de la Direction 1.4. Pré-titularisation conditionnelle (tenure track): procédure d'évaluation, 2005. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

[http://www.google.ch/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CB0QFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.unil.ch%2Finterne%2Ffiles%2Flive%2Fsites%2Finterne%2Ffiles%2Ftextes leg%2F1_ress_hum%2Fdir1_4_pretitularisation_conditionnelle1.pdf&ei=HrOAVjBBcHOygOS2ICwCw&usg=AFQjCNEj3C7AdN4NnvXJZq33CdsbZfmSCA](http://www.google.ch/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CB0QFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.unil.ch%2Finterne%2Ffiles%2Flive%2Fsites%2Finterne%2Ffiles%2Ftextes_leg%2F1_ress_hum%2Fdir1_4_pretitularisation_conditionnelle1.pdf&ei=HrOAVjBBcHOygOS2ICwCw&usg=AFQjCNEj3C7AdN4NnvXJZq33CdsbZfmSCA)

Direction UNIL. Directive de la Direction 1.6. Maîtres assistants: Procédure d'engagement, durée du mandat et procédure de stabilisation, 2005. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

[http://www.unil.ch/interne/files/live/sites/interne/files/textes leg/1_ress_hum/dir1_6_MA_proc_engag_dure_stab2.pdf](http://www.unil.ch/interne/files/live/sites/interne/files/textes_leg/1_ress_hum/dir1_6_MA_proc_engag_dure_stab2.pdf)

Direction UNIL. Directive de la Direction 1.32. Procédure d'engagement des Professeurs assistants boursiers du FNS, 2008. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

[http://www.unil.ch/interne/files/live/sites/interne/files/textes leg/1_ress_hum/dir1_32_prof_boursier_FNS.pdf](http://www.unil.ch/interne/files/live/sites/interne/files/textes_leg/1_ress_hum/dir1_32_prof_boursier_FNS.pdf)

Direction UNIL. Directive de la Direction 1.34. Procédure d'engagement des assistants diplômés et des premiers assistants, 2011. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

<http://www.google.ch/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0CB0QFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.unil.ch%2Finterne%2Ffiles%2Flive%2Fsites%2Finterne%2Ffiles>

[%2Ftextes leg%2F1 ress hum %2Fdir1_34 engagement assist.pdf&ei=YbSAVIPHNeboywOgx4CgCA&usg=AFQjCNH8P dxkGWnV00DdaIfaC59JVm38aQ](#)

Direction UNIL-BEC (Bureau de l'égalité). Plan d'action de l'Université de Lausanne pour l'égalité entre femmes et hommes 2013-2016 : Programme CUS «Egalité des chances» 2013 – 2016, 2012. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

<http://www.unil.ch/egalite/home/menuintst/promotion-de-legalite/plan-daction-pour-legalite.html>

Direction UNIL-CHUV. (Université de Lausanne – Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois), 2014. Directive du conseil de direction UNIL-CHUV sur la politique de promotion. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

<https://www.google.ch/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=OCB0QFjAA&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.unil.ch%2Ffbm%2Ffiles%2Flive%2Fsites%2Ffbm%2Ffiles%2Fshared%2Fakarlen%2FCCP%2F Directive %2520CDir politique promotion Vz %25255BADOPTEE CDIR 09.10.14%25255D.pdf&ei=fbqAVKLMCqe9ygODs4LoDA&usg=AFQjCNFWjxOAPev3F7WBRsz5mmfzlWu4pQ&bvm=bv.80642063.d.bGQ>

FASSA, Farinaz, Sabine KRADOLFER and Sophie PAROZ, 2012. *Enquête au royaume de Matilda. La relève académique à l'Université de Lausanne*. Lausanne : LIVES Working Papers n°11.

Office fédéral de la statistique (OFS), 2011. *Education et science: Personnel des hautes écoles universitaires 2011*. Neuchâtel : OFS.

Le Feuvre, Nicky, 2009, « Exploring Women's Academic Careers in Cross-National Perspective: Lessons for Equal Opportunity Policies », *Equal Opportunities International*, Vol 28 n°1: 9-23.

Le Feuvre, Nicky and Emmanuelle Latour, 2007, « Understanding Women's Academic Careers in France », in R. Siemienka et A. Zimmer (eds.) *Gendered Career Trajectories in Academia in Cross-National Perspective*, Varsovie, Scholar: 43-74.

SNSF (Swiss National Science Foundation), 2008. Règlement relatif à l'octroi de subsides Professeurs boursiers FNS. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

www.snf.ch/SiteCollectionDocuments/fp_reglement_f.pdf

Studer, Matthias, 2012, *Etude des inégalités de genre en début de carrière académique à l'aide de méthodes innovatrices d'analyse de données séquentielles*, PhD thesis in Economics and Social Science, Geneva University.

UNIL. Annuaire statistique 2012-2013. Retrieved on 52.1.2014 from

<http://www.unil.ch/statistiques/files/live/sites/statistiques/files/shared/AnnuaireUNIL2012.pdf>

UNIL. Loi sur l'Université de Lausanne (LUL), 2004. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

<http://www.unil.ch/interne/files/live/sites/interne/files/textes leg/LUL 1.pdf>

UNIL. Règlement d'application de la loi du 6 juillet 2004 sur l'Université de Lausanne, 2004. Retrieved on 4.12.14 from

<http://www.unil.ch/interne/files/live/sites/interne/files/textes leg/RLUL 14 1.pdf>

Annex 5

Data on Academic staff at Lausanne University, 2012

Table A1. Type of full-time equivalent positions, funded by the canton budget, 2012

Catégorie de personnel	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
Professeurs ordinaires et associés	204.6	209.0	224.3	229.9	223.0	218.9	232.3	235.7	251.4	262.5
Femmes	28.6	28.5	35.2	37.7	37.8	38.5	43.8	44.9	52	55.3
% Femmes	14.0	13.6	15.7	16.4	16.9	17.6	18.8	19.0	20.7	21.1
Professeurs assistants	29.3	31.9	34.6	31.3	28.3	37.0	39.5	33.2	33.4	37.6
Femmes	6.6	6.5	9.5	12.7	10.7	14.2	17.7	14.8	16	17.8
% Femmes	22.4	20.4	27.5	40.5	37.8	38.3	44.8	44.6	47.9	47.3
Autres enseignants^c	146.7	165.0	169.7	178.2	179.8	181.5	203.6	223.7	239.5	238.5
Femmes	48.1	58.9	63.9	61.7	63.4	62.3	67.4	77.4	85.7	83.5
% Femmes	32.8	35.7	37.6	34.6	35.3	34.3	33.1	34.6	35.8	35.0
Assistants	525.2	529.6	628.2	610.0	550.3	583.6	603.0	612.0	608.7	641.2
Femmes	225.1	231.6	292.9	298.6	262.1	267.5	281.7	283.7	292.6	310.7
% Femmes	42.9	43.7	46.6	49.0	47.6	45.8	46.7	46.4	48.1	48.5
Pers. admin. et techn.	403.9	404.7	444.2	477.8	529.0	587.8	604.4	606.1	625.2	659.1
Femmes	215.3	218.4	247.5	271.0	311.2	336.8	357.5	360.7	369.5	383.8
% Femmes	53.3	54.0	55.7	56.7	58.8	57.3	59.2	59.5	59.1	58.2
Apprenants et stagiaires	39.1	36.6	32.5	33.1	35.1	37.5	41.3	38.4	39.5	34.9
Femmes	23.1	19.6	17.0	17.6	21.1	19.5	20.3	19.7	18.6	16.8
% Femmes	59.1	53.6	52.3	53.2	60.1	52.0	49.2	51.3	47.1	48.1
Tot. personnel en EPT, ss cliniques	1'348.8	1'376.8	1'533.5	1'560.3	1'545.5	1'646.3	1'724.0	1'749.1	1'797.7	1'873.7
Femmes	546.7	563.4	665.9	699.3	706.2	738.7	788.4	801.2	834.4	867.8
% Femmes	40.5	40.9	43.4	44.8	45.7	44.9	45.7	45.8	46.4	46.3
Nombre de personnes^d	1'942	1'984	2'152	2'205	2'286	2'347	2'395	2'531	2'604	2'693
Femmes	812	848	961	1'008	1'077	1'078	1124	1'210	1'273	1'305
% Femmes	41.8	42.7	44.7	45.7	47.1	45.9	46.9	47.8	48.9	48.5

Source: Annuaire statistique de l'Unil, 2012-2013: p. 55.

- Enveloppe budgétaire de l'UNIL: subvention cantonale + subvention LAU (Loi fédérale sur l'Aide aux Universités) + revenus AIU (Accord inter-cantonal universitaire) + recettes d'exploitation de l'UNIL.
- Les séries temporelles sont affectées par les transferts d'unités de la Faculté des sciences à l'EPFL et à l'Université de Genève:
A l'EPFL: 1.10.2001 Section de chimie; 1.10.2003 Sections de mathématiques et de physique
A l'UNIGE: 01.01.2004 Section de pharmacie
- Professeurs titulaires, Privat-docents, Professeurs invités, Professeurs remplaçants, Chargés de cours, Maîtres d'enseignement et de recherche, Maîtres assistants, Remplaçants du corps intermédiaire.
- Les nombres de personnes ne sont pas répartis dans les catégories de personnel, car une personne peut appartenir à plusieurs catégories. Les nombres de personnes se basent sur les effectifs du mois de décembre uniquement.

Table A2. Type of full-time equivalent positions, funded by the canton, by Faculty, 2012

Faculté	Catégorie de personnel		2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
SSP	Professeurs ordinaires et associés	Tot	26.4	31.7	31.7	36.1	37.7	33.9	35.2	38.1	38.5	40.3	41.1
		F	4.6	6.7	6.4	9.4	9.9	10.2	12.5	13.5	14.8	16.2	14.6
	Professeurs assistants	Tot	3.1	2.1	2.5	3.5	3.7	3.7	5.7	5.7	4.1	4.4	6.4
		F	1.6	0.6	0.0	1.5	1.7	1.7	2.7	2.7	1.2	0.9	2.0
	Autres enseignants	Tot	22.4	21.7	30.1	35.9	37.1	40.2	47.2	48.4	50.9	52.0	50.7
		F	8.0	8.4	13.4	16.9	17.1	18.4	20.2	18.7	18.9	19.7	19.6
	Assistants	Tot	59.5	71.3	88.3	107.0	107.7	99.7	106.9	124.5	119.7	125.3	121.9
		F	30.1	32.3	44.7	55.1	61.7	56.3	59.0	64.1	62.8	69.8	69.6
	PAT	Tot	18.8	20.4	23.2	30.7	32.1	32.8	51.7	47.9	40.7	38.1	37.4
		F	15.9	16.8	19.7	27.0	26.6	27.6	39.3	37.6	35.1	32.4	32.7
	Apprenants et stagiaires	Tot	3.9	3.5	2.0	2.5	3.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.1	1.9
		F	3.9	3.5	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	1.7	1.9
	Total	Tot	134.1	150.6	177.7	215.7	221.8	212.8	249.3	267.1	256.5	262.2	259.4
		F	64.0	68.2	86.2	110.9	118.9	116.6	136.2	139.1	135.3	140.7	140.4
FBM	Professeurs ordinaires et associés	Tot		39.3	41.9	43.4	43.4	43.3	44.3	43.7	45.5	51.6	52.8
		F		4.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	4.5	3.5	3.6	3.8	5.2	4.9
	Professeurs assistants	Tot		8.0	7.9	8.0	4.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	7.0	7.4	7.6
		F		0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.4
	Autres enseignants	Tot		40.3	45.1	45.1	50.9	46.2	42.1	47.2	50.8	52.0	52.1
		F		9.8	13.5	13.2	12.0	13.6	10.9	11.0	12.5	14.0	12.8
	Assistants	Tot		147.9	152.6	198.1	196.3	174.2	193.9	194.8	201.2	186.8	203.5
		F		71.1	70.1	104.5	104.7	83.3	91.8	97.1	92.4	90.5	100.5
	PAT	Tot		116.3	118.4	144.3	156.9	162.6	176.1	180.6	185.6	185.1	191.2
		F		74.9	75.1	91.1	102.1	103.1	113.2	120.6	125.5	125.5	127.5
	Apprenants et stagiaires	Tot		18.0	18.0	14.0	15.0	19.0	18.0	20.0	19.6	23.7	20.9
		F		10.0	12.0	10.0	11.0	13.0	12.0	11.0	10.9	11.3	9.1
	Total	Tot		369.7	383.9	452.9	466.3	449.2	480.2	494.2	509.7	506.7	528.0
		F		169.8	174.6	223.7	234.7	217.5	232.3	245.3	247.0	248.5	257.2
Total UNIL sans les cliniques	Professeurs ordinaires et associés	Tot	214.6	204.6	209.0	224.3	229.9	223.0	218.9	232.3	235.7	251.4	262.5
		F	27.4	28.6	28.5	35.2	37.7	37.8	38.5	43.8	44.9	52.0	55.3
	Professeurs assistants	Tot	19.5	29.3	31.9	34.6	31.3	28.3	37.0	39.5	33.2	33.4	37.6
		F	5.3	6.6	6.5	9.5	12.7	10.7	14.2	17.7	14.8	16.0	17.8
	Autres enseignants	Tot	145.3	146.7	165.0	169.7	178.2	179.8	181.5	203.6	223.7	239.5	238.5
		F	44.1	48.1	58.9	63.9	61.7	63.4	62.3	67.4	77.4	85.7	83.5
	Assistants	Tot	514.8	525.2	529.6	628.2	610.0	550.3	583.6	603.0	612.0	608.7	641.2
		F	208.5	225.1	231.6	292.9	298.6	262.1	267.5	281.7	283.7	292.6	310.7
	PAT	Tot	390.0	403.9	404.7	444.2	477.8	529.0	587.8	604.4	606.1	625.2	659.1
		F	210.6	215.3	218.4	247.5	271.0	311.2	336.8	357.5	360.7	369.5	383.8
	Apprenants et stagiaires	Tot	36.9	39.1	36.6	32.5	33.1	35.1	37.5	41.3	38.4	39.5	34.9
		F	19.9	23.1	19.6	17.0	17.6	21.1	19.5	20.3	19.7	18.6	16.8
	Total	Tot	1'321.2	1'348.8	1'376.8	1'533.5	1'560.3	1'545.5	1'646.3	1'724.0	1'749.1	1'797.7	1'873.7
		F	515.8	546.7	563.4	665.9	699.3	706.2	738.7	788.4	801.2	834.4	867.8

- a. Les séries temporelles sont affectées par les transferts d'unités de la Faculté des sciences à l'EPFL et à l'Université de Genève:
 A l'EPFL: 1.10.2001 Section de chimie; 1.10.2003 Sections de mathématiques et de physique
 A l'UNIGE: 01.01.2004 Section de pharmacie
- b. Transférée entre 2001 et 2004 à l'EPFL, en GSE et à l'UNIGE.
- c. Avant la fusion avec la biologie.

Source : Annuaire statistique de l'Unil, 2012-2013 : p. 59-60.

Swiss Federal Equal Opportunity at Universities Programme, 2000-2013

See the flyer: "Swiss Federal Equal Opportunity at Universities Programme 2000-2011" ([PDF](#))

6. Slovenia

6.1. Introduction

STEM: Department of Agronomy, Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

The Biotechnical Faculty (BF), established in 1961, includes 7 Departments, of agronomy, biology, forestry, landscape architecture, wood technology, animal science and food science and technology. In 2013, there were 566 employed people, and almost 70% of them were engaged in pedagogical and scientific research activities. The **Department of Agronomy (DA)** has been selected for the purposes of the GARCIA project. The department provides university level, advanced professional, and postgraduate education, as well as scientific research and technical and consulting work concerning agriculture. In December 2013, there were evidenced 119 people (66 women and 53 men) employed in the 6 Chairs, some of them (pedagogical and mostly research personnel) are engaged in 3 research programmes and 16 research groups (basic, applied and developmental research work).

SSH: Fran Ramovš Institute of the Slovenian Language, Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (ZRC SAZU)

Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (ZRC SAZU) established in 1981 is the leading Slovenian research centre in the humanities and covers the natural and the social sciences. ZRC SAZU comprises a network of researchers and technicians (320 in total) within the framework of 17 institutes. The Institute of Slovenian Language was established in 1945. Since the establishment of ZRC SAZU in 1982, it has included the sections for lexicological, etymological-onomastic, dialectological and terminological dictionaries. In 2013, there were evidenced 43 employees, from which 34 as researchers and others as technical personnel (26 women and 13 men).

Availability of requested data

STEM: Calls for job vacancies (2010–2014) of the Biotechnical Faculty (Department of Agronomy) are available at the University of Ljubljana's website in Slovenian (http://www.uni-lj.si/aktualno/prosta_delovna_mesta/) and in English (http://www.uni-lj.si/news/job_vacancies/). HR documents (Systematisation of employees' working positions and Minutes (Appointment Reports) on selected candidates at the DA) are available in the HR Office of the DA. Due to the *Personal Data Protection Act*, the Secretary of the DA was not

allowed to show the appointment reports. Therefore, the secretary handed out curtailed appointment reports without names, but gender labels (M/F) were used instead. By the assistance of the key informant (the Professor from the DA), the list of appropriate candidates for interviews and participants for a focus group (FG) was created afterwards. The interviewees and FG participants were selected by a snowball technique.

SSH: Calls for job vacancies (2010–2014) for the positions of Research Assistant and Research Fellow are rather exception since a 'typical' recruitment and selection process for these positions does not exist. These positions are under the promotion system where academic personnel progress from one rank to another. In the infrequent cases when the new vacancy is open, these are the people already planned in the project proposal and once the financing of the project is accepted, they are formally employed for the duration of the project. The position of a Young Researcher appeared to be the only one we can track the formal requirement practices, which depend both on the individual merits of an academic, but on the available positions as well. Consequently, the analyses included descriptions of job vacancies (in years 2010–2014) for Young Researchers (temporary, 3.5 year, non-PhD position) – one call for Research Assistant and 3 calls for the position of Research Fellow. HR documents – Regulation/Systematisation of ZRC SAZU are available in the HR Office. Accordingly, with the specific requirement process related to Research Assistants and Research Fellow, the analyses included job description and criteria for three positions: Young Researcher, Research Assistant and Research Fellow.

6.2. Formal Criteria

Formal criteria STEM: Department of Agronomy at the BF UL

Necessary explanation of the selection of certain profiles of the candidates:

The analysis of formal criteria includes the selection process of the candidates in the period from 2010 to 2014 for 3 working positions: 'Research Assistant' (researcher with PhD) and two university teachers: 'Assistant' (with PhD) and 'Assistant Professor'. In the period observed, there are publicly announced 11 calls for job vacancies at the DA. In these cases, the procedure requires passing the information about job vacancy on both the University of Ljubljana and the Employment Service of Slovenia. The analysis does not consider researchers (among them are 3 female postdocs employed at the DA), who are temporarily employed for the period of research project duration, since there is **no selection procedure for this type (temporarily employed researchers) of the candidates**. In such cases, the HR official

informs the Employment Service of Slovenia about the job vacancy announcement and the already **'known candidate'** without any detailed job description and requirements. The official completes the electronic form 'only' with some general items (name of working position, required education, duration of employment (permanent/temporary), type of employment (full time/part time), whether the working experience and command of foreign language is required or not). In such cases, the Employment Service does not publicly announce the job vacancy and as a result, there are no other candidates except the only one 'known candidate' and no commission is organised.

The commissions are organised only for three types of job vacancy announcements: for Young Researcher (without PhD, temporarily employed), Research Assistant (PhD Researcher), and the higher education teachers (two forms of job vacancy include 3 grades of assistants (with diploma/MA/PhD), and 3 grades of University Professors (Assist. Prof. / Assoc. Prof. / Full Prof.). The procedure of employment of higher education teachers at the University of Ljubljana consists of the public international announcement of job vacancy based on the 31st Article of the Statute of the University. After the announcement of a job vacancy, the dean of a particular Faculty is obliged to nominate a commission of three members (one employed at the same faculty, the other at the other faculty, but within the same University, and the third one outside the University). Particularly important is to emphasise the discrepancy between the academic title and position/work place on which some personnel members work: at the DA, there are academic personnel members with higher academic titles (e.g. associate Professors and even one Full Professor) employed at the position of an Assistant **irrespective of their age**. The same applies for other profiles of working posts as well.

Regarding job descriptions, the analysis consists of 6 out of 11 public international announcements of job vacancies in 2010–2014 at the Department of Agronomy, Biotechnical Faculty, and UL. The following 5 announcements, which do not meet the C/D criteria - *temporary (T) / first permanent (FP) positions*,²² are excluded from the analysis:

- the researcher with diploma,
- the university teacher (Associate Professor),
- two part time Professors (one Associate and one Full Professor),
- the Visiting Assistant Professor (at the later stage, the announcement was withdrawn by the DA), and
- the Assistant (internal reorganisation of the already employed candidate at the DA).

²² Since we do not have a category of tenure in Slovenia, we decided to use categories of *temporary (T) and first permanent (FP) positions*.

Table 1: Public international announcements of job vacancies at the DA, 2010–2014

	R (diploma)	Assistant	Research Assist.	Assist. Prof.	Assoc. Prof.	Full Prof.
2010	1	1	1	1	1	
2011		1		1		
2013		1		1	1/2	1/2
2014				1		

HR Documents (STEM: Department of Agronomy at the BF UL)

Analysing the ‘Systematisation of working positions for the Department of Agronomy’, the following profiles are discussed:

- ‘Assistant’ (pedagogue with PhD)
- ‘Research Assistant’ (with PhD)
- ‘Assistant Professor’

It is worth mentioning that this Systematisation was ‘modernised’ in October 2012 regarding the number of working positions at the DA. As an illustration, if there had been 5 employed assistants (pedagogues) in one of the six Chairs of the Department of Agronomy when the Systematisation was ‘modernised’, the renewed document in 2012 included 5 work positions for this profile – Assistant (pedagogue), without a possibility of change.

Attention paid in the documents to temporary (T) / first permanent (FP)²³ positions / junior academic careers

In the Systematisation, every working post is described uniformly and in a very generic way. As an illustration, all (10) working posts for ‘Assistant’, which are defined as a pedagogical working position in the document, are described uniformly with the same text structure (sections and subsections) and content items as well. The only two variables, which distinguish (10) Assistant working posts among themselves, are related to ‘the field’ of academic title (e.g. Assistant for genetics) and the number of announced working posts for the particular academic field. There is no particular attention paid to junior academic careers.

Description of academic excellence and/or quality in the documents

In the document, academic excellence or quality required for each type of work position can be extracted from the subsection ‘Functional knowledge and other requirements (skills and language)’ under the section (2) ‘Requirements for a working position’. In turn:

²³ Since we do not have a category of tenure in Slovenia, we decided to use categories of *temporary (T)* and *first permanent (FP)* positions.

- ‘Assistant’ (pedagogue with PhD):

is expected to be active and creative mostly in pedagogical work with students, at the same time is subordinated to superior professor, to be capable of participating in scientific-research work and responsible for safety working conditions. PhD from biotechnical or other field of natural sciences is mandatory and the already valid academic (pedagogical) title. Academic excellence is assessed through candidates' talent for organisation of their own work and students' work, and their capabilities to use computer tools. Previous work experience and trial working period are not required.

- ‘Research Assistant’ (with PhD):

is expected to be capable of mostly scientific-research work, to have proven expertise and to participate to a minor extent in the undergraduate and graduate studies. Such candidate is also expected to fulfil various tasks (administrative, organisational) of their superiors. PhD from biotechnical or other field of natural sciences is mandatory, yet the valid academic (pedagogical) title is not required. Academic excellence requires a candidate's organisational, communicative and innovative skills, capability of teamwork, knowing at least one (world) foreign language, and computer tools. One year of working experience and 3 months of trial working period are required.

- ‘Assistant Professor’:

is expected to be autonomous, creative, and engaged mostly in pedagogical work with students. PhD from biotechnical or other field of natural sciences is mandatory and the valid academic title (Assistant Professor) is required as well. Academic excellence is assessed through the following expected personal characteristics: rhetorical, innovative skills, and a capability of organising their own work and work of other associates.

In sum, academic excellence required for every working position is defined in very general terms – expected skills and talents. Innovative, communicative, organisational and other abilities are not additionally described.

Criteria for C/D level positions presented in the formal documents

In the document, there are uniform criteria for every work post description. Five general sections and their subsections include the following items:

- (1) Description of work post / 1.1. General description;
- (2) Requirements for a working position:
 - 2.1. Required education (grade and field),

2.2. Valid academic title and a field of habilitation,

2.3. Functional knowledge and other requirements (skills and language),

2.4. Work experience,

2.5. Trial period of work;

(3) Responsibility for one's own work and a control over the other associates and working means (description of responsibility, mandates, higher/lower working position, etc.);

(4) Working conditions, and

(5) Number of working posts.

There are only minor variations in description of work position under the same academic title as are the following:

- 'Assistant' (pedagogue with PhD):

In the document, there are 10 (almost the same) forms of description of work position for the 'Assistant' (pedagogue with PhD). The only two variables are related to 'the field' of academic title (Assistant for the field of genetics, etc. under the subsection 2.2. 'Valid academic title and a field of habilitation'), and the number of announced working posts (from 1 to 5, under the section 5 'Number of working posts'). These two variables and various Chairs with fixed but different number of working posts elucidate 10 forms of description of working position for 'Assistant' (pedagogue with PhD) in the document..

- 'Research Assistant' (with PhD):

In the document, there are 6 (almost the same) forms of work position description for the 'Research Assistant' (with PhD). In this case, the only variable refers to the number of work posts, which expands from 1 to 5 posts. This variable and various Chairs indicate 6 forms of the same work post.

- 'Assistant Professor':

So, 14 forms of very similar described work post for the 'Assistant Professor' vary only by the field of academic title, Chair and a number of work posts (from 1 to 4).

To sum, for all three forms of work posts ('Assistant', 'Research Assistant' and 'Assistant Professor') the job descriptions has been made generic, formal and taxative. The only variables refer to the field of academic title, number of work posts and the Chair under which the post is announced.

The mode and extent of specified criteria

The above-mentioned criteria are generic in description. Beside already mentioned minor variations within descriptions of the same work position, there are divergences among the 3 observed profiles. In turn:

(1) Description of working post / 1.1. General description: required items of general description vary among Assistants, Research Assistants and Assistant Professors. For both pedagogical titles (Assistants and Assistant Professors), requirements predominately refer to pedagogical work and to a lesser extent to scientific research work, quite the contrary applies for the Research Assistants, who are expected to be mostly engaged in scientific research work. Compared to Assistants, Assistant Professors are expected to be more active and autonomous in creating and updating curricula and education programmes, and to give lectures to students.

(2) Requirements for a work position:

2.1. Required education (grade and field) as to the academic title,

2.2. Valid academic title and a field of habilitation,

2.3. Functional knowledge and other requirements (skills and language),

2.4. Work experience,

2.5. Trial period of work: Assistant and Assistant Professor are expected to have valid academic title, which does not apply for the Research Assistant. However, the latter is expected to have 1 year of working experience and 3 months of trial work, while these requirements do not apply for teaching personnel. Knowledge of one world foreign language is explicitly required only from the Research Assistant.

The difference between required criteria for tenured and non-tenured positions

There is no category of tenure in Slovenia and therefore the only difference is between permanent and temporary employment.

Extent of matching the official criteria in HR policy documents with the criteria in the job descriptions:

Compared to the document (Systematisation), the criteria of job vacancy are not specified anew. Only in the case of Assistant Professor, there is additionally required a command of the Slovenian language under the (2) Degree criteria, and scientific research work requirement (development of new concepts, theories and methods) is added in (3) Short description of work and tasks of a job vacancy (see the section *Job descriptions*, below).

In the document, there is *no reference to affirmative action/gender equality policies* of the university.

Job Descriptions STEM: Department of Agronomy at the BF UL

Description (generic or specific) of the job profile in terms of academic discipline

Job vacancies of the Department of Agronomy, the Biotechnical Faculty (2010–2014) are announced publicly and internationally on the website of the University of Ljubljana. All 3 types of observed academic profiles were described in line with the ‘Systematisation’, however, in even shorter and summarised way.

Description of excellence and/or quality in the job descriptions

In the HR document (Systematisation) one may find excellence or quality description under the subsection ‘Functional knowledge and other requirements (skills and language)’ which belongs to the section (2) ‘Requirements for a working position’, yet in the descriptions of job vacancies these elements are missing. Actually, a short description of work and tasks required for a particular job is much-summarised version of the section ‘(1) Description of working post / 1.1. General description’ from the document *Systematisation*.

The mode and extent of specification of these criteria

Compared to the Systematisation, the criteria of job vacancies are not specified once more. Only in the case of Assistant Professor, there is additionally required the knowledge of the Slovenian language under the (2) Degree criteria, and scientific-research work requirement (development of new concepts, theories and methods) is added in (3) Short description of work and tasks of a job vacancy. In the case of Research Assistant, the (2) Degree criteria are expanded to innovative, communication and organisational skills, teamwork ability, and one year of work experience, which again, is not a novelty compared to the document.

The following items are present in (3) Short description of work and tasks, which is the summarised version of (1) Description of work post / 1.1. General description from the Systematisation:

- ‘Assistant’ (pedagogue with PhD):

Supervising students: running practical tutorials, collaboration with a Professor in preparing tests and other teaching activities and similar,

Participating in research,
 Controlling work equipment,
 Contributing to academic field by pedagogical and research work.

- ‘Research Assistant’ (with PhD):

Scientific and research work,
 Expertise and collaboration with a project financier,
 Writing reports and expertise,
 Participation in undergraduate and postgraduate study,
 Writing proposals for purchasing research equipment and its maintenance.

- ‘Assistant Professor’:

Creating and updating curricula,
 Organising of every activity related to the course implementation,
 Coordinating of work of other associates in the course,
 Teaching and evaluating tests and exams,
 Mentorship,
 Scientific-research work: developing new concepts, theories and methods.
 In short, job vacancy criteria are summarised in much shortened version of the criteria defined in the HR document ‘Systematisation of work positions for the Department of Agronomy’ (Biotechnical Faculty UL).

The dominant criterion in the job descriptions

No criterion is particularly stressed. It seems that the (2) Degree criteria (e.g. PhD and valid habilitation title) are the most important.

Difference in required criteria for tenured and non-tenured positions

As mentioned above, all observed job vacancies are announced for permanent (full-time) positions.

References to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university

Except the F/M option under the (1) Announced job position, there is no other reference to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university.

Formal criteria SSH: Fran Ramovš Institute of the Slovenian Language

Necessary explanation of the selection of certain profiles of the candidates:

The methodology used for analysing formal criteria was framed by the fact that for the position of ‘Young Researcher’ (without PhD) **is the only position** in which we can trace the formal recruitment process at ZRC SAZU, as already noted in the introductory part of the report. For that position, the recruitment procedure is organised in a way that the supervisors apply to the call of the Slovenian Research Agency (<https://www.arrs.gov.si/en/novo.asp>) annually. The candidate who wishes to become a Young Researcher applies for the position at a research organisation and the supervisor, who has been successful at the Call for mentors for Young Researchers in the selected research areas. For recruitment of a Young Researcher, the shortlisted candidates have passed the first stage of selection. The decision regarding selection is left to supervisor (or a committee she or he forms at the institute), whilst the role of the committee on the Research Centre level is to confirm selected candidates and assures that the protocol was fully followed. As a result, the analyse is made at the level of the whole research institution (ZRC SAZU) and not just at the level of the selected unit (the Institute of Slovenian Language) in the timeframe of 2010–2014 there have been 6 new employments for the T/FP positions:

Table 2: Number of employed research personnel at the Institute of Slovenian Language, 2010–2014

	Young Researcher	Research Assist.	Research Fellow
2010	1 (M)		1 (F)
2011	1 (M)		1 (F)
2013	1 (M)	1 (M)	
2014			

HR policy documents – Systematisation of ZRC SAZU

Attention paid in the documents to junior academic careers

In the Systematisation, every position from lower to high is described uniformly and in a very generic way (that also concerns positions of Young Researcher, Research Assistant and Research Fellow).

Description of academic excellence and/or quality in the documents

Descriptions are made generic, formal and exhaustive for all three positions. For the positions of Young Researcher and Research Assistant, there are three main categories/tasks: *Research* (in accordance with the agreement signed with the Research Agency), *Publication record* and

Knowledge transfer. Criteria are not specified for the particular scientific field, but they are generic for all disciplines.

Criteria for C/D level positions presented in the formal documents

- ‘Young Researcher’

Research: For the position of Young Researcher, emphasis is on research within both the individual project (under the mentor's supervision) and the research group or programme a Young Researcher is affiliated.

Publication record: Publishing of the results of the research (from this early stage) is already emphasised.

Specific criteria: a good knowledge of (at least) one foreign language.

- ‘Research Assistant’

Research: emphasis is on individual independent research.

Publication record: Publishing is mentioned in two (of four) tasks description which proves a strong emphasis on it.

Specific tasks: a new demand – collaboration on demanding tasks is introduced.

Specific criteria: a good knowledge of two foreign languages.

- ‘Research Fellow’

The job description for Research Fellow differs in comparison with first two and the new tasks are introduced: *Knowledge transfer*

Research: Project management is the new task included. The emphasis is on international collaborations, leading and participating within various project teams. Candidates should be able to develop the new concepts, theories and methods and put them in practices. The results of the research should have significant echo in the domestic and international scholarly community.

Specific criteria: A specific criteria is an excellent knowledge of two foreign languages.

Additional: organisational and managerial skills

Extent of matching the official criteria in HR policy documents with the criteria in the job descriptions

- *years of experience* differs between job descriptions and HR policy documents (for Research Assistant required experience is 5 years, while for Research Fellow – which is higher position,

required experience is once 4, once 5 years, while in some cases no experience was required although this is in collision with the organisation's job descriptions

- *knowledge of languages* – for Research Assistant and Research Fellow in the Systematisation, while in the job description only one language is required (English), except in the case for the vacancy for Research Assistant at the Institute of Slovenian Language, where two languages are required (English and German).

In the job description of Research Fellow:

- the criteria of organisational and managerial skills are not mentioned
- the research excellence (project management, international collaborations) is not mentioned

Are there any references to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university?

In the job descriptions, there are no references to affirmative action or gender equality policy. There is no special attention paid to junior academic careers.

A difference in the criteria for Young Researchers and Research Assistant on one hand, and Research Fellow on the other—which can be considered as the first permanent academic position—although we do not have formal tenured positions (positions are not related to the type of contract – permanent or temporary) is quite obvious, and conclusion of permanent contract usually depends on the position within the Institute.

Descriptions of vacancies

How generic or specific is the job profile in terms of academic discipline?

For position of Young Researcher, job profiles are very generic in terms of academic discipline; the call encompasses several disciplines for which the job vacancies are opened; requirements are generic, only sporadically (in the calls for 2013 and 2014) there are additional requirements for certain disciplines (biology, geography, history). Vacancies were publicly announced at the Research Centre's web page as well as in the Slovenian daily *Delo*.

For positions of Research Assistant and Research Fellow, the used form is generic for all new vacancies by using the template required by the National employment service and it is not higher education/research institution specific.

How excellence and/or quality are described in the job descriptions?

The job vacancy descriptions follow common template, but they are usually very specific concerning academic discipline and field required. For example, in the case of the call for a

Research Assistant to be engaged for 7 months in an EU funded project, specific requirement for education is set.

Which criteria are present in the job descriptions?

- ‘Young Researcher’
 - good performance during studies (average grade is directly transferred into points, e.g. 8.32 is 8.32 points; better average is better ranking)
 - if the candidate has MA, average grade is not relevant
 - possession of MA degree (1 point)
 - enrolment in PhD studies (0.5 points)
 - possession of awards (the national (Prešeren) award – 1 point, other awards – up to 0.5 points)
 - publication of articles and existing record of academic work (up to 3 points)
 - participation in research projects (up to 3 points)
- ‘Research Assistant’ and ‘Research Fellow’
 - The requirement of education: there is an option for alternative educational profile, which was never used in the job descriptions.
 - The requirement of work experience may vary for same positions (e.g. for Research Assistant required experience is 5 years, while for Research Fellow – which is higher position, required experience is once 4, once 5 years, while once no experience was required, although this is in collision with the organisation's job descriptions, as indicated below).
 - Other specified requirements include knowledge of foreign languages, computer skills, driving license

How and to what extent are these criteria specified?

- ‘Young Researcher’

Criteria are specified and measured by number of points which value is exactly specified for education degree, average grade, current study enrolment and awards, while for article authorship and research record ones who select have more freedom and may value candidate in a range of points, whereby the maximum is defined. Criteria are defined by Regulations of the Slovenian Research Agency. The call from 2010 was the last one in which the age limit for the candidate was 28. In later calls, the number of years since the BA or MA degree was

received was limited to 5 years from the year of graduation. In addition, minimal average value of grades is at least 8 for BA and MA.

For various disciplines, there are additional requirements. For example:

- For candidate in **geography** include possession of driving license for B category (personal car);
- For candidate in **history**: knowledge of two foreign languages (preferably widely used ones as well as central European languages), driving license for B category (personal car) and good computer literacy).
 - ‘Research Assistant’ and ‘Research Fellow’

For these positions, discipline, field and description of tasks are also very specified (e.g. PhD in social anthropology – research and fieldwork in Africa and the Mediterranean; PhD in geology – research in the field of sedimentology of carbonates; PhD – research and editing of Legal terminological dictionary; PhD in linguistics – editing of entries for New dictionary of Slovenian language);

Very specified requirements and their variations within equivalent positions produce an impression that the analysed job vacancies for temporary positions (and one case of temporary non-PhD job for project assistant) were designed specifically for already existing candidates. This may also be argued for analysed calls for Young Researchers, which are very specific in terms of discipline and academic requirements.

Which criterion is dominant in the job descriptions?

- ‘Young Researchers’

The analyses shows that the dominant criterion in these calls is average grade, since it brings the highest number of points; ‘research’ criteria are also significant (article authorship and record of research).

- ‘Research Assistant and Research Fellow’

All criteria are presented as formally equally important

Is there a difference in required criteria for tenured and non-tenured positions?

There is no category of tenure in Slovenia and therefore the only difference is between permanent and temporary employment.

Are there any references to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university?

- ‘Young Researcher’

In terms of affirmative action and gender equality policies, these calls do not contain any statement that would refer to it. In the eligibility criteria, for candidates who used maternity leave, the age/number of years after receiving MA or BA degree limit is lifted for 1 year for each child. The same is applicable for documented sick leaves that were longer than 6 months.

- ‘Research Assistant’ and ‘Research Fellow’

Analysed description of job vacancies does not anyhow refer to or deal with affirmative action or gender equality. The only gender ‘aware’ aspect in the calls’ texts is usage of generic male designations for job positions followed by brackets in which it is indicated that these male designations refer to both male and female candidates.

Comparative conclusion on formal criteria stem and ssh

Formal criteria of selected departments show certain similarities which result from the several specificities of Slovenian context. The most important specificity is that for the first two junior academic positions (with PhD), already employed researchers and teachers automatically progress from one to another rank, according to the University/Research Centre promotion rules. In such cases, there is no formal announcement of job vacancy, but formal criteria defined in internal rules for promotion (Systematisation) are used. The second important specificity is that there is no category of tenure and therefore in Slovenia the only difference is between permanent and temporary employment. It is also worth mentioning that at STEM, there are employed people with higher academic titles on the lower positions (e.g. Associate Professors and even one Full Professor working on positions of assistants, irrespective of their age). The same applies for other profiles of working posts as well.

The main similarity between formal criteria at STEM and SSH is that in the cases of two first positions with PhD usually there are no other candidates except the only one ‘known candidate’ and no formal procedure with committee is organised. In such cases, the HR official informs the Employment Service of Slovenia about the announcement of job vacancy of the already ‘**known candidate**’ without any detailed job description and requirements. The official completes the electronic form ‘only’ with some general items (name of work position, required education, duration of employment (permanent/temporary), type of employment (full time/part time), whether the working experience and command of foreign language is required or not).

HR documents:

In the Systematisation in both STEM and SSH, work posts are described uniformly and in a very generic way. There are uniform criteria for description of every working post, which are described with the same text structure (sections and subsections) and content items as well. The only specific criteria refer to the specificity of particular scientific field. In sum, academic excellence required for every work position is defined in very general terms. In STEM, there are six general sections:

- Required education,
- Valid academic title and a field of habilitation,
- Functional knowledge and other requirements (skills and language),
- Work experience,
- Trial period of work,
- Responsibilities for one's own work and a supervision of other associates and working means (description of responsibility, mandates, higher/lower working position, etc.). Excellence is described in a rather general way – as expected skills and talents (innovative, communicative, organisational etc.), and abilities are not further operationalised/described.

In SSH, four general sections are written:

- Research,
- Publication,
- Knowledge transfer,
- Specific criteria.

The above-mentioned criteria are also generic in description. Beside already mentioned minor variations within descriptions of the same working position, there are divergences among the 3 observed profiles.

Job description

In sum, criteria defined in descriptions of job vacancies are summarised versions of the criteria defined in the HR document 'Systematisation' in both STEM and SSH. While in STEM job vacancy is much-shortened version of 'Systematisation', some discrepancies in SSH between HR documents and job description are noticeable. There is a lack of some requirements (e.g. knowledge of two languages) or job vacancies contain very specific requirements that are adapted for already existing candidate, particularly if she or he is part of the project application team. The discrepancies are visible in the categories of years of experience (*e.g. in HR 4–5 years in job description NO experience*), knowledge of languages,

without mentioning the criteria of organisational and managerial skills, and of research excellence (project management, international collaborations).

In both STEM and SSH, analysed description of job vacancy does not anyhow refer to or deal with affirmative action or gender equality policies. The only gender 'aware' aspect in the calls' texts is a usage of generic male designations for job positions followed by brackets in which it is indicated that these male designations refer to both male and female candidates. Therefore, except the F/M option under the announced job position, there is no other reference to affirmative action/gender equality policies of the university.

6.3. Actual practices

Interviews and focus group stem: Department of Agronomy at the BF UL

As explained in the introduction, the interviewees are selected by a snowball technique.

Table 3: Interviewees (STEM“)

	Committee member (C)	Committee member (D)	Total
Female	1	2	3
Male	2	1	3
Total	3	3	6

C-level appointment refers to Assistant Professors in all three cases while D-level appointment refers in one case to Assistant with PhD (a pedagogue) and in two cases to Assistant with PhD (a Researcher).

Table 4: Focus Group Participants (SSH)

Gender	Participants by a position in a recruitment procedure
Female	Assistant Secretary of the Biotechnical Faculty, Human Resources
Male	President of a Commission of The Criteria for Appointment to the Titles of University Teacher, Researcher and Associate at the University of Ljubljana
Male	Head of the Chair of Phytomedicine at the Agronomy Department
Male	Deputy Dean of the Agronomy Department
Female	Secretary of the Agronomy Department
Total	5

Abstract criteria

Criteria used to select candidates for a T/FP-level position by interviewees (I) and participants of focus group (FG)

Besides the required formal criteria, all committee members (CM) emphasise that it is important to know the candidate for a longer period. Personal experience in work with a

candidate is a decisive criterion in selection procedure, an assurance that a selected candidate would fit to a team group. As illustration,

‘This means that you know them more than a year, that you know what kind of a pedagogue they will be. You cannot see this from their grades... The majority of the candidates who are employed here are actually my former students or I worked with them before’ (CM C-level).

Similar musings can be extracted from FG participants. They believe that employing ‘already known candidates’ is a Slovenian speciality. In some academic fields, there are simply not enough candidates in a country. At the departmental level, the most often cases are when the job vacancy is announced to replace a retired professor and to maintain their work posts. In a procedure, at first formal criteria are examined. Then, it is decisive whether the committee members know the candidate or have work experiences with them.

Considering an important criterion for a D/C-level position, the interviewees emphasised that *education* is already verified in procedures for appointment to the academic titles. They also stressed that more important criterion is the institution that granted a certificate. Some interviewees trust more to certificates obtained within the University of Ljubljana (UL) than to certificates from ‘less qualitative’ faculties outside the UL or else payable study programmes of ‘poor quality’ as to their academic fields.

The FG participants stressed again that knowing a candidate through their participation in research and teaching in the course of their education was of prime importance. Therefore, *teaching experience* and *research* are important, but there were always very few of such candidates. In the context of national research policy, which prioritises the criterion of abundant scientific publishing, only an independent and enthusiastic researcher may have a more stable academic career. As an illustration,

‘If you are capable of running a project and respecting deadlines, then there is a great probability that you will be successful in other working fields as well’ (CM C-level).

Discussing capabilities of *acquiring research funding*, the interviewees differ. The committee members for C-level stressed that this criterion is more and more important in a context of reduced national funds for teaching to 80%. In agronomy, as very applicative academic discipline, it is expected that a candidate at C-level is capable of acquiring additional funds from various users of their expertise (e.g. the ministry for agriculture, food-processing industry). On the contrary, the committee members for D-level do not expect the candidates at early stages of their careers to be capable of acquiring research funding, but primarily to fit into a team group and only later to acquire research funds by themselves. Moreover, the

participants of FG do not know an example that a candidate at D-level was expected to acquire research funding although they admit that this criterion is gradually becoming a very important one.

The interviewees do not recognise *the management experience and media appearances* as decisive criteria, but as desired criteria.

International mobility is seen as a very important criterion, which reflects a candidate's capability, courage and adaptability to new environments. Yet, the interviewees who experience a family formation in an early stage of their academic career de-emphasise this criterion as a decisive one. Finally, they all agree that longer staying abroad is very important for international research networking.

The most important criteria cited by the interviewees pertain to 'fit in the team' and a candidate's 'personality' with all characteristics mentioned. A candidate's enthusiasm and their 'compatibility with a team' are the most desired characteristics whereby both sides benefit. As an illustration,

'Abroad, it is very important to prove that you are capable of teamwork. I do not know how this is manifested in practice. Here, we still do not require a capability of team working officially' (FG participant).

The most important criterion in their specific academic field for participants of FG is attributed to research since everything else stems from the success in research work. The committee members for C-level, however, prefer an average, but enthusiastic candidate in all three fields of work (teaching, research and expertise) compared to an excellent candidate in one field only, e.g. research. The committee members for D-level prefer a candidate capable of interdisciplinary work emphasising their 'openness for other academic fields' and reliability of 'on-time performing tasks' as the most desired characteristics. As an illustration,

'Our work is interdisciplinary. A candidate, who acquires education in one academic field, has to be interested in other fields as well. I prefer a meteorologist who is a physicist from a farm. I am looking for a complete person who is positively oriented towards everything he does not know' (CM D-level).

Describing the difference between a candidate with minimal requirements and an excellent candidate the interviewees differ. Both the committee members for FP-level and participants of FG define as an excellent candidate a person who is above-average in the majority of listed characteristics, while a candidate with minimal requirements fulfils 'only' formal criteria of announced job vacancy. The same applies also for a candidate who shows excellence in one

criterion only (e.g. research), but is an introvert or individualistic person incapable of teamwork. The committee members for C-level also discuss a formal criterion – ‘mandatory command of the Slovenian language’. On the one hand, they see employment of foreign candidates as a solution to a deficit of specific academic professionals in Slovenia. On the other hand, they identify a difficulty in communication of foreign candidates with extension services and farmers in Slovenia, and students at undergraduate level as well, since their command of English is very poor. The committee members for D-level prefer personal characteristics as decisive in defining an excellent candidate. They are expected to take the initiative, and to be analytical, communicative, creative and completely compatible with a team and a mentor. Again, minimal requirements are equated with the announced formal criteria. At the same time, they cited that many already employed people fulfil minimal standards only due to the existing procedure of re-election. They see a solution in a public announcement at each time of re-election.

Actual / recent selection process

The course description of selection process of the latest appointment of a D/C-level position by the interviewees

The committee members for C-level described the prevailing practice at the Agronomy Department – the selection of the already known and employed candidates who as a rule studied at the Biotechnical Faculty UL and as students participated in research and teaching. Usually this is a candidate already employed in a lower working position (as an Assistant with PhD or a Lecturer), yet with obtained academic title as an Assistant Professor. In all three cases, the candidates were employed at the Department and were selected to replace the retired Professors. As an illustration,

‘We decided to employ an Assistant who replaced the retired Professor... There were other candidates in Slovenia, but nobody applied for this work position. It was somehow logical that somebody from the group was selected, who had a title of an Assistant Professor for twenty years, but who had been working in a lower paid working position as an Assistant. She was a proved professional, running Professor's tutorials and participating in research projects. She deserved that position’ (CM C-level).

Similar ‘inbreeding’ is characteristic for a selection of D-level candidates. It is usually a candidate raised at the Department:

‘We announced a particular profile of a candidate, an agro-meteorologist. We knew in advance that we would select a candidate who was raised at our Chair. Actually, I raised all the candidates by myself, and a selection procedure was irrelevant, i.e. it was only a formality. At first, we struggled for this position at the Chair, and we won. Then we announced the job vacancy, and there were no other applications except of that of our candidate’ (CM D-level).

There was only one case where three female candidates applied for a D-level working position:

‘There were three applications. I was the president of the commission and I prepared a proposal based on applications’ results. All three candidates fulfilled the application requirements, but one among them was extraordinary. She had 27 publications in the journals with impact factor while other candidates had only six to seven comparable references. This candidate was also a mother with two children and the decision was relatively easy’ (CM D-level).

As to appointment reports, the interviewees barely remember *the composition of the committee*. Regarding the requirement procedure, they mentioned several times (incorrectly) that a secretary from the department participated in the decision-making about a candidate. Actually, she checked only formal criteria, but she was not involved in the decision-making. Some committee members for C-level knew that there were three members in the selection procedure: two from the University of Ljubljana and one outside the University. The committee members for D-level also mentioned the actual process in which secretary made a preliminary selection of the candidates. In all cases, there was *informal recruitment of the candidate*. However, the procedure was carried out in line with the official rules. As a result, the *decision-making process* was also a formality, and a consensus among the committee members was easily reached. As an illustration,

‘There was no huge discussion at all because there was usually only one applicant... A committee member outside the University never contradicts the decision. It is obvious that these institutions work according to the principle not to be involved in another institution’s decision. Probably a returned favour is expected’ (CM C-level).

The decisive criteria in the selection of the appointed candidate refer to the already known, employed, proven and raised candidates at the Department. To illustrate with typical descriptions:

‘It was decisive that he was already employed here and could take over immediately all the tasks and teaching responsibilities from the Professor’ (CM C-level).

‘Our experiences with her were decisive. Even today, I see her as a very good lecturer. Well, as the Head of the Chair, I would also like to see her to be more engaged in research and international networks’ (CM C-level).

‘A lot of publications, regular work with students, she was reliable... In brief, considering her work so far, and also that she at the same time have been taking care of a family, she has proved that everything can be done’ (CM D-level).

The committee members for D-level assess all their candidates as *excellent candidates*, while the committee members for C-level value their candidates a bit lower; as one said, with 4 out of 5. The majority of interviewees emphasised that their candidates met their expectations and only one mentioned a candidate who happened to be beyond expectation:

‘Once, we got a Croatian and we did not understand at all who the person we got is’ (CM D-level).

The same applies for the opposite case. The majority did not experience the selection process, which turned out to be a failure. Only one interviewee remembered a case 15 years prior when a candidate with excellent references turned out to be very poor in communication skills.

Gender

The role of gender in the selection of candidates

All collocutors, including the participants of FG, agree that gender does not play a significant role in the selection of candidates. Moreover, the employed candidates at C-level prove a very balanced gender structure. Yet, they identify an unbalanced gender structure in Young Researchers and leading personnel. In the first case, there are more selected female candidates, since they have higher grades compared to male candidates. Some interviewees believe that women are more ‘focused’, ‘reliable’, ‘persistent and capable of sitting’, or that men are at first less ambitious, and show their capabilities later in their academic career. All interviewees strive for a balanced gender structure in their working groups, however, some reports on an unbalanced gender structure where women were in majority. To illustrate,

‘Now, in our Chair (soil science), there is a problem with feminisation. Before, this was an explicit male chair. In the field, you need to work physically with a shovel. Women, we cannot do it by ourselves... Rules and requirements prioritise grades, and women are better than men are. Now, we will probably give a priority to a male candidate to balance the group’ (CM for C-level).

In the selection procedure, one's own experience also plays a significant role. Two interviewees preferred to employ female candidates following the examples of their first employments:

'Having an opportunity, I prefer to employ a woman. When I got a job, my director didn't employ a potential mother, but a good worker' (CM for D-level).

'Here are mainly women employed, but pragmatically, because they are hard-working. However, my successor is a male candidate... not because he is a male, but because he is very good. The successor must be absolutely the best' (CM for D-level).

Finally, all interviewees agree that men prevail in leading posts.

The existence of gender policy on recruitment and selection within the institution and collocutors' attitudes towards them

All interviewees believe that gender policy on recruitment and selection does not exist at the level of department or at the faculty in general. They agree that the departments, chairs and research groups have to be gender balanced. Yet, they also admit that the current trend of employment of young people at the beginning of their career gives the priority to women, but later (obtaining higher titles and leading positions), men are preferred candidates. Therefore, they agree that it is necessary to introduce a policy to stimulate women not at the beginning of their academic career but later on. To illustrate,

'For leading posts, we should have a rule, one term a man, next term a women. We do not need the quotas, but the rotation, a regular succession... However, in research work, I would not do it the same way. One cannot employ somebody just because she is a woman' (CM for D-level).

Some FG participants believe that gender policy, which prioritised women participation, is already introduced in the calls' requirements for the majority of European projects. This practice might gradually influence the selection and employment of candidates 'at home'.

The majority of interviewees *do not apply gender policy in practice*. As a rule, they select the candidates according to the announced job criteria irrespective of gender. Few interviewees emphasise that they implicitly apply gender policy by stimulating young associates to continue their academic career, or by preferred employment of a candidate who contributes to a gender balanced structure of the working group.

Appointment reports STEM: Department of Agronomy at the BF UL

Qualitative analysis:

The decisive criteria:

- ‘Assistant’ (pedagogue with PhD) (Total: 2):

The decisive criteria for selection of 2 assistants (in 2010 and 2013 respectively) were required Degree criteria (PhD and academic title – Assistant for the announced academic field). In 2010, 1 candidate out of 2 was selected; the second one did not fulfil the required degree criteria while the first one had even higher ranked title – Assistant Professor for the announced job vacancy of assistant. In 2013, only one candidate submitted the application form with required degree criteria.

- ‘Research Assistant’ (with PhD) (Total: 1):

The decisive criterion for selection of 1 candidate for a Research Assistant in 2010 (out of 3 candidates) was ‘research experience’.

- ‘Assistant Professor’ (Total: 3):

In 2010, 1 candidate was selected based on Degree criteria (PhD, academic title – University Teacher for appropriate academic field and command of the Slovenian language). The same applied for 2 selected candidates in 2012 and 2013 respectively.

Emphasis on research, teaching or other criteria

The above-mentioned degree criteria were decisive for selected candidates who applied for positions of Assistant and Assistant Professor. In the case of selected Research Assistant, research experience was the most decisive criterion.

Attention paid to the gender of the candidates

In the appointment reports, there is no attention paid to the gender of the candidates.

Competencies and skills of the preferred candidate

In the appointment reports, only degree criteria of the candidates are mentioned.

Quantitative analysis

Ratio between T/FP time positions

All 6 candidates were selected for permanent, regular, full-time employment.

Gender ratio of appointed candidates

Table 5: Selected candidates, 2010–2014, by gender (F/M)

	Assistant	Research Assist.	Assist. Prof.
2010	1F	1F	1M
2012			1F
2013	1 F		1M
Gender ratio (F:M)	2:0	1:0	1:2

Table 6: The gender composition of 2–3 members committee (mc)

	Assistant (2 mc)	Research Assist. (2 mc)	Assist. Prof. (3 mc)
2010	1F candidate (Mmc/Mmc)	1F (Mmc/Mmc)	1M (Mmc/Mmc/Mmc)
2012			1F (Fmc/Mmc/Mmc)
2013	1F candidate (Mmc/Mmc)		1M (Fmc/Mmc/Mmc)

Table 7: Number of the candidates by gender for a particular working post

	Assistant	Research Assist.	Assist. Prof.
2010	2F candidates	3F candidates	1M candidate
2012			1F candidate
2013	1F candidate		1M candidate

All positions were publicly (internationally) announced on the website of the University of Ljubljana.

Interviews and focus group SSH: Institute of Slovenian Language, ZRC SAZU

The interviews were conducted with four persons (2 male, 2 female), who are all in leading positions at their units and as such have decisive role in the research policy creation and candidate selection processes the positions of Research Assistant and Research Fellow, where there is no committee for selection and candidates are usually selected based on previous collaboration).

Focus group was conducted with four persons (2 female, 2 male), who are all involved in the process of selection Young Researchers – which is the only selection process at the SSH institution which involves committee.

Table 8: Focus Group Participants (SSH)

Gender	Participants by a position in a recruitment procedure
Female	Secretary of ZRC SAZU, Human Resources
Female	President of a Committee for Selection of Young Researchers, Researcher and Associate at the Institute of Slovenian Language
Male	A member of a Committee for Selection of Young Researchers
Male	Head of the Institute of Geography
Total	4

Abstract criteria

Apart from quantified criteria in case of Young Researcher position – average grade during BA/MA studies and research record in the specific field – knowledge and expertise in the field are stressed as the principal criteria decisive for selection of candidates. According to one selection committee member who participated in the focus group, knowledge must be broader than specific field for which the candidate applies, since they must be capable of working on various projects. One of the interviewees emphasised that for C-level candidates, it is essential to bear potential for an excellent researcher.

The affinity for *teamwork* and *self-confidence* is also mentioned as important criteria. According to an interviewee, candidate's social skills are even more important than her/his knowledge and research excellence:

'Someone may be a very good researcher, but socially problematic individual. Such person would destroy the team, so we would rather decide to employ not so great scholar, but socially intelligent individual, since our ambition is to build a strong team'.

The next are intelligence, clear ideas what to research, ability to react promptly, agility, ability to perform multiple tasks successfully and knowledge of foreign languages.

Ability to *acquire funding* was essentially important for most of the interviewees. This is seen both as the way person can secure more stable research position, and can be able to solidify institute's economic situation. One of the interviewees, however, did not see this as that important criterion, and prioritised readiness to conduct group research over it.

For most of the interviewees, candidate's international experience and networks play very important role. This is considered both as a confirmation that one's research is acknowledged and valued internationally, and as a way to secure financial stability of the institute through participation in international projects and consortia. One interviewee, however, stated that for his specific field (Slovene language studies) international experience was not that important:

'Between a candidate who graduated at Harvard and Ljubljana, I would rather select the latter'.

Criteria specific for specific SSH fields

As a field specific criteria, the interviewees and focus group members listed the following: ability to conduct thorough desktop-work (lexicography/Slovene language studies), excellence in fundamental research (philosophy), ability to conduct fieldwork (geography, migration studies), internationally comparable excellence, ability to write well (good literacy), publication records, participation in the teaching process (ethnology).

The difference between a candidate with minimal requirements and a real excellent candidate

Excellence is predominantly construed as *research excellence* (references, publication record, research experience, knowledge); characteristics of the candidate that would contribute to sustainability and recognition of the institute are also important elements of excellence construction (readiness to work and learn; readiness to make a compromise between personal research ambitions and research team's needs; successful applications for projects). Excellent candidates are expected to take initiative and be able to secure their own position within the institute by gaining projects and widening international network:

'young people cannot expect that the job is offered to them on a plate'

stressed one of the interviewees. Another interviewee thus described the difference between a candidate with minimal requirements and a real excellent candidate:

'Minimal criteria include publications, in candidate's field and broader; excellent candidate, on the other hand, is a person who fulfils the following three criteria: has good publication record, is active in teaching, and has a developed international network'.

Actual / recent selection process

In the actual process of selection, *familiarity* with the candidate seems to be a decisive factor. This is particularly true for the C-level candidates, but also largely valid for D-level (Young Researchers): for all new C-level employments within last 5 years have been selected the researchers, who participated in project proposal preparation and who were consequently employed when the application was successful. There were no committees, but candidates were selected based on already existing (personal) ties. Focus groups members and interviewees involved in the D-level selection as the best practice stress the one in which those who participate in the teaching recruit candidates among students. According to an interviewee, selected candidates at her unit usually already have a record of cooperation (while they were students, or based on short term, external contracts). In words of one of the interviewees:

'We always know the candidate – either I or some of my colleagues was his teacher. It is almost impossible that we invite for a job interview someone we know nothing about. Moreover, even if that happens, I know when s/he studied and would call his/her teacher and make a query. This is not the USA or Germany'.

For long-term C-positions, candidates are usually recruited from a pool of researchers, who were already part of research group (as Young Researchers and Research Assistants).

Gender

Gender of candidates was not considered as a decisive criterion neither among focus group participants nor among interviewees. On the other hand, they stress the importance of gender balance for functioning of research groups.

‘If two candidates are equally good, I would give priority to women’, stressed the interviewee from the unit where men dominated. In a women dominated unit, the interviewee stated that she would probably choose a man to improve gender balance; ‘gender balance is essentially important for group dynamics and its successful functioning’

The existence of gender policy on recruitment and selection within the institution and collocutors' attitudes towards them

The interviewees and focus group members are not aware of any gender policy on recruitment and selection of candidates on the institutional or unit level. They prioritise other criteria over gender, but stress the importance of gender-balanced teams.

‘I am for gender balance, but I am against enforcing it; that would be discrimination against the other sex; in the process of candidate selection each candidate is personality on its own and that is what influences on decisions’

Some interlocutors stressed the danger of feminisation in their specific fields (geography, ethnology); one of the focus group members emphasised that for his field (geography) it is not acceptable that women dominate research teams, because they are not capable of independent fieldwork (due to heavy equipment). They also stressed that

‘women are usually hard-working and engaged, but not specialised in specific field’

The other member said that

‘women usually have higher grades, but men have more awards and better research record’.

Appointment reports SSH: Institute of Slovenian language, ZRC SAZU

The report comprises the content analysis of the texts of meeting minutes from 5 meetings held by committee for selection of Young Researchers (2010–2014). This analysis concerns the selection process for the ‘Young Researcher’ position, since only for this position there is a committee on the institutional level which issues a report (meeting minutes) whereby it formally confirms (or rejects) appointment of selected candidates and assures that the protocol was fully followed.

Qualitative analysis

The decisive criteria:

Decisive criterion is average grade during B.A. or M.A., since it brings the highest number of points; significant are also 'research' criteria (article authorship and record of research). Other important criteria include possession of MA degree, enrolment in PhD studies, and possession of awards. Criteria are specified and measured by number of points which value is exactly specified for education degree, average grade, current study enrolment and awards, while for article authorship and research record those who select have more freedom and may value candidate in a range of points, whereby the maximum is defined.

Research experience is important criterion for selection of Young Researchers; scholarly publications, awards, and participation in research project are highly valued in the selection process. The minutes of Committee for selection of Young Researchers state that committee members also take into account expert and research profile of the selected candidates with regard to needs of respective institutes.

In terms of affirmative action and gender equality policies do not anyhow refer to or deal with affirmative action or gender equality.

Quantitative analysis

All candidates selected were appointed for fixed term positions: the duration is usually 3.5 years with the possibility of extension for 6 months.

Gender ratio of appointed candidates

Table 9: Selected candidates, 2010–2014, by gender (F/M)

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Young Researchers	3 male 6 female	4 male 4 female	5 male 3 female	5 male 1 female	1 male 0 female

Table 10: The gender composition of 2–3 members committee (mc)

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Young Researchers	1 male 2 female	1 male 2 female	1 male 2 female	0 male 3 female	0 male 3 female (1 male member of the committee who could not join was replaced by a female member)

For number of the candidates by gender for a particular working post (per discipline), data are not available.

Comparative conclusion STEM and SSH actual practices

Interviews and Focus Group

In both STEM and SSH, committee members (CM) emphasise that it is important to know the candidate for a longer period. Personal experience with a candidate is a decisive criterion in selection procedure, an assurance that a selected candidate would fit to a team group. They believe that employing ‘already known candidates’ is a Slovenian specialty (particularly since in some academic fields there are simply not enough candidates in the country). This is usually a candidate who has been already employed in a lower working position (as an Assistant with PhD or a Lecturer), yet with obtained academic title as Assistant Professor or in the cases of SSH, a person already hired under *contract for a ‘project work.’* In all the cases, there was informal recruitment of the candidate. However, the procedure was carried out in line with the official rules. As a result, the *decision-making process* was also a formality, and a consensus among the committee members was easily reached.

Abstract criteria

In the case of STEM, the institution that granted a certificate is more important. Some interviewees more trust to certificates obtained within the University of Ljubljana (UL). For SSH, these criteria are not mentioned at all.

Despite the strong emphasis on the importance of *publication record* in the formal criteria, the interviewees from both STEM and SSH did not see this criteria as particularly important.

For STEM, this criterion is gradually becoming a very important one in a context of reduced national funds for teaching to 80% (it is expected that a candidate at C-level is capable of acquiring additional funds from various users of their expertise), but for SSH, this criterion appeared as crucial (for both T/FP positions):

Criteria of *management skills* appeared as important in SSH and particularly in the institutes in which the research team had to acquire the project and provide the funding by them. In opposition, in STEM this criterion is not presented as important.

For STEM, one of the important abstract criteria appeared to be the *international mobility*: the long-term staying abroad is very important for international research networking and a very important requirement, unlike in the case of SSH. In addition, in the STEM they see an employment of foreign candidates as a solution to a deficit of specific academic profiles in Slovenia. Simultaneously, they are aware of difficulty of foreign candidates to communicate with various Slovenian audiences. Therefore, the committee members for C-level insist in a formal criterion – ‘mandatory command of the Slovenian language’. On the contrary, for SSH

international mobility was positioned rather low at the list of important criteria. Regarding foreign candidates, they appeared to be extremely rare.

The most important criteria cited by the interviewees in both STEM and SSH pertain to *fit in the team* and a candidate's 'personality' with all characteristics mentioned. A candidate's enthusiasm and their 'compatibility with a team' are the most desired characteristics for both STEM and SSH. Other criteria for D appeared to be particularly important for SSH – to abandon their own research interest in order to contribute to the joint work of the group.

Gender

All collocutors and the participants of FG agree that gender does not play a significant role in the selection of candidates. All interviewees strive for a balanced gender structure in their working groups; however, some reports on an unbalanced gender structure indicated women are in majority.

All interviewees believe that gender policy on recruitment and selection does not exist at the level of department and at the faculty in general. They agree that the departments, chairs and research groups have to be gender balanced. In STEM, they agree that it is necessary to introduce a policy to stimulate women not at the beginning of their academic career, but later. In SSH department they believe that this is not necessary, although one of the interviewees (female) admit that the current tendency of employment of young people at the beginning of their career prioritize women, but later men are preferred candidates, due to higher titles and leading positions obtained.

APPOINTMENT REPORTS

Qualitative analysis

Both STEM and SSH obviously emphasise degree and research experience. Degree criteria were decisive for selected candidates who applied for the positions Assistant and Assistant Professor. In the case of selected Research Assistant, research experience was the most decisive criterion.

Attention paid to the gender of the candidates

In the appointment reports, there is no attention paid to the gender of the candidates.

Quantitative analysis:

In STEM, all 6 candidates were selected for permanent, regular, full-time employment. The number of candidates did not significantly exceed the number of posts (for the position Assistant in 2010, 2 female candidates applied and 1 was selected, while for the position of

Research Assistant 3 female candidates applied and one was selected). It is interesting that those who applied for the highest observed working positions (Assist. Prof.) were male candidates. All positions were publicly (internationally) announced. In SSH all selected candidates were appointed for full-time temporary positions; in case of Young Researchers it is usually 3.5 years with the possibility of extension for 6 months. As for appointment candidates, the graduate increasing number of male candidate is visible (which is also related to the scientific discipline for which they apply – in 2013 the majority of applicants was for Geography, traditionally a male-dominated discipline in Slovenia). Regarding committee composition, female members are in the slight majority. In both STEM and SSH vacancies were publicly advertised.

6.4. Conclusions

The gap between formal criteria and actual practices is strongly related to the fact that for T/FP positions formal requirement process is rather an exception. These positions are under the promotion system where academic personnel progress from one rank to another. In the case of SSH which is not university, but research centre with 'project-based' work, in rare cases when there is a new job vacancy, these are the people already planned in the project proposal and once the financing of the project is accepted, they are formally employed for the duration of the project. As for STEM, these are people who entered into Department as PhD students (as teaching assistants) or were already engaged to work on projects. In both STEM and SSH in the case of postdocs (which is, as explained on p. 3, rather specific position in Slovenian context), again there is no formal procedure and the HR official informs the Employment Service of Slovenia about the announcement of job vacancy for the already *known candidate* without any detailed job description and requirements. In such cases, there are no other candidates except the only one 'known candidate' and no commission is organised.

It seems that there is no clear boundary between formal criteria and actual practices. Since there is often no 'formal recruitment process', the selection of a candidate is made only through actual practices and undefined (abstract) criteria. In general, in both STEM and SSH interviewees, a *personal experience in work with a candidate* is a decisive criterion in selection procedure, an assurance that a selected candidate would *fit in to a team group*. In the cases where the formal procedure takes place, at first formal criteria are examined. Then, it is

decisive whether the committee members know the candidate or have working experiences with them.

In terms of affirmative action and gender equality policies, neither in formal criteria nor in the actual practices gender is particularly acknowledged. Regarding formal criteria, only for the position of Young Researcher (without PhD) the eligibility criteria, for candidates who used maternity leave, the age/number of years limit from receiving MA or BA degree is lifted for 1 year for each child. The same is applicable for documented sick leaves that were longer than 6 months. The appointment reports in both STEM and SSH do not anyhow refer to or deal with affirmative action or gender equality.

All interviewees believe that gender is relevant only as a factor in making a balanced research teams. Gender balanced groups are presented as more desirable. They agree that the departments, chairs and research groups have to be gender balanced. In STEM, they consider that it is necessary to introduce a policy in order to stimulate women not at the beginning of their academic career, but later. On the contrary, in SSH department they believe this is not necessary since women are more typical candidates in the current tendency of employment of young people at the beginning of their career.

Published by University of Trento,
Via Calepina, 14, Trento, 38122, Italy

Design Teresa Burzigotti • formicablu • www.formicablu.it

ISBN 978-88-8443-610-8 • 2015

<http://www.garciaproject.eu>

